

Legality Attentive Data Scientists
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Glossary, Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronyms	Definitions
ADMS	Automated Decision Making System
ADPC	Advanced Data Protection Control
AGCM	Italian Competition Authority
AGID	Agenzia per l'Italia Digitale
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
AIA	AI Act
AMIE	Articular Medical Intelligence Explorer
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
ARF	Architecture Reference Framework (EU Wallet ARF)
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CI	Contextual Integrity
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CNR	National Research Council of Italy
CON	Central Orchestration Node
CR	Crossroad
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DA	Data Act
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCMT	Dublin Core Metadata Terms
DDG	Decentralised Data Governance
DGA	Data Governance Act
DID	Difference-in-Differences
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNT	Do Not Track
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DSA	Digital Services Act
DTC	Direct To Consumer
DTI	Data Transfer Initiative
DTCGTCs	Direct To Consumer Genetic Testing Companies

Acronyms	Definitions
EC	European Commission
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
eIDAS	electronic Identification, Authentication and trust Services
EMR	Electronic Medical Record
EPOS	Electronic Point Of Sale
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
EU	European Union
FedAvg	Federated Averaging
FedOpt	Federated Optimization
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FFNPD	Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation
FL	Federated Learning
FLaaS	Federated learning as a service
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPC	Global Privacy Control
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
HDAB	Health Data Access Body
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on AI
HITL	Human In The Loop
HL7	Health Level Seven
HODA	Hoda case (Hoda v. Google)
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HOTL	Human On The Loop
HW/SW	Hardware / Software
IID	Independent and Identically Distributed
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions — Innovative Training Networks 2020
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IMI	Internal Market Information system
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLM	Large Language Model
LOO	Leave-One-Out (maschera / metodo)
LoA	Level of Assurance
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
ML	Machine Learning
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology

Acronyms	Definitions
MPC	Multi-Party Computation
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
N/A	Non Applicable / Non Available
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NN	Neural Network
NoSQL	Not Only SQL
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OOP	Object Oriented Programming
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDS	Personal Data Store
PETs	Privacy Enhancing Technologies
PHR	Personal Health Record
PHIMS	Personal Health Information Management System
PID	Personal Identification Data
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
PIMS	Personal Information Management System
PPML	Privacy Preserving Machine Learning
PSI	Private Set Intersection
PSU	Private Set Union
P2PFL	Peer-to-Peer Federated Learning
QoS	Quality of Service
QTSP	Qualified Trust Service Provider
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RE	Requirements Engineering
RF	Random Forest (modello)
RFC	Random Forest Classifier
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SP	Service Provider
SL	Split Learning
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
SME	Small/Medium Enterprise
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SyRI	Systeem Risico Indicatie
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TEE / TEEs	Trusted Execution Environment(s)
TFL	Transfer Federated Learning
TILLS	Technology and Law Innovation Labs
UI/UX	User Interface / User Experience
UKVI	UK Visa & Immigration
vCard	Virtual Card format

Acronyms	Definitions
VFL	Vertical Federated Learning
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XAdES	XML Advanced Electronic Signatures
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition

Executive Summary

This report consists of a collection of scientific reports that the Early Stage Researcher (ESR) drafted to briefly illustrate the results of the research activities that they have carried out during the project.

Each scientific report presents the state of the art of the topic analyzed by each ESR, summarizes the research findings, and discusses their broader implications.

The report is organized as follows:

Chapter 1 introduces the overarching objectives of the LeADS project;

Chapter 2 explores the shifting domain boundaries between data protection, consumer protection and competition law on a conceptual as well as empirical level;

Chapter 3 focuses on the development of concrete technical solutions for the implementation of privacy and security in various technologies;

Chapter 4 delves into elements that enable data sharing and composing legal, technical and user-centred perspectives; and

Chapter 5 presents original views on the trustworthy development and deployment of AI.

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1 Introduction

In an increasingly datafied world, data scientists become ever more indispensable to analyze, understand and anticipate human and natural phenomena, as well as to propose solutions to the wicked problems of our time. Because of the significance that the collection, processing and generation of data increasingly exert on individual and collective decision-making, with short-term as well as long-term impacts, data scientists in the modern society are required to be able to grasp the ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) of their activities. They are also asked to direct their professional activities towards the amelioration of the common welfare, while reducing risks deriving from fast-paced technological advancement. In the new digital decade imagined by the EU, a growingly complex interplay of norms attempts to regulate personal and non-personal data use, the development of artificial intelligence, the secure uptake of technologies in all sectors of society, and so on. This is why, even the new generation of jurists needs to be equipped with innovative skills: they are called to create and apply laws to an extremely wide set of emerging technologies, understand the intersections and the tensions between different regulatory instruments, and ensure legal certainty for fostering the economy of the internal market in a globalized world.

Such a complete, enlightened understanding cannot derive from traditional training paths. It rather needs, and deserves, an *ad hoc* audacious, innovative training program that enables a safe-by-design, inclusive digital transformation of public and private services: LeADS. From the onset, LeADS has represented a highly ambitious program of training and research, that has set the mission of creating the next generation of researchers and practitioners who can easily cross the boundaries between the disciplines of law and data science.

The LeADS project has carried out an unprecedented, intensive plan of training activities to prepare Early Stage Researcher (ESR) who are apt to positively contribute to society both within and outside academia. In the LeADS project, collaboration (as a soft skill) and interdisciplinarity (as a hard skill) have represented the guiding principles that have contributed to achieve groundbreaking results that would have been simply impossible otherwise. The four Crossroads reports (D7.1) are a tangible result of this approach: framed as living documents that were continuously re-elaborated for 3 years, they were drafted by small interdisciplinary working groups. Each member contributed with his/her specific disciplinary expertise to a collaborative dialogue that enabled an original co-creation of knowledge on intersectional topics such as Privacy and Intellectual Property (Crossroad 1), Trust in Data Processing and Algorithm Design (Crossroad 2), Data Ownership (Crossroad 3), and Empowering Individuals (Crossroad 4). Another significant occasion where the ESRs have further trained their ability to cross disciplinary boundaries and pio-

near new knowledge through collaborative discussions are the joint Working Papers (WOPAs) (D5.2). Some WOPAs have also been published in international venues, thereby amplifying the outreach of the project's results.

But engaging in interdisciplinary work does not simply occur naturally to individuals who have followed traditional, mostly mono-disciplinary academic curricula. This is exactly one of the challenges that the project intended to overcome by recurring to creative educational and training instruments that have fostered theoretical and applied research. The ESRs have participated in an intensive training program with a great breadth of topics at the forefront of research, policy-making and industrial progress spanning across three years. Moreover, they all have carried out research activities and actively continued their training during two secondment periods at the institutions of other Beneficiaries (i.e., other academic institutions) or project Partners (i.e., companies or independent authorities). The participation in the 4 Technology and Law Innovation Labs (TILLS), as well as the management of the Innovation Challenge and the design of boardgames, among the others, have all been occasions for learning to master newfound skills, including problem-solving, effective communication and successful presentation skills, and for applying their knowledge to relevant complex, real-world problems.

This report, D.7.5 - Final Scientific ESRs Reports, illustrates the individual paths that the ESRs have followed to become Legality-Attentive Data Scientists: in addition to the training and research activities described above, all the ESRs have also pursued a personal research goal on an assigned topic, decided at the time of the drafting of the project proposal but that in several instances has evolved to adapt to changes in the regulatory framework, in technologies or in the individual ESRs' interests. Although it was not a requirement in and for the LeADS' project, in order to address this challenge, the ESRs have all been enrolled in a PhD program of their own institution and they are at date illustrating their research results in a PhD thesis. As the ESRs increasingly mastered their individual research topic and integrated their own original perspective, while society, regulations and technologies evolved, the assigned topics have also evolved to better address the more pressing needs of the contemporary era. This report contains the research findings of each ESR, in the form of a scientific report: each individual contribution contains the objectives and the scope of the research, the methodology, the research findings, a discussion, and future work. The scientific supervisors of the ESRs have reviewed and approved the included reports.

The report is organized in four thematic sections. Chapter 2 explores the shifting domain boundaries between data protection, consumer protection and competition law on a conceptual as well as empirical level. Chapter 3 focuses on the development of concrete technical solutions for the implementation of privacy and security in various technologies. Chapter 4 delves into elements that enable data sharing composing legal, technical and user-centered perspectives. Chapter 5 presents original views on the trustworthy development and deployment of AI.

1.1 Interplay of data protection, consumer protection and competition law

The first contribution “Data as Property and Regulatory Subject Matter in European Consumer Law” by Onntje Hinrichs) constitutes the first comprehensive study that examines to what extent data has become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law. The regulation of data in consumer law might ultimately lead to legal fragmentation and thus risks undermining the objective of European data protection law to provide a fully harmonized legal framework that facilitates the free flow of data. Moreover, the ESR’s work has sought to understand how ‘data openness’ can be reconciled with privacy and economic interests in data, since existing intellectual property rights regimes do not confer property rights in data. The research evaluated the limitations of a property rights approach and highlighted how ultimately it was abandoned in the European Data strategy, in favor of a new focus on facilitating data access and data sharing. The study showcases how data is a difficult fit for traditional legal categories and the challenges it provides to policy-makers in creating a coherent legal framework across legal disciplines.

The second contribution, titled “The Interplay Between Personal Data Protection and Online Platform Market Competition under the GDPR”, by Qifan Yang, explores the role of personal data in the business value creation of online platforms, specifically the social media market, and the impacts of the GDPR on the EU social media market concentration, based on data science, economics, and law. The findings reveal that between 2015 and 2020 the GDPR has resulted in a decrease in EU social media market concentration and a particular negative impact on large social media companies. The GDPR framework (due to transparency, data portability, and compliance costs) curbed the dominance of leading platforms and levelled the playing field for small competitors. In the long term, the impact of the GDPR diminished after 2020 as large companies adopt appropriate strategies to comply with the regulation. The study also identifies two factors that influence the impact of the GDPR: the scale of the Internet market and the level of technology.

“Unchaining data portability” by Tommaso Crepax highlights the current ambiguity surrounding data portability. At present, there is no clear consensus on how much or what type of data should be transferable to meet legal standards. The study argues that, by focusing on data quality, and more specifically, on how well data serves its intended purpose (“fitness for purpose”), we can develop a clearer benchmark to guide existing and future regulatory reforms. This insight is far-reaching, with implications not only for the legal frameworks that govern our digital lives, but also for how data markets evolve, how digital businesses build their models, and how fundamental rights are protected in the process.

1.2 Solving practical hurdles to privacy and security implementation

The second section of this report has a more practical nature since it proposes solutions for the effective implementation of privacy and security requirements into various technologies. “Assessing digital identity solutions” by Cristian Lepore revolves around the timely topic of self-sovereign identities (SSI) that aim to return control of personal data to citizens, thereby reducing

the risk of misuse and building greater trust in digital services. However, the concept remains elusive, lacking a clear, uniform interpretation. Efforts to define SSI are mostly led by academic initiatives, but the concept often remains abstract and disconnected from practical business needs. As a result, many digital identity systems claim to follow SSI principles, but it is difficult to assess how closely they adhere to its core values. This work seeks to offer a formal definition of Self-Sovereign Identity and introduce a practical, structured model for evaluating digital identity solutions with the aim of providing both designers and citizens with a tool to help them choose the best platform for creating a digital identity.

Louis Sahi, in “Distributed reliability and blockchain-like technologies”, describes his work on distributed reliability, blockchain-like technologies and trust in data processing. Starting from defining the main components of data processing, the study presents why collaborative data processing in Europe raises challenges of trust, reliability and legal compliance. Thanks to a systematic literature review and interviews with data experts, the author identified the relevant data quality criteria, and classified them by trust and reliability. Moreover, the thesis proposes a blockchain-based solution that implements some criteria and demonstrates how this solution can maintain data quality and ensure reliability and trust in decentralized data management. However, this solution is not taking the exhaustive list of data quality criteria. A future direction of the work will concern an automated data quality assessment that describes the use of algorithms, rules, or models to assess trust and reliability without the need for direct human intervention.

“Data management and analytics on edge computing and serverless offerings” by Armend Duzha describes a new approach to protect against risks related to personal data exploitation, drawing a methodology for the implementation of data management and analytics in edge computing and serverless offerings in considering privacy properties to modulate prevention of risks and promotion of innovation. In addition, it establishes AI-driven processes to increase the users’ ability to define in a more accurate way their offerings in edge computing environments as well as the data management and analytics concerning privacy protection. The work also designs the architecture in terms of data governance and analytics linked with the resource management on such dynamic environments .

“User empowerment in health through Personal Health Information Management Systems” by Christos Magkos examines Personal Health Information Management Systems (PHIMS) as transformative tools in healthcare data management, addressing three critical challenges: individual data control, insight generation, and privacy preservation. The investigation reveals significant potential in two key technological domains: risk stratification for predictive healthcare and Large Language Models (LLMs) for data processing and diagnostic support. The study identifies and addresses fundamental challenges including data quality issues (missing data, selection bias, non-stationarity), LLM limitations (explainability, bias, privacy), and regulatory compliance requirements (GDPR, AI Act, MDR). Key findings demonstrate that successful PHIMS implementation requires robust privacy-by-design approaches, standardized data integration protocols, and patient-centric interface development. The research emphasizes interoperability and security as foundational requirements, while highlighting the necessity of inclusive design to prevent demographic marginalization.

In her thesis titled “Privacy friendly AI: benefiting from AI without giving away privacy”, Soumia el Mestari elaborated the fine lines between the guarantees required by the EU data protection directives and regulations and the actual threats and defense strategies with the technical guarantees they offer. A detailed threat model that considers stakeholders, deployment choices, and different phases of the pipeline before and after using PETs was built. Another finding was the limitations of the current legal framework against some complex machine learning (ML) settings, namely the case of transfer learning of models, where the basic aims of enabling data subjects to have a flow governance over their data may be bypassed and lost. As a further step, this work investigated the superficial mapping between the meaning of legal anonymization and the technical tools named as ‘anonymization algorithms’, which leads to a narrow application of these algorithms, a shallow attempt to achieve lawful processing and a wrong usage of PETs. From another angle, the issues of privacy in the machine learning system may be tricky to spot before an actual leakage of massive data is revealed. One of these attacks is membership inference attacks in federated learning with a malicious aggregator and under transfer learning settings for large language models, where the findings suggest that this kind of attack is hard to detect and defend against, especially if one wants to preserve privacy and still maintain a good model performance.

1.3 Legal, technical and user-centred enablers of data sharing

The topic of data sharing is at the centre of this third and last section of the report.

Barbara da Rosa Lazarotto in “Sharing information for the public good” focuses primarily on the topic of governmental access to privately held data. The work examines not only the traditional legal framework of data ownership but also how control over data could be enhanced through technological and policy-based mechanisms, ensuring that the benefits of the digital economy were more equitably shared. The research further investigates the tensions between data protection and data sharing regulations within the European Union’s legal framework, highlighting the dual objectives of data protection, which seeks to safeguard the rights and control of data subjects, and the regulations promoting data sharing such as the Data Act and the Data Governance Act, which aim to enhance the digital economy through the reuse and exchange of data. Furthermore, the research identifies the potential for legal fragmentation resulting from these competing regulatory frameworks. The study offers a nuanced analysis of the protective and limiting aspects of data subject rights, exploring the complex interplay between individual control and the broader goals of economic innovation.

“A framework for user-centered, legal-ethical collective consent models: genomic data sharing” by Xengie Doan is a theoretical and empirical study on collective consent processes for health data sharing. First, the study explores the need for collective consent from a privacy, biomedical, and legal-ethical lens and analyzed the transparency and user-relevancy of policies from notable Direct to Consumer (DTC) genetic testing companies to find gaps in the status quo. Then the author reports findings from the testing of methods in the framework for transparent, user-centered collective consent with employees from a welfare technology company to better understand pros and cons in future implementation. A survey of adults about their attitudes to-

wards consent management and engaging elements within different consent mediums has led to a better understanding of their needs and desires. Together, this framework shows promise for addressing end-user and business needs for collective consent, and upon further iteration could also be relevant in the future to other types of shared data in the EU.

Fatma Dogan in “To Use or Not to Use? Re-using Health Data in AI Development” aims to critically examine the challenge of balancing bias mitigation and data protection in AI-driven healthcare within the European Union’s regulatory landscape. The study focuses on three pivotal frameworks: the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the AI Act, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The findings reveal that while the EHDS aims to facilitate AI development through secondary use of health data, emphasizing anonymization and pseudonymization, the AI Act permits processing of sensitive data for bias detection and mitigation in AI systems. These approaches potentially conflict with GDPR’s strict rules on processing sensitive health data. The research uncovers how anonymization and pseudonymization requirements in the EHDS may impede the creation of representative datasets crucial for bias mitigation in AI. Furthermore, it highlights how the AI Act’s provisions for data re-identification in bias detection contradict GDPR’s data protection mandates. This study provides critical insights into the implications of the current regulatory framework for developing unbiased, innovative AI technologies in healthcare while maintaining robust data protection standards.

“How to collaboratively train AI in a secure way” written by Maciej Zuziak, explores how modern data governance can be amplified with the use of decentralised learning techniques. It provides an in-depth examination of modern alternative data governance frameworks and decentralized learning models, exploring their key findings, implications, and contributions to the fields of data science, law, and policymaking. As the volume and complexity of data grow, traditional governance structures are being challenged, giving rise to alternative models that promote greater transparency, security, and individual control. Decentralized learning, particularly through federated learning systems, offers innovative ways to leverage data while maintaining privacy, reducing the risks of central data breaches, and fostering collaborative research across institutions. The research highlights the transformative potential of these approaches, showing how they can enhance data security, uphold privacy standards, and democratize access to data insights. Additionally, the findings suggest that regulatory frameworks must adapt to accommodate decentralized data systems, ensuring that they align with ethical standards and legal requirements.

Lastly, Aizhan Abdrassulova in “Boundaries of data ownership: empowering data subjects in the EU” focuses on the difficulty of determining a legal status of data ownership, due to the dynamic nature of data. The study provides a detailed analysis of data as an object of civil rights and examines the positions of supporters and opponents of this approach, as well as the GDPR provisions regarding the concept of data ownership. Although ownership may not be an appropriate category for formulating and recognizing the requirements of data subjects, strengthening access rights and data portability in data management systems constitutes a valuable solution. As attempts are being made to go beyond ownership, thereby bringing flexibility and compliance with rapidly changing realities in the field of data, the study provides arguments in favor of data governance with the help of technical measures.

1.4 Trustworthy development and deployment of AI

Mitisha Gaur in “A Sociotechnical Approach To Revealing The Invisible Hand That Guides the Adoption of AI in Public Administrations” aims at simplifying the various elements that form the interaction between humans and algorithms in the context of the application of AI systems in the judicial sphere, in particular Predictive Justice algorithms. The study identifies the technological, organisational and social elements of such algorithms and focuses on three broad crucial building blocks associated with the deployment of Trustworthy AI systems, namely (1) Meaningful Transparency, (2) Algorithmic Accountability and (3) Human Oversight. However, this is where tensions emerge, such as the use of differential privacy as a privacy preserving technique which is at odds with the need for meaningful algorithmic transparency and adequate human oversight. The study also identifies two primary vacuums, namely (1) the lack of organisational precision with most deployers i.e. judicial bodies spontaneously deploying AI systems leading to considerable setbacks to health, safety and fundamental rights and (2) the exclusion of the persons subjected to the decisions of the Predictive Justice system (decision-subjects) from the conversation surrounding the use of Predictive Justice, leading to irreversible erosion to the principle of human agency as well as the rule of law. The study concludes with recommendations split across ex-ante and ex-post algorithmic accountability requirements focused on facilitating reliable and trustworthy AI systems functioning to preserve health, safety and fundamental rights.

Lastly, “The Complexity of Value Alignment: Justice and Discrimination in Automated Decision-making Systems” by Robert Poe focuses on of tools have been developed to prescript normative constraints on automated decision-making systems, such as fair machine learning (FML). The AI Act is relying on such prescriptive technologies to perform "value-alignment" between automated decision-making systems and European fundamental rights. It is in this way that technologists are becoming the watchmen of European fundamental rights. However, the information asymmetry between experts in the field and those traditionally engaged in legal interpretation, raises the age-old question of who is watching the watchmen themselves? The main goal is to develop a set of "rules for the rules" applied to the "code as law" tradition, specifically focusing on the debiasing tools of algorithmic discrimination and fairness as a case study. Such rules for the rules are especially important given the threat of an algorithmic Leviathan.

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2 Data Protection, Consumer Protection and Competition Law

2.1 Data as Property and Regulatory Subject Matter in European Consumer Law

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2.1.1 Executive summary

This final scientific report provides an overview on the research conducted by ESR 13 throughout the Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) project. The research can be roughly divided into two interconnected parts: (i) research on the topic which was assigned to him as ESR 13: 'solving conflicts between data owners and exploiters through a spectrum of quasi-property models' (ii) research on ESR13's PhD thesis entitled 'Data as regulatory subject matter in European consumer law'. Both parts are strongly interconnected since the research on property rights in data informed and shaped his research on the regulation of data through consumer law.

ESR 13's topic, part of Crossroad 1 on Intellectual Property vs Privacy, focused on a core difficulty in the regulation of the data economy. How can tensions that result from conflicting interests in data be resolved? How can 'data openness' be reconciled with privacy and economic interests in data? Since existing intellectual property rights regimes do not confer property rights in data, scholars and policy-makers debated for decades whether or not such a property right should be created. The research evaluated the limitations of a property rights approach and highlighted how ultimately it was abandoned in the European Data strategy. The new focus on facilitating data access and data sharing in the emerging European data law further informed interdisciplinary research in cooperation with ESRs 6 and 12 how the current European approach to data governance might be realized through technological means. A case study on data collaboratives with the use of decentralized learning adopted the LeADS approach by focusing on both: the regulatory and technological layer in data governance to analyze how conflicting interests in data can be resolved not through property rights but technology that is implemented in compliance with obligations on data access and data sharing.

ESR 13's topic on solving conflicting interests in data through property rights further informed and shaped his PhD research. Whereas a property-rights approach in data has been abandoned, the underlying rationale, i. e. empowering individuals with regard to their data, is still existent.

In his research ESR13 focused on a different field of law and how it might impact the protection of consumer data: European consumer law. Whereas data has traditionally not been subject matter that belonged to the regulatory ambit of consumer law, this has changed gradually over the past decade. ESR13's PhD thesis constitutes the first comprehensive study that examines to what extent data has become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law. This report presents some of its findings in particular with regard to the interrelation between consumer and data protection law. Whereas consumer law has the potential of, for instance, protecting consumers from unfair commercial practices based on the exploitation of vulnerabilities revealed through the processing of consumer data, it equally bears the risk of polluting the privacy ecosystem when it conceives personal data as payment in contracts for digital content and services. Furthermore, ESR 13's research shows how the regulation of data in consumer law might ultimately lead to legal fragmentation and thus risks undermining the objective of European data protection law to provide a fully harmonized legal framework that facilitates the free flow of data.

A core theme that links the research on data property and the regulation of data through consumer law thus has been the regulatory complexity of the data economy and the difficulty of finding appropriate legal responses that achieve policy objectives. It showcases how data is a difficult fit for traditional legal categories and the challenges it provides to policy-makers in creating a coherent legal framework across legal disciplines. It further showcased that understanding and addressing these challenges oftentimes necessitates an interdisciplinary perspective. Whilst LeADS has not transformed ESR 13 into a data scientist, it certainly has made him more attentive to data science and the necessity of cooperating across academic disciplines to solve regulatory problems within the data economy.

2.1.2 Introduction

The Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) project aimed at training a new interdisciplinary professional figure skilled in both law and data science. These new experts should help expand the legal frontiers in line with innovation needs, preventing the enactments of legal rules which might be technologically unattainable or legally ineffective in achieving their intended goals. A legality attentive data scientist, or in my case, a data science attentive lawyer, should be equipped to navigate the regulatory complexities of the data economy, understanding its unique challenges and how the law should (or should not) respond to them.

My topic as ESR 13, situated in Crossroad 1 on 'Privacy versus Intellectual Property', lay at the core of this LeADS objective: How should conflicting interests by 'data owners' and 'data exploiters' be reconciled? More specifically, to what extent may property rights in data constitute a valid instrument to empower both, individuals and companies with regard to data? Could property rights constitute a valid instrument that not only enable data control, but equally data access and data sharing through, for instance, facilitating the emergence of data markets? Data, being intangible and non-depletable upon consumption, has been described as a difficult fit for traditional economic and legal categories. [Ker17] Its dual nature as both a commodity-like object and a 'social and technical lubricant' challenges the notion that any singular description of data could adequately underpin a regulatory framework. [Mad20] Such an understanding of data

thus puts into question the viability of traditional legal instruments, such as property rights, in governing data. From a legal perspective, it also prompts a deeper examination of regulatory consistency between questions, for instance, property rights and European data protection framework that is grounded in the protection of fundamental rights.

This report first presents findings of my research that investigate the legal status quo whether or not intellectual property law already provides for some kind of property-right regime for the protection of data as such. It continues by presenting findings on why a property-rights approach has ultimately been abandoned by both scholars and policy-makers and how in the recent European Data Strategy a major shift occurred towards the creation of a regulatory framework that intends to facilitate data sharing and data access. Finally, it presents the findings of an interdisciplinary working paper [Zuz+23] on data collaboratives with the use of decentralized learning that might simultaneously facilitate data control and data sharing and thus exemplifies how conflicting interests in data may be resolved through a legally compliant implementation of technology – highlighting the necessity of adopting a LeADS approach to certain regulatory problems.

This report further presents the findings of my PhD research on ‘Data as Regulatory Subject Matter in European Consumer Law’. It shows how my PhD research, which constitutes the first comprehensive study that analyzes to what extent data has become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law, is very much grounded in core questions which LeADS attempts to address: how to address the regulatory complexity of the data economy and how to ensure legal consistency when the regulation of data is no longer confined to a single legal discipline. [Str21] It exemplifies this problem of regulatory consistency by highlighting how the regulation of data in European consumer law interacts and conflicts with the twofold objectives of European data protection law: the protection of the fundamental right to data protection [Hin23] and the free flow of data [Hin24].

This report concludes by highlighting two overarching key take aways of my journey as an ESR in the LeADS project: it significantly furthered my understanding of the regulatory complexity of the data economy. It significantly furthered my understanding of the necessity of interdisciplinary research to address such complexities.

2.1.3 Research Findings and Analysis

2.1.3.1 No Property Rights in Data in Intellectual Property Law

Should data be protected through the creation of new property rights in data? Since I my LeADS research was integrated in Crossroad 1 on Intellectual Property vs Privacy, I first analyzed to what extent data can be protected through existing intellectual property rights regimes. The concept of “intellectual property” thereby refers to a loose cluster of legal doctrines that regulate the uses of different sorts of ideas or their expression. [Fiso1] It includes different legal regimes that, for instance, aim at protecting creative works of the human mind in the case of copyright laws¹,

¹Cf. e. g. Directive 2001/29/EC on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society, Directive 2009/24/EC on the legal protection of computer programs, Directive 2019/790 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market.

inventions in the case of patent laws, secret information that has commercial value in the case of trade secrets², or databases that have been subject to substantial investment³. IP laws are thus concerned with the recognition and protection of limited exclusionary rights regarding different categories of subject matter. [DP18] Their justification from a utilitarian perspective⁴ thereby aims at facilitating the creation of efficient markets for works that due to their intangibility would otherwise be difficult to commercialize.

First, copyright protection is conferred on subject matter that can be regarded as an authorial work that constitutes the author's own intellectual creation.⁵ Copyright protection thus extends only to the author's original treatment of subject matter but not the underlying ideas or information themselves. According to the idea/expression dichotomy, protected subject matter can only subsist of the creative expression of ideas. [Gin18] Copyright has therefore not created any new property rights in data as such.⁶ Second, databases can be subject to two kinds of intellectual property regimes. On the one hand, databases 'which, by reason of the selection or arrangement of their contents, constitute the author's own intellectual creation shall be protected as such by copyright.'⁷ Since many databases do not fulfil this originality criterion, the European legislator created a sui generis database right if 'there has been qualitatively and/or quantitatively a substantial investment in either the obtaining, verification or presentation of the contents of that database.'⁸ Contrary to copyright, the focus from the sui generis right lies thus not on the protection of creations of the human mind but on results of investment. Individual data, however, are not protected.⁹

Third, trade secrets protect information that (i) is secret (ii) has commercial value due to its secrecy (iii) and that has been subject to reasonable steps to be kept secret.¹⁰ Trade secrets can therefore often offer protection for information that cannot be protected by conventional intellectual property rights, for instance, in the case of data-generating patents. The exclusionary protective effect can, however, disappear once information is no longer secret. Trade secrets do therefore not protect data as such, but they rather protect information against breaches of a confidential relationship. [Ree21] Finally, according to the European Patent Conventions patents can be granted for inventions that are new, involve an inventive step and are suscepti-

²Directive 2016/943/EU on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure

³Directive 96/9/EC on the legal protection of databases

⁴For an overview on other approaches to intellectual property see [Fiso1]

⁵Case C-5/08 Infopaq International A/S v Danske Dagblades Forening [2009] ECR I-6569 and case C-393/9 Bezpečnostní softwarová asociace - Svaz softwarové ochrany v Ministerstvo kultury [2010].

⁶Data can, however, be protected if part of a creative work. European copyright legislation has therefore created, for instance, exceptions for text and data mining purposes for scientific research, see Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market.

⁷Directive 96/9/EC on the legal protection of databases, article 3(1).

⁸Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases, article 7(1).

⁹See however [Wes21] who fears that the case law of the CJEU might have created an exceedingly wide protection of databases subject to the sui generis right that in some instances might come close to protecting data as such. But see also the recent Data Act which explicitly specifies that data obtained from or generated by the use of a product or a related service is not protected by the sui generis right.

¹⁰Article 2(1) Directive 2016/943 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure.

ble of industrial application.¹¹ Presentations of information as such, however, are excluded from patentability.¹² Data as such would therefore not qualify for a patent since only “inventions” that fulfil the above-mentioned criteria are an eligible subject matter.

2.1.3.2 Creating Property Rights in Data to Empower Individuals and Facilitate the Emergence of Data Markets?

If data is not subject to a comprehensive protection through intellectual property law, should new property rights in data be created to empower both individuals and companies to be in control of ‘their’ data? Would such a property rights regime facilitate the emergence of competitive data markets and thereby ensure the availability of data to a wide variety of stakeholders? In other words, could data property rights be an instrument that achieves both the protection as well as the availability of data?

We already intuitively speak about ‘our data’, which expresses how we feel about information that relates to us. Since the traces which we leave when we browse the internet oftentimes reveal private and intimate information about us, such as our sexual orientation or political views when we ‘like’ certain content on social media, it makes sense to intuitively claim ownership over such data and to prevent others from using them. ‘Our’ data should belong to us. Such language thus reflects how the notion of ownership can be a psychological concept that expresses a sense of belonging. Similarly in economics, property rights have been defined as an individual’s ability to consume a good directly or to consume it indirectly through exchange. [Bar] This economic definition of property rights is therefore not concerned with what people are legally entitled to do but rather what they believe they can do. Property in law, however, denotes something else than psychological attachment to or de facto control over objects. As stated by Van Erp, the essence of property law concerns legal relationships between people with regard to objects, from which rights ensue that may be invoked against more than a number of specific persons and which therefore involves the normative creation of objects that qualify as property. [VE19] Property law therefore creates things as normative concepts that are then assigned to persons, and property rights determine the extent of the granted exclusive power. [Rah10] Property law thus raises the distributive question of why we treat some things as objects of property and why we deny the same treatment to others.¹³

Counter-intuitively, the question if data should be ‘treated’ as property is not a new question but pre-dates the era of big data or the internet. Already in 1968, decades before the collection of data both online and offline has become ubiquitous, authors argued that the right we as individuals have over our personal information should be understood as a property right. [Wes68] Debates, however, intensified with the internet era where the collection of large amounts of consumer data was increasingly getting facilitated through technological means.

Lessig proposed to link the protection of data with the incentives of the market by using the

¹¹European Patent Convention Article 52(1).

¹²European Patent Convention Article 52(2).

¹³[Pen97] One explanation, for instance, is offered by Katharina Pistor [Pis19] who argues that law constitutes a ‘powerful social ordering technology’ and that legal coding (e. g. via contract or property rights) is key for the commodification of objects, their subsequent exploitation as well as the distribution of wealth.

laws of property as a control mechanism. [Les99b] If data could only be transferred with the owner's consent, individuals would be put in the position of valuing their privacy according to their personal preferences. [Rev99] Such a commodification of data, which would turn it into an object that can be bought and sold on the market, would thus enhance privacy since individuals would be in full control over their data. Such a property rights approach to data, however, has been criticized by different authors. Recognizing property rights in data might ultimately erode existing levels of privacy if individuals simply increasingly traded away their personal data. [Cohoo] Furthermore, as the value of data is linked to uncertain future uses it would be almost impossible for individuals to ascribe value to information. Aggregated data and inferences that can be drawn from it further complicate this task since a 'comprehensive collection of data about an individual is vastly more than the sum of its parts'. [Cohoo] In such cases where trades are characterized by information asymmetries, property rules alone have thus been regarded as suboptimal to achieve efficient outcomes. Market solutions based on a property rights model would therefore not cure any of the problems related to control, but they would only legitimize them. [Litoo]

A property rights approach has in particular been regarded as problematic in Europe where information privacy is seen as a fundamental right.¹⁴ Consequently, propertizing these rights would be 'contrary to the theory, history, and practice of European information privacy and would require a concerted effort of dramatic proportions.' [MS10] Other authors, however, remind us that although the EU data protection framework is conceived in fundamental rights terms, it equally functions to ensure the free flow of personal data. Similar to a property rights regime, EU data protection rules would provide a framework that legitimizes rather than discourages trade in personal data. [Lyn15] Furthermore, the status quo devoid of well-defined property rights in data would already result in a de facto assignment of economic property rights to the information industry, eroding data subject's autonomy, privacy and informational self-determination. [Pur15]

The debates on data property culminated when the European Commission proposed the creation of a 'data producer's right' in non-personal data.¹⁵ Criticism on the creation of a new property right in data, however, prevailed. Since data would already be subject to transactions and businesses would have technical means to shield data against competitors and reach factual exclusivity, a contractual inter partes protection would suffice. [Dre17] Since Big Data analytics would rely on permanent access to real time data sources, individual ownership rights in data would present major challenges in terms of governance and enforcement of individual rights. [Dre17] Creating a new layer of rights in data would furthermore cause disruptive overlaps with both copyright and the sui generis databases right. [Hug18] The consequence would be multiple competing claims of ownership over the same content. Such a "tragedy of the anticommons" would hence risk resulting in an underuse of data due to the high number and complex in-

¹⁴On the history of the fundamental right to data protection within the EU see e. g. [GF14] On the distinction between privacy and data protection see e. g. [DHGo6b] For an overview how to conceptualize the link between privacy and data protection see [Lyn15] who distinguishes between (i) data protection and privacy as separate but complementary rights (ii) data protection as a subset of the right to privacy (iii) data protection as an independent right that serves a multitude of purposes.

¹⁵European Commission, 'Building a European Data Economy' (2017) SWD(2017) 2 final.

terrelations of overlapping property rights. [Ste20] Since data constitutes a non-rivalrous but at the same time excludable resource that might suffer from a contextual incentive problem for the production of certain types of data (raw versus inferred data), it would constitute a difficult object for traditional legal categories like property. [Ker17]

2.1.3.3 Abandoning the Idea of Property Rights and Moving Towards Data Access and Data Sharing

Some years after the proposal of a “data producer’s right”, however, such an incentive-oriented approach has been abandoned. Neither the 2020 European Strategy for Data¹⁶ nor two of its key actions, the 2022 Data Governance Act (DGA)¹⁷ and the 2023 European Data Act¹⁸, contain any references to data ownership or sui generis rights in data. Whilst the goal of the European Strategy for Data remains to realize a ‘genuine single market for data’, any reference to (legal) data ownership rights disappeared from the Commission’s communications and proposals. Commentators hence described the strategy as a ‘paradigm shift’ in EU policy from data ownership towards facilitating data access and sharing. [MA21b] Since data would constitute an essential resource for companies to develop new products, services or train AI systems, a regulatory environment should enable stakeholders to have easy access to an almost infinite amount of data. Regulation should enable data to flow easily while at the same time ensure that European rules and values are fully respected. Key pillars of the European Strategy for Data thereby attempt to enable precisely the creation of such a regulatory environment.

The DGA intends to facilitate access and encourage use of data held by public sector bodies. Whilst the Open Data Directive¹⁹ already established minimum rules governing re-use for data that is not subject to intellectual property rights or commercial confidentiality, the DGA harmonizes access conditions for re-use of protected categories of data. Moreover, the DGA puts in place a framework for ‘data intermediation services’ and ‘data altruism organizations’ which should play a key role in the data economy by supporting, facilitating, and promoting (voluntary) data sharing. Furthermore, the Commission intends to create Common European Data Spaces²⁰ in strategic sectoral fields²¹ that bring together relevant data infrastructures and governance frameworks to facilitate data pooling and sharing. The new Data Spaces are strongly connected with the data intermediaries by the DGA which, as trustworthy, neutral data intermediaries, should facilitate the emergence of data spaces. Third, the Data Act constitutes together with the DGA the second horizontal legislative instrument of the European Data Strategy. Whilst the DGA aims at opening up data held by public sector bodies, the Data Act creates mandatory access rules to data held by private actors in B2C, B2B as well as B2G relations. The data access rights are thereby supposed to fulfil the twofold purpose of empowering individuals and companies over ‘their’ data while at the same time ensuring that data is available for other stakeholders.

¹⁶European Commission, ‘A European Strategy for Data’ (2020) COM(2020) 66 final.

¹⁷Regulation 2022/868 on European data governance (Data Governance Act).

¹⁸Regulation 2023/2854 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act).

¹⁹Directive 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information.

²⁰European Commission, ‘Common European Data Spaces’ (2022) SWD(2022) 45 final.

²¹European Commission. 2022. Proposal for a Regulation on European Health Data Space.

Finally, this paradigm shift towards fostering data access is not only visible in the European Strategy for Data but has also been observed in other new European digital regulations. For instance, provisions in the Digital Markets Act²² (Article 6(9)) have introduced obligations for gatekeepers to allow users to port data they provided or generated by their use of the platform's services. Noto la Diega highlights that this would reflect the clear policy stance in favor of openness via portability and access and against proprietary considerations. [NLD23] With regard to the Digital Service Act (DSA)²³ he remarks that it would leave out consumers by not doing much about private remedies. However, it would still provide incentives for opening up enclosed data by imposing obligations on intermediary service providers to, for instance, give access to data that are necessary to monitor and assess compliance with the DSA (article 31), or to provide users with information that they are being presented with advertisement, who is behind it, and which parameters were used to target them (article 24).

The legislative initiatives by the EU of the past four years therefore reflect the EU's attempt to open up data while at the same time finding a balance between new access and transparency obligations and competing interests in data. New access and/or portability obligations in the DMA, DSA, and the AI Act would therefore equally constitute part of the latest regulatory effort of the EU to end data enclosure while departing from a 'single-minded rights-based and data ownership approach'. [NLD23] At the same time, however, access and data sharing are equally conflicting with privacy and economic interests of stakeholders. Creating data access obligations might be in conflict with, for instance, motivations by companies to keep their commercial information secret or their intellectual property rights protected. Similarly, consumer might have an interest to allow third parties access their data while simultaneously remain in control of it. This challenge of allowing access to data whilst at the same time protect the interests of 'data holders' (whether companies or individuals) further informed interdisciplinary research I conducted with two other ESRs from the LeADS project which resulted in a paper that was presented at the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency in Chicago. [Zuz+23]

2.1.3.4 Facilitating Data Access and Data Sharing Through Technology: An Interdisciplinary Perspective on Data Governance

The starting point of our reflection was the evolution in EU data governance from property rights towards facilitating data access and data sharing. With a property-rights approach towards the regulation of data being discarded, we looked at literature on the Commons. Scholars on the commons have argued that an alternative approach to resource regulation, one that does not rely on property rights to prevent the tragedy of the commons²⁴, is possible". [Ost90] Since commons are based on the idea of access rather than exclusion, they would challenge the dom-

²²Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 on Contestable and Fair Markets in the Digital Sector and Amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act).

²³Regulation 2022/2065 on a Single Market For Digital Services (Digital Services Act).

²⁴A famous example for an explanation of the necessity of property rights in society constitutes the 'tragedy of the commons' elaborated by Garrett Hardin, 'The Tragedy of the Commons' (1968) 162 Science In a society without property rights, scarce resources would ultimately end up being overexploited and depleted: freedom in a commons would bring ruin to all. To avoid this tragedy, private property rights would enable efficient resource allocation through the market.

inance of private property [Mar17] or even constitute the opposite of property [MQ17]. The main function of commons would therefore be to institutionalize freedom to operate within symmetric constraints, free of the particular risk that any other can deny use of that resource set. [Ben14] The commons-framework therefore does not imply unmanaged access to a particular resource, but requires that groups engage in managed resource sharing. [Mad20] Whilst initially conceived for the management of natural resources whose characteristics are evidently very distinct from data, they would still be highly relevant with regard to data governance as they could provide insights for assessing the types of institutions needed to govern access and use of data. [MFS10] How data could be subject to regulation via commons governance institutions has been subsequently further analyzed within research on governing knowledge commons that have been defined as "institutionalized community governance of the sharing and, in some cases, creation, of information, science, knowledge, data, and other types of intellectual and cultural resources". [FMS14] Its key insight would be how information resources are governed as a shared resource via a collective and not in markets via intellectual property rights regimes or state intervention. [Mad20] New technologies thereby would have played a key role for the possible development of knowledge commons as they facilitated the ability to capture the previously uncapturable and to draw value from it by means of advanced data analytics. [Pur17]

Studies therefore attempted to adapt Ostrom's design principles for collective self-managing institutions and translate them to and extract useful insights for data governance [Ins21b] [Coy+20] [Pra19]. This further resulted in discussions and analyses [Ins21b] [WHB22], on various models of data stewardships, such as data trusts, data foundations, data cooperatives or data collaboratives [WHB22]. Data collaboratives thereby have been described as new emerging forms of partnerships where privately held data is made accessible for analysis. The collaboration between participants that is facilitated within these structures aims to result in new insights and innovation and to unlock the public good potential of previously siloed data. [Gov20] Building on that research, we analyzed how data collaboratives based on an application of decentralized learning could provide a substantial leap towards independent and self-sovereign data management inside trusted communities. By looking at both, the regulatory and the technological layer in data governance, we analyzed how legal obligations and policy objectives can be realized by technological solutions (decentralized learning). This interdisciplinary, i. e. legality attentive data scientists perspective, thus allowed us to better understand the importance of cooperating across academic fields to find legally compliant solutions to regulatory complexities.

2.1.3.5 A New Role for Consumer Law and Policy to Empower Consumers with Regard to Their Data

The data access and sharing obligations created by the various legislative instruments over the past years by the EU, however, are not as comprehensive in scope as a property rights regime for data would have been. Whereas the Data Act, for instance, certainly creates new data access rights for consumers and might thus empower them to a certain extent with regard to 'their' data, it is in no way comparable to the degree of control new property rights would have conferred to them. [Hin22] A central motivation behind my LeADS research topic, however, related

to the question how to empower individuals with regard to their data – beyond the regulatory framework created by European Data protection law. For my PhD research I thus asked myself how the law, if not through property rights, can protect and potentially empower consumers with regard to their data. In my PhD thesis I therefore conduct the first comprehensive analysis to what extent data has become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law.

Whereas data and consumer protection share the commonality that both intend to protect ‘weaker parties’ (the ‘consumer’ and the ‘data subject’) both were separate fields of law until 10 years ago. Contrary to data protection law, the consumer law acquis was firmly rooted in the analogue world and slow to adapt to legal challenges by digitisation [Hel+13b]. Data has traditionally not been subject matter that belonged to the regulatory ambit of consumer law. This, however, has changed gradually over the past decade. Today, the regulation of data is spread over various legal disciplines, with data protection law forming its core. [Str21] The EU legislator is thus confronted with the challenging task of constructing different dimensions of data law without infringing its core, i. e. to coordinate each dimension with the ‘boundary setting instrument’ of the GDPR. [DH23]

Changes in the marketplace induced by the development and rapid diffusion of information and communication technology affected both the array of goods and services available and the way consumers buy these products. [OEC10] The datafication of consumer markets would go hand in hand with the digitalisation process. [Mak18] Whilst consumers benefited from these developments it equally gave rise to new complexities and challenges. Earlier accounts in EU policy documents acknowledged that electronic commerce would have the potential to most profoundly change the relationship between businesses and consumers and the nature of consumption itself.²⁵ However, at first only the lack of harmonisation of national laws was identified as a principal problem. The resulting legal uncertainties would prevent businesses and consumers from fully taking advantage of the potential of e-commerce in the internal market²⁶. This, however, changed with the growing awareness of the importance of data for economic growth. Scholars observed how the European legislator intends to expand the internal market’s four existing freedoms (free movement of goods, services, capital, and labour) with a fifth freedom: the free flow of data. [CM22] Both national²⁷ as well as supranational institutions²⁸ increasingly recognised the importance of data for an effective consumer protection online, and that data protection and privacy rules should be included in future consumer strategy programmes. Furthermore, with the advent of Big Data in EU policy and expectations attached to data-driven innovation, data was increasingly getting framed as a new crucial economic resource (“the new oil”, “the fuel of a new industrial revolution”, a “goldmine”) to be mined and

²⁵European Commission, ‘Consumer Policy Action Plan 1999-2001’ (1998) COM(1998) 696 final 3.

²⁶European Commission, ‘Green Paper on European Union Consumer Protection’ (2001) COM(2001) 531 final.

²⁷The German Federal Ministry for Food, Agriculture, and Consumer Protection, ‘Charta on Consumer Sovereignty in the Digital World’ (2007) stressed growing the importance of data protection for consumer policy and that ensuring fair data processing would constitute a competitive advantage for companies.

²⁸In 2008 the European Parliament adopted a resolution on the EU consumer policy strategy 2007-2013, pointing out that in the digital environment personal data would have become a “trade product as well as an ingredient of commercial methods, for example behavioural targeting” and that data protection and privacy rules should therefore be included in any consumer strategy, see European Parliament, ‘Resolution of 20 May 2008 on EU Consumer Policy Strategy 2007-2013’ 2009/C 279 E/O4.

exploited and to thus “turn this asset into gold”. [Rie18] Since consumers were at the origin of this valuable resource in the online environment, it was subsequently observed that data had become a new currency with which consumers are paying ‘free’ services. This, in turn, would engage fundamental rights of consumers and would ultimately raise questions on the relationship between constitutional and contract law [Mak13]. Furthermore, if conceived as a currency, it could potentially trigger the application of various consumer law instruments related to, for instance, unfair commercial practices (services advertised as “free”) or contract law (unfair contract terms). [Slo13]

In a first attempt to address these new challenges and to facilitate the emergence of a vibrant digital single market²⁹, the European Commission proposed a Regulation on a Common European Sales Law.³⁰ To ensure that also ‘free’ digital content or services would fall under the scope of this instrument, it stipulated that it equally applied where consumers provided non-monetary consideration such as giving access to personal data. In addition to the growing number of scholars who recognised that the protection of personal data would constitute an integral part of consumer protection [Hel+13a], the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) highlighted their complementarity.

In 2014 the EDPS published a preliminary opinion on privacy and competitiveness in the age of big data where it highlighted the interplay between data protection, competition law and consumer protection in the digital economy. All three policy areas would converge around a twofold purpose: promote a thriving internal market while at the same time offering protection to the individual. An adequate regulatory response to technological change where ‘big personal data’ would have become a company asset and a currency for consumers to purchase ‘free’ services would have to rely on the three distinct policy areas. Consumer welfare would not only be determined by price but also other factors such as quality and consumer choice – both would constitute relevant concerns for data protection.

At the same time, the 2014 EDPS opinion continued, consumer welfare might be at risk where control over one’s personal information is restricted. Consumers would be blinded by deceptive advertising offers that promote services as ‘free’ despite relying on the provision of personal data. The various consumer law measures that focus on the provision of clear information about the cost and value of services would mirror the importance of transparency in data protection law and to provide information on data processing in an intelligible way. Consumer law’s concern for product safety would complement the general risk-based approach of the GDPR, its impact assessment and in general the principle of accountability. Privacy and data protection were thus described as factors to evaluate the impact by business activities on consumer welfare – both would have become entangled as part of the economic interests of consumers. A lack of interaction between consumer and data protection policy in an economy where data represents a significant intangible asset might ultimately put consumer welfare at risk and fail to set incentives for the development of privacy-enhancing services.

My PhD research thus concerned the central research question to what extent data has become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law which includes in particular the following

²⁹ European Commission, ‘A Digital Agenda for Europe’ (2010) COM(2010)245 final 7.

³⁰ ‘Proposal for a Regulation on a Common European Sales Law’ (2011) COM/2011/O635 final.

sub-questions:

- How has data become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law?
- How does the regulation of data under European consumer law complement and or/conflict with data protection law in reaching its twofold objective (i. e. the free flow of data and the fundamental right to data protection)
- What does the regulation of data under European consumer law tell us about the general regulatory approach of the EU with regard to data and about the legal conceptualisation of data in EU law?

These questions are answered through several chapters in my PhD which focus in particular on (i) how consumer law and policy developed a concern for the regulation of data over the past decades (ii) on legal anthropology and the difference between protecting ‘data subjects’ versus protecting ‘consumers’ (iii) the constitutionalization of the right to data protection and the principle of consumer protection in EU law (iv) the analysis how various EU consumer law instruments shape the regulation of data, such as the 2019 Digital Content and Services Directive , the 2005 Unfair Commercial Practices Directive , or the 1993 Unfair Contract Terms Directive and and (v) an analysis of the position of the consumer in the new data laws of the EU (such as the DA, DGA or DMA) .

Whilst I am still in the writing process of my PhD thesis, some of my findings exemplify the regulatory complexity of the data economy – a core theme of the LeADS project. Whilst consumer law certainly has the potential of protecting consumers with regard to their data, it equally conflicts with the twofold objective of European data protection law: (i) it not only protects but equally risks polluting the privacy ecosystem [Hin23] (ii) it bears the risk of undermining the objective of European data protection law of creating a fully harmonised legal framework that facilitates the free flow of data [Hin24].

2.1.3.6 Regulating Data Through Consumer Law: Protecting or Polluting the Privacy Ecosystem

The latest EU consumer agenda identified the digital transformation as one of its key areas and states that “online” consumers should be protected on a comparable level as “offline” consumers.³¹ Consequently, the impact consumer law has on the regulation of data is likely going to increase. The perspective I offer in my research should thereby further the understanding how consumer policy interacts with data protection policy. By analysing the growing importance consumer law has for the regulation and protection of consumer data my research shows how consumer law may complement as well as conflict with data protection law. Whilst consumer policy is anchored in economic market integration, the regulation of data has traditionally been anchored in data protection law which is underlined by a fundamental right rationale. Whereas it has become clear that both policy areas no longer constitute separate monoliths and are often complementary in protecting consumer data, this does not imply that their pursued objectives might not conflict with each other at times.

³¹European Commission, ‘New Consumer Agenda: Strengthening Consumer Resilience for Sustainable Recovery’ (2020) COM(2020) 696 final.

In my research I disagree with authors who claimed that data and consumer protection might clash in their objective of protecting the weaker party, i.e. when consumer law offers stronger protection to consumer data than provided by the GDPR. [Sva18] Instead, it provides a new perspective by transposing tensions that exist between consumer and environmental law to the relationship between consumer and data protection law.³² Objectives in line with the economic interest of the consumer (low prices or access to goods and services) risk not only polluting the environment, but ultimately also the privacy ecosystem. Some protective dimensions of consumer policy thus clash with data protection policy when, for instance, consumer law tends to enable data (“counter-performance”) to be commodified in consumer contracts that package pieces of data into pieces of trade. Mirroring the concept of sustainable consumption which functions as a bridge between consumer and environmental policy, it exemplified that these tensions could at least in part be overcome by stronger integrating the concept of privacy by design and by default into the consumer law acquis and thereby strengthening the ties between both policy areas.

2.1.3.7 Consumer Law and the Free Flow of Data: Upsetting the Balance of the European Data Protection Framework

My research further exemplifies how consumer law instruments, such as the 2019 Digital Content and Services Directive (DCDS) and the 1993 Unfair Contract Terms Directive (UCTD), interact with the free flow of both personal and non-personal data. In case studies on consumer directives, I demonstrate how consumer law potentially undermines the objective of data protection law to create a fully harmonized legal framework. Whilst both fields of law might often complement each other in the protection of consumer privacy, the growing intersections between consumer contract and data protection law bear the risk of leading to legal fragmentation. First, different legal traditions complicate the endeavor of harmonizing core areas of contract law, which was exemplified, for instance, by the failure of the proposal for a regulation that should create a common European Sales Law. Thus, when consumer law provisions that impact the free flow of personal data are interpreted (e. g. with regard to the unfairness assessments under the 1993 Unfair Contract Terms Directive or the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive) or implemented (e. g. with regard to the scope of the 2019 Digital Content Directive) differently on the national level, the results are heterogeneous levels of protection. Furthermore, they sometimes directly interfere with the interpretation of GDPR provisions when, for instance, the 2019 Digital Content Directive stipulates that national law should regulate contractual consequences in cases where consumers withdraw consent for the processing of personal data. Here, the result are again diverging solutions in national contract law in an area that belongs to the core of European data protection law (legal bases for the processing of personal data) and therefore should have been exhaustively harmonized on the European level through the GDPR.

³²On the link and tensions between environmental and consumer policy see e. g. Klaus Tonner, ‘Consumer Protection and Environmental Protection: Contradictions and Suggested Steps Towards Integration’ (2000) 23 *Journal of Consumer Policy* 63; Ludwig Krämer, ‘On the Interrelation between Consumer and Environmental Policies in the European Community’ in Norbert Reich and Geoffrey Woodroffe (eds), *European Consumer Policy after Maastricht* (Springer 1994).

Second, the unclear characterization of the economic value of personal data in contractual relations reflects the difficulty to articulate the different foundations of data and consumer protection law, i. e. a fundamental rights rationale versus market-oriented foundations. However, simply delegating unresolved questions that result from contrasting rationales that underlie consumer (contract) and data protection law to the national legislator and national courts, is a recipe for creating diverging national solutions. Whilst consumer protection law might have the potential to elevate the level of protection of consumer data and thus complement the fundamental right to personal data protection, it simultaneously bears the risk of leading to legal fragmentation across the EU and therefore undermining the objective of facilitating the free flow of personal data across Member States. Is there a possible solution to counter the emergence of a regulatory patchwork? EU consumer policy does not provide for an equivalent to the EDPB which, in EU data protection law, has the capability of ensuring a consistent interpretation and application of the GDPR through, for instance, the adoption of guidelines or binding decisions. Coordinated enforcement, however, among national authorities could be pursued within the Consumer Protection Cooperation (CPC) Network. In response to Facebook's 'pay-or-consent' model, consumer associations have already called for a coordinated response by the CPC-Network to provide guidance about the misleading and aggressive nature of this practice. A more sustainable solution, however, would require intervention by the EU legislator, for instance, in response to conclusions of the still ongoing fitness check of EU consumer law.³³ Commentators have already proposed an updated 'future-proof' unfairness test for the UCPD which in its current state would lack the necessary concreteness in order to respond to challenges posed by the data economy.

At the same time, the examples of the 2019 Digital Content Directive and the 2023 Data Act in my research demonstrate how not only the free flow of personal, but also non-personal data is being impacted by European consumer law and consumer interests. Contrary to the free flow of personal data, however, the risk of legal fragmentation seems less relevant. The provisions of the 2019 Digital Content Directive on the use of consumer non-personal data in case of termination of contract do not leave any room for Member States to introduce more or less stringent rules (maximum harmonization). Whilst Member States had introduced far-reaching data portability consumer rights for non-personal data in the past, such diverging (and more protective) regulation is no longer possible.³⁴ Similarly, the new data access and data sharing rights of the 2023 Data Act are directly applicable and do not bear the risk of divergent implementations in national law – with the exception of the application of the 1993 Unfair Contract Terms Directive to the contract which data holders have to conclude with consumers for the use of non-personal data. By creating an exhaustively harmonized legal framework for the use of consumer non-personal data, consumer law mirrors the approach of the European data protection framework to facilitate the free flow of data.

³³European Commission, 'Digital Fairness – Fitness Check on EU Consumer Law' (2022) https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13413-Digital-fairness-fitness-check-on-EU-consumer-law_en.

³⁴See e. g. the case of France and its law n° 2016-1321 from 7th October 2016 which amended its consumer code accordingly in article 48. See also Sergio Cámara Lapuente, 'Termination of the Contract for the Supply of Digital Content and Services, and Availability of Data: Rights of Retrieval, Portability and Erasure in EU Law and Practice', *Data as Counter-Performance - Contract Law 2.0?* (Nomos 2020).

Furthermore, both examples show and reflect that consumers in the digital economy increasingly have interests in data that go beyond the concept of informational self-determination that underlines the European data protection framework. Instead, the free flow of data becomes a pre-requisite for exercising their rights as consumers, such as being capable of freely using their IoT-device and to contract with aftermarket services of their choice – a necessity grounded more in economic needs (related to the use of consumer products) than a fundamental rights optic (related to human dignity and informational self-determination). Whilst both, the 2019 Digital Content Directive and the 2023 Data Act, enable consumers to use and access non-personal data to a certain extent, the balance of rights seems strongly skewed in favor of data holders thus confirming their position as de facto owners over such data.

2.1.4 Conclusion

2.1.4.1 Understanding the Regulatory Complexity of the Data Economy

A core theme of both my research as ESR 13 as well as of my PhD thesis has been the regulatory complexity of the data economy and the difficulty of finding appropriate legal responses that achieve policy objectives. My research as ESR 13 within Crossroad 1 in particular and the LeADS project in general investigated to what extent data property might constitute a viable instrument to solve conflicting interests in data – interests by individuals to be in control of their data as well as companies protecting and gaining access to data. Could property rights in data empower individuals with regard to their data whilst simultaneously facilitate the emergence of data markets? Could data property achieve the policy objective of ensuring that ‘data is as open as possible, as closed as necessary’? A (legality attentive data scientists) analysis of the viability of property rights in data revealed the difficulty of transposing traditional legal instruments to the regulation of data. As intangible subject matter it cannot simply be assigned as someone’s property. It would neither empower individuals with regard to their data, nor would it facilitate the emergence of data markets.

That regulatory complexity further extends to other areas of law, as analyzed throughout my PhD. My PhD thesis provides the first comprehensive analysis to what extent data has become regulatory subject matter in European consumer law. To a certain extent, consumer law does empower consumers with regard to their data and thereby fulfils a regulatory function which property rights were supposed to fulfil: it directly protects consumer interests in data when it offers protection to consumers in contracts for digital content where consumers ‘pay’ with ‘their’ data. It provides indirect protection to consumer data when it regulates unfair commercial practices that exploit consumer vulnerabilities that were revealed through the collection and processing of consumer data. At the same time, however, it equally risks undermining objectives of European data protection law when it turns consumer data into a form of payment. The idea of paying with data seems irreconcilable with the fundamental right to data protection and data processing principles such as the data minimization principle. Consumer policy that merely focuses on the economic interests of consumers thus risks polluting the privacy ecosystem. At the same time, my research showed how the regulation of data in consumer law might ultimately lead to legal fragmentation and thus undermine the objective of European

data protection law to provide a fully maximized legal framework that facilitates the free flow of data.

2.1.4.2 Understanding the Necessity of Interdisciplinary Research

The complexity of the regulation of the data economy, however, encompasses not only different legal disciplines but also academic disciplines, i. e. law and data science. For instance, whereas basic definitions of legal terms such as ‘personal data’ that lie at the core of the European data protection legal framework are often easily taken for granted by lawyers, their viability got immediately challenged by data scientists within discussions that took place throughout the LeADS project. It trained us as legal researchers to challenge the viability of traditional legal categories or instruments with regard to their application to data.

Furthermore, a legality attentive data scientist’s perspective had to be adopted during our working paper on how to implement data access and data sharing rights that ensure both: (i) giving control to data holders and protecting their privacy and economic interests with regard to their data (ii) facilitate data access and data sharing. Whereas the law may impose obligations to facilitate data access and data sharing, their implementation requires technical knowledge. A legally compliant implementation further requires a constant dialogue between lawyers who are trained in data protection law, the emerging new data laws (and other legal fields that gain in relevance such as consumer law) and data/computer scientists. Such a dialogue, however, can only be fruitful if academics from each discipline share at least to a certain extent each other’s vocabulary to arrive at a common understanding. Whilst LeADS has not transformed me into a data scientist, it certainly has made me more attentive to data science and the necessity of cooperating across academic disciplines to solve regulatory problems within the data economy.

2.2 The Interplay Between Personal Data Protection and Online Platform Market Competition under the GDPR

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2.2.1 Executive summary

This study to explore the role of personal data in the business value creation of online platforms specifically the social media market, and the impacts of the GDPR on the EU social media market concentration, based on data science, economics, and law.

The findings reveal that personal data is the foundation of online platforms, which create significant value based on personal data through content personalisation, recommendation systems, and targeted advertising. Personal data can also increase the accuracy of algorithmic predictions, thus giving online platforms more competitive advantages. From 2015 to 2020, the GDPR has resulted in a decrease in EU social media market concentration, particularly negatively impacting large social media companies. The GDPR regulation framework (including transparency, data portability, and compliance costs) curbed the dominance of leading platforms and levelled the playing field for small competitors. In the long term, the impact of the GDPR diminishes after 2020 as large companies adopt appropriate strategies to comply with the regulation. The study also identified two factors that influence the impact of the GDPR: the scale of the Internet market and the level of technology.

The study provides empirical evidence of the relationship between personal data protection and market competition. The strict personal data regulations can hinder dominant companies by large compliance costs, but regulators need to know that large companies may find ways to reduce their compliance costs over time. Personal data protection regulations need to keep pace with technological and market changes.

2.2.2 Introduction

Initially, the internet-based digital market was envisioned as an expansive global marketplace, where market players (including individuals and companies) could encounter an endless array of competitors with minimal transaction costs[NG]. With the emergence of “behemoths” bred by the digital economy, the last two decades have witnessed the breakdown of this idealistic and utopian paradigm. The distinctive structures and effects in online platforms are generally perceived as the breeding ground for big platform companies [FAG; Gaw].

In two(multi)-sided platforms, participants on both sides of the market are mutually attracted. Individual users appeal to advertisers or sellers on the other side of the platform as potential consumers, while also seeking to access the products or services they require from the vast pool of information available [NG]. The whole process can support big online platform companies to enjoy potential advantages in the accumulation of data from “a significantly larger number of third parties than other undertakings”, which comes from combining end-user personal data

collected from different services, cross-using personal data, and signing in end-users to different services to combine personal data.

While this market structure and the effects undoubtedly contribute to the current market dynamic and market share concentration in the online platform marketplace, by following up further, the current status and structure of the online platform market are the pre-determined consequence of the basic element: data and its legal or de facto rules in the market. The review of data generation reveals that the most important and valuable source of data is created by individual users [FSW]. Individual users are “no longer mere consumers of goods, information and services, but public producers of often valuable data” [JJW]. Companies based on online platforms have the economic motivation to misuse personal data without adequate protection when they can easily capture it at a low cost, since personal data have gradually become a competitive asset in the online platform market [CM; Sup]. The expanding control of user personal data from online platform companies creates an insurmountable barrier to entry for market competition in this area [New]. The judgment in *Meta Platforms Inc and Others v Bundeskartellamt* from the European Court of Justice explains the correlation between market power in the social media market and the ways to obtain personal users’ data [202].

Based on this, the personal data of users constitutes an essential element of personal interest protection as well as an important source of competitive advantages for online platform companies. Personal data has a more complex influence on data subjects and online platform companies compared to other data. Thus, striking a delicate equilibrium between the protection of personal data and economic utility is of paramount importance. Six years after the GDPR came into force, this study explores these questions from a long-term perspective: (1) How the online platform market works and the role of personal data in online platforms. (2) How the GDPR affects market concentration in the typical online platform market - the social media market.

2.2.3 Methodology

Competition law and personal data protection law are the main subjects of this study. The study requires not only a historical review of the evolution of relevant laws, theories, and principles, but also a comparative analysis of the legislation in different countries or regions. It is necessary to cover the different implications of different personal data protection rules. This study also employs some theories and methods of relevant branches of economics, like microeconomics, information economics, behavioural economics, etc. Microeconomics will provide some fundamental theories and assumptions to explain how markets and companies work and how they react to interventions. Information economics and behavioural economics will help to elucidate the rationale behind market choice, individual choice and so on. Due to the complexity of the research questions, both quantitative and qualitative analyses will be taken.

2.2.4 Literature review

Some studies have examined GDPR compliance through online tracking and cookie settings, given these significant changes in the legal text. Libert et al. investigated third-party web content and cookies on a selection of European news websites, finding a 22 percent reduction in

cookie settings without user consent and a noticeable decrease in third-party social media content [LGN]. Degeling et al. examined changes in privacy policies and cookie notices across 6,759 websites, noting that many companies updated their privacy policies before the GDPR came into effect [Deg+]. Similarly, Dabrowski et al. observed a significant 49.3 percent of cookie settings without consent on the first visit among cookie-using websites of the Alexa Top 1,000 when EU users visited these websites, suggesting the GDPR's effectiveness in curbing unwanted data collection [Dab+]. This result of personal data processing limitation is manifested as a shrinking scale of data collection after the GDPR, while on the other hand, stricter obligations bring about higher costs of data collection and protection for companies. Koski and Valmari explored the short-term impact of the GDPR on companies' financial performance by using companies-level data on EU and US companies from 2014 to 2018, finding that the compliance cost of the GDPR for EU companies was substantial and profit margins of EU data-intensive companies increased by approximately 1.7 to 3.4 percentage points less than their US counterparts [KV]. Based on these data processing limitations and the high compliance costs of the GDPR, Jia et al. reported negative impacts of the GDPR on the number of financing deals and the amount of financing for newer, data-related and business-to-consumer companies, relative to their counterparts in the US and the rest of the world [JJW]. At the market level, the impact of the GDPR is more nuanced and context-specific than industry expectations, as significant differences exist in the costs and benefits of privacy across industries and contexts [GT]. Most of the current empirical research focuses on online tracking, suggesting a drop in third-party cookies and increased concentration among web technology providers, with large companies gaining market share post-GDPR [CSS; Dab+; LGN; LMS; Peu+; SKb; Urb+]. The studies on the industry of web technologies also reported that websites reduced their connections, especially requests involving personal data to web technology providers [MA]. Website use of web technology vendors declined by 15 percent for EU residents after the GDPR, and websites were relatively more biased towards retaining the large vendors, which has led to a 17 percent increase in vendor market concentration [JSG]. In the long term, large vendors may increase their market share in key areas like advertising and analytics [Peu+]. The shrinkage of the overall market and the disproportionate impacts on dominant vendors and smaller organisations have led to an increase in the market share of the dominant vendors and the concentration of the market [Dab+; HU14; HS; LGN; SKb; Urb+]. Whilst the impact of GDPR on online tracking shows a negative trend towards market competition and smaller companies, such negative impacts do not necessarily trickle down to their upstream or downstream markets. For instance, Zhuo et al. noted a reduction in data usage in the European Economic Area relative to other markets has no visible consequences at the infrastructure layer across the multiple measures [Zhu+]. Urban et al. focused on the underlying information sharing networks among online advertising companies, and the decrease in ID syncing connections after the GDPR has no effect on the amount of tracking and the general structure of cooperation [Urb+]. Lefrere et al. also showed a similar result that "a reduction in average page views per user on EU websites" has "no statistically significant impact on EU websites' provision of new content, social media engagement with new content" [Lef+]. Not much research has been done on the impact of GDPR on one core downstream market built on data collection and platform service. This research examines the impact of the GDPR on a core downstream market built on personal data collection – the social media market. The social

media market can exemplify the typical characteristics necessary for examining the interplay between personal data protection and market dominance, such as the multitude of platform providers competing for user attention and data, and the prevalence of user engagement and targeted advertising in this ecosystem [Oca; PD]. Data is collected from each EU member state and 32 other countries over the period 2009-2022 to explore the impact of the GDPR as an EU-level regulation on the market concentration of social media in the EU as well as its impact intensity.

2.2.5 Research findings and analysis

2.2.5.1 Personal Data as the Foundation of Online Platforms

Online platforms derive revenue by providing content and products to the user side or by assisting third parties to reach the user side. When personal data is utilised for optimising the platform's own services and all-sides users' experience, it is generally considered as internal usage like personalizing content, improving algorithms, or enhancing user interactions [van+]. As more and more individual users join an online platform, the platform collects more personal data and analyses that data to improve the individual users' experience, which in turn attracts more individual users, thus creating a positive loop [PS]. Internal data usage plays an important role in fostering network effects, a critical component of online platform success [BGL; Gaw; PNF; OECb; PPVA; Per; PS; Sch]. By contrast, external usage involves leveraging the collected data to provide services or insights to third parties, such as through targeted advertising or data analytics services [van+]. For instance, online platforms mainly based on the advertising revenue model need a larger user base and more refined data analytics capabilities, enabling the platform to offer more effective advertising solutions and attract more advertisers [PV]. Such online platforms capture user-generated data and de facto monetise it for their huge profits and dominant positions [Gaw]. Given the two (multiple) sides of the online platform, both uses exist and can occur at the same time in the online platform market. Fast et al. categorised the business value creation channels from user data into three domains, i.e., content and service personalisation, recommender systems, and targeted advertising.

Content and service personalisation

Content and service personalisation is to deliver "the right content to the right person at the right time" for maximising business opportunities [TH]. The abundance of personal data and better data quality can make online platforms easily build individual user profiles that approximate users' interests and preferences [TMJ], and automatically tailor products for consumers' needs and interests [KKR; SCS]. The large amounts of data can also be used to improve Artificial Intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, or Big Data Analytics [KD], and individual users' data can be also analysed to explore patterns and trends of the market [de +; SL; SKa]. By some empirical studies, content and service personalisation can attract users to spend more time on their platform and even increase their willingness to pay [Ben]. The fulfilment of personalised needs will enhance perceived user experience [Lie+] and boost customer loyalty in different products or services markets [TS]. Content and service personalisation increases switching costs and improves customer loyalty, making it more difficult for competitors to capture customers

in online markets [AM].

Recommender systems

A recommender system is a type of information filtering system that provides the most relevant suggestions from a potentially overwhelming number of items for a specific user [RRS]. Recommender systems can highlight the products or content that align with the preferences of targeted users and reduce search costs, based on users' previous interactions [LGP]. Furthermore, recommendations are likely to boost demand and increase consumption by providing relevant products or complementary products when individual users browse an item or have already purchased an item [HL; Pat+]. The empirical studies from Adomavicius et al. also show that recommender systems can change individual users' preferences and potentially increase their willingness to pay [Ado+a; Ado+b]. In a sense, the recommender system can switch costs and improve customer loyalty, and the platform will generate revenue by charging fees to third-party merchants or users based on the recommender system.

Online Advertising

The collection and analysis of personal data is almost the most critical factor separating the online advertising market from the traditional advertising market [GT]. Large amounts of low or no-cost personal data, location tracking, and other technological developments make it possible to send different personalized advertisements to different target groups. This behavioural targeting can help reduce companies' costs and increase the probability of successful transactions, and related empirical studies confirm this value that behavioural targeting advertisements are 2.68 times more expensive than untargeted advertisements [ATb; Bea]. Farahat and Bailey estimate that the revenue generated by targeted advertisements was, on average, twice as high as that generated by untargeted advertisements [FB]. Goldfarb and Tucker revealed that with clickstream data showing the extent of a consumer's product search, the performance of behavioural targeting can be improved, and they further show that the performance of behavioural targeting can be improved when combined with clickstream data that help to identify the consumer's degree of product search [GT]. Targeting also lowers the cost of searching for consumers and improves the match between consumers and businesses [Cor]. The analysis and prediction of consumer choice and behaviour trends can assist companies in managing their supply chains more effectively and enhancing operational efficiency of companies [CV; GT]. Fast et al.(2023) categorise data-driven business value created by users' data into three main categories: (1) improved customer retention, (2) increased revenue in the consumer market, and (3) increased revenue on other market sides [FSW].

2.2.5.2 Impacts of the GDPR processing principles on data controllers under the static model

Compared to principles relating to data quality in Directive 95/46, the main improvements in principles relating to the processing of personal data under the GDPR are in the following areas: (1) higher transparency and security requirements for the processing of personal data (Article 5(1)(a) and Article 5(1)(f)); (2) stricter limitations on the scope of personal data involved in data processing (Article 5(1)(b), Article 5(1)(c), Article 5(1)(d) and Article 5(1)(e)); (3) stronger accountability requirements for data controllers (Article 5(2)). To bridge the uncertainty created by the

Figure 2.1: Data-driven business value created by personal data

principles, the GDPR also provides more detailed rules to clarify the obligations of controllers. During the pre-processing phase, the controller must plan and implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure compliance with the GDPR (GDPR Article 24), consider data security from the outset (e.g. encryption, access control), and ensure that by default only necessary data is processed (GDPR Article 25). For those processes with a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, controllers must carry out data protection impact assessments or consult with the supervisory authority in order to sufficiently identify and mitigate security risks (GDPR Articles 35-36).

Article 12 in the GDPR sets out the transparency rules of the information or communication: controllers should provide any information referred to the provision of information to data subjects (Articles 13-14), communications with data subjects concerning the exercise of their rights (Articles 15-22), and communications in relation to data breaches (Article 34) to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, without undue delay and unreasonable fares.

When processing personal data, controllers and processors must keep documentation of the processing activities (GDPR Article 30), implement appropriate technical and organisational measures (e.g. pseudonymisation and encryption) (GDPR Article 32), and promote the adoption of codes of conduct (GDPR Article 40) and authentication mechanisms (GDPR Article 42). Throughout this process, the controller must continue to monitor and assess the security measures to ensure the security level appropriate to the risk (GDPR Article 32), and notify the relevant supervisory authority and the data subject without undue delay in the case of a personal data breach (GDPR Article 33-34). And the DPO is responsible for overseeing compliance with

GDPR, including monitoring security measures, responding to data breaches, and advising the controller or processor on risk management (Article 39).

Figure 2.2: Impacts of the GDPR processing principles on online platform providers

For online platform companies as data controllers, the principles of transparency, security, accountability and their related obligations can bring about higher costs than before in theory, which may manifest as one-time costs of compliance (e.g. the cost of change to a new system or reshape the previous system) and ongoing costs of maintaining compliance (e.g. the cost of maintaining a competent system) [LYH]. According to the PricewaterhouseCoopers survey, 71 percent of survey respondents focus on information security, privacy policies, GDPR gap assessment and data discovery, and the cost of compliance is likely to exceed 1 million US dollars [Pri]. The strict limitation of the personal data scopes is most likely to have a direct negative impact on the amount of user data available to the data controller [GJS]. A pure reduction in data volume can deliver lower costs of collection, processing and storage, but the reduced data volume in the GDPR is embedded in the processing design of data minimisation, which may create some technical and administrative costs [LEC]. At the same time, the shrinking data volume may have weakened the company’s profitability somewhat [GA; Jan+].

Considering the online platform service based on personal data, the total provider revenue and total provider cost in this market are determined by two key factors: total personal data scale S

and technology level t , where $t \in (0, 1)$ represents the technological efficiency in utilizing personal data. In the baseline model, assume that total provider cost is driven by two components: fixed costs and variable costs that depend on the scale of personal data. The variable costs of processing personal data will rise as the personal data scale increases.

Let the total provider cost function, $C(S)$, be defined as:

$$C(S) = C_0 + (\alpha S + f_1(S))(1 - t)$$

where C_0 represents fixed costs, αS represents the variable cost that grows linearly with the personal data scale S , $\alpha > 0$ is the cost coefficient in this linear function, and $f_1(S)$ reflects the variable cost of a nonlinear growth function with increasing marginal cost as personal data scale expands.

In general, users on the online platform do not pay companies real money for their services, but instead provide their personal data. For companies, personal data is typically characterized by diminishing returns, i.e. the decrease in marginal benefit as the personal data scale is incrementally increased, like any other factor of production (Agrawal et al., 2019). The total revenue of the companies is given by:

$$R(S) = t f_2(S)$$

where $f_2(S)$ is a nonlinear growth function with diminishing marginal benefit as personal data scale S increases.

The marginal cost is given by:

$$MC = \frac{dC}{dS} = (1 - t) \left(\alpha + \frac{df_1(S)}{dS} \right)$$

which indicates that the marginal cost is influenced by both the variable cost per unit of data (α) and the nonlinear growth function $f_1(S)$ of costs with the impact of technology.

Similarly, the marginal revenue is derived from the revenue function:

$$MR = \frac{dR}{dS} = t \frac{df_2(S)}{dS}$$

which shows that marginal revenue depends on how much additional revenue the companies can extract from increasing their personal data scale, weighted by the technological efficiency in utilizing personal data (t).

The optimal personal data scale of production S_{pre}^* is determined by the condition where marginal cost equals marginal revenue:

$$(1 - t) \left(\alpha + \frac{df_1(S)}{dS} \right) = t \frac{df_2(S)}{dS}$$

After the GDPR, two types of compliance costs have been introduced into the cost structure: fixed compliance cost C_1 representing a one-time cost for GDPR compliance, and the variable compliance cost $C_2 = \beta S + f_3(S)$, where $\beta > 0$ is the cost coefficient and $f_3(S)$ reflects

a nonlinear growth function with increasing marginal compliance cost as personal data scale grows. The new total cost function becomes:

$$C_{\text{new}} = C_0 + C_1 + \beta S + f_3(S) + (\alpha S + f_1(S))(1 - t)$$

And the new marginal cost function is:

$$MC_{\text{new}} = \frac{dC_{\text{new}}}{dS} = \beta + \frac{df_3(S)}{dS} + (1 - t) \left(\alpha + \frac{df_1(S)}{dS} \right)$$

The new optimal personal data scale of production S_{post}^* after the GDPR is given by:

$$\beta + \frac{df_3(S)}{dS} + (1 - t) \left(\alpha + \frac{df_1(S)}{dS} \right) = t \frac{df_2(S)}{dS}$$

When comparing S_{pre}^* and S_{post}^* , the marginal benefit function $t \frac{df_2(S)}{dS}$ is consistent in both equations. However, the left-hand side of the equation for S_{post}^* includes an additional positive function $\beta + \frac{df_3(S)}{dS} > 0$, indicating that the GDPR has introduced extra costs that increase marginal costs.

Assuming that $S_{\text{post}}^* \geq S_{\text{pre}}^*$, $\frac{df_1(S)}{dS} > 0$ and $\frac{d^2 f_1(S)}{dS^2} > 0$, because $f_1(S)$ is a nonlinear growth function with increasing marginal cost. $f_1(S)$ is a convex function, so the line segment between any two distinct points on the function lies above or on the function curve, which implies:

$$\frac{df_1(S_{\text{post}}^*)}{dS} \geq \frac{df_1(S_{\text{pre}}^*)}{dS}$$

Since $\beta + \frac{df_3(S)}{dS} > 0$, the following inequality can be obtained:

$$\beta + \frac{df_3(S_{\text{post}}^*)}{dS} + (1 - t) \left(\alpha + \frac{df_1(S_{\text{post}}^*)}{dS} \right) > (1 - t) \left(\alpha + \frac{df_1(S_{\text{pre}}^*)}{dS} \right)$$

$$\frac{df_2(S_{\text{post}}^*)}{dS} > \frac{df_2(S_{\text{pre}}^*)}{dS}$$

The above inequality generates a contradiction with the inequality $\frac{df_2(S_{\text{post}}^*)}{dS} \leq \frac{df_2(S_{\text{pre}}^*)}{dS}$ given by $f_2(S)$. Since $f_2(S)$ is a nonlinear growth function with diminishing marginal benefit, $\frac{df_2(S)}{dS} > 0$ and $\frac{d^2 f_2(S)}{dS^2} < 0$. As $f_2(S)$ is a concave function, the line segment between any two distinct points on the function lies below or on the function curve. Given $S_{\text{post}}^* \geq S_{\text{pre}}^*$, we have:

$$\frac{df_2(S_{\text{post}}^*)}{dS} \leq \frac{df_2(S_{\text{pre}}^*)}{dS}$$

Thus, the increase in the compliance costs of the GDPR implies that the optimal data scale S_{post}^* must decrease, i.e. $S_{\text{post}}^* < S_{\text{pre}}^*$, which is also confirmed in the empirical studies in 2.2.5.3.

2.2.5.3 The Impact of the GDPR on Social Media Market Concentration in the EU

The synthetic control method is employed to identify and quantify the causal effect of the GDPR reform on the social media market concentration at the EU level and EU average level. The results at the EU level and at the EU average level show the GDPR reform may have an ex-ante effect caused by the legislative process with voting and publication drafts, which is evidenced by a downward trend from 2015. The negative impact of the GDPR on the EU social media market reaches a maximum in 2017, when the CR8(social media) indexes decreased by 0.252 at the EU level and by 0.383 at the EU average level.

Figure 2.3: CR8 trends in the social media market at the EU level and EU average

This decline in social media market concentration may be attributed to the following reasons: (1) Transparency and accountability in the GDPR make it harder for social media platforms to misuse user data, which gives users more control over their data and force platforms to consider the scale of data collection based on costs. (2) Data portability provisions allow users to easily move data from one platform to another, further breaking down data exclusivity and market concentration. (3) A strong data protection regulation can impose compliance costs on dominant platforms, which may level the competitive landscape as these platforms cannot leverage their data collection advantages as freely. When dominant platforms are restricted in their data processing practices, new entrants can compete more effectively without the limitations of exclusive data to offer competitive services.

After 2020, the negative impact of the GDPR on EU social media market concentration gradually diminishes. The latent reason is that leading companies have rebuilt their competitiveness through strategic adjustment to cope with the negative influence of the GDPR. Within the EU,

the results based on generalised DID estimator show that the GDPR significantly reduces market concentration within the social media sector across EU member states. Its impact on large companies in the EU social media market is more pronounced than on smaller companies. In this case, a 1 percent increase in the GDPR fines results in an approximate 0.216 reduction in market concentration among the three largest companies and a 0.0143 reduction for the eight largest companies.

Table 1. The effects of GDPR on social media market concentration

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Panel A	Two-way fixed effects estimators			
	<i>CR3</i>	<i>CR4</i>	<i>CR6</i>	<i>CR8</i>
<i>Policy</i> × <i>lnFines</i>	-0.216** (0.097)	-0.127** (0.060)	-0.0502** (0.019)	-0.0143*** (0.005)
Constant	128.0 (216.237)	119.8 (132.464)	154.0*** (51.339)	108.1*** (14.468)
Observations	324	324	324	324
Adjusted R ²	0.741	0.748	0.699	0.648
Panel B	de Chaisemartin & D'Haultfoeuille (2020)'s <i>DID_M</i> estimators			
<i>DID_M</i>	-0.1472*** (0.0227)	-0.0924*** (0.0149)	-0.0151*** (0.0067)	-0.0062*** (0.0015)
<i>DID_M^{t=2016}</i>	-0.6146*** (0.1907)	-0.6011*** (0.1794)	-0.1353** (0.0615)	-0.0342* (0.0195)
<i>DID_M^{t=2017}</i>	-1.772*** (0.4914)	-1.0669*** (0.3508)	-0.0989 (0.1712)	-0.1796*** (0.0646)
<i>DID_M^{t=2018}</i>	-2.4300*** (0.7367)	-1.3146*** (0.4614)	-0.4289* (0.2445)	-0.1946*** (0.0720)
Baseline controls	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES
Country fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES

Note: The values above each variable in parentheses represent their estimated coefficients, and the values in parentheses are the corresponding robust standard errors with country-level clustering. The significance levels are denoted as *, **, and *** which indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively. *DID_M* in this table is the simple average of the yearly effects starting from the years after the GDPR adoption (i.e., years after 2016) using the *DID_M* estimation suggested by de Chaisemartin and D'Haultfoeuille (2020). The *DID_M* Stata package provides the standard errors directly. Baseline controls involve *lnGDP_{pc}*, *Researchers*, *FBS*, *MCS*, *Government*, *Regulatory*, and *lnPopulation*. All control variables are included with the interaction of year fixed effects to control the corresponding time trends. We do not report the estimated coefficients of the above control variables due to the content limitation.

This difference may result from the heterogeneity in market share and technological levels, so this study further explores the moderating effect of the Internet market scale and high technologies between the GDPR and the social media market concentration in each EU member state. In social media markets, specifically, the Internet market scale to some extent enhances the impact of the GDPR because the compliance costs imposed by the GDPR clearly have a theoretical positive correlation with the scale and complexity of the market. With larger companies being hit more, SMEs may benefit from the reduced dominance of these larger firms. In this case, the large number of new entrants in the social media market may strongly shock the market concentration of the leading companies. Meanwhile, higher technological levels will likely mitigate the negative impact of the GDPR on smaller companies rather than the top companies. The technological advantage can help companies in the social media market to adapt to new regulatory systems faster and at a lower cost. Besides, the large companies with technological advantages in the social media market will likely come under strong attention from the DPAs,

thereby decreasing their market concentration more obviously than smaller companies.

In-space placebo tests use randomly selected fake treatment units and in-time placebo tests employ fake treatment times. In the in-time placebo test, the adoption of GDPR (i.e., 2016) is shifted forward by one to four years (i.e., from 2015 to 2012) to create four false GDPR adoption periods. The impact of the GDPR on social media market concentration is then re-estimated. The estimated results are shown in 2.4 and 2.5. After including control variables, the in-time placebo test results show that the estimated coefficients are all nonsignificant at the 5 percent level, which indicates that the impact of GDPR on social media market concentrations in the EU is not attributable to potential effects generated by other policies.

Figure 2.4: Results of the in-time placebo test (without control variables)

The fake GDPR fines are randomly assigned to EU states, and regression is run to simulate random interference of the GDPR on social media market concentration. Iterating the above process 500 times yields a density plot of tin-space placebo estimated coefficients, as shown in 2.6. The figure shows that the true estimated coefficients are very far from the fake coefficients, which suggests that the effect of the GDPR on social media market concentration is not affected by unobservable random factors.

2.2.6 Conclusions

The value creation from online platforms comes in the forms of communication, information, matching, and choice or diversity [Eur], and the network effects service as unique boosters for the process of their value creation. The existence of online platforms is finally to assist with economic decisions by participants through their services to match or integrate the information [Agy+; Gaw; Gen+; HMK; Hei+; Sem; SMJ]. As Sachs notes in his book “The Ages of Globalization: Geography, Technology, and Institutions”, economic decisions are made by software

Figure 2.5: Results of the in-time placebo test (after including control variables)

programs in the digital age, not by management in the modern industrial age [Acs+; Sac]. This shift underscores that the cornerstone and original source of online platforms even the digital economy is based on the generation and analysis of data that the online platform or subjects hold [Gaw], especially the personal data [ATa]. The value creation of online platforms is intrinsically linked to their ability to capture and utilise user data. By controlling user interactions and accumulating vast databases of user activities, online platforms enhance their services and create market dependencies that shape the dynamics of the digital economy.

This work empirically studies the impact of the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on the social media market concentration in the EU, employing both the synthetic control method and the generalized difference-in-differences method. The findings reveal that the GDPR significantly reduced social media market concentration from 2015 to 2020, with a stronger impact on large companies. However, in the long term, the impact of the GDPR on EU social media market concentration is gradually fading, which has been very weak after 2020. Furthermore, the impact strength of the GDPR on the social media market concentration can be changed by Internet market scales and high technology levels. These insights contribute to a deeper understanding of how data protection policies shape the market dynamics of social media companies. This study along with other studies offers strong causal evidence of the interplay between personal data protection and digital market competition, and further proves that the impact of privacy protection is nuanced and context-specific [GT]. This means that the regulation of personal data protection is no longer the task of a single authority, but requires close cooperation across regulatory fields, such as market competition, consumer protection, and artificial intelligence. To ensure that the GDPR is effectively enforced, the DPAs should choose a regulatory model with long-term impact, and the regulatory practices should evolve with changes in technologies and market areas. A more cautious stance should be taken

Figure 2.6: Results of the in-space placebo test

in the regulation of the GDPR, such as more consideration of its context - the Internet market scale and high technology level, etc.

2.2.7 Future work

This study attempts to provide a new perspective on the impact of the GDPR on social media market concentration in the EU, but also has some limitations. First, the study focuses on the GDPR framework at the EU level, providing a general EU perspective while leaving much potential for future in-depth research on the differences between EU member states, especially in terms of the incorporation of the GDPR framework into national laws as well as the regulatory models. In addition, while this study compares key aspects of the EU, the US, and China, it lacks detailed, systematic analyses of legal texts, market structures, and regulatory models. Further research on global personal data governance and regulatory harmonisation is needed to address these gaps.

This study's discussion of personal data disclosure and optimal personal data scale relies on several theoretical assumptions such as rational choice theory, without deeply exploring the game between market players. Future research could relax these assumptions and conduct a more dynamic analysis of the strategic interactions around data disclosure and optimal data scale in this market. Moreover, consumer trust and engagement, overall welfare, as well as competition dynamics in the online platform ecosystem need to be explored in depth. Surveys or experiments could be designed to assess the trade-offs users perceive between utility and personal data protection.

Given that this study explored the fading negative impact of the GDPR on market concentration after 2020, a longitudinal analysis could be conducted in future research to assess the evolu-

tion of GDPR compliance and how platforms are adapting their business models in response to regulatory changes. This could include case studies of social media platforms and their strategic adjustments over time. Besides, the synthetic control evaluation can continue to be improved, such as increasing sample sizes and including more variables for accuracy.

2.3 Unchaining Data Portability

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2.3.1 Executive summary

This report summarizes the research performed in the framework of the Legality Attentive Data Scientist project, a Marie Skłodowska Curie Action funded by the European Union. The findings are coalescing into a Ph.D thesis valid as Joint Doctorate of the National Doctorate in Artificial Intelligence from the University of Pisa and of the Doctorate in Laws from the Vrije Universiteit Brussel. The research is devoted to analyze the opportunities and challenges surrounding data portability within the European Union's regulatory landscape. The report offers a thoughtful exploration of its dual role: empowering individuals to control their own data while shaping the dynamics of data-driven markets. It also introduces a fresh approach—the legality attentive data scientist (LeADS) method—to uncover the nuanced tensions that underpin data portability, presenting it as a microcosm of the broader struggles within EU data policy.

A key issue highlighted in the research is the current ambiguity surrounding data portability. At present, there is no clear consensus on how much or what type of data should be transferable to meet legal standards. The research of this report argues that by focusing on data quality, and more specifically, how well data serves its intended purpose (“fitness for purpose”), it is possible to develop a clearer benchmark to guide existing and future regulatory reforms. This insight is far-reaching, with implications not only for the legal frameworks that govern our digital lives, but also for how data markets evolve, how digital businesses build their models, and how fundamental rights are protected in the process.

Bringing together perspectives from law, market competition and technology, this research underscores the need for interdisciplinary approaches when tackling the complex regulatory issues of the digital age. It provides valuable reflections on the current trajectory of data portability, while also laying the groundwork for deeper discussions on the relationship between data quality and regulation.

2.3.2 Introduction

2.3.2.1 Background

In the midst of a rapidly expanding digital era, businesses, personal lives, and relationships are increasingly dependent on a wide range of digital services and products to function both effectively and efficiently. Much of our offline existence has seamlessly integrated with the online world, to the point where, for many, life without constant internet connectivity or the convenience of digital services is almost unimaginable.

Every day, individuals interact with an extensive array of digital platforms. For instance, consumers and professionals alike use messaging applications such as WhatsApp, Signal, or Telegram to communicate with friends, family, and colleagues. Email services, like Gmail, Thunderbird, and Outlook, facilitate ongoing work communications. Social networks, such as Facebook,

Instagram, TikTok, and LinkedIn, serve as spaces for maintaining relationships, sharing photos and updates, sending messages, and exchanging content. Cloud-hosting services like Google Drive, OneDrive, and Dropbox are widely used to store documents, photos, presentations, and videos. Online marketplaces, including Amazon and Vinted, connect buyers and sellers, while software platforms like Google Playstore and Apple Appstore provide access to a variety of services. Even in the real estate sector, platforms like Airbnb and Booking support users in finding rental properties.

The use of these services generates a vast volume of data, typically acquired by the individual digital service providers. Messages, photos, posts, emails, listings, videos, and documents are collected, processed, stored, and managed according to the specific requirements of each system. Once this data is transformed to meet the technical specifications of digital infrastructures and stored, it effectively resides with entities often referred to as “data holders.” However, the question of ownership arises: who “owns” this data held by these service providers? Do individuals not possess certain rights over personal photos, conversations, or private documents, given that they directly concern them and, to some extent, *belong* to them? Should consumers not have the intuitive right to cease using a platform and reclaim what is rightfully theirs? It would indeed seem unreasonable if, when changing banks, one were denied the right to transfer their deposits. Similarly, should there not be a right to reuse data that has been uploaded, generated, or published? For professionals managing an e-commerce website via a hosting platform, renting out properties through Booking, or handling communications through Microsoft Teams, should there not be the right to terminate a service contract and switch to a more competitive provider offering better terms?

If these questions appear rhetorical, it is because the vast majority of consumers would undoubtedly answer them in the affirmative.

Nonetheless, many—including some of us—have encountered situations where switching digital service providers resulted in the loss of all data stored with the previous provider.³⁵ Others may have avoided changing services entirely, unwilling or unable to risk losing the data held within the initial system. In such instances, users become victims of lock-in practices. These tactics, along with other factors characteristic of digital and platform economies, have contributed to the disproportionate growth of certain tech giants that now possess vast amounts of global data, functioning as *de facto* monopolies in the data economy.[Pur]

It is no coincidence that when asked to name leading messaging services, most individuals would readily cite WhatsApp; for social media, Facebook and Instagram; for professional cloud services, Amazon Web Services; and for search engines, Google Search and Safari. However, identifying alternatives to these dominant platforms often proves to be a far more challenging task.

Why is this the case?

At market level, the evolution of data dynamics, particularly with web 2.0 and cloud computing, has significantly transformed the nature of data flows.[Li19] A mixture of new business models based on the commodification of personal data and digital advertising, strong network effects and economies of scale, the concentration of market power with a rise of new *de facto* data

³⁵One example might be switching operating systems on a phone or computer.

monopolies, the creation of data-driven markets with high barriers to entry, and the rise of the platform economy,[Zub19; CA23] has led to “structured and durable” market failures.[AAGP20] Acknowledging such failures,³⁶ and realizing that no existing competition law mechanism could resolve them,[Mar+20] the EU strategic response to the established predominance of American and Chinese tech giants³⁷ has been the creation of an alternative digital ecosystem of open,[Lan+20] shareable, and reusable data—as outlined in the European Commission’s “A European strategy for data.”[Com20c]

The European Strategy for Data aims to create a single market for data, enabling its free flow across sectors and countries within the EU while respecting data protection principles and ensuring security. It seeks to empower individuals, businesses, and public institutions by increasing access to high-quality data to foster innovation, economic growth, and public welfare. It also strive to establish clear rules on data use, promote data portability, and support the development of European data spaces in various sectors like health, agriculture, and finance.

Such ecosystem, necessarily fueled by constant and free flows of data, requires that virtually all data, both personal and non-personal data, be portable, so to create a European data space³⁸ where to fulfil the foundational tenets of the European Union through free movement of goods, services, people, capital, “and now data.”[ZZ21]

Data portability offers a solution to these issues. It enables a set of data to be easily transferred across different software applications, operating systems, or devices, with minimal friction or loss of functionality. Data portability—at least in theory—has the potential to reduce lock-in practices, lower switching costs, and enhance consumer welfare, thereby positioning itself as one of the most vital tools in the European regulator’s arsenal.

The Impact of Data Portability on Fundamental Rights, Consumer Welfare, and Market Competition When a user, whether as a data subject, consumer, or business entity, seeks to switch service providers while retaining the data they uploaded or generated with the previous provider, fundamental rights come into play. These include the right to data protection and control over personal data (Art. 8 of the Charter),[Par12] the right to a high level of consumer protection (Art. 38 of the Charter), and the freedom to conduct business (Art. 16 of the Charter), which inherently implies access to undistorted competition. It therefore follows that if the current data holder employs lock-in tactics—such as preventing users from transferring their conversations from one messaging service to another, or restricting the migration of applications, content, or websites—this would surely interfere with, or even violate, these fundamental rights.

Undesirable lock-in situations have significant detrimental effects. They not only limit individuals’ autonomy in managing their personal information, but also negatively impact consumer welfare and market dynamics by restricting healthy competition among service providers. As a result, the emergence of more advantageous alternatives for consumers is stifled.

³⁶See the Explanatory Memorandum to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector (Digital Markets Act) COM/2020/842 final.

³⁷Quoting from the European Data Strategy: “In the US, the organisation of the data space is left to the private sector, with considerable concentration effects. China has a combination of government surveillance with a strong control of Big Tech companies over massive amounts of data without sufficient safeguards for individuals.”

³⁸Defined as a “genuine single market for data, open to data from across the world – where personal as well as non-personal data, including sensitive business data, are secure”.

The European policymaker has recognized that these practices, beyond creating market distortions, have also locked up a vast amount of data that is highly valuable to the market, public administrations, and European citizens. In an increasingly data-hungry world, where every decision—from the most personal and individual to the most complex and coordinated—is becoming data-driven,[Com20c] the European policymaker has begun to pursue a policy more inclined toward the proportional and appropriate sharing and reuse of data, not only held by public bodies but also by private entities.

Recognizing the immense value that unlocked data could offer, the European policymaker has developed strategies aimed at encouraging greater data sharing. A series of policies and subsequent legislation has followed, aimed precisely at unlocking as much data as possible, so that it can be accessed and used for the benefit of all. It is within this context that the concept of data portability emerges as a necessary requirement for fostering a more competitive digital market.

2.3.2.2 Objectives and Scope

In the realm of data governance, the European Union has increasingly acknowledged the significance of data portability as integral to the Union's policies.[Com20c] However, despite its introduction, the right to data portability has been,[Com20b] and still is underutilized today. If it is established that implementing data portability is so crucial for the European policymaker, and considering that—if not the European policymaker—who else should be capable of achieving this goal given their vast resources, what then are the main obstacles?

In order to understand the reasons behind data portability's dormancy, the primary research question guiding this research is: to what extent are the current EU legal framework and digital economy landscape adequate for upholding the beneficial effects of data portability? Additionally, it explores whether a gap exists between the potential and the expressed power of data portability, and if so, how legal and technical barriers hinder its full realization. Finally it delves into the analysis of what principles should guide the design of information systems and tools for data portability.

The scope of the research covers three key dimensions:

- **Legal Dimension:** Assessing the adequacy of existing regulations. The work done proposes a detailed examination of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Digital Markets Act (DMA), and Data Act (DA), focusing on how these regulations conceptualize and limit data portability rights.
- **Market Dimensions:** Exploring how data portability impacts competition and the structure of data-driven markets. Drawing on works such as the Drexl *et al.* report,[Dre+22] the research examines how portability impacts market structures, particularly the risks of cementing the power of dominant data holders.
- **Technological Dimension:** Investigating how technological solutions to data portability, especially regarding data quality and formats, can shape legal and economic outcomes. The investigation focuses on structured data formats, such as JSON and XML, and on

the technical complexities of ensuring portability across heterogeneous systems. The research also considers the challenges of syntactic, semantic, and content heterogeneity.

2.3.2.2.1 Research's Main Argument: The Indeterminacy of the Content of Data Portability's Obligatory Claim Through the analysis of the three key dimensions, the ultimate objective of this work is to convince the reader that the greatest obstacle to realizing data portability is the non-determinability of the content of data portability's obligatory claim.

The subject matter of the legal obligation to data portability, according to the normative provisions, is incorporated in the data provided by the right holder. To say it differently, the right holder can request the simple delivery of the data they have provided. However, this determination is only seemingly straightforward, as it is fraught with complexities in its practical application. In concrete terms, the right holder has no certain way of knowing exactly how much data they have actually provided, nor how much has been processed and recorded by the service provider/obligated party—except through a complex procedure that does not guarantee the genuineness of the obligated party's response. Further complicating the matter is that even if the obligated party acted in good faith to make the requested data available, they may still not provide a sufficient amount of *information* with respect to the purposes of the portability request. Discussions about reusability and data content can be found in [Pub21] This also means that not only it would not be possible for an appointed judge to assess the adequacy of the performance by the obligated party, but also for a portability right holder to know the extent of their right.

Among the essential characteristics of an obligation is that it must be determined or determinable, meaning that, from the outset of the relationship, the content of the performance must be identified or, at the very least, all necessary elements must be present to define the performance when it is due to be executed.

For any justice system to operate effectively on the basis of rights and obligations, these obligations must be either determined or determinable.

This work will support and demonstrate the following statement: in the case of data portability, *obligations are neither determined nor determinable*. No metrics have been established to define the adequate content of a ported data set, preventing a data portability right holder from objecting that “necessary information is missing,” an obligor from asserting fulfillment of the obligation, or a judge from effectively ruling on the matter.

2.3.2.3 State of the Art

The conversation around data portability sits at the intersection of law, market competition, and digital technologies with each field bringing its own perspective to how we understand and shape the concept.

2.3.2.3.1 The Metamorphosis of Data Portability in EU law An early insight supporting this research is the recognition that the meaning of data portability has significantly morphed as it has been carried across various regulations. What began as a consumer-focused right to transfer

data between service providers has gradually transformed into a market-driven obligation for providers to ensure data availability.

Legally, data portability is primarily governed by Article 20 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which gives individuals the right to transfer their personal data between service providers in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format. More recent regulations, like the Digital Markets Act (DMA) and the European Data Act (DA), have expanded on this right, introducing obligations for major digital players, or “gatekeepers,” to promote wider data-sharing practices. The literature has often focused on analyzing the concept of data portability within individual legislative texts, such as the GDPR, DMA, or DA. However, the research conducted adopts a holistic and cross-regulatory analysis of the legal texts to demonstrate that there is not just one unified concept of data portability. Instead, there are several concepts—often ontologically quite different—that are nonetheless referred to by the same name, despite having distinct natures, purposes, and implications depending on the regulatory framework in which they are situated.

Through the deconstruction of the concept of portability in its basic building blocks that is, data movability, data transportability, and data ease of carry, different regulations envision data portability diversely. At its basic level, the concept of data portability should embed the characteristics of data movability from one place and of transportability in a context dependent, sufficiently easy fashion. This notwithstanding, regulations such as the GDPR, Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation (FFNPD) and DMA each directly define or indirectly intend portability as a set of data (a dataset, in fact) to be treated differently, depending on, for instance, the use of specific technical data format, the timing of service provision, and so on.

The literature analysis reveals that data portability is not merely a matter of individual rights—which characterizes it, as such, as already complex,[\[Alb14\]](#) but also a regulatory tool aimed at fostering competition in the digital market. Relevant scholarship notes that portability serves as a bridge between data protection and competition law,[\[GHP18\]](#) enabling users to break free from the lock-in effects of dominant digital service providers, thereby promoting market dynamism.[\[DH+18; GHP18; Lun22; Lyn20\]](#) This duality—portability as a personal right and as a market regulator—[\[Cor16\]](#) presents a significant challenge for regulators, who must balance these sometimes conflicting goals.[\[Syr+21; Kra+23; TT24; SL13; VU17; Man21\]](#) In fact, contrary to the beliefs of the Article 29 Working Party,[\[Par17b\]](#) it is not possible to regulate data portability without impacting on data markets and data-based businesses and services.

2.3.2.3.2 Data Portability as Microcosm of Unresolved Conflicts Understanding the informational background of the right to data portability cannot be confined to its inter-legal conceptualization, but must extend to its role as a conceptual representation of unresolved conflicts that permeate the digital ecosystem today.

In traditional, non-digital contexts, individuals maintain control over their private information by limiting disclosure and protecting it through various means. However, once that information crosses a “line of secrecy” and enters the public domain or is shared with third parties, it becomes vulnerable. A crucial characteristic of data governance is that once data exits the control of the individual, it is nearly impossible to “regain control over it.”[\[Koo14\]](#) In the physical world,

assets can be retrieved or secured through reactive measures, such as recovering a stolen car. In contrast, in the digital realm, data is non-rivalrous and non-excludable, meaning that once shared, it is difficult, if not impossible, to retract or fully control.[Spi+15]

Counter-intuitively, the concept of data portability is built on the premise of reinforcing individual control through enhanced data sharing. Yet it has been argued that the corporate emphasis on privacy-as-control, on which data portability policies are based, serves rather the data extraction goals of companies than the true interests of users.[Wal21a] The pretence that more sharing equals more control is a facade, in reality allowing corporations to “justify their data-gathering practices” while giving users the illusion of control.

If anything, data portability tends to exacerbate the problem of data sharing rather than solve it. Once data is ported, it often ends up being further distributed, leading to further processing and exploiting by third parties and diminishing individuals’ control. Historically, critical privacy issues stemmed not from the initial data controller’s collection of data, but from the lack of mechanisms to control how the data could be shared with third parties.[Koo11] Thus, allowing users to port their data does not equate to giving them genuine control. Instead, it expands the number of recipients who can potentially misuse or exploit that data, leading to what Mitchell describes as a false sense of autonomy.[Mit23] As Koops rightly emphasizes,[Koo14] data protection regulations, as they are currently written, offer only an illusory form of control. Informational self-determination, the very principle on which data protection is built, becomes unenforceable in a world where data, once shared, can no longer be meaningfully controlled. This illusion of control provided by data portability, far from empowering users, aligns more closely with competition law than with privacy protection. Graef[GHP18] and Purtova and Newell[PN24] argue that data portability might be more suited for regulating competition and innovation, rather than being seen as a genuine privacy-enhancing tool.

Thus, the concept of data portability, while seemingly empowering, ultimately contributes to the proliferation of data-sharing, and weakens individuals’ grasp over their personal data. Rather than providing a solution to privacy concerns, data portability might be better understood as a mechanism designed to stimulate competition and innovation in the digital market, but with limited efficacy in truly enhancing user control.

Evidence suggests that portability can serve as the quintessence—the epitome, even a microcosm—of the various conflicts and tensions that exist within the realm of data regulation, between control and re-use, between protection and free-flow.

Some core tensions both inherent generally in data regulation and specifically in the study of portability are here summarized:

- *Privacy as confidentiality vs. privacy as control*: [GA16] Data portability challenges the notion of privacy, shifting from a focus on secrecy to a dynamic of empowering users with control over their data.
- *Opacity vs. transparency*: [DHGo6a] data portability raises questions about the transparency of systems and whether users truly understand what happens to their personal data once shared and reused.

- *Protection vs. free flow*: the right to data portability embodies the tension enshrined in article 1 of GDPR between safeguarding personal data and promoting the free flow of information across services.
- *Data minimization vs. reusability through multiplication*: the GDPR principle of data minimization, requiring that only the personal data that is necessary, relevant, and limited to the specific purpose for which it is being processed should be collected and retained, which is central to personal data protection, can conflict with the European Data Strategy goals of data reusability and portability.
- *Privacy vs. data protection*: while related, privacy—interpreted as the right to be left alone—and data protection—which allows third-party data processing for legitimate interests—can clash in the context of data portability, as seen in the balancing of individual rights and broader regulatory objectives.
- *Informational self-determination vs. informational self-determination*: Portability both strengthens and complicates the notion of informational self-determination, offering control while introducing new risks of third-party use.
- *Private protection vs. sharing and reusing*: Users are expected to protect their personal data, but at the same time, data portability encourages them to share and reuse it across platforms.
- *Business data protection vs. data market competition*: Portability poses challenges to businesses that aim to protect proprietary data, as it could facilitate competition by enabling easier access to consumer data by competitors.

This tension-filled landscape underscores the complex and multifaceted nature of data portability, touching on nearly all key areas of data law and policy. Some of such concepts are in the following—by no means exclusive—list: data governance, fundamental rights protection, data control, fairness, digital markets competition, personal and non-personal data protection, information system design, technological reference architectures, data modelling, artificial intelligence, market power, economics of data, data security, and more.

In this microcosm of tensions, it is also possible to observe an evolutionary parallel between, on the one hand, European policies on the management of the digital economy, markets, and digital services, both public and private, and on the other, the concept of data portability. It becomes evident how the focus has shifted from more protective models regarding data generated by individuals, businesses, and public administrations, supported by an individualistic approach to data, towards a model of sharing and reuse, supported by a pro-social approach.

2.3.2.3.3 Technological Landscape for Data Portability: Heterogeneity of Syntax, Structure, Semantics... and Content! After observing that data portability has undergone a conceptual transformation throughout its historical and legal evolution, and that the complexity of its regulation and implementation stems—if not primarily—from its role as an emblem of longstanding

conflicts within the digital society, the analysis of its informational background must inevitably shift focus towards the *technical and technological* aspects.

The technical literature highlights the intrinsic complexity of data portability, particularly due to, on the one hand, the foundational difference between data and information, and, on the other, to the heterogeneity of data formats,[USM18] structures,[Fl14; Flo11; Nic21; Bat+16; Gel22; Flo10; PN24] and metadata across different services.[Jan17]

Differences Between Data and Information In the context of personal data portability, there is a crucial distinction between “data” and “information.” The GDPR equates data with information, defining personal data as “any information relating to an identifiable natural person.” However, this equation raises fundamental questions. The conceptual separation between data and information is often overlooked, with the two terms being used synonymously, leading to ambiguities in both legal interpretations and technical applications.[Byg15; Zino7; HDH16]

Scholars such as Bygrave, Gellert, and Floridi have ventured into this complex distinction, yet the debate remains underexplored in both doctrine and case law.[Byg15] The challenge lies in their ontological differences: while data is often considered objective, syntactic, and quantitative, information is perceived as subjective, semantic, and qualitative.[Ros13] This creates a minefield for regulation, particularly when it comes to obligations like data portability, which require a precise understanding of what is being transferred and controlled—whether data or information. The literature reveals varied approaches to defining these terms, particularly within information theory.[CH03; Flo11]

The legal field complicates matters by adopting inconsistent definitions across regulations. For instance, while the GDPR treats data as synonymous with information, the Data Act distinguishes between data as a digital representation and information as the interpretation of such data—as already noted in [Ros13] This distinction in legal texts has significant implications for the scope and application of data portability, as well as for broader digital regulations. There seem to exist varied regulatory logics within the GDPR itself. While data portability is treated as a right on data—therefore as meaning-agnostic right—many other GDPR provisions, such as rights to accuracy and rectification, are clearly meaning-driven, necessitating an understanding of the information’s semantic content.[PN24] This dual approach within the same regulation reflects a broader struggle to appropriately address both syntactic and semantic dimensions of data in a coherent legal framework.

The importance of distinguishing between data and information is not a theoretical exercise, but a fundamental issue for effective legal regulation of the digital society. Without this clarity, “data laws” risk being blunt instruments that fail to address the nuanced challenges posed by the digital age.

Data Syntax and Structure in Data Portability The technical scholarship examines the complexities of data formats, syntax, structure, and metadata in relation to data portability. It acknowledges the role of syntax in data handling and communication, drawing a parallel between grammatical rules in natural languages and the syntactic formalism of programming languages. Each programming language has its own syntax, which determines the structure and sequence of elements, as noted by Li,[LF21] who emphasizes that the correct organization and encoding of data within a format is essential for it to be readable and valid for machine processing .

The structural formalism of data is equally crucial. Different types of data structures—structured, unstructured, and semi-structured—present varying challenges for data portability. Unstructured data, such as text documents or multimedia files, lacks a predefined schema, making it difficult to query or process. Structured data, exemplified by tabular formats like CSV, follows strict schemas that allow for efficient querying and processing. Between these two extremes lies semi-structured data, typified by formats such as XML and JSON, which contain tags or markers that provide a loose structure for hierarchical relationships. While these semi-structured formats are widely used in Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and web services, they bring challenges due to their relative lack of strict constraints, as discussed by Wong and Henderson,^[WH18] who note that such lax constraints often hinder seamless data portability.

The literature also highlights the importance of schema heterogeneity in data portability. The integration of data from diverse sources, each with its own schema, presents significant challenges. *Doan et al.* illustrate that even when the same requirements are given, different developers will produce distinct schemas.^[DH12] Schema conflicts arise from differences in naming conventions (synonyms and homonyms) and the organizational structure of data, leading to logical mismatches between systems. This heterogeneity complicates data portability, as the importing system must often develop specific import procedures to accommodate the schemas of exporting providers.

In the context of data portability, machine readability of data is paramount. Regulations such as the GDPR require data to be ported in a “machine-readable” format, which mandates that the data be organized in a way that machines can automatically process. Formats like CSV, JSON, and XML are frequently cited in the literature as examples of machine-readable formats. However, as *Kranz et al.* argue,^[Kra+23] despite the technical compliance of many formats, true interoperability often falters when systems fail to adhere to standardized schemas. The challenge of maintaining machine readability and ensuring consistent data interpretation across systems remains a central concern in the literature.

Metadata plays a critical role in data portability.^[WH19a] Metadata—data about data—provides necessary context for understanding and processing dataset. Effective metadata allows systems to interpret the structure and content of data, but inadequate metadata can lead to significant obstacles in achieving true data portability. The lack of clear guidelines on the types and standards of metadata to accompany ported data exacerbates the challenges faced by service providers. Furthermore, metadata standards like the Dublin Core Metadata Terms (DCMT) and Data Catalog (DCAT) vocabulary are essential for achieving interoperability, as they provide a structured framework for cataloging and describing data, so improving interoperability. Yet, without sufficient documentation or standardized metadata, the receiving system may struggle to make use of the ported data.

In summary, the literature emphasizes that the success of data portability hinges on a combination of factors, including adherence to syntactic rules, the resolution of schema heterogeneity, and the provision of adequate metadata. While semi-structured formats like XML and JSON provide flexibility, they also present challenges in achieving the level of structural consistency required for seamless data exchange. The role of metadata in ensuring both machine-readability and semantic interoperability is crucial but remains underdeveloped in current reg-

ulatory frameworks. As the literature demonstrates, addressing these technical issues is vital for realizing the goals of data portability as envisioned by regulations such as the GDPR, the DMA and the Data Act.

Semantic Heterogeneity and Data Portability Semantic heterogeneity, the challenge of aligning meaning across different data systems, is a key issue in the context of data portability. It is important to understand how data retains or loses meaning in the transfer between systems. The relevant literature focuses, once again, on the distinction between data and information, the role of semantic heterogeneity, and approaches for resolving these issues through database integration methods.

Wand and Weber outline two critical processes in information systems: [WW93] representation transformation, where a real-world system is modeled and populated with data, and interpretation transformation, where the system is used to infer insights. [Hil18] The disconnection between these two processes is particularly problematic in data portability because the data is generated and formatted in one system (the source) but interpreted in another (the recipient). Hildebrandt emphasizes the challenge of aligning these two transformations, as the meaning of data is often tied to its original context.

The distinction between data and information is central to understanding semantic heterogeneity. Data refers to the raw symbols or signs, while information is the meaning derived from them. Veltman [Velo1] and Shannon [Sha48] argue that for effective communication, both syntax (structure) and semantics (meaning) must be aligned. Shannon's entropy theory, which measures the uncertainty or randomness in a set of data and quantifies the amount of information needed to describe its possible outcomes, suggests that in communications, the goal is to reduce uncertainty so that the receiver correctly interprets the message. In data portability, this problem is exacerbated because the receiving system often has different expectations or requirements for data usage than the originating system, which leads to misalignment in the transfer of meaning.

The literature shows that there have been plenty of approaches to addressing semantic heterogeneity, particularly from the field of database integration, which offers useful solutions for resolving these challenges. Rahm and Bernstein describe semantic schema mapping as a common method for addressing discrepancies between different systems. [RBo1] Schema mapping involves aligning vocabularies or data structures across systems to ensure that data retains its intended meaning when transferred. Noy *et al.* [NDH05] and Doan [DHI12] extend this by focusing on creating unified semantic frameworks for integrating heterogeneous databases. AI and machine learning approaches are also emerging as effective tools for resolving semantic inconsistencies. Koutras highlights the ability of AI to analyze large datasets and recognize patterns, even when the data is unstructured or semi-structured. [Kou19] These techniques can help systems learn to reconcile differences between data sources, making it easier to integrate data without relying solely on predefined schemas. Ontology-based integration methods are another important approach. Gagnon [Gag07] and Allemang [AHG20] discuss the use of ontologies to define common vocabularies within a domain, enabling consistent interpretation of information across systems. Ontologies help establish shared meanings, which is critical for achieving semantic interoperability in large-scale data integration efforts, such as those required for the

Semantic Web.[Noy04]

Data portability is oftentimes hindered by issues of heterogeneous data structures. The diverse nature of data in portability rights—ranging from personal data under the GDPR to business data under the DMA and Data Act—further complicates the issue of semantic heterogeneity. Strauch notes that NoSQL databases, which handle semi-structured data like JSON or XML,[Str11] are increasingly common in managing personal and business data. However, these databases differ from traditional relational databases, making integration more complex. Finally, Kranz *et al.* highlight the need for standardized formats and schemas to ensure successful data portability, particularly in cloud services.[Kra+23] Business data stored in cloud platforms like Amazon Web Services or Google Cloud often involves a variety of data formats and structures, requiring harmonization at the database level. This challenge is also present in the Data Act, where real-time access to raw data from connected devices must be accompanied by sufficient metadata to maintain data quality and meaning.

In conclusion, semantic heterogeneity presents significant challenges in data portability, particularly when transferring data across systems with different structures and expectations. The literature provides valuable insights into resolving these issues through approaches like schema mapping, ontology-based integration, and AI-driven solutions. As data portability becomes more prominent in regulations, addressing the semantic challenges will be essential for ensuring meaningful data exchanges between systems. Integrating the solutions developed for database integration into data portability frameworks will help overcome these hurdles, ensuring that data retains its meaning across different contexts.

Attempts at Addressing Structure and Semantic Heterogeneity

Structural Harmonization and Semantic Artifacts in Data Portability.

In the field of data portability, ensuring the exchange of meaningful and interoperable data across systems presents a complex challenge, particularly due to issues surrounding syntactic and semantic heterogeneity. Several strategies have emerged to address these issues, ranging from the development of syntactic data standards to the establishment of semantic frameworks that facilitate meaningful data exchange.

Syntactic and Semantic Standardization. Syntactic standards refer to the formatting and structuring rules for data, which are often defined by widely used formats such as XML and JSON. These formats ensure that data can be stored and exchanged in a machine-readable manner. However, syntax alone does not guarantee interoperability because it lacks the ability to convey meaning. For example, XML Schema and JSON Schema define structural constraints, but the lack of semantic agreement may lead to confusion about the intended meaning of the data.[KSS20] Semantic standards, on the other hand, focus on ensuring that data is described consistently across systems by providing shared vocabularies and taxonomies. These standards allow systems to interpret data in a meaningful way by ensuring that terms, attributes, and relationships are uniformly defined. Controlled vocabularies and ontologies play an essential role in harmonizing semantics. Ontologies, such as those used in the Web Ontology Language (OWL), enable the definition of entities and their relationships in a way that is independent of the specific format in which data is represented.

Merging Syntax and Semantics.

Although syntactic and semantic standards have traditionally been developed separately, certain tools merge these two aspects to facilitate both structural and semantic interoperability. For instance, XML and JSON formats often allow developers to define tags and keys autonomously, but the development of controlled vocabularies or ontologies can introduce shared semantics within these syntactic structures. OWL, for example, provides a harmonized semantic framework that can describe entities independently of their syntactic representation, thus promoting interoperability. In specific sectors such as healthcare, comprehensive standards like HL7's FHIR address both syntactic and semantic issues simultaneously.³⁹ FHIR integrates standardized data models with semantic vocabularies to facilitate the exchange of clinical information on a global scale. This approach ensures that data exchanged within and between healthcare systems remains meaningful, even in highly complex environments.

Coordinated Frameworks for Data Sharing.

In competitive commercial settings, such as those governed by private data portability regulations,[SEE24] there is often little incentive for companies to share data among each other (Business-to-Business, or B2B), with consumers (Business-to-Consumer, or B2C) or the state (Business to Government, or B2G). However, solutions from non-competitive public-sector frameworks offer useful insights.[SEE24] For example, the Open Data Directive⁴⁰ and the Data Governance Act⁴¹ in Europe mandate the sharing and reuse of public data, often requiring standardized schemas for data exchange.⁴² In Italy, the National Guidelines for the Enhancement of Public Information Assets mandate that data schemas, such as XSD for XML and JSON Schema, be shared to ensure accurate data interpretation.[AGI23]

Data Schemas and Structured Formats.

The flexibility of syntactic standards like XML has contributed to their widespread adoption but has also introduced challenges for interoperability. XML allows for autonomous schema creation, which can result in syntactically valid data that lacks semantic consistency across systems. XML Schema (XSD) was developed to address this issue by specifying the structure, constraints, and data types required for valid XML documents.[Bik+13] Similarly, JSON Schema defines a structured approach to validate JSON data against predefined models. These schemas are critical for ensuring that data exchanged between systems is both syntactically correct and semantically meaningful. XSD and JSON Schemas are available, open source tools that could already be put to use to standardize data schemas and structures for purposes of portability.

Semantic Artifacts and Ontologies.

The need for semantic harmonization has led to the development of semantic artifacts such as controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies. These tools provide a structured way to represent and share knowledge across systems. Ontologies, in particular, offer a high level of ex-

³⁹See FHIR specification at <http://hl7.org/fhir/index.html#0>.

⁴⁰Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information, PE/28/2019/REV/1, OJ L 172, 26.6.2019.

⁴¹Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act), PE/85/2021/REV/1, OJ L 152, 03/06/2022.

⁴²See also the Regulation (EU) No 1024/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on administrative cooperation through the Internal Market Information System and repealing Commission Decision 2008/49/EC ('the IMI Regulation'), OJ L 316, 14.11.2012.

pressiveness by defining concepts, relationships, and rules within a specific domain. Ontologies such as OWL, which build on the Resource Description Framework (RDF), enable a common understanding of data across different systems, promoting interoperability even in heterogeneous environments.[Gru93]

In the public sector, for example, the European Union’s Core Vocabularies, developed under the Interoperable Europe initiative, provide simplified and reusable data models that capture the fundamental characteristics of entities in a context-neutral fashion. These vocabularies ensure that essential properties, such as those related to persons or organizations, are consistently shared across public-sector systems. The alignment of vocabularies across different namespaces, as seen in the mapping between Schema.org and the Core Vocabularies, further illustrates the importance of semantic consistency for effective data exchange.

In conclusion, the literature on structural harmonization and semantic artifacts underscores the critical role of both syntactic and semantic standards in achieving effective data portability. Syntactic standards like XML and JSON ensure that data can be structurally validated, while semantic standards such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies guarantee that the data exchanged retains its intended meaning. As data portability regulations continue to evolve, the integration of these approaches—through tools like XML Schema, JSON Schema, and OWL—will be crucial for overcoming heterogeneity and ensuring meaningful data exchange across systems.

Data Content

Several studies have examined the practical application of data portability systems and their existing challenges. Syrmoudis *et al.*[Syr+21] and Wong and Henderson[WH19b] have identified key issues within these systems, notably data fragmentation and the variability in “data richness.” These challenges highlight how data formats and content differ across platforms and services, leading to inconsistencies in the quality and usefulness of transferred data. The issue of data format heterogeneity has been extensively covered in the literature, with a focus on standardizing data models through schemas like XML Schema (XSD) and JSON Schema, which define properties for specific data types. Object-oriented programming (OOP) concepts can help explain the structuring of data in these systems. For example, the “class” and “attribute” model in OOP, where high-level classes encapsulate general functionalities and lower-level classes capture specific details, has been applied to data types in services like Google Contacts.

In the context of data portability, the concept of “data richness” becomes crucial. It refers to both the variety of data types a service collects and the *amount of information embedded within each type*. Google Takeout, for instance, offers a wide range of data types, such as contacts, emails, and photos—*richness in types*, with each type containing various attributes like name, email, and phone number—*richness in information per data type*. This richness in information per data type is defined by the number of data fields available within each data type, as illustrated by the case of Google Contacts, which includes 25 different data fields out of a potential 45 based on the vCard standard. This selective inclusion of data attributes highlights the arbitrary nature of data model design, where developers decide which fields are necessary or optional based on the functional needs of the system.

The concept of data richness, when applied to the single data type (or class), refers to the amount of information, the attributes (fields) about that data type, therefore to how much in-

formation about the data type is embedded. The realization that the information contained in similar data types (same contacts from a list) among different systems (Google Contacts, Apple Contacts, WhatsApp Contacts) may differ in quantity of information per data type uncovers the most important finding of this research that is, what matters is how much data per data type is each system allowing to port. Data portability is really about *data of data portability*.

Despite the existence of standardized formats like vCard, companies often create their own subsets of these models, leading to further inconsistencies in data portability, disregarding how much information per data type “should” be provided.

This research reveals that a fundamental issue, overlooked by the current scholarship, concerns the heterogeneity content of ported data. This complexity raises concerns about the quantity of information per single data type, therefore about the *quality of ported data*, as the current legal frameworks do not sufficiently address the level of detail and granularity required for effective data portability. For instance, questions remain about how many and which specific attributes should be included in the model for ported data, which introduces uncertainty in meeting legal obligations.

This research endeavor positions data quality—specifically interpreted through the economic view of *data fitness for purpose*—as a central principle in resolving these challenges. By ensuring that data is not only portable in structure but also meaningful and complete in content, this work proposes a shift toward a more robust interpretation of the legal and technical requirements underpinning data portability. Moreover, data quality becomes the objective metrics to determine whether a right or obligation has been fulfilled. This framework bridges existing gaps in the literature, offering a more integrated approach that considers both the regulatory intent and the technical realities of the European digital agenda.

2.3.2.3.4 Data Portability: Towards the Purpose of Reusability The concept of reusability plays a significant role in the European Data Strategy and related legal frameworks. According to Wand and others,^[WW96; WW90; WW95] an information system is designed for its users, but in the context of data portability, this becomes complex as data from one system must be reusable in another, often unknown, system. The European Data Strategy emphasizes reusability, particularly when it comes to data that must remain valuable as it moves across different markets. A European Commission report on data quality highlights the importance of reusability for data publishers, stressing that data must be easy to discover, analyze, and visualize by potential reusers.^[Pub21] This perspective introduces a more circular view of data, where it is treated as a resource that should remain accessible and useful beyond its original system.

A core element of reusability is captured in the principle of “fitness for use,” which has been widely discussed in technical and philosophical literature. Wang *et al.*^[WSF95] and Floridi,^[Fl14] among others, argue that data quality is not just about accuracy but also about ensuring that data meets the specific needs of the task at hand. For example, the ISO 8000-1:2022 standard defines data quality as data that is accurate, complete, and relevant to the intended use. AgID’s guidelines for data quality similarly stress that the adequacy of data depends on both the context and the conditions under which it is used.^[AGI23] Thus, ensuring data is “fit for reuse” requires not just technical interoperability, but also sufficient quantity and quality to meet legal

and practical standards.

Moreover, the literature on data quality consistently portrays it as a multidimensional construct. Initially centered around accuracy, the concept has expanded to include other dimensions such as timeliness, completeness, and relevance. Empirical studies, such as those by Wang and Strong,[[WS96](#)] identify four key categories of data quality that encompass, but are not limited to accuracy: *intrinsic* data quality, resonating with concepts such as data accuracy, and objectivity; data quality as *accessibility*, highlighting the importance of access and security; *contextual quality*, reinforcing the idea that qualitative data shall be timely and complete; and *representational quality*, suggesting that only essential data can support conciseness and, in turn, interpretability. These dimensions directly align with the needs for overcoming heterogeneity in data portability, further supporting the notion that reusability hinges on ensuring that data quality principles are embedded in portability frameworks.

The legal discussion around data quality has evolved in parallel with the technical developments. Historically, data quality was referenced in early data protection frameworks, such as the European Data Protection Directive, and continues to be a key principle in the GDPR. Legal scholars like Dimitrova have highlighted the growing significance of data quality in data protection law,[[Dim21](#)] noting how it subsumes the principle of data accuracy and extends to broader concepts like adequacy, relevance, and timeliness. As such, data quality is becoming an integral component in ensuring compliance with legal requirements for data portability, ensuring that data remains functional and valuable as it is reused across different contexts.

2.3.3 Methodology

2.3.3.1 The LeADS Method

The legality attentive data scientist approach forms the foundation of the methodology used in this report. This interdisciplinary method combines legal analysis with technological expertise, offering a holistic perspective on data portability. By examining the technical underpinnings of data portability—such as data formats, structures, and metadata—alongside the legal and regulatory frameworks, this approach uncovers issues that remain invisible to those focused solely on law or technology. The LeADS approach acts as both a hermeneutical mechanism, offering a deeper and more holistic understanding of the problems, and as a discovery tool that suggests the existence of similar in-between issues in other areas of technology and law.

The methodological framework centers on the idea that data portability is about more than the transfer of data—it is about the quality of information being ported. Facing the unpredictability of outcomes from the legal, economic, and technological investigations, and mindful of the deadlines for chapter submissions and reviews, it seemed appropriate to draft three conceptual papers. Each paper would encapsulate the core ideas destined for further expansion into chapters and sections of the dissertation. Upon completing the legal conceptual paper—dubbed the “legal backbone”—I discovered that a substantial portion of the necessary legal research was already conducted, making it relatively straightforward to integrate this work into the Ph.D thesis. The technological part of the research was tackled first. The was strategically timed to align with the implementation of the Digital Markets Act (DMA) on March 6, 2024, mandating data porta-

bility for major platforms, notably including Meta and Google, who had recently faced scrutiny from competition authorities. Such regulatory shift offered a prime opportunity to examine system design changes pre and post DMA enactment, allowing to gain practical insights into XML and JSON data schemas, APIs, deployment models, and reference architectures. During this phase, the active engagement with the US-based Data Transfer Initiative (DTI) enriched the research with valuable firsthand information, through interacting with technologists developing data portability systems.

The legality attentive data scientist method encompassed:

Legal Analysis

- Legal Literature and Case Law Analysis (Desktop Research) Examining EU regulations such as the GDPR, DMA, Free Flow of Non Personal Regulation, Digital Governance Act, and Data Act, with a focus on how these laws define and limit data portability rights. The work analyses recent case law by the European Court of Justice considering the interactions between data protection and competition law (Meta v. Bundeskartellamt), as well as data portability cases before the Italian Competition Authority (Hoda v. Google).
- Field Research: The Hoda case was analyzed during an internship at the Italian Competition Authority (AGCM), involving field research and interviews with relevant case handlers.

Technical Analysis

- Desk research in the field of computer and data science on secondary sources for data standards and formats;
- Discussions with experts in law and information technologies (data science; computer science; information system engineering), also in the context of academic secondment at Vrije Universiteit Brussels (Belgium);
- Field research on information system's portability of healthcare data during industrial secondment at BY.TE (Greece);
- Examination of case studies by DTI implementing data portability solutions, to understand technical choices.

The LeADS method itself emerged as a discovery, revealing its practical utility exploring the interplay between law and data science. These two disciplines interact and offer mutual insights. For example, it was only through studying Python and object-oriented programming that it was possible to grasp the potential scarcity of properties within data models. This realization triggered a legal intuition: if the right to data portability imposes a legal obligation, it must be treated as a civil obligation requiring the determinability of performance—a principle known as *quantum debeat*. Data science further enriches this understanding by demonstrating that the same data model can be implemented in countless ways, influencing whether the creditor's or right holder's claim is met under the applicable legal framework. Moreover, information economics

introduces the notion of data quality as fitness for purpose, offering a practical, actionable standard for assessing the quantifiability of data portability obligations. This approach allows for a proportionate balance between the competing interests that need protection, offering a clear metric to assess whether the legal obligations have been appropriately fulfilled.

Challenges encountered during the research include the dual nature of data portability—balancing informational self-determination with the broader economic and market effects—and the sheer volume of technical literature required to fully grasp the problem. The scarcity of interdisciplinary experts made it difficult to validate findings across fields, underscoring the need for more professionals with hybrid skills.

The research culminates in a proportionality-based metric system that tailors data portability obligations to the specific context in which they arise, whether in data protection, consumer protection, or competition law. This system offers a scalable solution to the indeterminability problem by focusing on data quality as a guiding principle.

2.3.3.1.1 Methodological Note to the Reader The issue of inseparability of souls has consistently arisen not only in broader theoretical discussions, but also on a more detailed level within the structure of this work. Ideally, all three components—law, economics, and technology—should progress simultaneously, akin to three columns on a single page, each with its content. Readers would ideally absorb information from all three columns concurrently, like skilled harp players. However, this is not practically feasible. Consequently, structural decisions had to be made regarding the order of addressing these components—what to tackle first, second, and third.

This structural approach may sometimes give readers the impression that certain information or concepts introduced in earlier chapters have not yet been fully developed enough to grasp their significance in the argument. Nevertheless, readers need not be concerned, as these concepts will be elucidated in subsequent chapters and cross-referenced throughout the book. By the conclusion of the book, all these elements will converge, providing a comprehensive understanding.

2.3.4 Research Findings

The key findings of this work reveal significant gaps in the current regulatory framework for data portability, primarily related to the determinability of obligations and the quality of data being ported. What follows is a summary of findings.

2.3.4.0.1 Data Portability is a Microcosm of Policy Tensions Data portability encapsulates many of the tensions inherent in the European Data Strategy, including the conflict between data minimization and data reusability, privacy and transparency, individual rights versus market regulation, and more (See State of the Art section above). The extreme concentration of complex concepts and conflicts within such a condensed formulation, as is the case for data portability in the GDPR, limited to a few lines in a relatively obscure article, has created a real interpretative breakdown. This issue affects not only legal experts but also those in economics,

competition, and information technology. It is nearly impossible to fully grasp the concept of data portability in its current, dense form, let alone regulate it in a way that effectively and efficiently achieves its often-conflicting policy goals. It needs to be expanded and unpacked—just as the research behind this report has done. The key finding, therefore, is that in its current condensed version, data portability cannot be used solely as a data protection tool without affecting competition law and information technology design.

2.3.4.0.2 Data Portability is a Morphing Concept in EU Policy The study reveals a significant issue hindering the actual implementation of data portability within the framework of the European Data Strategy. The comparative analysis identifies an unclear mixing of subjects, objects, functions and, to some extent, natures, revealing that, in EU legislation, the lack of a clear and consistent understanding of portability characterizes it as a morphing concept. In the context of the legal analysis of data portability's main EU regulations, there are a few corollary findings, namely that: (a) data portability exists in a spectrum; (b) its transformation defines a shift from a data transfer to a data access model, which (c) affects competition –more specifically, contestability of prime data holders—and which (d) only provides an ephemeral sense of control. Initially aimed at enabling consumers to export and move data while switching services, the concept has eventually shifted towards ensuring third party services the availability of data in a flexible machine-readable format, without depriving their initial holders. This evolution (or is it an involution?), in its effectiveness, seems however to mark a transition from an active role of users in managing their data to a more passive role, where the focus is on their data accessibility and usability also by others. While the EU Data Strategy highlights data portability's significance, its legal definition in the EU context is vague and applied inconsistently. The examination of relevant legal texts shows that the notion of data portability has substantially evolved: initially centered on facilitating users' data export and transfer, it has progressively shifted focus to making data accessible to various entities in an easily-modifiable machine-readable format. In such chaotic landscape, there is a need for clarification and systematization. In that line, what follows is a blueprint for a toolset of concepts, specifically applied to descriptive Types, which should come useful in real-world scenarios to answer the question: is this dataset considered portable according to this legislation?

- Type-0: The data(set) is “movable” from one service and “transportable” in a format aligned to the communications network requirements. In ICT contexts, this means that the payload data has, for instance, a fitting size.
- Type-1: the dataset is easily transferable to a new environment to a sufficient degree.
- Type-2G (Generic): the dataset is formatted in a fashion that is generically adaptable to a new environment (i.e., in commonly used, machine-readable, structured formats).
- Type-2S (Specific): the dataset is extracted and managed in a format that is compatible with the specific new environment.
- Type-3: the dataset contains data that the porting environment can read with ease (syntactic-specific portability). The new environment can “read the sentence,” meaning it is

able to read the information (written in a similar or compatible programming language) and the logical structure of such information.

- Type-4: the dataset contains data that the receiving environment can understand and act upon (semantic-specific portability). The new environment “understands the message,” meaning it can read the set of information in its logical structure, but also understands the conveyed message.
- Type-RT: the dataset is usable “upon request” and “in real time” by the new environment (Real-Time portability).

Without clear and specified Types, there is a risk that each participant in the digital market interprets regulations differently. This lack of uniformity could undermine the goals of data portability as they were intended by each legislature, and ultimately procure market failures in data sharing. Establishing precise Types helps creating a standardized understanding and, consequently, implementing data portability, fostering consistency and reliability across diverse players, as well as balancing the diverging interests at stake. This solution, however, also requires efforts in the harmonization of data ontologies, formats, syntax, semantics, and development of best practices to reduce the significant risks of incurring in substantial costs for the actual reuse of existing data (due to the necessity to sanitize and adapt for each porting environment) or losing valuable data that cannot be effectively reused.

The market would benefit from the legislator’s acknowledgement that data portability exists in a spectrum, which entails distinct Types thereto. Nomenclature standardization, meaning the process of standardizing different ways in which a concept shows itself, is not just a matter of convenience in this case, rather a crucial factor in ensuring the efficient and meaningful exchange of data within the Digital Single Market. Each regulation should therefore clarify what Type of portability is regulated so that the portability rights are respected, what is needed from information systems to comply with portability requirements, and hopefully disclose a few technological designs that are presumed compliant. All such could better be implemented through the adoption of delegated acts, leveraging their capability of subsequent modifications in response to technological advancements, while preserving the Regulation’s core principles.

2.3.4.0.3 Data Portability Does Not Enhance Control The right to data portability, while presented as a mechanism for enhancing user control over personal data, offers only an illusion of such control. Implementation of data portability in practice, particularly through services like Google Takeout, intersects with competition concerns, such as potential abuses of dominance and limitations on data formats and cloud storage options. For instance, the analogy to the Google Android case, where the European Commission found Google’s tying practices between Google Search and the Play Store to be an abuse of dominance, serves as a pertinent example. Similarly, in the HODA case, Google’s decision to tie its Takeout service to Google Drive presents potential self-preferencing behavior that may restrict users’ ability to switch to alternative providers. The research touched on the restrictive nature of Google’s data formats, which may pose barriers to new service development and competition. As Schweitzer and Metzger noted, data holders often structure and format data according to their business objec-

tives, limiting third-party access and innovation. Furthermore, the choice of cloud storage services—restricted to options like Google Drive and Dropbox—raises additional concerns about limiting user choice and potentially exposing them to privacy risks. These examples emphasize the challenges in ensuring fair competition while respecting user rights to data portability, especially as new regulations like the Digital Markets Act come into force. The DMA, for instance, requires continuous, real-time data access, yet Google's Takeout system currently only offers periodic access through a mediated link. This delay in access underscores the need for further adjustments to meet the DMA's standards for seamless data portability. To address these issues effectively, future regulatory efforts should integrate both competition law and data protection, ensuring that commitments, like those made by Google, are assessed not only for their immediate impact but also for their long-term consequences on market fairness and user autonomy.

2.3.4.0.4 As Technological Design of Portability Shapes Policy Outcomes, Technological Specificity is Needed The research highlights the critical need to understand technology deeply, particularly in contexts like data portability, where the technical and legal realms are intricately connected. Regardless of one's perspective—whether focused on the societal impacts of technology or on the regulatory challenges it presents—both sides agree on the essential role of technological literacy. Understanding the technical building blocks of data systems is foundational to any regulatory efforts aimed at governing complex systems like data portability. Concepts such as data formats, structures, syntax, and semantics, as well as advanced notions like ontologies and knowledge representation, are all crucial for creating a common technical language that bridges the gap between legal, technical, and economic discussions.

The complexity of data protection as a legal field is a major theme. It is not only complex due to the varied nature of data itself, which includes information, knowledge, and its flow across systems, but also because it involves competing rights and societal values that must be protected simultaneously. As the literature points out, this inherent complexity is compounded by the risk-based nature of data protection regulation, which requires a balance between managing technological innovation and protecting individual rights. The interaction between technology and law is particularly important, as legal principles often emerge in response to technological innovations. In this regard, technology design processes may sometimes conflict with legal norms, especially when it comes to values like ethics, legitimacy, and democratic accountability.

The research addresses the debate around technological neutrality versus specificity in regulation. While technology-neutral laws are generally preferred, especially for their adaptability to future technological developments, the discussion points out that certain areas, like data portability, require a more specific regulatory approach. This is because technology-specific laws can directly address unique challenges or moral concerns raised by specific technologies, ensuring that human rights and other fundamental principles are protected. Hildebrandt's work is cited to underscore this point, highlighting that sometimes a technology-neutral approach fails to achieve its intended goals, and specific legislation becomes necessary to counter the risks introduced by technological design choices. In conclusion, regulatory success in fields like data portability and data sharing largely depends on the implementation of technical standards by industry actors. The effectiveness of laws governing these domains hinges not only on the legal frameworks themselves but also on how well they are integrated with the technological realities

of the systems they seek to regulate.

The technical solutions used to implement data portability significantly impact the policy goals that are achieved. For instance, if dominant data holders control the structure and content of ported data, they may consolidate their market power by creating de facto standards. Conversely, more user-centric systems can empower individuals by giving them control over their data, while society at large benefits from increased data sharing and reusability.

2.3.4.0.5 Meaningful Data Portability is Information Portability The analysis of personal data portability within European regulations reveals a fundamental issue stemming from the conflation of “data” and “information.” The GDPR’s approach to data portability, which treats it as a meaning-agnostic problem, overlooks the inherent need for meaningful content in the transfer process. Scholars like Purtova and Newell criticize this oversight, arguing that the right to data portability should be understood as a problem of knowledge communication rather than mere data extraction and transmission. The crux of the issue is that data portability focuses on the transfer of data but fails to ensure that the information—data imbued with meaning—retains its significance in the new context of processing.

A functional re-interpretation of data portability must treat it as a communication process where data is not only transferred but also remains meaningful to both the sender and the recipient system. As Florida’s General Definition of Information emphasizes, data must be well-formed and meaningful to qualify as information. Thus, for data portability to be effective, data must be transferable in a way that maintains its semantic integrity, which is not currently achieved under the GDPR. Additionally, the legal framework must acknowledge the difference between data and information, as highlighted in the recent Interoperable Europe Act, which distinguishes between data, information, and knowledge. This distinction is crucial for a coherent legislative approach that aligns with the real-world application of data in digital environments.

Ultimately, the goal of data portability should be the transfer of meaningful information rather than raw data. This requires a shift in how legislators and regulators conceptualize data portability, moving from a technical task of data migration to a process that ensures the preservation and usability of information across different systems. The failure to address this issue has led to the underachievement of data portability as a right, leaving individuals with the ability to transfer data but not necessarily the information they need.

2.3.4.0.6 Data Portability Needs Structural Harmonization and Semantic Artifacts The flexibility in designing data models and structures, while promoting innovation, has led to significant challenges in data portability due to structural heterogeneity. Kramer et al. (2020) highlight that the data models and formats used for representing, storing, and exchanging data are largely dependent on the type of data. This flexibility results in a lack of consistency across different systems, necessitating the development of standards like XML Schema (XSD), JSON Schema, and RDF Schema to standardize data structures. These schemas impose clear rules on properties within data models, ensuring consistency and interoperability across various platforms. For instance, Facebook’s Graph API, which uses nodes, edges, and fields, aligns with the structural concepts seen in these schema-based formats, facilitating data exchange between systems.

Despite the apparent differences between data formats like XML, JSON, and RDF, the underlying structural similarities offer a pathway toward harmonization. Developed by W3C, many of these formats share a common foundation in how they model data objects and their properties. For example, XML and HTML, though designed for different purposes, have similar architectures based on tags, and both XML and RDF/XML serialize data in a similar manner. This allows for schema mappings across formats, meaning that data portability can be enhanced by translating the structures between different systems, reducing the risks associated with structural heterogeneity.

Schemas also play a crucial role in restricting and defining the nature of data objects, their properties, and their relationships within a system. XSD and JSON Schema, for instance, allow developers to explicitly specify data types, set constraints, and determine mandatory and optional fields, which helps mitigate inconsistencies in data interpretation. In social media, for example, the Facebook Graph API's use of nodes and edges to represent users and relationships demonstrates how these structured formats ensure that data remains actionable and interpretable, regardless of the platform receiving it.

The research further suggests the need for unified conceptual blueprints across different industries to address data heterogeneity. Core schemas could be developed to define key objects and properties in fields like healthcare, finance, and social media, ensuring that data exchanged during portability requests is structured and meaningful. Similar efforts, such as the EU Core Vocabularies—in the inter-administrative sector—and Schema.org offer frameworks for standardizing these concepts. By mandating the use of shared schemas and namespaces in data portability laws, regulators can ensure that data exchanged is not only well-structured but also semantically consistent, enabling effective reuse of the data across different systems. This would uphold the essence of data portability rights by ensuring that transferred data retains its meaning and usability even in contexts of private data sharing. Private data sharing, in this context, means data sharing among private parties, such as businesses, organizations, professionals, or individuals. [SEE24][p. 3]

2.3.4.0.7 In Data Portability, Quantity Matters Research into data portability systems, particularly Google Takeout, reveals substantial fragmentation in both data format and content. For instance, Symoudis et al. found that after data export, there is a noticeable variation in “data richness,” which could either stem from the variety of data types used by the source system or the richness of content within each type. This finding underscores the complexity of ensuring that data retains its full utility when transferred between services, as companies often limit the amount of information available for export. Google, for example, limits the attributes included in the Contact data type, potentially withholding additional data fields that could be useful for the user in another context.

Furthermore, data models are arbitrarily defined by developers, leading to variations in what is shared during portability. Google's decision to include only 25 out of the possible 45 vCard attributes in its Contact data type, while still complying with the necessary requirements, exemplifies how companies use selective data modeling to control the flow of information. This practice creates challenges for users and platforms attempting to reuse the data meaningfully,

as the excluded data fields may contain valuable information. Additionally, even when data is transferred according to standard formats, the completeness of the information remains an issue, with developers having the discretion to include or exclude certain attributes.

The findings also highlight the difficulty of regulating data portability in a heterogeneous digital ecosystem. The infinite variability of data types and properties across different services complicates the implementation of standardized data exchange practices. There is a need for more systematic approaches to simplify and categorize data types, reducing complexity and promoting meaningful reuse. By developing common guidelines and schemas for data exchange, similar to the EU Core Vocabularies, the effectiveness of data portability rights can be significantly enhanced, ensuring that transferred data retains its intended richness and utility across platforms.

Finally, the research emphasizes the importance of moving beyond just data formats to consider the content being ported. Even if data is transferred in a compatible format, it loses value if it cannot be meaningfully reused by the receiving system. As the European Data Strategy emphasizes, “The value of data lies in its use and re-use.”⁴³ This calls for a shift in focus towards specifying the quantity and quality of data that must be shared during portability requests, thereby creating a more predictable and enforceable framework for both data controllers and users. This approach would align the legal requirements of data portability with the practical realities of data reuse in a heterogeneous digital environment.

2.3.5 Research Analysis

2.3.5.01 Data Quality—meaning: fitness for use—is the Guiding Principle for Meaningful Data Portability The research demonstrates that data reusability is central to the European Data Strategy, emphasizing the need for data to remain accessible and valuable when transferred between systems. One significant finding is the application of the principle of “fitness for use” to data quality, showing that reusability is not solely about ensuring data can be technically transferred, but also about maintaining its usefulness in different contexts. For instance, the European Commission stresses that data must be provided in formats that allow potential reusers to understand and make use of it effectively. This highlights the responsibility of data holders to ensure that data is fit for purpose beyond its original system.

Reusability involves ensuring both quantitative and qualitative aspects of data are addressed. The EC Data Quality Guidelines indicate that providing insufficient amounts of data reduces its usefulness, making reusability impossible. This issue aligns with the concept of “data quality as fitness for use,” where good quality data must be accurate, complete, and contextually relevant. An example of this principle in practice can be found in the ISO 8000-1:2022 standard, which reinforces the importance of data being fit for the specific task it is intended for. This finding stresses that data quality is essential for supporting meaningful data portability. Another key finding is that data quality is not a uniform concept but must be tailored to the needs of its intended users. The empirical approach highlighted in the literature, particularly by Wang and Strong, focuses on understanding data from the consumer’s perspective. This consumer-centric view aligns with the idea that data portability must consider the expectations of the data

⁴³European Commission, European Data Strategy, p. 6.

recipient, whether that is the data subject or a third-party reuser. The findings suggest that by applying data quality principles, such as those found in ISO standards, the right balance can be struck between providing adequate content while ensuring the data remains reusable and fit for purpose.

The research also identifies legal frameworks where data quality is explicitly referenced. In particular, the European Health Data Space and the Data Governance Act both highlight the role of data quality in ensuring effective data exchange. These legal instruments underline that data must not only be provided but must also retain its value across different uses, a principle that can be applied more broadly to other data portability systems. Ultimately, the findings suggest that data quality, particularly when framed as “fitness for use,” provides the only metric for ensuring that data portability obligations are both fulfilled and aligned with the broader goals of data governance and consumer protection.

2.3.5.0.2 Data Portability Really Means Data Of Data Portability One of the core issues identified is the lack of clarity regarding how much and what type of data needs to be ported to satisfy legal obligations. This problem of “data of the data”—specifically with regards to attributes—introduces a level of complexity that current regulations do not adequately address. By introducing data quality as a guiding principle, the report proposes a framework for determining what information must be included in the ported data to ensure it meets the needs of both users and regulatory bodies.

1. Proportionality-Based Metrics: The research introduces a proportionality-based approach to data portability, suggesting that the quantity and quality of ported data should vary depending on the regulatory context. In GDPR, where the focus is on informational self-determination, applying the principle of data quality to the right to portability would allow individuals to port as much personal data as they wish. In competition law, however, where the goal is to promote market functionality, the principle of data quality might allow that a lesser amount of data may be sufficient. This flexibility ensures that data remains fit for purpose across different legal frameworks.

2. Data Quality as Fitness for Purpose: Finally, data quality—interpreted as fitness for purpose—should become the guiding benchmark for data portability. By ensuring that ported data retains its value in subsequent services and applications, data quality serves not only to fulfill legal obligations but also to create a more functional digital ecosystem.

The findings of this report reveal the inherent complexity of data portability, emphasizing that it cannot be fully understood or regulated within a single legal framework. Data portability is a microcosm of most, if not all, of the conflicts and tensions that are inherent in the European Data Strategy. These tensions, which span from data minimization versus data reusability, to privacy versus market openness, underscore the importance of an interdisciplinary approach to regulating data portability.

2.3.5.0.3 The Duality of Data Portability The dual purpose of data portability—to uphold informational self-determination and promote market competition—remains one of its most complex and unresolved aspects. As Graef *et al.* highlight,[\[GHP18\]](#) data portability has impli-

cations for both privacy and competition, a view supported by Purtova,[\[Pur15\]](#) who stresses that while portability may enhance user control, it also introduces challenges related to market dynamics and power imbalances. The report extends this argument, showing that attempts to regulate portability solely through data protection law will inevitably have ripple effects on competition law and the design of information technologies. By focusing on the legality attentive data scientist approach, this research has identified key areas where the legal and technical aspects of data portability intersect. For instance, the determinability problem—the challenge of defining the scope of data to be ported—cannot be resolved without technical expertise regarding the attributes, data types, and metadata of the data. This is a point echoed by the scholarship,[\[Sha24\]](#) who cautions that dominant platforms may exploit the lack of clarity to cement their control over data formats and standards.

2.3.5.0.4 Data Quality and Fitness for Purpose The report introduces data quality, particularly its fitness for purpose, as a guiding principle that can bridge the gap between the legal and technical dimensions of data portability. This idea builds on Wang and Strong’s argument that the value of data is closely tied to its reusability and fitness for purpose,[\[WS96\]](#) particularly in a data-driven economy. Undeniably, data access and sharing foster competition and drive innovation, yet it is data quality that defines whether ported data remains useful across different services. By integrating data quality into the analysis of data portability, this report proposes a proportionality-based metric system that tailors the quantity and type of data to be ported based on the context. For example, in the context of GDPR, the emphasis is on informational self-determination, meaning that individuals should be able to port as much personal data as they wish. In competition law, the focus is on ensuring market functionality, so a more limited amount of data may suffice. This proportionality-based approach ensures that data portability remains meaningful across different regulatory frameworks, avoiding a one-size-fits-all solution that could undermine both privacy and competition goals. Graef et al. (2018) support this view, noting that data portability should not become a “mere formalistic exercise,” but rather a tool that balances the needs of individuals, companies, and society at large.

2.3.6 Conclusions

The research on which this report is based makes significant contributions to the understanding of data portability within the European Union’s legal and regulatory framework. By employing the legality attentive data scientist approach, it reveals the interdisciplinary challenges inherent in regulating data portability and demonstrates that the concept cannot be adequately addressed without considering its dual purpose—enhancing informational self-determination and fostering market competition. The research on which this report is based advances the understanding of data portability through an array of contributions.

1. Data Portability as a Microcosm of Broader Conflicts: Data portability encapsulates many of the conflicts at the heart of the EU’s Data Strategy, including the tension between data minimization and reusability, as well as between privacy and competition. These tensions

cannot be resolved through regulation within a single domain, such as data protection or competition law, without affecting the other.

2. **Technological Solutions and Policy Goals:** The choice of technical solutions for implementing data portability has significant implications for policy outcomes. Systems that prioritize user control and data quality can empower individuals and promote transparency, while systems that allow dominant data holders to control the structure and content of ported data risk reinforcing existing market power.
3. **Data Quality as a Central Principle:** The introduction of data quality, particularly its fitness for purpose, as a guiding principle for data portability, represents a major contribution to this research. By ensuring that data retains its utility and completeness in subsequent services, this principle provides a framework for assessing the adequacy of ported data across different contexts.[Pur15]
4. **Proportionality-Based Metrics:** The report proposes a proportionality-based metric system that tailors data portability obligations based on the specific regulatory context, ensuring that the right remains flexible and adaptable to different legal frameworks.

2.3.7 Future work

The future of data portability research lies in further exploring the interplay between data quality and existing regulatory frameworks. Taking the data quality fitness for purpose benchmark as a guiding principle of the digital world could be revolutionary. This principle has the potential to transform how data is shared and reused, affecting everything from the development of data markets to the functioning of public services, while achieving the overarching goal of the Data Strategy to give businesses and public authorities access to high-quality data.

3 Solving Practical Hurdles to Privacy and Security Implementation

3.1 Assessing Digital Identity Solutions

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3.1.1 Executive summary

The Internet, as it exists today, lacks robust and reliable mechanisms for trust and security. While this was not a significant concern in the early days of its development, the rapid growth of online platforms and increasing dependence on digital services have made trust an urgent issue. Digital identity offers a potential solution to many of the challenges surrounding trust and security online. For this reason, companies and governments are collaborating to provide citizens with secure and reliable electronic identification systems. For example, since 2014, the European Commission has implemented a framework for promoting equal access to public and private services throughout Europe. This initiative is known as eIDAS (Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services) and it is based on the proposed architecture of decentralization, such as the Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI).

SSI aims to return control of personal data to citizens, reducing the risk of misuse and building greater trust in digital services. However, the concept remains elusive, lacking a clear, uniform interpretation. Efforts to define SSI are mostly led by academic initiatives, but the concept often remains abstract and disconnected from practical business needs. As a result, many digital identity systems claim to follow SSI principles, but it is difficult to assess how closely they adhere to its core values. For this reason, this work aims to close that gap. It seeks to offer a formal definition of Self-Sovereign Identity and introduce a practical, structured model for evaluating digital identity solutions. In the long term, this will provide both designers and citizens with a tool to help them choose the best platform for creating a digital identity.

3.1.2 Introduction

3.1.2.1 Background

Digital services for businesses and citizens requiring an identity have become crucial for economic growth. However, every time an App or website asks us to create a new digital identity or easily log on to a platform, we have no idea what happens to our data. Nearly 72% of users wish to know more about how their data is processed when they open an account, and 63% of EU citizens want a trusted European identity.¹ The European Commission upstreams this challenge by providing a unique digital identity for over half a billion people.

Since 2014, the European Commission has overseen eIDAS, a framework for the cross-border interplay of national e-identities with equal conditions for accessing public and private services [Eid]. The eIDAS aims to harmonize the use of electronic identification and trust services across Europe. It defines identification schemes that require users to authenticate to a service with a level of confidence that can be low, substantial, or high. Once authenticated, users have access to a range of services that allow them to sign documents (eSignature), ensure the origin of data (eSeal), and provide evidence (timestamp, delivery service, website authentication) [SAA22]. The provisioning of identity information starts with the issue of personal data (PIDs) for holders who store them in their wallet storage component. The holder then presents credentials to the Relying Parties [ASM21]. To meet the requirement for data flow, the Commission is working on a decentralized architecture that recalls the Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) paradigm.

Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) is a theoretical concept from academia that promises users control of personal information [All]. The concept received great attention among practitioners and is today used as a reference guide for the design of e-identity solutions. However, SSI is still elusively defined as a set of principles, and past attempts to converge to an agreed-upon definition failed due to technical challenges [KP21], divergent visions from practitioners [Ruf18], interoperability issues [Ghi+23], and legal hurdles [SAA22]. Thus, a rigorous formalization of Self-Sovereign Identity would help design solutions and validate their completeness and correctness [SC22].

3.1.3 Objectives and Scope.

This report outlines the concept of Self-Sovereign Identity through a rigorous definition of principles. We outline concepts, relationships, and rules governing identity ecosystems' entities and provide a formal specification of principles and a semantic taxonomy of SSI. We then delineate a model based on our implementable tweak of SSI principles to assess any worldwide digital identity system. We demonstrate our model value with an in-depth analysis of the major European digital identity framework. In the long run, we aim to enable future startups and governments

¹Digital Identity for all Europeans; a personal digital wallet for EU citizens and residents. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-digital-identity_en

to rank solutions, spot weaknesses, and intervene accordingly. Our model also helps citizens to choose their best-fit e-identity system.

3.1.4 State of the Art

SSI was firstly described as a set of principles in [All]. Subsequent works complemented these principles with social considerations [And16; Gil+20], along with a technical analysis [FCA19]. Principles were categorized in a three-way taxonomy by Tobin [TR16]. Andrieu provided a tech-free description of SSI [And16], while other papers extend previous definitions to cover blockchain-based e-identity systems [FCA19] and add security properties [Gil+20]. Sheldrake considers only essential principles of Self [She19]. Lastly, a business-oriented analysis of SSI results from [Blo]. Sometimes these definitions have been used to formalize the archetype for SSI systems. For example, [Sch+21] uses an empirical approach to systematize e-identity offerings into eight archetypes and evaluates solutions. Satybaldy et al. [SNE20] propose a framework to describe, evaluate, and compare SSI systems. Tobin [Tob22] evaluates the eIDAS framework. However, those works need to define criteria for evaluation – otherwise, the contribution of their content analysis is limited. All works revealed the need for more effort to produce an agreed-upon evaluation model. Furthermore, all works require periodic adjustments anytime the identity system updates.

3.1.5 Methodology

Our state of the art results from a systematic review study. A systematic literature review provides a coarse-grained overview of the research field through several steps: 1) defining the research questions, 2) conducting the search, 3) screening papers, 4) defining criteria for inclusion/exclusion of articles, and 5) extracting knowledge [PVK15]. First, we define broad research questions to cover the topic from interdisciplinary perspectives. From keywording research questions, we produced search strings and hit online databases to gather articles. We define classification criteria, filter out articles and categorize results. We plot results into a two-axe chart to help spot literature gaps. The steps are detailed as follows.

- 1. Defining the research questions.** We aim to span the scope of the research field through broad search strings. We then use search strings to hit online databases. A scientific approach to comprehensively cover a topic of interest is to explore the intersection of legal, social, and technical fields (LST) [Cus+10; Bad+13]. First, we produce general research questions for each field of study (legal, social, technical). As a tool to guide us in designing research questions, we refer to the *Five W's* (What, When, Where, Who, and Why) [Har96] and propose at least one or more research questions for each "W". Table 3.1 reports our research questions. Rows are the five W's; columns are the fields of research. From keywording the research questions, we produced the following search strings.

- Legal: ("governance" AND "digital identity") OR ("legal framework" AND "norms" AND "identity") OR ("rights" AND "regulation" AND "digital identity")

Table 3.1: Research questions for a comprehensive literature review (LST) of the research field. Questions are designed as the "Five W's."

Legal aspects	Social aspects	Technical aspects
- What are the legal requirements governing digital identity?	- What are the impact and consequences of digital identity on people?	- What are the archetypes employed on digital identity?
- When governments started to design/implement legal frameworks?	- When did digital identity systems gain prominence and recognition in society?	- When did protocols for authentication first emerge?
- Where are the leading players in providing digital identity?	- Where do individuals establish their digital presence and manage their social identity?	- Where are digital identity standards and communication protocols commonly implemented and enforced?
- Who is responsible for enforcing legal compliance?	- Who is contributing to the development of social norms of digital identity?	- Who is responsible for designing and implementing technical standards for digital identity systems?
- Why do legal frameworks succeed? Why not?	- Why is digital identity important for individuals in terms of self-expression, representation?	- Why is it essential to have technical standards to design identity solutions?

- Social: ("digital identity" AND "people") OR ("identity" AND "society" AND "control")
- Technical: ("identity" AND "ecosystem members" AND "control") OR ("archetypes" AND "design" AND "identity") OR ("solutions" AND "identity" AND "technical standard")

2. Searching. We used search strings and hit databases on ACM, ArXiv, Google Scholar, and IEEE Xplore, gathering 250 results. We identified articles with keywords appearing on titles and abstracts. Identity models date back to the early 2000s. As we wish to have the latest trends, we skimmed outcomes.

3. Paper Screening. We defined inclusion and exclusion criteria to filter out non-pertinent results. a) The relevance of the subject matter of interest (digital identity), b) the date of publication, c) the novelty of the work, d) whether the article provided empirical studies, or e) proofs-of-concept. We excluded off-topic hits and works available as slides or abstracts only, while prioritizing recent publications. We applied the inclusion/exclusion criteria on abstracts and conclusions to collect 95 articles subject to full review.

4. Classification scheme. We set up a classification scheme to sort articles. We read the 95 articles and penciled out information about their objectives, outcomes, state of knowledge, risk of bias, uncertainties, computational method, worked part, limitations, and future works. We used these fields to render thirteen groups as in Figure 3.1.

5. Data extraction. We assigned articles to the most relevant group. We plotted those groups in a two-axis chart with the horizontal axis (x-axis) sketching technical to legal matters (left to right) and a vertical axis (y-axis) that grades the social aspect from less to more social (bottom-up). The result is represented in Figure 3.1, with \diamond (diamonds) rendering groups and numbers defining the instances of articles for each group. The position of the diamond in the two-axis chart is based on the category of the conference/journal in which

Figure 3.1: A systematization of knowledge in a two-axes chart. The dashed circle is the SSI topic. ◊ (diamonds) represent groups of articles, and numbers define instances of articles in each group.

the article was published. We used the *Scimago Journal & Country Rank*² as a reference indicator to assess and compare journals and help us categorize papers. If most of the articles in the group pertain to technical journals, we aligned the diamond in the technical area of the chart. The more articles published in technical conferences/journals, the more the diamond shifts toward the left corner. Vice-versa, the more articles published in the legal field (within the group ◊), the more the diamond shifts to the right hand of the chart.

3.1.6 A Model to Assess e-Identity Solutions

We based our definition of SSI on the following *what* and *how* questions: What are the fundamental human rights? What properties guarantee those rights? How can security be implemented? How to scale up an e-identity? Based on these questions we refine a set of principles and provided a four-group taxonomy as *Individuals' Rights, Trustworthiness, Secrecy, and Sustainability*.

3.1.6.0.1 Individuals' rights. The category pertains to human rights and encloses three principles: Existence, Persistence, and Protection.

- Existence. Individuals have an independent existence cast by attributes and interplay with identity providers [AI]. Existence refers to the ability of individuals to affirm attributes to services as proof of their identity.
- Persistence. Individuals' existence must persist over ceasing the asserted authority [FCA19]. Persistence refers to the possibility of individuals presenting the same attributes from multiple issuers.

²Scimago Journal & Country Rank. <https://www.scimagojr.com/>

- **Protection.** It refers to the ability of systems to avoid censorship. In particular, we refer to the entity/ies that can update the list of identity and service providers. In different systems, several players can maintain this list: government agencies, the private sector, a consortium of organizations, private individuals, etc. Those who can modify the list control the system and corresponding entities. Protection ensures that the list is fairly managed.

3.1.6.0.2 Trustworthiness. The category encodes paramount properties that ease the spread of trust among users in using digital identities. It considers who can access the list of providers of identities or IdPs and attributes, what attributes it is possible to share with whom, and recalls rules for the transparency of policies to manage service providers (SPs).

- **Access.** The property refers to the possibility of individuals accessing the list of identity providers anytime an individual wishes. Additionally, users must be able to obtain information about their attributes from the identity provider.
- **Control.** It refers to the list of attributes and SPs. Individuals must control their attributes and decide what to share with whom.
- **Transparency.** Policies and rules to manage the ecosystem members (add/remove an IdP/SP) must be transparent and clearly stated from the beginning of the design stage.

3.1.6.0.3 Secrecy. The category frames properties for the Secrecy of information. We stick with the definition of secrecy by Nissenbaum in [Nis18] as limiting the data transfer (data minimization). In the broad sense, secrecy also includes other techniques, such as Access Control Lists (ACLs) and encryption methods. However, ACL fits best authorization and access to resources and finds only partial application in limiting the information disclosed. Encryption is meant to hide information. Consent management is a pre-stage of data minimization. Thus, the properties framed in this category are data minimization and consent management.

- **Consent.** Consent is the permission given by individuals to collect, use, and share their personal data [Car16].³ We extend this definition of consent with a more recent definition from McLachlana et al. that emphasizes the individuals' ability to opt in and revoke consent anytime they wish [McL+].
- **Data minimization.** Users must share only the minimum data to guarantee the service (secrecy).

3.1.6.0.4 Sustainability. The category includes principles that advocate for the large-scale adoption of e-identity systems.

³Directive 95/46/EC on protecting individuals concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

Table 3.2: Ranking System. The first three principles refer to Individuals' Rights (a). The last three principles refer to Trustworthiness. Pts stands for points.

Individuals' Rights (a)			
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight
Existence	- What attributes can attest to an e-identity?	- Assigned attributes (Username and Password) - Multi-Factor Authentication - Accumulated attributes (PIDs) - Inherited attributes (Biometric data) - Digital certificates (e.g., X509) - Other attributes (e.g., eSign, timestamp)	5 pts 7 pts 10 pts 10 pts 10 pts 10 pts
Persistence	- Who can issue attributes?	- Qualified Trust Service Providers (QTSPs) - Trust service providers (Non-Qualified) - Other public bodies (e.g., Gov agencies, Univ.) - Other private bodies (e.g., Microsoft, Okta)	10 pts 10 pts 10 pts 10 pts
Protection	- Who maintains the list of IdPs and SPs?	- Private sector (e.g., banks, credit bureaus) - Consortium of organizations (e.g., Kantara) - Gov agencies (e.g., national identity authority) - Other gov institutions (e.g., EU Commission) - Community of contributors (open)	5 pts 8 pts 10 pts 10 pts 10 pts
Trustworthiness (b)			
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight
Access	- How users obtain information about their attributes? - Can users access the list of IdPs?	- Local agent (wallet) - Shared ledger of IdPs	10 pts 10 pts
Control	- Do users negotiate the release of attributes to SPs?	- User negotiates attributes but PIDs - User negotiates PIDs - Users can choose the service provider	10 pts 15 pts 15 pts
Transparency	- Are policies and rules to manage ecosystem members transparent and clearly stated?	- General guidelines only - Transparent rules and procedures	5 pts 10 pts

- **Cost.** A digital identity system must be profitable for individuals, public and private organizations [FCA19; Gil+20].
- **Interoperability.** IdPs and SPs can be under different jurisdictions. Interoperability means that users can present to SPs attributes released by IdPs under a different jurisdiction [CDP21].
- **Portability.** The list of attributes featuring an e-identity can be transportable on a different ecosystem (Art. 20(1)(2) of the GDPR).
- **Standard.** An e-identity system must ensure the most outstanding level via standards as open and globally recognized as possible. Private organizations (e.g., Evernym [SK16], and OpenID Connect [Sak+14]), and working groups (e.g., W3C Verifiable Credentials Working Group (VCWG) [Sed+21]) have already proposed protocols, standards for attributes exchange and decentralized identifiers widely recognized among practitioners.

The above-mentioned list of principles and taxonomy draws a new definition of Self-Sovereign Identity. The formalization is still theoretical and expressed in natural language. Hence, we aim to fill the gap between theory and practice by providing a ranking system that appears as a three-way process. First, *challenges* question principles to start binding theoretical properties with actual initiatives. Then, each challenge produces a variable number of *dimensions* that encode parameters. Finally, each dimension receives a *weight* as the degree of confidence in testing real-life solutions. Table 3.2 and 3.3 contains a description of the challenges and dimensions.

Table 3.3: Ranking System. Consent and Minimization refer to Secrecy (a). The other principles refer to Sustainability (b). Pts stands for points.

Secrecy (a)			
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight
Consent	- Does consent result adequately expressed and managed?	- Freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous consent	10 pts
		- Dynamic consent	15 pts
Minimization	- Does the service lawfully collect only the minimum amount of information? - Do users employ techniques to limit data sharing?	- Post-consent	20 pts
		- Adequate and relevant data collection	10 pts
		- Minimization of attributes but PIDs	10 pts
		- Minimization of PIDs	15 pts
		- Transfer only a subset of attributes	5 pts
- Transfer one attribute at a time	10 pts		
- Transfer the associated information only	15 pts		
Sustainability (b)			
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight
Cost	- To what extent does the e-identity is profitable for stakeholders?	- Profitable for public services	10 pts
		- Profitable for private services	10 pts
		- Profitable for citizens	10 pts
Interoperability	- To what extent can IdPs attest attributes to SPs across different jurisdictions?	- Among public services	10 pts
		- Among private services	10 pts
Portability	- To what extent can users transport the list of attributes on different ecosystems?	- Between public authorities	10 pts
		- Between private authorities	10 pts
		- Full portability	15 pts
Standard	- Who can issue standards for e-identity systems?	- Working/Community groups	10 pts
		- Industry sector (e.g., Avast)	10 pts
		- Public agencies (e.g., gov)	10 pts

3.1.6.1 How to use the ranking system?

Each dimension receives a coefficient to mark the degree of adherence to the system. The coefficient renders three values: full, half, and empty. Full represents a score of one. Half is a score of 0.5. Empty is zero. If the solution is consistent with the requirements, we assign a full coefficient. If it partially meets the requirements, we assign half coefficient. On the contrary, an empty coefficient. Our ranking system returns two types of information: the functional dependency to describe similarities between categories and the global score to rank solutions.

3.1.6.1.1 Functional dependency. The objective is to study the correctness and relationships among categories. Each category is a mini-batch β_i of weights that returns a σ_i (sigma) value as a degree of confidence of the outcome, expressed in percent (%). The higher the score, the better the outcome. Algorithm 1 presents the sequence of steps to compute the functional dependency. First, weights multiply by the coefficient and apply the reward when needed (Step 1). Coefficients allow us to fine-grain our evaluation. Then, partial results from the same challenge get summed (Step 2); normalization guarantees that every challenge receives the same importance (Step 3). The computation relies on Min-Max normalization because it is easy to employ and fits any data distribution [PS15]. We know its limitation on losing information when data narrows or its tendency to outliers. However, the *No Free Lunch Theorem* claims no one-size-fits-normalization suits all datasets [Kur+15]. Thus, we tested other methods, but they introduce unnecessary complexity into our computation (Decimal unit scaling) [Sin22], deviate from the information we are analyzing (Percentile), apply to data with a stable distribution (Z-

score) [HWR21], or with greater standard deviation (Logarithmic) [Shio4]. Finally, each mini-batch averages results (Step 4) and applies the Cartesian product to express results in percent (Step 5). Results consider values from each principle and challenge, yet they are unbiased on the number of principles and mini-batches.

A simple outcome may come $\langle 45; 78; 32; 12 \rangle$ (values are in percent (%)) from which we can conclude that the digital identity system has an advanced state of development considering properties of Trustworthiness (grade: 78). At the same time, countermeasures should focus on the large scale properties (grade: 12). It is important to remember that the study of functional dependencies opens to a comprehensive analysis. However, this rendering does not immediately express the quality of the work. A single number as a final score would be more appropriate for that. To clarify the reason for this, suppose an e-identity offering results $\langle 100; 20; 20; 0 \rangle$. While a second e-identity system: $\langle 0; 40; 50; 60 \rangle$. It is not immediately clear from the exploded results of Algorithm 1 which of the two systems is better. Thus, we pair a global score with the functional analysis.

3.1.6.1.2 Global score. The Global Score (G) provides a single indicator to study the correctness and convergence of initiatives to SSI. It computes the average of σ values obtained from step 5 of the functional dependency as $\sum_{i=1}^4 \sigma_i$ where i is an index that iterates over the four categories. The higher the score, the better the convergence to SSI. That means, a score of 70% is better than a score of 20%. The importance of keeping both results (functional dependency and global score) is quickly said: back to an extreme example, but still realistic, a digital identity with $\langle 0; 0; 40; 40 \rangle$ obtains a G of 20%; same G of a system scoring $\langle 40; 40; 0; 0 \rangle$. Thus, a global indicator is quick to render but may hide relevant information about the subcategories of development. Both results give stakeholders an overall feeling of the solution (global score) but remain open to a deeper analysis through the functional dependency.

3.1.7 Research Findings

In this section we test our model to assess eIDAS. During the evaluation stage, each dimension obtains a full coefficient (●), half (◐), or empty (◑). Coefficients multiply weights. We stick with factual things of the regulation and do not consider future considerations or expectations from the current revision of eIDAS. We then calculate results according to the steps in Algorithm 1 and plot results in a Kiviart chart. The chart helps to identify patterns, similarities, and disparities between categories.

- *Existence. What attributes can attest to an e-identity?*

Evaluation. Electronic identification under eIDAS allows individuals to attest to an e-identity through different attributes (username, PID, biometric data). The regulation promotes a high level of assurance. Member States define the Levels-of-assurance (hereafter LoA) according to local policy and rules, creating unfair situations in which countries can increase or decrease the requirements for LoA, thus increasing or decreasing the number of services with which its citizens can attest to an e-identity in other Member States. That generates entry-level barriers. Furthermore, two Member States (Portugal and Bulgaria)

still need to notify an identity scheme under eIDAS.⁴

Outcome: 42%. Individuals can authenticate to a service and prove their existence under eIDAS in several ways, but a different definition of LoA among Member States generates entry-level barriers.

- *Persistence. Who can issue attributes? How many IdPs can provide the same attribute?*
Evaluation. Member States appoint special service providers as TSPs and QTSPs under the conditions specified by the Regulation. Although flexibility exists, the requirements are precisely defined by the European Union. Several trust service providers can issue the same trust services, thus producing overlaps. Examples exist in Italy where Postecom S.p.A. and InfoCert S.p.A. can issue the same attributes. By contrast, the regulation does not allow any other public or private body to issue trust services unless they become TSP.
Outcome: 33%. Only trust service providers can issued an e-identity under eIDAS. Although, some attributes can be attested by many TSPs.
- *Protection. Who maintains the list of IdPs and SPs?*
Evaluation. Member States establish, maintain and publish the trusted list of TSPs and QTSPs (Article 22 (1) of the eIDAS regulation). The national supervisory bodies appointed by each Member State are responsible for the management and security of the list and notify the Commission (Article 22 (2)(3) of the eIDAS). The private sector, consortium, and other institutions cannot be a Trusted List maintainer if not appointed by the Member State.
Outcome: 23%. Only authorities within the list of TSPs and QTSPs can issue e-identities.

Table 3.4 (a) summarizes the evaluation for Individuals' rights. σ is 32%, with all principles under 50%.

- *Access. How users obtain information about their attributes? Can users access the list of IdPs?*
Evaluation. The Commission foresees a European Wallet to obtain, store, and issue credentials [Com23]. Notifications are periodic bulletins in the form of pop up that announce relevant information about the use of digital identity. The wallet functionalities listed in the ARF are precise, although the wallet implementation is ongoing, and no functionalities for a notification system are specified yet. The European Commission maintains a central map of trust service providers,⁵ provides access to the Trusted Lists of all EU member states. Users can browse the list and retrieve information about each country's trusted identity providers and service providers.
Outcome: 60%. The Commission plans to introduce a European Wallet for obtaining, storing, and issuing credentials. To date, there is no specific implementation of the wallet.

⁴Overview of pre-notified and notified e-identity schemes under eIDAS.<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/wikis/display/EIDCOMMUNITY/Overview+of+pre-notified+and+notified+eID+schemes+under+eIDAS>

⁵EU/EEA Trusted List Browser. <https://www.eid.as/tsp-map/#/>

- Control.** *Do users negotiate the release of attributes to SPs?*
Evaluation. Attributes exchange is service-dependent but generally possible with most service providers. PIDs are, instead, not negotiable as they are a unique set of personal information used to identify users and are difficult to negotiate with x509 certificates. Referring to service providers, users can freely choose the SP they wish to authenticate to, as long as it is in the list of trust service providers published by Member States.
Outcome: 50%. The eIDAS gives only a limited possibility to negotiate attributes from a pre-set list of service providers.
- Transparency.** *Are policies and rules to manage ecosystem members transparent and clearly stated?*
Evaluation. The eIDAS does not provide just guidelines but rules for electronic identification, authentication, and trust services. The regulation defines policies, procedures and promotes transparency through mutual recognition, which allows e-identities in a Member State to be recognized and accepted in other Member States.
Outcome: 67%. The eIDAS establishes rules instead of general guidelines for the electronic identification.

Table 3.4 (b) summarizes the evaluation for Trustworthiness. The σ value is 59%, more than halfway from mere SSI, with no principle below 50%.

- Consent.** *Does consent result adequately expressed and managed?*
Evaluation. Consent management is treated under several texts. The GDPR lays down the rules for processing personal data in the information society services in Europe, and (the GDPR) specifies conditions for consent to be valid (specific, informed, freely given, and unambiguous). However, the regulation leeways Member States with a certain degree of room to specify further norms. For example, ages specified within the GDPR do not apply to certain services (e.g., adult video content). Dynamic consent is not mandatory, while the service provider determines the best-fit consent management solution for its needs. So far, the GDPR and eIDAS do not foresee implementing other (post) consent management systems.
Outcome: 22%. The eIDAS does not specify consent models other than the classical regulated under the GDPR.
- Minimization.** *Does the service lawfully collect only the minimum amount of information? Do users employ techniques to limit data sharing?*
Evaluation. The service provider must collect adequate and relevant data for data processing. The digital certificates (e.g., the x509) allow sharing a subset of attributes but not the single attribute, or the associated information.
Outcome: 23%. Data minimization is extremely compromised under eIDAS.

Table 3.5 (a) summarizes the evaluation for Secrecy. σ is stuck at 22.5% with all principles below 25%.

- **Cost.** *To what extent does the digital identity is profitable for stakeholders?*
Evaluation. The framework aims to decrease costs for public and private services and benefit citizens by fostering market competition [Dom20]. However, the lack of official studies and available data limits our assessment.
Outcome: 50%. The framework aims to decrease costs for services in Europe. However, lack of evidences to prove it affect the score.
- **Interoperability.** *To what extent can IdPs attest attributes to SPs across different jurisdictions?*
Evaluation. The regulation enables cross-border transactions between public and private services. Several international transactions exist for exchanging goods or opening bank accounts between EU countries. Thus, the discriminant factor is the roomy coefficient; public and private services act multi-country within the European Union. Nevertheless, not all Member States declare an e-identity Scheme under eIDAS.
Outcome: 75%. On paper, the eIDAS is an interoperability framework, but there is no evidence of concrete results.
- **Portability.** *To what extent can users transport the list of attributes on different ecosystems?*
Evaluation. Although transferring personal data across countries is an important aspect of data portability, the regulation does not focus on data portability, regulated by the GDPR and reinforced by further texts currently under discussion (e.g., the Data Act). It foresees the possibility for users to export data creating a copy of the wallet. No solution from the industry exists today.
Outcome: 0%. The eIDAS does not foresees data portability.
- **Standard.** *Who can issue standards for e-identity systems?*
Evaluation. International organizations like ISO can promote standards for credentials exchange and electronic signature under eIDAS. For example, by implementing the XAdES protocol in eIDAS, trusted service providers, such as certificate authorities, can offer compliant solutions for creating and verifying XML-based advanced electronic signatures [RAC21]. This standard enables organizations and citizens to use advanced electronic signatures securely and reliably for various purposes, such as signing contracts, submitting official documents, and more. Public agencies (e.g., European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)) can play an important role in defining formal specifications for the eIDAS protocol.
Outcome: 100%. The eIDAS employs a combination of standards from the industry, working groups, and academia.

Table 3.5 (b) summarizes the evaluation for Sustainability. σ scores is 56%. Three principles over 50%; one is at zero.

3.1.8 Research Analysis

The eIDAS obtained a *Global Score* of 42,4%, almost halfway from a perfect SSI solution. The analysis of functional dependency reported $\langle 32; 59; 22; 56 \rangle$ (values are in percent (%)). We plot results in a Kiviati chart to visually interpret relationships among categories (Figure 3.2). Our Kiviati chart consists of four axes radiating from a central point, each axis representing a category of our taxonomy. Outcomes from each category are along the corresponding axis, and a line connects points between adjacent axes. The thicker (blue) rumble is the eIDAS assessment. The dashed (outer) rumble represents the guideline for a fair SSI solution with the same values for all categories. The eIDAS performs well in two categories (Trustworthiness and Sustainability) with grades closer to 60%, with Trustworthiness marking the highest score. Two categories score less than 40%, with Secrecy stuck at 22,5%, indicating that work remains to enhance systems' privacy and secrecy design. An overall analysis of principles shows that six principles score below 50% with four principles $\leq 25\%$ and one at zero (Portability). Portability suffers from the lack of a standard for the EU wallet (the ARF provides only guidelines) and discrepancy of regulations in Member States. Five principles evaluate over 50% with Interoperability and Standard scoring significantly high (75% and 100%). Here the effort of the EU in pushing for a cross-border framework is worth it. Standard reflects the involvement of a manifold of players, although most likely rely on dated standards. We measure the variation or dispersion of results from principles from the average, namely the standard deviation [LIL15]. A low standard deviation implies that values cluster around the mean, whereas a large standard deviation indicates that values are more widespread. We calculate the standard deviation by taking the square root of the variance of the values subtracted from their average value [Waco9]. The Formula 3.1 computes the standard deviation.

$$(x - \mu) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where x_i is the i^{th} principle value as resulting from step 3 of Algorithm 1, μ is the mean of x values, N is the number of principles (population size). The resulting standard deviation is 29.6, which suggests that values vary widely from the mean of 45%. This dispersion of results, particularly from the score of the Secrecy, affects the global evaluation. In the other three categories (except the Secrecy), about 60% of the principles score higher than the mean, and 80% of them above a score of 40%, confirming the effort of the Commission to foster several aspects of the framework in different disciplines. Only two principles: Protection and Portability, in three categories (except the Secrecy) score less than 25%. For both, the diversity of regulations from Member States lowers the result.

The flaws of eIDAS are twofold. First, the Secrecy. Approaches like consent management and data minimization still refer to the old way of managing consent and sharing personal information. Consent management was dated back to the early Internet days when websites were different and mobile applications did not exist. Informed consent through pop-ups is tedious, and understanding what is "informed" is based on a case-by-case study. On the other hand,

data minimization is impossible through digital certificates in the form of x509, and policymakers should enforce legal value to coming standards for data exchange like Verifiable Credentials and Presentations. The second issue of eIDAS spreads across (almost) all principles and concerns the European Union. Each Member State has a leeway to implement the framework through slightly different approaches that reflect, for example, the various implementations of the LoA or the design of the EU wallet. The Commission provides guidelines for the wallet functionalities through its Architecture Reference Framework (ARF). Four working groups provide use cases to test the wallet functionalities. Although the process may take longer, the final implementation will come from the collaboration with the Member States, which in the end, will play a crucial role in implementing the wallet. They will be the finalizer of the wallet functionalities. Yet, without Member States working together on common standards, the risk is to disperse the effort and obtain several wallet proposals, each with pros and cons. A better approach would be to find everybody working on one prototype for the wallet (maybe two) with strict constraints from the Commission. That would speed up the process and avoid discrepancies in actions. Our assessment is helpful in pinpointing weaknesses in the design of identity systems. For example, eIDAS proves weaknesses in consent management and data minimization. On the other hand, it strengthens the acceptance rate of solutions. Acceptance is users' confidence in using an e-identity [Acc], which results in crucial system design. If people trust an e-identity system, they will be willing to adopt it.

3.1.9 Recommendations

Our findings open the discussion on the quest for a perfect SSI solution. First, a mere SSI might only be worthy for some people. For example, having a system that exerts exclusive user control of the recovery key requires technical skills. If users lose the key, the wallet and its content will be burned. It is like being in a foreign country and losing the passport. Alternatively, someone (maybe a government) should have access to the wallet to back up its content periodically. On the other hand, a perfect SSI is also not feasible. Parameters are strongly tied, and increasing a score in one modifies the others. That means the eIDAS rumble of Figure 3.2 can be enlarged to a certain extent but not achieve a perfect diamond with corners at 100%. We believe a corner can be stretched as long as others are squeezed. Thus, an ideal SSI remains a utopistic idea. As a second point for discussion: corporations might have the power to stretch the diamond, but they might not be willing to invest in it, as opposed to startups. Suppose a mature solution ranks high in half of the parameters and zero in the others. It can receive a Global grade of 50%, still higher than a startup averaging 40% in each parameter. Apparently, the corporate solution is better than the other, but this analysis would not consider different aspect of the system. For this reason, a better definition of SSI would encode a combination of Global Score and σ values, where the constraint for the Global Score G would be relaxed to justify the name "quasi" as long as the constraint for the functional dependency stays the same. The functional dependency study can be used to strengthen the constraints and force solutions to respect parameters in each development area. We then leverage a more pragmatic definition for SSI, as follows:

Definition 1 (Quasi-SSI). *Quasi-SSI is a lighter and pragmatic version of SSI that respects criteria 1 and 2, defined as follows:*

Figure 3.2: A Kiviatic chart reporting the Global Score and each category σ value. The thicker (blue) rumble is the outcome of eIDAS. The inner thinner (green) rumble is our pragmatic definition of SSI. The dashed (outer) rumble represents the guideline for a fair SSI solution.

1. $G \geq 40\%$
2. $\sigma_i \geq 35\% \quad \forall \sigma_i \in \Sigma$

Where G is the global score and σ_i results from Step 5 of the functional dependency (Algorithm 1).

The first criterion relaxes the constraints of SSI to a Global score above 40%. The second reinforces criterion 1 and pretends solutions will perform significantly well in every category of the taxonomy: all categories should have a score $\geq 35\%$. The overall result imposes constraints in the progression of development in each category (Individuals' rights, Trustworthiness, Secrecy, and Sustainability). The two conditions must happen in conjunction. According to our new definition of quasi-SSI, eIDAS fails in the second criterion and cannot be considered a quasi-SSI solution. As an outcome of our analysis, we can refine the previously stated notion of acceptance in light of our new definition of quasi-SSI. Acceptance is the degree of confidence of users in using an e-identity system that, aftermath applying our model, respects the parameters defined in Definition 1.

From the analysis of eIDAS through our model, we provide six legal and four technical recommendations for eIDAS from the twelve principles we analyzed. We specify between parenthesis the principles from which our recommendations come. From the legal advice: 1) the Commission should work to decrease the ambiguity of LoA, specifying parameters that are unique for Member States to follow. Today, Member States have tuned those parameters for LoA, generating inequality across e-identity schemes in the European Union. 2) Streamline the procedure for

service providers to become TSPs (Persistence). The process to become a TSP lasts from a few months up to a year (sometimes even more). Due to the importance of TSPs in the framework, the Commission should act to decrease the time to become TSP without relaxing the requirements. This would lift the number of TSPs from 14% in 2021 to the goal (of the Commission) of 80% by 2030. 3) Move the management of the list of service providers from Member States to a "super partes" entity of the European Union or an open community of contributors (Protection). Our objective is that no authority from a Member State shall control the list of IdPs/SPs, thus decreasing the risk of censorship from the Member States. 4) In terms of costs and benefits, once the revision of the regulation is applied, and the wallet adopted by the Member States free of charge for businesses and citizens (first quarter of 2025), analyzing eIDAS in terms of cost saving for citizens, public and private services (Cost). That would narrow the focus of the Commission to employ resources where needed. 5) Add a chapter in eIDAS that specifically addresses governance-related issues and portability to embrace and help quickly adopt coming standards from the technical field (Portability). Standardization will be key to interoperability between different platforms and networks, enabling the seamless use of identities, avatars, data, virtual assets, experiences or environments, and the associated rights across platforms and networks. This would also help to 6) embrace cutting-edge standards (e.g., the Verifiable Credentials) and speed up the process to give them legal value.

Along with these recommendations, we highlight a few technical challenges. 1) The Commission should allow citizens to negotiate Personal Identification Data (PID), embracing coming standards different from digital certificates (Control). 2) Implement data minimization so that users should not disclose all personal information when they provide their identity (Minimization). 3) Enable consent preferences to travel along with claims (e.g., digital certificates, verifiable credentials, etc.) and provide a dashboard for users to manage consent preferences transparently (Consent). In general, more effort should be made by the Commission to extend the classical consent management proposal to include post-consent solutions. For example, controlling the flow of information and providing users with a dashboard to manage their preferences online. The final recommendation 4) the Commission should revise the use of middleware to foster interoperability (Interoperability).

3.1.10 Conclusions

The Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) ecosystem is young and immature, with a manifold of actors providing solutions that follow common design patterns. Yet, no tool exists to assess those offerings, thus allowing anyone to declare adherence to SSI. This work proposed a formalization of concept to study the convergence of systems to SSI. We tested our model on the major European identity framework (eIDAS) and discussed the results. The model promises to rank solutions, streamline the design pattern, and spot weaknesses. In the long run, it can be used to determine the historical progression of e-identity systems toward SSI, as opposed to period-related rankings. Our Comprehensive Rating System (CRS) is left purposely general to avoid overfitting it on specific solutions, and we also generalized some featuring aspects of eIDAS during the assessment. Many implementation-specific parts were left blank for practitioners to fill in and were not tested by our model. For example, we generalized privacy-related issues of

wallet authentication and trust services with LoA. However, the potential of our model is the process of moving from a list of theoretical principles to practical evaluation, and we are aware that in this migration process, we lose some information. Today, parameters and weights are based on the literature review, but often we cannot find proper guidelines to help us choose values for the weights and their ratio. In the future, we aim to strengthen the quality of our model, sharing parameters and weights with a recognized community of experts and conducting surveys to tune values. With this, we aim to achieve recognition from a global community of experts. Meanwhile, testing further industry-based initiatives will be a plus value in refining our parameters. Our model's current state of the art led to a more pragmatic definition of SSI as quasi-SSI that promises to guide the future development of e-identity solutions. Quasi-SSI constrains our tweaked definition of SSI to distinguish practitioners doing well from solutions needing further improvement. Through a better model, we can also improve the definition of quasi-SSI to represent real-world values. The final breakthrough is to push policymakers and practitioners to strengthen the state of the art of digital identity to meet the promise of SSI and pave the road of the research field in evaluating e-identity offerings

Algorithm 1: Functional dependency (pseudo-code)

Data: $w_1, \dots, w_n \in W$ such that $w \in \{5, 7, 8, 10, 15, 20\}$; /* set of weights */

Input: mini-batches β_i , β_i is a category $\{w \mid w \subseteq W \text{ weights of dimensions}\}$

$\beta_i = \{(w_1, c_1), (w_2, c_2), \dots, (w_j, c_j), \dots, [\dots]\}$ where

$\forall i = 1, \dots, n, c_i \in \{0, 0.5, 1\}$

Output: $\Sigma = \{\sigma_1 \rightarrow \sigma_2 \rightarrow \sigma_3 \rightarrow \sigma_4\}$; /* functional dependency */

$\Sigma \leftarrow \emptyset$

In parallel for each mini-batch β_i do

for each challenge C do

Step 1: multiply weights by coefficients

$w'_j = w_j \times c_j$ for each dimension $d_j \in C$

Step 2: sum results

$S_c = \sum_{d_j \in C} w'_j$

Step 3: normalize weights

$\|S_c\| = \frac{(S_c - w_{\min})}{[w_{\min}, w_{\max}]}$; /* Min-max normalization */

end

Step 4: compute weighted average

$\sigma_i = \text{Avg} \sum \|S_c\|$; /* Avg of norms in mini-batch */

Step 5: collect results as a power of ten

$\Sigma \cup \{\sigma_i \times 100\}$; /* Cartesian product of 100 */

end

Return: $\Sigma \leftarrow \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4\}$

Table 3.4: Individuals' rights an Trustworthiness assessment. Pts stands for points.

Individuals' rights (a)				
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight	Coeff.
Existence	- What attributes can attest to an e-identity?	- Assigned attributes (Username and Password)	5 pts	●
		- Multi-Factor Authentication	7 pts	●
		- Accumulated attributes (PIDs)	10 pts	○
		- Inherited attributes (Biometric data)	10 pts	●
		- Digital certificates (e.g., x509)	10 pts	○
Persistence	- Who can issue attributes?	- Other attributes (e.g., eSign, timestamp)	10 pts	○
		- Qualified Trust Service Providers (QTSPs)	10 pts	●
		- Trust service providers (Non-Qualified)	10 pts	●
		- Other public bodies (e.g., Gov agencies, Univ.)	10 pts	○
Protection	- Who maintains the list of IdPs and SPs?	- Other private bodies (e.g., Microsoft, Okta)	10 pts	○
		- Private sector (e.g., banks, credit bureaus)	5 pts	○
		- Consortium of organizations (e.g., Kantara)	8 pts	○
		- Gov agencies (e.g., national identity authority)	10 pts	●
		- Other gov institutions (e.g., EU Commission)	10 pts	○
		- Community of contributors (open)	10 pts	○
Trustworthiness (b)				
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight	Notify
Access	- How users obtain information about their attributes? - Can users access the list of IdPs?	- Local agent (wallet)	10 pts	○
		- Shared ledger of IdPs	10 pts	●
Control	- Do users negotiate the release of attributes to SPs?	- User negotiates attributes but PIDs	10 pts	○
		- User negotiates PIDs	15 pts	○
		- Users can choose the service provider	15 pts	○
Transparency	- Are policies and rules to manage ecosystem members transparent and clearly stated?	- General guidelines only	5 pts	○
		- Transparent rules and procedures	10 pts	●

Table 3.5: Secrecy and Sustainability assessment. Pts stands for points.

Secrecy (a)				
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight	Coeff.
Consent	- Does consent result adequately expressed and managed?	- Informed consent	10 pts	●
		- Dynamic consent	15 pts	○
		- Post-consent	20 pts	○
Minimization	- Does the service lawfully collect only the minimum amount of information?	- Adequate and relevant data collection	10 pts	●
		- Minimization of attributes but PIDs	10 pts	○
		- Minimization of PIDs	15 pts	○
	- Do users employ techniques to limit data sharing?	- Transfer only a subset of attributes	5 pts	●
		- Transfer one attribute at a time	10 pts	○
		- Transfer the associated information only	15 pts	○
Sustainability (b)				
Principle	Challenge	Dimension	Weight	Coeff.
Cost	- To what extent does the e-identity is profitable for stakeholders?	- Profitable for public services	10 pts	○
		- Profitable for private services	10 pts	○
		- Profitable for citizens	10 pts	○
Interoperability	- To what extent can IdPs attest attributes to SPs across different jurisdictions?	- Among public services	10 pts	○
		- Among private services	10 pts	○
Portability	- To what extent can users transport the list of attributes on different ecosystems?	- Between public authorities	10 pts	○
		- Between private authorities	10 pts	○
		- Full portability	15 pts	○
Standard	- Who can issue standards for e-identity systems?	- Working/Community groups	10 pts	●
		- Industry sector (e.g., Avast)	10 pts	●
		- Public agencies (e.g., gov)	10 pts	●

3.2 Distributed reliability and blockchain-like technologies

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3.2.1 Executive summary

Data processing and AI-based techniques are now widely used in multiple sectors, including business, sociology, healthcare, mobility, research, etc. The new applications creating from (big) data analytics technologies are impacting our daily lives and will do so even more in the future, as reported by Forbes. Moreover, companies and public organizations have produced and/or collected various types of data which today are stored in data silos that need to be integrated to build a data economy that drives innovation. Such data spaces should involve different stakeholders in collaborative data processing including distributed data life cycle as well as decentralized data governance. Naturally, when several systems are interconnected to carry out each step of the data life cycle, this data life cycle can be defined as distributed. When multiple entities manage data governance, this type of data governance is called decentralized data governance. Collaborative data processing raises several issues and challenges, especially, ensuring the reliability of distributed systems, trust in the decentralized governance of data processing, and compliance with legal requirements concerning data processing. Data quality plays a central role in these challenges to create a data economy. Data quality evaluation is a potential indicator to enhance the reliability, trust and legal compliance of shared data across collaborative data processing. The main contribution of my research will respond to the questions such as: are data governance stakeholders able to make the right decisions to maintain data quality? What are the data quality criteria that can be used to assess trust in all data governance stakeholders based on their actions and decisions? What are the data quality criteria pertinent to data governance? Then, how to assess the reliability of all components in distributed systems, i.e. the ability of each component to perform correctly and not degrade the quality of the data? How to create data quality contracts at each step of the data life cycle based on appropriate data quality criteria? Finally, how to respond to the fact that, there is no existing work that categorizes data quality criteria according to regulations (RGPD, Data Act, Data Governance Act, AI Act, Open Data EU regulation...)?

3.2.2 Introduction

Data processing covers a wide range of operations aiming to transform data into meaningful information. Nowadays, multiple entities produce, transform and use data from various sources for different purposes [SPM20; SPM21b; Gra22b; Kit21]. Given that data has an important impact in our daily life, many legal requirements are established to regulate data management in the world and especially in the European Union that is promoting data spaces to enforce data sharing and innovation. Such ecosystem will require private and public organizations to process data by using a decentralized governance and distributed technologies [Gan+17].

Data became the new oil [SPM21c]. Public and private organisations consider data as an asset and include it in their business strategies [KB10]. Some organisations collect data from other

entities for discovering knowledge and facilitating innovation. Important volumes of data are exchanged between organisations, thus, data is moving from different distributed systems. This makes the data lifecycle distributed and decentralized. A distributed system is an infrastructure that encompasses a set of autonomous systems interconnected through a computer network, which cooperate to carry out tasks with large-scale and high performance computing [Jia16; OV11c]. For instance, Liu et al. [LCH11] proposed a distributed data mining system for e-business using multi-agent model. Each data source processes its own data locally and sends only the local models to the main host, reducing network traffic and enhancing security and data privacy. Moreover, organisations collaborating to produce and process data contribute in the decision-making task related to data management. Hence, the data governance becomes decentralized. Having data on distributed systems managed by decentralized governance introduced the collaborative data processing.

This collaborative approach of data processing raises some issues and challenges. One of the most important issues is how to ensure the reliability of distributed systems [Jon+17], trust in the decentralized governance of data processing, and compliance with the legal requirements concerning data processing [Noae; Noai]. Reliability is the probability that a system (including all hardware, firmware, and software) will perform the task for which it was designed or intended, for a specified time and in a specified environment [AW13; OV11b]. While trust is relation among entities where one believes that the other has the willingness and capability to achieve its expectations. [MFGL12; AD+19; DPO4].

The EU is regulating these collaborative data ecosystems by promoting the European Common Data Spaces. A data space is a trustworthy environment that enables the pooling, access, sharing, and reuse of data. Common European Data Spaces allow organizations and individuals to share data from various domains while adhering to EU rules and values, ensuring privacy and security. These data spaces aim to form an interconnected European data economy, fostering the development of new products and services. A critical aspect of the data Space concept is that data is not stored centrally but remains at its source. Therefore, data is only transferred when and where it is necessary. This joint approach to data management in the EU highlights the importance of effective collaborative data processing and data quality assurance strategies. Collaborative data processing not only helps to manage data within decentralized governance models but also face the challenges of compliance, trust, and reliability, which are essential components for ensuring the quality of shared data in such dynamic and distributed environments.

In this context, data quality (DQ) plays a critical role, as it is essential to ensure that data is relevant and fit for purpose of operational activities, strategic planning and decision making. In fact, ensuring an appropriate level of DQ throughout the data lifecycle is fundamental to the production of valuable and reliable results. [CZ15; Tal+16]. Ted Friedman, vice president and distinguished analyst at Gartner (a leading research and advisory company that provides insights, and advices for business leaders in various industries), explained at the Gartner Data & Analytics Summit 2018 that, "As organizations accelerate their digital business efforts, poor data quality is a major contributor to a crisis in information trust and business value, negatively impacting financial performance"[Moo18]. DQ aims to measure the suitability of the data to produce meaningful information and the ease with which it can be processed [Wes+21]. It also

refers to the ability to meet the needs and expectations of data users (entities consuming and using data from publishers) [Noaa; Sid+12]. The measurement of DQ is a combination of a set of parameters that characterise the value of the data or the process that produced or modified it [Sid+12]. These parameters are called Data Quality Criteria (DQC).

Then, the objective of this document consists in representing the process from which we proposed a data quality evaluation method to assess the level of trust, reliability and legal compliance in a collaborative environment. The remainder of the document is structured as following: The section 2 presents the state of the art of collaborative data processing including fundamentals of trust and reliability. The section 3 describes two academic and industrial approaches that consolidate data quality criteria in collaborative data processing ecosystem. The section 4 presents a Blockchain-based prototype for transparent and traceable data portal. And the section 5 concludes the analysis.

3.2.3 Background and problem statement

With the emergence of Big Data, organizations today need to analyze massive and heterogeneous data in order to gain knowledge allowing to understand users behavior and users need for performing public service (like health and education) or organizations business. This allows them to stay competitive, and quickly adapt to changes. This data analysis is only one step of a more comprehensive process called data processing [Jia16; GMG10].

Data processing is performed in a series of steps where raw data is fed into a process to obtain data sets useful for improving the governance of organizations and governments (Figure 3.3). Shah et al. [SPM21b] proposed a consolidated data life cycle framework, called DaLiF, for data-driven governments, which is composed of two layers.

3.2.3.1 Data lifecycle (Layer 1)

This layer encompasses ten stages through which data passes throughout its life in the system.

- The **planning phase** determines the activities during the data life cycle. The output is a holistic data management plan. A data management plan is a document that determines a mandatory basis for handling data during the data life cycle. It defines responsibilities and regularizes access rights. It defines the basis of workflows in project involving several entities [Noao].
- The **collection phase** includes the activities to gather data from various sources like social networks, the Internet of things, surveys, biological records, satellite observations, and commerce statistics.
- The **preparation phase** filters, integrates and enriches data to obtain data sets able to reduce the complexity in the data processing.
- The **analysis phase** is responsible for developing all data analysis to extract knowledge and discover new insights. It encompasses activities like data Mining [HF09], clustering

[JP73; Bero6], classification [Mag07; Qui14] or outlier detection [LSMoo]... This phase can output interpretations and knowledge from raw or prepared data.

- The **visualization phase** deals with the presentation and visualization of the previous outputs.
- The **access phase** provides communication system between the data controllers and data life cycle output consumers as well as access control policies. This step is not mandatory.
- The **Share/Publish phase** is about the distribution of data. The sharing of information benefit to the stakeholders such as governments, businesses, citizens, researchers, scientific partners, and federal agencies, this phase is mandatory [WC21; Noan].
- The **Use, re(use), and feedback phase** combines two activities. One is related to the use and reuse of data by consumers while feedback consists in collecting users comments/-suggestions to improve the published data.
- The **archiving phase** keeps records of obsolete data that are finally destroyed.
- The **end of life phase** consists of removing from the system duplicated data, no longer required data as well as useless data.

3.2.3.2 Data governance (Layer 2)

This layer consists of the overall process of managing and controlling data to maximize its use and its value. This includes 3 tasks:

- The **quality task** aims to maintain data quality during the whole life cycle. High quality data are data that are fit for use by data consumers. We can assess quality data by accuracy, accessibility, completeness regarding processing purpose, and interpretability [CRRO20].
- The **storage task** controls how data is stored throughout the life cycle for ensuring confidentiality, integrity, availability and privacy. This ensures that important information or data will be reusable and protected unauthorized uses.
- The **security and protection task** deals with data protection in terms of integrity, security, access control, and privacy. Data confidentiality refers to preventing the active attack of unauthorized entities on data. It consists also to ensure that only authorized people are able to access and obtain the data. Data integrity is the reliability of the data. It means that data can not be arbitrarily tampered with and replaced. Data availability emphasizes that data can be accessed or downloaded by users at any time. Then privacy protection consists to guarantee that personal data, such as identity, location, and sensitive data for the public and private organizations remain secret from curious adversaries and for malicious purposes [Yan].

Figure 3.3: The DaLiF data life cycle [SPM21b]

3.2.4 State of the Art: Towards collaborative data processing

3.2.4.1 The need for collaborative data processing

Performing all stages of the data processing life cycle locally and in a centralized way causes several problems. First, a centralized architecture can lack scalability as it suffers from limited capacities in terms of storage, bandwidth, energy consumption, security, etc. It therefore would not handle a large amount of data [GHO6; XJO2; SGM14; Bero6]. A centralized architecture also lacks reliability as it represents a single point a failure. If it fails the whole system will stop operating. Also, concurrence, merger and collaboration in activities of public services and enterprises lead them to adopt decentralized data processing. In this decentralized ecosystem encompassing several phases, governance and responsibilities of each phase is specific. For all these reason we will focus our study on data processing through decentralized governance and distributed systems. Having a decentralized governance to manage all the data rises a question of trust. The neutrality of the entity processing the data is not necessarily guaranteed [Yan22]. To overcome the problems related to centralized data processing, collaborative data processing emerged [CTCo6; Zen+12]. It is a community-based approach for managing and exploiting data. In other words, this is a high-capacity combined system that covers the entire data life cycle. It includes participation and interaction between humans and computer systems [SPV12; Gan+17; Qiu+16]. Such approach benefits for combining and filtering data from different systems to enrich knowledge [PCSo0], reducing storage costs and enhancing data security as well [AL; GBKo4]. The lack of capacity, reliability and trust of a single system is thus resolved by multiple systems working together.

To achieve this, a combination of collaborative tools and distributed systems are used to enable a wide range of people in an organization (and beyond) to participate in data processing in a de-

centralized way. Two concepts come out of this: decentralization and distribution. Distribution is about the physical infrastructure of a system. It is compound of set of autonomous processing entities, interconnected through a computer network and which cooperate to carry out tasks assigned to them [OV11a]. It is also about distributing data sets on multiple sites in a partial or total way [DTR19]. In data processing, distribution concerns systems acting in the entire data life cycle [Biro6] (p22-24). While, decentralization is more about governance and decision making. In other words, it consists of having not one but multiple individuals or organizations to control the computers and the system [DTR19; Asa+18]. In data processing, decentralization concerns the second layer (data governance) of the scheme presented previously.

3.2.4.2 Collaborative data processing challenges

Among the challenges facing data processing three are particularly important: reliability, trust and legal compliance. However trust and reliability are closely linked and often confused. They are different like distribution and decentralization. **Reliability** is **objective** and applies on the physical infrastructure of a system. **Trust**, on the other hand, is **subjective** and is about governance and decision making. Furthermore, the way we consider reliability and trust are changing due to the introduction of collaboration in data processing. Before, we needed to rely and trust centralized third parties for any type of exchange between two entities. Now, we are switching to distributed systems with decentralized governance. This is why we now talk more about distributed reliability and decentralized trust.

Reliability is the probability that a system (including all hardware, firmware, and software) will perform the task for which it was designed or intended, for a specified time and in a specified environment [AW13]. Distributed reliability consists of extending this concept to distributed systems. In this section, we are interested in the application of distributed reliability to collaborative data processing. Reliability has indeed a great importance when the life cycle of data is distributed.

Technology trust is defined as the subjective probability by which organizations believe that the underlying technology infrastructure is capable of facilitating transactions according to their confident expectations [DPO4]. Decentralized trust consists of extending this concept to decentralized governance. In this section, we are interested in the application of decentralized trust to collaborative data processing. Trust has indeed a great importance when data governance is decentralized. The following writing will presents some criteria required for establishing trust.

3.2.5 Objectives and Scope

The concept of a Data Space implies a community-based approach for managing and exploiting data. Within such a community, commitments need to be formalized through contractual agreements, such as confidentiality or non-disclosure. This raises questions about how the underlying layers will ensure compliance and define a level of adherence to regulations. How can we formalize data quality through contracts, guarantee it, and establish a means of evaluation? Especially, regulatory requirements may change according to the type of data and its use. To the best of our knowledge, there is no existing work that categorizes data quality criteria according

to regulations (RGPD, Data Act, Data Governance Act, AI Act, Open Data EU regulation...). There is a need for scientific research to develop a framework that aligns data quality criteria with the evolving regulatory landscape, particularly in the context of community-driven data spaces.

3.2.5.1 Ensure reliability of distributed systems

Reliability is the likelihood that a system, including hardware and software materials, will successfully perform its intended tasks under specified conditions and over specified periods of time [AW13]. Distributed reliability extends this concept to distributed systems. Akimova et al. [AST18] define the reliability of distributed systems as the ability to maintain the defined criteria required to perform a given task under the influence of failures, breakdowns, hardware-based or human errors, etc. In the context of data processing, distributed system reliability means that each step is performed with fault tolerance by all the technologies involved, resulting in high quality outputs. The reliability of distributed systems depends on the systems, the data life cycle phases (data collection, data preparation, data analysis, etc [SPM21b]), the data transactions and, most importantly, the quality of the data outputs. It is therefore necessary to assess the reliability of all entities in distributed systems, i.e. the ability of each component to perform correctly and not degrade the quality of the data. Future research should focus on to create data quality contracts at each phases of the data life cycle based on appropriate data quality criteria.

3.2.5.2 Increase trust in decentralized governance

Trust is a subjective concept characterizing a relationship among two or multiple entities with a common purpose [MFGL12]. In decentralized data governance, it is the belief that all participants in that data governance are willing and able to produce high quality data outputs. Indeed, having multiple entities managing data raises trust concerns, as the self-interest of one entity processing the data may conflict with the overall benefit of other entities [Yan22]. Assessing the trustworthiness of individual contributors and their commitment to producing high quality data outputs is essential. This need leads to the following questions: are data governance stakeholders able to make the right decisions to maintain data quality? What are the data quality criteria that can be used to assess trust in all data governance stakeholders based on their actions and decisions? What are the data quality criteria relevant to data governance?

3.2.5.3 Achieve compliance with regulations

The concept of a Data Space implies a community-based approach for managing and exploiting data. Within such a community, commitments need to be formalized through contractual agreements, such as confidentiality or non-disclosure. This raises questions about how the underlying layers will ensure compliance and define a level of adherence to regulations. How can we formalize data quality through contracts, guarantee it, and establish a means of evaluation? Especially, regulatory requirements may change according to the type of data and its use. To the best of our knowledge, there is no existing work that categorizes data quality criteria according

to regulations (RGPD, Data Act, Data Governance Act, AI Act, Open Data EU regulation...). There is a need for scientific research to develop a framework that aligns data quality criteria with the evolving regulatory landscape, particularly in the context of community-driven data spaces.

3.2.6 Methodology

To reach the resolution of the aforementioned challenges, we faced two main tasks:

- Identify the relevant data quality criteria (DQC),
- Classifying these criteria by trust, reliability or legal compliance.

We managed these tasks by using respectively theoretical and practical methodologies which encompassed specific sub-steps. First, we conducted a systematic literature review to identify the DQCs. Then, we consolidated this list based on discussions and recommendations from data experts. Finally, we classified the resulting DQC. The remainder of this section describes all details of each steps of our methodology.

3.2.6.1 Systematic literature review

This part describes the methodology to conduct our systematic literature survey. It explains how we selected and redefined the resulting DQC collected from the survey. Our methodology is similar to those of Shah et al. [[SPM21c](#); [SPM21b](#)] and Bowling Ann et al. [[Bow05](#)]. The survey was structured in four main steps:

1. Formulation of the research questions.
2. Identification of the pertinent research works.
3. Selection of best articles through inclusion and exclusion criteria.
4. Analysis and verification.

We realized a comprehensive analysis of the current surveys and research works on DQCs. We chose IEEE Xplore, Science Direct, ACM, Springer Link, Web of Science and Google Scholar. In each library, we formulate research queries to identify the pertinent DQC. The requests generated 3480 documents. Then, we picked the articles with headings related to "data" and "quality" or "information" and "quality". This resulted in 604 relevant scientific reports for our investigation. Moreover, we identified the top 30 research articles based on their number of citations. The last article on the list had 24, whereas the first had 2412. Next, we studied all the data quality criteria presented in these papers. These papers described a total of 270 DQC. However, several research articles proposed the same DQC. Thus, we regrouped the DQC having the same name and a similar definition to avoid redundancy. Then, we realized there were just 30 common DQC in the entire set of papers.

Figure 3.4 summarizes this systematic literature review and the criteria are presented by figures 3.5, 3.6, 3.7 and 3.8. However, we proposed an exhaustive description of this systematic

Figure 3.4: Selection of relevant research articles

literature review in at the conference CSE 2023 untitled "Towards Reliable Collaborative Data Processing Ecosystems: Survey on Data Quality Criteria".

3.2.6.2 Semi-directive interviews with data experts

This section describes our strategy for proposing a standardized framework of DQCs that is taking into account the overall context of collaborative data spaces in Europe and its corresponding challenges of reliability, trust and legality. It focuses on our list of 30 data quality criteria. As DQCs are essential in our mission, it was mandatory to validate the methodology of the systematic literature review and the resulting list of criteria in order to ensure the significance of our solutions. Then, we take advantage of the secondment program of LeADS Project to discuss our methodology with several professors in cybersecurity; business and innovation; and laws. Our objective is to validate and select the most relevant criteria by gathering feedback from several data experts. These interviews will allow us to evaluate the relevance of each criterion and understand how to apply them to real data sets. These exchange is a practical validation of the list of criteria to reduce the gap between academic methodology and industrial applicability.

So, we had the opportunity to realise the aforementioned interviews with internal and partners having highest interest on quality of their data during the secondment at Intel Corporation (Belgium).

The interviews at Intel Corporation aimed to gather the expertise of professionals and partners to help us to recognize 'quality' data sets. For each professional, they consisted in collecting firstly their opinions on the relevant criteria (their criteria, definitions, evaluation levels, etc.), then asking comments and feedback concerning our criteria, definitions and evaluation levels of DQCs.

So, we selected nine data experts working in European companies and having important experiences on data management. They were coming from different backgrounds such as: cyber security (O2) ; data privacy, protection and compliance (O4) ; supply chain data management (O1) ; statistics and performance (O1) ; data documentation (O1). Each interview was conducted online between 30 and 45 minutes. The questionnaire which led the discussions contained **open and semi-directives** questions such as:

- Do you use datasets as part of your business? What type of data? Where does it come from (internal or external (linked to a contract or not)? What type of processing do you carry out on this data?
- Have you encountered any problems with data quality during processing?
- How do you define a dataset of good quality? And what are the quality criteria?
- What definition do you propose? What are the evaluation levels for the criterion? Does this criterion enhance the trust, reliability or regulatory compliance of the data?

We recorded all the interviews then extracted the relevant information of interest by taking into account the context of their activity and nature of their data. These discussions generated many information concerning data management and DQCs such as:

- 31/32 criteria mentioned by the interviewees plus 4 others criteria
- 69 comments on the mentioned criteria.
- These comments can be represented as full acceptance (06), recommendation on definitions or names and details on criteria and their evaluation methods (59), then the rejections (04).
- The activities of the interviewees concerned the mandatory steps of the data life cycle and the governance task (collection, preparation, analysis, reuse and feedback, sharing, governance)

3.2.7 Research Analysis

This part of the analysis concerns the solution we proposed to establish trust, reliability and legal compliance in collaborative data processing. This solution will be based on blockchain which is a set of secure and distributed storage nodes.

3.2.7.1 Classified data quality criteria

Performing the systematic literature review and the interviews with data experts allow us to gathered list of pertinent and consolidated DQCs which can be categorised in a data life cycle. This results is presented in the following figure "3.2".

This picture describes the main contribution of our research. The methodology we used generate 4 categories of data quality criteria. Each categories contains criteria corresponding to a specific collaborative data processing challenges. Furthermore, this result proposes a step-by-step procedure to accomplish the aforementioned challenges.

Security & infra and **Data oriented DCQs**: can be associated to reliability. In fact, distributed reliability consists in evaluating the ability of each component of the distributed system to **perform correctly with fault tolerance** and **not degrade the quality of the data**. The *security & infra oriented DQCs* focuses on the correct performance and fault tolerance part of the challenge. They ensure hardware and software of the overall ecosystem are aligned to perform successfully under specified conditions and over specified periods of time. The maintenance of these criteria is paramount because they prevent breakdowns, failures and hardware-based or human errors. On the other side *data oriented DQC* focuses on the quality of the content and structure of the data. In fact, as data is part of the information system it must be valuable and quality data, otherwise the overall system must not be considered as reliable. The content must be accurate and believable to generate valuable and safe results, when the structure must be built to facilitate the usage and reuse. Data oriented DCQs must be carefully guaranteed to justify the investment in system performance and keep the reliability of distributed system. These criteria need more attention during the data generation and collection.

purpose and process oriented DCQs: can be considered as properties of trust. As mentioned above, trust characterizing a relationship among two or multiple entities with a **common purpose** [MFGL12]. *Purpose oriented DQCs* evaluate the commitment of data governance to pro-

ducing high quality data outputs. Also, they guarantee the interests of all entities managing data are not conflicting and whether they are aligned with regulations. They ensure the purpose of the data processing is valuable and aligned with data life cycle, and data reuse is *compliant*. They help to align data quality criteria with the evolving regulatory landscape. They help to determine the appropriate requirements according to the type of data and its use. They can be associated as indicator of compliance in collaborative data processing. Furthermore, *process oriented DQCs* assess the trustworthiness of all stakeholders in data management by tracking their actions and decisions on data. These criteria inform about who manage data, where, how, and when? They ensure transparency of data generation and lifecycle so that people will be able to trust the data governance. Finally, security & infra and data oriented will enforce reliability which is a sub-criterion of trust. When, purpose and process oriented DQCs will increase the trust in collaborative data processing by bringing respectively compliance and transparency.

This overall analysis generated more meaningful information. It provided standardized definitions and names based on theoretical and industrial contribution which take compliance and legal boundaries into account. Furthermore, it gives the connection between all the criteria to understand how they support and impact each of them.

3.2.7.2 A blockchain based solution for data quality criteria traceability

We implemented a solution to using blockchain and smart contracts to track datasets and DQC information. This platform aims to guarantee transparency, reliability and trust in data management. As centralized solutions lack of transparency, we aim to implement a storage platform using blockchain. In fact, centralized platforms such as unb.ca/cic/datasets and data.gouv.fr propose datasets and give details about their data generation without providing proof and traceability. For example unb.ca/cic/datasets, provides IoT, Dark web, operational technology and DNS datasets. Each dataset on the platform is described by a document called data paper which detailed the data lifecycle. The platform also gives the possibility to download the dataset. However, data users are not able to verify the data lifecycle and have clear information regarding DQC. To best of our knowledge, they can see information concerning the origin of the data but we are not able verify directly that origin, more, they can not reproduce these datasets. They have to trust the platform without real information. The trust relationship between data users and providers is completely focused on central party: the platform. At the opposite, blockchain gives high traceability and can not perform without transparency and awareness of all members in the consortium. It allows all members in the consensus to participate to the verification of new transactions. All action is transparent in the blockchain. To increase trust in data processing, we propose to use smart contracts to describe the protocol that manages information within the blockchain. A smart contract is a computer program that describes a transaction protocol to automatically execute, control or document events and actions according to the terms of a actions specified by the contract. A smart contract is a transparent secured stored procedure, as its execution and codified effects cannot be manipulated without modifying the blockchain itself. Therefore, smart contract limit trust assumptions.

In our solution, any dataset creator can execute our smart contract to register his dataset as well as the metadata used to evaluate DQC. When this dataset depends on another dataset

(e.g. the produced dataset reuse data from another dataset), this relation of dependency can be specified too. As a consequence, the final user of any registered dataset can evaluate its quality by assessing the metadata of the dataset and the original datasets just by querying the blockchain transactions. Therefore, anybody can retrace the generation and reuse process of any datasets. This information is trustworthy because information inside the blockchain cannot be modified, and smart contracts available and executed by the nodes of the blockchain using a consensus algorithm.

3.2.8 Conclusions and future work

This document describes our analysis of distributed reliability, blockchain-like technologies and trust in data processing. Starting from defining main component of data processing, we presented the way collaborative data processing in Europe raises challenges of trust, reliability and legal compliance. Knowing data quality is a central parameters to evaluate these needs we used a systematic literature review and interviews with data experts to identify the relevant data quality criteria before classifying them by trust and reliability. Moreover, we propose a blockchain-based solution to implement some criteria and demonstrate how this solution can maintain data quality and ensure reliability and trust in decentralized data management. However, this solution is not taking the exhaustive list of data quality criteria. A future direction of the work will concern an automated data quality assessment that describes the use of algorithms, rules, or models to assess trust and reliability without the need for direct human intervention.

Nb	DQ criteria names	Other names	Definitions or significations of criteria
1	Accessibility	Availability, access	The ability, ease or difficulty with which data is available, easily and quickly retrievable [PLW02, KSW02, CZ15]
2	Accuracy	Data accuracy, precision, correctness	The data are accurate when their values in the database match up to real world values. Again, accuracy refers to the closeness between a data value to a known reference value of one object [CZ15]. Furthermore, it is the degree to which data are correct, reliable, certified, free of error, believable, and valid [BCFM09, ZKS+13, CR19]
3	Appropriate amount of data	Appropriate amount of information, amount of data, amount of information, data resolution	It verifies if the data volume and amount are sufficient and appropriate for the task (neither too much nor too little) [KSW02, SAZS17, HSJB12]
4	Auditability	Verifiability	Auditability means that data quality (accuracy, integrity...) shall be properly assessed by auditors in a sufficient time period, with low numbers of staff, during the different phases [CZ15]
5	Authorization		Authorization is the degree to which an individual or organization has the right to use the data [CZ15]
6	Believability	Credibility	The degree to which data is regarded as true, credible, trustworthy specially as within range of known possibility or probability [PLW02, ML09, TDC05]
7	Communication		It requires that data must reach the right person at the right time in a clear and understandable way [KZF18]
8	Completeness	data coverage, information completeness	The quality of an information system or database to represent all valid and meaningful values describing a real world system [WW96]. It is also the level to which data are of sufficient breadth, depth and scope for a given task [PLW02]. Moreover, completeness means the level to which data units are present in between collected data. Percentage of the real-world information entered in the sources and/or the data warehouse [MMB12]. It also shows whether or not data have all required parts to answer some questions and or cover specific needs [Fan15]. Completeness deals with the ratio between the number of non-null values in a source and the size of the universal relation. All values that are supposed to be collected as per a collection theory. It can be evaluated at database, dataset, data record, and data rows levels.
9	Concise representation	Concise, format, representational conciseness, conciseness	The measure of the level to which data is compactly represented without being overwhelming (i.e. brief in presentation, yet complete and comprehensible) [PLW02, WW96]. It indicates whether data is without superfluous detail, well formatted and well presented to data users [CRRO20, ML09, SSPA+12].

10	Consistency	Conciseness, consistency and synchronization, data consistency	Consistency indicates the degree to which all elements in the data set follow the same semantic rules including format, structure, range of values, data type, intervals and representation [BCFM09, TDC05, SEKTN16]. This property avoids any contradictions and violations of constraints within the data set [UKN ⁺ 99]. Moreover, consistency infers that data objects of the same real-world entity cannot have different values when they are collected in identical conditions [WW96, ST11]
11	Consistent representation	Representational consistency, presentation	The degree to which data is presented and structured in the same format [PLW02, ZKS ⁺ 13]. Then, it refers to the ability to be marked by harmony, regularity and free of change, deviation or contradiction [ML09]
12	Currency, timeliness and volatility	Currentness, freshness, timeliness and availability, data currency, temporal reliability, up to date, temporal relevance, chronology of data and goal	Currency: The degree to which the data are sufficiently up to date to perform a task [PLW02]. Timeliness: It is the degree to which age of the data is relevant for the task at hand [SSPA ⁺ 12]. More, it specifies the delay between a change of the real-world state and the correspondent modification of the state in databases. Again, it is the length of time before data was recorded [WW96]. Volatility: it refers to the period for which information is valid in the real world [BCFM09, SSPA ⁺ 12]
13	Data integration	Interlinking, navigation	Data is often spread out across multiple data sources. Data integration evaluates whether relevant data sources are identified and linked between them. Furthermore, it assesses if the relevant data are collected when integrating them [KZF18, ZKS ⁺ 13, SSPA ⁺ 12]
14	Duplication	Data deduplication, uniqueness	The ability to be free of duplication and redundancy when collecting or integrating data [SSPA ⁺ 12, SAZ ⁺ 19, Fan15]
15	Ease of manipulation	Useability, ease of operation, flexibility, reuse	It indicates the abilities of data to be easily manipulated, customized and able to be assigned to multiple purposes [TDC05, HSJB12].
16	Free of error		The degree to which the data is correct and reliable [PLW02, KSW02, SSPA ⁺ 12]
17	Generalizability		Generalizability includes statistical and scientific generalizability. Statistical generalizability refers to inferring from a sample to a target population. Scientific generalizability means applying a model based on a singular target population to other populations [KZF18]
18	Integrity	Data integrity fundamentals	Integrity also deals with the fact to maintain and ensure the correctness and consistency of data over their entire life cycle. It indicates that any data characteristics, including those relating to business rules, relations, dates, content, format, definitions, must be correct and unchanged [SSPA ⁺ 12, TDC05].
19	Interpretability	Readability, definition, documentation	This criterion refers to the degree to which data is in relevant languages, symbols, units, ranges of valid values, business rules [CZ15] and the definitions are clear [WW96, HSJB12, SSPA ⁺ 12]. It ensures that data should be interpretable, with clear and appropriate representation so that data users can understand this data [SAZ ⁺ 19, TDC05]

20	Objectivity	Objective, unbiased	Objectivity checks if data is based on objective, based on facts, unbiased, unprejudiced, impartial and was objectively collected [TDC05, KSW02]. Moreover, it means that data collection is not influenced by personal feelings or opinions, collected without using subjective judgements which introducing to bias [SAZS17]
21	Relevancy	Fitness, effectiveness, useful, efficiency, transactibility, convenience, appropriateness, relevance, operationalization	This criterion evaluates if data outputs will lead to the desired business expectation and whether concrete actions derived from these outputs [SSPA+12, KZF18]. Relevancy also indicates whether data is applicable and useful for one or many contexts [KSW02, SSPA+12]. Furthermore, it assesses if data is provided in accordance with specific purpose and deals with customer's needs [ML09, TDC05].
22	Reliability		This criterion indicates the degree to which data is correct, free of error and provided by a trustworthy source [SSPA+12]. A reliable data has the ability to conform with customer needs by answering questions and problems for which it is generated or collected, [WW96, ST11]
23	Reputation		This criterion measures if data sources and content are trustworthy [PLW02, KSW02, SSPA+12]
24	Safety		Data have acceptable risks of damage to persons, processes, assets or the environment [SSPA+12]
25	Security		The level to which data access is restricted in a manner that ensures their security [HSJB12]. Thus, security criterion challenge the existence of adopted measures to protect against espionage, sabotage, crime, attack, escape, people and natural disasters [ML09, TDC05]. It assesses also the compliance with confidentiality and privacy requirements [GEkN19, AA17]
26	Structure		It consists in identifying the best type of data for a given objective [KZF18]. Then, data structure is the level of difficulty when transforming semi structured or unstructured data into structured data through technology [CZ15]
27	Traceability		Traceability assesses the existence of history and documentation serving to record and trace all actions on data like collection and modification [VCT+16, GEkN19, HSJB12]
28	Understandability	Metadata, learnability, data specification, ease of understanding, meaningfulness, usefulness	Firstly, it shows if data is clear, readable, unambiguous and easily comprehensible for human and machines. Secondly, understandability displays the level to which metadata describe all aspects of datasets to avoid misunderstandings and inconsistencies [CZ15, VCT+16]
29	Validity	Compliance	Validity measures the extent to which data items comply with their respective standards and value domains [VCT+16, TDC05]. [ES07] said that "a data item is invalid in all these following conditions: if it is defined to be integer but contains a non-integer value, or defined as an element of a finite set of possible values but contains a value not included in this set, or contains a NULL value whgre a NULL is not accepted"

30	Value added		The extent to which data are beneficial then have an operational or organisational advantage for its use [PLW02, ML09]
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Figure 3.5: 30 agreed-upon data quality criteria with their respective names and definitions

Figure 3.6: Classification of DQCs by trust and reliability

3.3 Data governance in distributed IoT systems and edge computing

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3.3.1 Executive summary

Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized various fields by enabling the processing of large amounts of data from an increasing number of IoT devices. This research proposes a new approach to protect against risks related to personal data exploitation, drawing a methodology for the implementation of decentralized data governance in distributed IoT systems and edge computing. In addition, it establishes AI-driven processes to increase the user's ability to define and control their offerings in edge computing environments and data management with respect to protecting their privacy. This study contributes to the fields of data science, law and policymaking by providing critical information on the interactions between regulatory frameworks and ethical guidelines and their implications for the development of innovative AI-enabled systems while maintaining robust data protection standards. Key findings demonstrate that successful data governance implementation requires robust privacy-by-design and by-default approaches, standardized data integration and sharing protocols, and usage control mechanisms. The research emphasizes privacy and security as foundational requirements, while highlighting the need for federated machine learning and blockchain-based tracking mechanisms. Future development priorities include practical implementation in specific domains like electric vehicles and smart cities in order to provide a concrete example of applicability and demonstrate its potential for market adoption.

3.3.2 Introduction

3.3.2.1 Background

Recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the ubiquity of the Internet of Things (IoT) have increased the collection of data and the complexity of digital infrastructures to an enormous scale. Data are gathered in various, extremely diverse (mobile apps, social media, sensors, devices, etc.) and continuous ways, contributing to a large and unique data fingerprint for every product and service in use. Despite its potential to transform the global economy, IoT systems currently face challenges in processing large amount of data due to limited compute capacity, storage, and connectivity. Additionally, cloud services are limited by latency and lack of local processing capabilities, hindering the effective analysis of data [Voz+23]. Traditionally, cloud systems have been the norm. However, this process results in high communication overhead, latency, and energy consumption [Cai+20]. With the exponential growth of IoT devices, the compute capacity of the cloud is also becoming limited. For latency-sensitive applications such as autonomous driving this means that the cloud is unable to deliver quick responses due to its distance from the data source [Khe+18]. IoT data has unique characteristics such as large-scale streaming data, heterogeneity, time and location, making it distinct from traditional Big Data [Moh+18]. To effectively support the high-speed data streams and time-sensitive require-

ments of IoT, new approaches, technologies, and algorithms are needed. Edge computing systems have gained popularity in recent years due to their ability to process and analyze data more efficiently and effectively than cloud-centric systems [Shi+16]. Edge computing has the advantage of reducing latency by processing data closer to the source, making it ideal for applications that require real-time processing such as autonomous vehicles and smart cities. This is because the miniaturization of IoT devices and their increasing compute capacity have made them capable of performing computation inside them or near the source, driving the need for edge computing. Edge computing also improves security by reducing the amount of data that needs to be transferred over the network. By storing and processing data locally on edge devices instead of a centralized location, edge computing reduces the amount of data that needs to be transferred, thus making the system more secure. Additionally, edge-enhanced analytics allows for pre-processing data at the edge, reducing communication overhead and latency, thereby improving application response times and Quality of Service (QoS) [KSG23]. However, several challenges arise when performing analytics on IoT devices through edge computing. AI-based applications require a considerable amount of computation, making it challenging to deploy them directly on these devices for analytics. Many IoT devices still face limitations in terms of storage and computational capacity. Additionally, over-compression of the network can result in a decrease in performance, and limited resources can lead to high communication latency. The uptake of Federated Learning (FL) provides a solution to these challenges by allowing multiple edge devices to execute lightweight algorithms and process data locally, thus reducing the amount of raw data transmitted across the network and making the most of the limited but increasingly powerful computational resources at the edge. Moreover, the synergy of FL and blockchain gives stakeholders unparalleled control over data in addition to security [al.24]. It creates an environment of trust and accountability among players by protecting intellectual property rights and promoting openness. Additionally, it promotes interoperability and seamless data exchange, thereby reducing fragmentation and improving collaboration.

3.3.2.2 Objectives and Scope

The aim of this research is to investigate the combination of blockchain and federated learning (FL) to improve the processing capacity of IoT devices for data analytics, without affecting the privacy of the users. The vision is for decentralized data governance deployments, achieving benefits such as reliability and trust, low latency analytics, and reduced computational resources. To achieve the overall goal, the following research questions (RQ) were addressed in the research:

1. **RQ1:** What are the privacy challenges and risks associated with data processing and management in distributed IoT systems and edge computing?
 - (a) How the methodology of analysis of such risks shall be refined?
 - (b) What tools, technologies and methods are being currently used for privacy preservation?
2. **RQ2:** How can AI-driven processes be used to increase the user's ability to define and control her/his privacy in more accurate way throughout the entire data lifecycle?

- (a) What (legal and technological) approaches and measures are optimal for data management and analytics in edge computing?
 - (b) What factors could increase user's ability to define their offerings in edge computing and data management and analytics needs?
3. **RQ3:** What are the prerequisites for a renewed approach to data governance in distributed IoT systems and edge computing?
- (a) What are the regulatory and ethical guidelines and principles that support the development of such architecture in IoT and edge computing?
 - (b) What are the evaluation criteria and success factors for validating it?

3.3.2.3 State of the Art

With the advent of edge computing and the Internet of Things, today organizations are confronted with the need to handle vast and diverse amount of data to gain valuable insights and knowledge. By engaging in data processing, organisations can effectively comprehend customers' needs and accomplish their business goals. This capability enables them to maintain their competitiveness, swiftly adapting to evolving circumstances, and capitalising on emerging opportunities. However, unlocking the full potential of IoT requires collaboration of different entities, which is essential to overcome the significant fragmentation of data. Integrating data governance with FL and blockchain technology has been an increasing interest and research area. Numerous studies have examined the technologies individually and in conjunction to address the pressing challenges of privacy. The next paragraphs provide an overview and thorough analysis of each of them, emphasizing their key advances and potential limitations

3.3.2.3.1 Data governance Data governance plays an important role in data processing, by establishing a system of policies, processes, and principles to maximize the value of data and its use. It refers to the system of decisions and accountabilities that regulate and guide information-related processes, ensuring adherence to pre-defined policies [al.20]. It outlines permissible activities, assign responsibilities to different entities and actors throughout the value chain, and determine the data to be used, when it can be used, by whom, and for what purposes [Nie17]. In distributed IoT systems, where multiple infrastructures and services are interconnected, data processing is performed by various entities, situated in different teams or organisations. In this context, we refer to decentralised data governance (DDG) that is defined as a set of policies, processes, and principles that govern the data related activities. The DDG represents a community-based approach for storing, managing, and sharing data, in contrast to a centralized one, where a single entity governs the decision-making throughout the data lifecycle [al.22]. The adoption of DDG is determined by the specific context, enabling organisations to establish a flexible data governance framework. An example of DDG can be found in the work of Gawusu et al., who proposed distributed data mining for sustainable energy development [GMD22]. Their solution utilises multiple systems for data collection and mining. By employing a multi-agent model, the model facilitates collaborative data processing and consolidates the outputs.

This approach reduces network traffic, enhance security, and addresses data privacy concerns [al.20]. Finally, DDG ensures compliance with legal, ethical, regulatory, and data protection requirements, specifically the constrains imposed on data processing activities. However, further research to address the challenges posed by decentralisation and distribution are necessary to guarantee that transparency and privacy are not compromised.

3.3.2.3.2 Federated learning The application of Federated Learning (FL) in distributed IoT systems has received significant attention in recent years, particularly in the areas of healthcare [Hak+20] [Bag+21] [Abd+22] and industrial IoT [Hsu+21]. This is driven by the need for data privacy, real-time response, and the geographically dispersed nature of assets. FL plays a pivotal role in building trust between the collaborating parties. Participants can verify at any time that no personal data is exposed, which is crucial for maintaining privacy [Foy+22]. In terms of resilience, FL enhances system robustness in many ways. For instance, it ensures efficient use of data even when network connectivity is poor [al.19]. Most of the computations happens locally, requiring only intermittent network access to transmit aggregated model updates. Additionally, FL builds resilience against device failures and data corruption. In the previous example, if one or more devices goes offline or has corrupted data, the FL process will continue with minimal disruption because it depends on many other IoT devices that continue to perform local computations. This redundancy makes FL models extremely reliable, ensuring their functionality in any adverse circumstances [al.24]. FL also promotes inclusivity in data processing. By enabling data to remain decentralized, FL allows many data sources as contributors to model training without compromising privacy. This can lead to more efficient and potentially more generalized models, since they can be trained on a wider variety of data that could not be possible in a centralized setting.

3.3.2.3.3 Blockchain Blockchain has recently emerged as a disruptive innovation with a wide range of applications, able to redesign interactions in business activities and society at large [Atz17]. It consists of a permanent, distributed, digital ledger, recording transactions across a peer-to-peer network [19]. Unlike other networks, a blockchain does not duplicate the value being transferred. Instead, it functions as a register, noting that a value has been successfully transferred from one entity to another. This technology introduces a ground-breaking innovation by enabling an open network where participants can interact without prior knowledge or trust in each other. Transactions are automatically verified and recorded by network nodes using cryptographic algorithms, eliminating the need for human intervention, central authority, or third-party intermediaries such as governments, financial institutions, or other organizations. Even in the presence of unreliable, dishonest, or malicious nodes, the network can accurately verify transactions and safeguard the integrity of the ledger. This is achieved through a mathematical mechanism known as proof-of-work, rendering human intervention or centralized control unnecessary. The underlying principle behind this protocol is decentralized trust or trust-by-computation. The blockchain serves as an immutable and transparent repository for storing records of documents, contracts, properties, and assets [ZH20]. It offers a versatile platform for embedding information and instructions, resulting in a wide array of applications. These include, for instance: a) smart contracts, namely automated and self-executing agree-

ments between two or more entities. By leveraging blockchain technology, smart contracts enable seamless execution of predefined actions, eliminating the reliance on intermediaries; b) multi-signature transactions, which require the consensus and approval of multiple entities before they can be executed. The blockchain facilitates this by providing a trustless framework that ensures the involvement and agreement of all relevant parties; and c) smart properties, namely digital ownership of tangible and intangible assets embedded to the blockchain, which can be owned, tracked or exchanged. This concept offers enhanced security, traceability, and efficiency by leveraging the blockchain's capabilities. When it comes to governance, the most significant innovation of blockchain is that it provides the ability to experiment with new organizational structures and distributed governance models, which are more transparent and less hierarchical than traditional ones. Indeed, blockchain allows the creation of so-called decentralized organizations, enabling entities and actors to coordinate themselves in a peer-to-peer manner, according to a set of protocols and rules incorporated into self-executing smart contract code [FMR20]. Nevertheless, a comprehensive assessment considering multiple factors is currently lacking to determine the viability of a blockchain-based governance model in meeting the necessary legal, security, ethical and technical requirements [21].

These technologies are reshaping data processing in different ways, offering new possibilities for enhanced efficiency, scalability, and connectivity. Simultaneously, they provide viable solutions that can be implemented in decentralised and distributed environments, ensuring greater reliability and trust.

3.3.3 Methodology

This study adopted an evolutionary approach (common in product development activities) by iterating a series of activities (as illustrated in Figure 3.7), aiming to successfully identifying the appropriate features that DDG needs to possess in order to achieve high technology acceptance and wider impact. The methodology involved a comprehensive and systematic analysis of relevant scholars in data processing and governance, including cutting edge technologies such as blockchain and FL, evaluating any remaining challenges and risks, and creating a standardized schema for enhanced understanding and automation. Domain specific studies were examined to evaluate the needs and requirements of different sectors, such as healthcare, smart cities, industry 4.0 and more. Interdisciplinary analysis was critical to integrate insights from regulatory frameworks and ethical guidelines.

The starting point was the Data Lifecycle Framework (DaLiF), as proposed by Shah et al [SPM21a], which was then enhanced and further developed using an iterative approach that ensures adherence to the principles outlined in the DMBok [HESC17]. It was followed by a comparative analysis and benchmarking of already existing reference architectures, such as IDSA, Gaia-X and BDVA, which integrate knowledge from distributed systems. The general criteria used in determining the suitability of one architecture over the other are: (i) efficiency, (ii) data privacy and security, (iii) scalability and adaptability, (iv) interoperability, and (iv) re-usability. This is a standpoint that suggests that when there are several architectural solutions considered, the most efficient, secure, scalable, interoperable, and reliable, in order of priority, will be chosen. The most efficient solution is the one that minimises: (i) the time needed to complete the ex-

Figure 3.7: DDG Evolutionary Process

pected tasks, (ii) the space needed to store data allowing its normal functioning, and (iii) the cost of communicating with other components to exchange requested data. When it was impossible to minimise all these three parameters at once due to conflict of conditions, the ‘best’ compromise has been selected. The criteria used to set the equilibrium entails giving the highest priority to the minimisation of the execution time requested to carry out the tasks, secondly to the minimisation of the communication overhead with other components, and finally to the minimisation of the amount of space required.

The proposed approach is flexible and adaptable to the needs of the different sectors and stakeholders, and aims at increasing the value of data and minimize data processing related costs and risks.

3.3.4 Research Findings

3.3.4.1 Decentralised Data Governance

This section presents the final iteration of the Decentralized Data Governance (DDG) model and describes the mechanisms for achieving and implementing the required provenance and reliability features while also respecting the privacy guidelines set by GDPR.

3.3.4.1.1 Reference architecture Figure 3.8 presents the high-level architecture of the Decentralised Data Governance (DDG) framework, which is an evolution of the architecture proposed in the first submission made to AIAI 2022 conference . It has been subsequently improved by integrating the Federated Learning as core component in the data processing layer. Moving outward, it stresses the importance of security, privacy and access control on one side, and ethical, legal and regulatory compliance on the other. These are combined with a blockchain-enabled transactions tracking mechanism, ensuring transparency throughout the system.

Figure 3.8: Decentralised Data Governance Framework

Figure 3: Overview of Privacy and Usage Control module

Figure 3.9: Overview of Privacy and Usage Control component

The proposed framework consists of three layers: the data layers, the analysis layer, and the user layer. The data layer is responsible for the preparation of the data to be consumed by the processing layer. This includes cleaning and normalisation so that data is of good quality, as well as an anonymization process before any data activities commences. It follows a decentralised storage approach where each resource remains autonomous. The analysis layer consists of the AI models and analytics pipelines that process the data derived from the data layer to deliver valuable insights that support informed decisions. Finally, the user layer allows to share the processed results and new AI models parameters with data consumers (citizens, researchers and organisations).

3.3.4.1.2 Components, modules and support services Privacy and Usage Control This component (see Figure 3.9) is designed to handle the reconciliation and enforcement of machine-processable policies, preferences, and conditions governing data usage. It facilitates a fine-grained description of requirements, enabling both data providers and data consumers to define and enforce data-sharing policies tailored to their specific needs. For instance, policies can specify constraints such as "use data only for a particular purpose" or impose restrictions on data retention or third-party access.

The model employs a structured and dynamic approach to ensure that these policies are both interpretable by machines and enforceable in real-time. To achieve this, it integrates a privacy module comprising a series of programmable filters or scripts that act as intermediaries between data resources and their consumers. These filters are configured to enforce agreed-upon conditions rigorously, ensuring compliance with the specified usage terms. This modular design not only improves flexibility but also simplifies updates to policy logic as requirements evolve. The privacy module operates as an active orchestrator, implementing key principles of privacy-by-design and by-default. For example, the filters can enforce policies such as:

1. **Purpose limitation:** Ensuring data is accessed only for explicitly agreed-upon purposes.

Figure 3.10: Overview of Federated Machine Learning component

2. **Data Minimization:** Limiting the scope of data shared to what is strictly necessary.
3. **Retention controls:** Automatically managing data expiration and deletion schedules.

Incorporating these mechanisms enhances trustworthiness and accountability in data-sharing activities. Furthermore, the architecture supports auditing capabilities, enabling stakeholders to verify compliance with established policies and legal standards, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the AI Act (AIA).

Federated Machine Learning This component (see Figure 3.10) is dedicated to the deployment of federated ML algorithms that provide strong and quantifiable privacy guarantees. By extending computation to the edge (where raw data resides), it ensures that sensitive data is never exposed or transferred to centralized servers. This approach aligns with the principles of privacy-by-design and enhances compliance with data protection regulations.

The component includes an ML orchestration framework that facilitates the collaborative development and training of highly accurate ML models on distributed local data stores. By enabling this decentralized learning paradigm, the system achieves several key benefits:

1. **Data privacy:** Local data remains securely stored on user devices or edge servers, minimizing the risk of breaches.
2. **Data Minimization:** Only model updates (e.g., parameters) are shared, significantly lowering bandwidth requirements.
3. **Retention controls:** Models can be tailored to local datasets, improving relevance and effectiveness while aggregating insights at a global level.

To ensure robust privacy guarantees, the component integrates advanced privacy-preserving techniques such as:

1. **Differential privacy:** Adding carefully calibrated noise to model updates, ensuring that individual data points cannot be inferred from aggregated outputs.
2. **Homomorphic Encryption:** Enabling computations on encrypted data, ensuring that neither raw data nor intermediate results are exposed during training.

Figure 3.11: Overview of Blockchain Transaction Tracking component

The orchestration system also includes model evaluation and validation tools, ensuring that the collaboratively trained models meet high accuracy and fairness standards while addressing potential biases in the distributed datasets. Adaptive aggregation algorithms, such as weighted averaging, are employed to reconcile diverse data distributions across edge devices, improving model robustness and scalability.

Blockchain-based Transaction Tracking This component (see Figure 3.11) leverages blockchain technology to log all data activities, including acquisition, sharing, access, and other interactions among the involved entities. By adopting a tamper-proof, decentralized ledger, the system ensures secure and immutable records of these activities, providing traceability, auditability, and non-repudiation. This transparency reinforces accountability while fostering trust among stakeholders in data-driven ecosystems.

Moreover, the blockchain-based logging mechanism operates across multiple layers - Data Level, Analysis Level, and User Level - creating a holistic view of all transactions. For instance, actions such as data submission, sharing, and access are securely recorded alongside metadata, including timestamps, user credentials, and purpose descriptions. These records are structured to adhere to confidentiality and data access permissions, ensuring that sensitive information remains protected even within a transparent framework.

Security, Privacy and Access Management This component ensures the secure and efficient execution of data processing across all system layers, from edge devices to cloud-based data centres, while minimising the movement of data from its origin. It builds upon smart contracts deployed on private blockchains, enabling a fine-grained access control mechanism for datasets and data streams with a minimal overhead in the number of data transactions processed. This is particularly advantageous for environments with high transaction volumes, where scalability and efficiency are critical. To ensure secure data processing, data is temporarily brought into a secure execution environment through a distributed proxy mechanism. These execution environments – such as Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) or confidential computing frameworks – isolate data and computation from unauthorized access, ensuring both data confiden-

tiality and integrity during processing. Once the data processing tasks are completed, the proxy revokes access, ensuring that data remains confined to the provider's secure repository and is not retained elsewhere. In addition, data provenance is maintained throughout the entire data lifecycle, documenting every stage of data management, from acquisition and manipulation to delivery. By leveraging blockchain's immutability and transparency, the provenance records are securely logged, enabling end-to-end traceability of data manipulations. These records support auditing, compliance verification, and dispute resolution, providing a robust mechanism for accountability and trust.

3.3.5 Research Analysis

Promoting privacy-by-default in DDG development is crucial for long-term success and widespread market adoption. To address evolving privacy challenges, the integration of advanced decentralized learning methodologies, such as federated learning, presents a robust approach. Federated learning enables collaborative model training across decentralized devices without sharing raw data, thereby minimizing privacy risks and ensuring compliance with data minimization principles. Combining FL with blockchain technologies enhances data integrity and security through transparent, immutable ledgers that manage data provenance and access control. Blockchain-based solutions can also facilitate decentralized identity management systems and smart contracts, providing automated governance and ensuring that data access aligns with user consent and regulatory mandates. Critically, these solutions must align with established legal and regulatory frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), AI Act (AIA), and Data Governance Act (DGA). Compliance with these standards not only ensures legal adherence but also builds public trust by addressing key concerns about accountability, transparency, and fairness in AI-enabled solutions. For instance, integrating explainability mechanisms and clear user consent protocols can further enhance transparency and trustworthiness.

3.3.5.1 Artificial Intelligence Integration

For good or worse, AI has become a key player in the digital economy, driving innovation and shaping industries. Its capability to automate many data processing activities and extract valuable insights from vast amounts of raw data offers unprecedented opportunities for informed decision-making. However, this power comes with significant risks, as AI systems can be leveraged to subtly influence or manipulate user decisions. These risks are exacerbated by the presence of bias in AI models, particularly when users lack transparency regarding the underlying data sources and training methodologies. Such biases can perpetuate inequalities, distort perceptions, and unfairly sway public opinion. Addressing these challenges requires the integration of privacy-preserving and trust-enabling technologies. For instance, blockchain technology provides a decentralized, tamper-proof mechanism for recording data provenance, ensuring transparency in the data sources and algorithms used in AI systems. This enables users to verify the origin and integrity of the data, fostering greater accountability. Federated learning on the other side, enhances both privacy and fairness by enabling AI models to be trained collaboratively across decentralized datasets. This method ensures that sensitive data remains on local

devices, reducing the risk of data breaches and centralization-related biases. By maintaining data privacy while aggregating insights, federated learning can help mitigate the risks of overfitting and promote equitable model performance across diverse user groups. When combined, blockchain and federated learning offer a powerful synergy to ensure transparency, fairness, and reliability in AI outputs. These technologies empower users with greater control over their data and enable stakeholders to audit and verify the fairness of AI systems.

3.3.5.2 Data Usage Policy Enforcement

By enforcing data usage restrictions, the DDG model can ensure the privacy and confidentiality of all involved entities, including users and organisation. Such safeguards are essential for building trust and fostering a sustainable digital ecosystem. However, to maximize the model's acceptability and usability, additional measures must be taken to engage and inform data consumers effectively. First, communication about data usage policies must be tailored to the target audience. The language used should balance accessibility with precision, ensuring clarity without oversimplifying critical details. It is essential to align the terminology with the norms and standards of the relevant industry and technology, fostering familiarity and reducing misunderstandings. To enhance comprehension, the inclusion of real-world examples is recommended. These examples can illustrate complex concepts, showcasing their applicability in practical scenarios. Additionally, clear articulation of the expected benefits of the technology, along with specification of any potential risks, is crucial. For AI systems and applications, adhering to the risk-based approach outlined in the AI Act is imperative. This framework involves categorizing AI applications based on their risk levels and tailoring transparency and mitigation measures accordingly. For individuals with lower literacy levels or less familiarity with technical jargon, innovative approaches should be employed. These may include interactive tutorials, multimedia explanations, or knowledge assessments to ensure users have genuinely read and understood the policies rather than agreeing blindly. These assessments could take the form of brief, scenario-based questions that confirm comprehension while fostering informed consent. Finally, such efforts not only ensure compliance with ethical AI principles and legal requirements but also contribute to building user confidence and promoting widespread adoption. A thoughtful and inclusive approach to communication ensures that policies are not just regulatory obligations but tools for empowering users to make informed decisions in a privacy-centric digital ecosystem.

3.3.5.3 Regulatory and Ethical Framework

The DDG is designed following the principles and guidelines established by key regulatory and ethical standards, including the GDPR, the DGA, and the AIA. Additionally, it adheres to the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, as developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (HLEG). These frameworks collectively emphasize the importance of transparency, accountability, fairness, and respect for fundamental rights in data processing and AI-driven activities. In line with the GDPR and other legal mandates, the model emphasizes safeguarding individual rights, including the rights to data access, correction, erasure, and portability. To achieve this, DDG imple-

ments mechanisms for meaningful user redress for individuals adversely impacted by AI technologies. These mechanisms include proactive measures such as risk assessment frameworks, real-time impact monitoring, and the provision of clear, accessible channels for users to challenge decisions or seek remedies. By integrating the ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI, the platform seeks to balance innovation with societal values. This entails respecting principles such as human-centricity, robustness, and sustainability, while ensuring compliance with evolving legal standards. Additionally, DDG incorporates tools to evaluate the societal and ethical impact of its AI systems, ensuring they align with the broader goals of fairness and inclusivity in digital services. Through this comprehensive approach, DDG not only strengthens its commitment to regulatory compliance but also fosters a privacy-centric and trustworthy digital ecosystem, contributing to long-term user confidence and societal trust in AI-enabled technologies.

3.3.6 Conclusions

The decentralised data governance represents a critical step towards responsible and ethical utilization of data in an increasingly interconnected digital landscape. The proposed approach builds upon an extensive review of existing reference architectures, design styles, and patterns, coupled with insights drawn from lessons learned and best practices from past and ongoing initiatives. This synthesis of knowledge, informed by widely accepted models, has shaped a refined framework designed to address the multifaceted challenges of modern data governance. Central to the proposed framework is the emphasis on clear principles and policies supported by state-of-the-art privacy-preserving technologies. Techniques such as blockchain and federated learning play a pivotal role in safeguarding data integrity, enabling secure and transparent data usage while minimizing privacy risks. Blockchain ensures tamper-proof data records and facilitates traceable and accountable data transactions, whereas federated learning enables collaborative AI model training on decentralized datasets without exposing sensitive raw data. Together, these technologies empower individuals and organizations with granular control over how personal and organizational data is accessed, processed, and shared. The approach is deeply grounded in compliance with key legal and normative frameworks. For instance, adherence to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) ensures that data governance practices respect fundamental rights such as data privacy and user consent. Similarly, alignment with the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) enforces a risk-based approach to AI systems, promoting accountability, transparency, and fairness throughout the data lifecycle. These legal foundations are further bolstered by principles outlined in the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, fostering the development of systems that are not only legally compliant but also ethically sound. By putting control over data back into the hands of users, the proposed decentralized governance model offers a pathway to balancing innovation with privacy, security, and societal trust. This alignment of technological advancements with robust legal and ethical considerations ensures that data processing is conducted in a manner that respects individual autonomy, organizational accountability, and societal values. Such an approach is indispensable for creating a sustainable, inclusive, and trustworthy digital ecosystem.

3.3.7 Future work

Looking ahead, the prospects that data governance can truly revolutionize the data economy is great. By facilitating secure and transparent data processing, decentralised data governance can drive innovations in different sectors, including healthcare, smart city and mobility, smart manufacturing, and finance. Its potential is huge, although some challenges still remain – respecting the ever-delicate balance between transparency and privacy and making sure that data processing does not jeopardise individual rights. The framework must continuously evolve in view of such problems, adapting to new types and sources of data, emerging technologies, or regulatory changes. By raising awareness of data value and governance principles, the benefits of the data governance can be realized while safeguarding privacy and data protection. This decentralised approach will help build trust and support for data-driven innovations, ultimately fostering a more responsible and secure data ecosystem.

3.4 User empowerment in health through Personal Health Information Management Systems

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3.4.1 Executive summary

This research examines Personal Health Information Management Systems (PHIMS) as transformative tools in healthcare data management, addressing three critical challenges: individual data control, insight generation, and privacy preservation. Through comprehensive analysis spanning healthcare, ethics, law, and data science, the study establishes PHIMS as essential infrastructure for modern healthcare delivery.

The investigation reveals significant potential in two key technological domains: risk stratification for predictive healthcare and Large Language Models (LLMs) for data processing and diagnostic support. The study identifies and addresses fundamental challenges including data quality issues (missing data, selection bias, non-stationarity), LLM limitations (explainability, bias, privacy), and regulatory compliance requirements (GDPR, AI Act, MDR).

Key findings demonstrate that successful PHIMS implementation requires: robust privacy-by-design approaches, standardized data integration protocols, and patient-centric interface development. The research emphasizes interoperability and security as foundational requirements, while highlighting the necessity of inclusive design to prevent demographic marginalization.

Future development priorities include: technical specification refinement for recommendation systems, practical implementation frameworks for individualized health management, and strategies for achieving population-level impact through enhanced data management and patient engagement. This work provides a comprehensive framework for advancing personal health information management while maintaining essential balance between technological innovation and ethical considerations.

3.4.2 Introduction

3.4.2.1 Background

The exponential growth in personal health data collection has created an urgent need for effective management systems that empower individuals while ensuring data security and privacy. Personal Health Information Management Systems (PHIMS) emerge as a critical solution to address the challenges of data control, accessibility, and insight generation in healthcare settings.

3.4.3 Background

This research addresses the methodologies and limitations of Personal Health Information Management Systems (PHIMS) within the comprehensive framework of the LeADS project. PHIMS

are proposed as a solution to three critical challenges in modern healthcare: enabling individuals to control their personal data accessibility, generating accurate and explainable insights, and maintaining privacy and security standards. These issues branch through multiple domains: healthcare, ethics, law, and data analysis, creating a need for a holistic approach, an approach that was shaped by the LeADS project and its training.

LeADS, an interdisciplinary project bridging law, technology, data, and humanities, has provided the foundational framework of this research. By bringing together domain experts, the project enables deeper consideration of research implications and integration into the broader interdisciplinary context of modern healthcare. The healthcare domain presents unique challenges in data management due to its highly sensitive nature. As data science rapidly evolves, three critical issues emerge:

1. **Explainability Challenge:** Modern models, while increasingly efficient, often function as "black boxes," making it difficult for patients to understand how recommendations are generated.
2. **Secondary Data Use:** While health data is essential for scientific advancement, maintaining transparency in data processing is crucial for maintaining trust in healthcare systems.
3. **Access Equality:** Varying levels of technological literacy and access create potential disparities in healthcare delivery.

The above-mentioned issues were brought forth through the project of LeADS and became a key part of this ESR's research in the context of PHIMS. This report addresses the impact of the ESR's research in the broader spectrum of LeADS, aiming to link the research performed to its broader implications in the fields of privacy and policy.

3.4.4 State of the Art

3.4.4.1 Personal Information Management Systems and their potential in healthcare

Personal data protection is considered a fundamental right according to the EU Charter Article 8, hence the GDPR aims to improve individual data control, rendering PIMS (Personal Information Management Systems) a useful tool in the implementation of individualized data management. PIMS consist of products and services allowing for individual control over personal data, empowering individuals in the process of data collection and management. Mediating, monitoring, and controlling data access, usage, and sharing are the key aims of PIMS and essential in the empowering of individuals in a data-centric online space, functioning as a privacy self-management tool [JCS20].

PIMS are generally accessed through platforms where the user accesses the PIMS infrastructure and is provided with certain tools to handle their personal data [JCS20]. Third parties request user data, and PIMS regulate the data flow through technical, legal, and organizational [JS22] means while ensuring users are in control of the process and third parties meet both user and

platform requirements. According to Janssen & Singh 2022, measures ensuring PIMS functionality enforce transparency in what data is collected, stored, processed, what analysis this data is undergoing, as well as oversight of the entire process.

Decentralized data processing refers to when third parties seeking information are not granted direct access to user data, only returning the results of any analysis or computation requested by the third party [JCS20]. Decentralized data processing minimizes the amount of data exposed to third parties and can greatly enhance PIMS technologies. PIMS may be supported by Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), which ensure immutability, traceability, and verifiability of personal data processing [ZFD20].

PIMS are characterized by access control as well as an access trail enabling individuals to track and be aware of who has accessed their information and online/digital behavior [Att+20]. In terms of data protection, PIMS offer a multitude of advantages to the individual, allowing for data protection by design/default, consent management, transparency and traceability, the “right to be forgotten,” data portability and interoperability, and data security [Att+20].

In the domain of healthcare, Personal Health Information Management Systems (PHIMS) offer a valuable potential tool towards empowerment of individuals in the management of their sensitive personal data. Personal health information management utilizing PIMS technologies can be a valuable asset in individuals actively participating in their own healthcare and managing their own personal health data [Pra+06].

A PHIMS consisting of a web-based patient-centered personal health record (PHR) was developed in order to allow both clinician access to complete patient health information and individuals to have a comprehensive singular platform for their information that would otherwise be distributed over multiple providers [Kim+04]. The platform met with satisfaction from both patients and clinicians; a preliminary study displayed satisfaction in 85% of respondents regarding usability of the platform over 32 patients. Patients, physicians, and patient care coordinators found both information access and messaging convenient and comprehensive, highlighting the usefulness and potential of PHIMS as a system for individual empowerment in healthcare.

PHIMS can be a powerful tool in the management of data from IoT devices (Internet of Things), which become of increasing relevance in medicine. IoT devices present a means for data collection that is personalized, clinically actionable, and can provide longitudinal data [Ten+08]. Sensors collecting bio-signals and analyzing biomarkers in real time consist of a more individual-centric rather than hospital-centric model of healthcare, which is much more in line with the shift of medicine towards a more personalized approach to patient care [Paw+22]. IoT devices are closely linked to the modern medical home, which aims to become patient-centric. Unified electronic health records and IoT devices through a PIMS framework could aid in multiple domains of healthcare such as but not limited to: telehealth, quality and efficiency evaluation, care transition, PHRs, registries, team care, and clinical decision-making, particularly for chronic diseases [BB10].

Blockchain technologies are a potent tool of great use in the PHIMS domain. Blockchain offers decentralized data entry and has been proposed to be of use in the health sector, being currently in early stages of use in Electronic Health Records (EHRs), PHR, and Clinical trials [Has+20]. Blockchain-based PHIMS, which aim to manage information from IoT devices and medical ap-

plications, could aid in the personalization, security, and privacy of PHIMS technologies, despite limitations in interoperability [Paw+22].

As PHIMS is a relatively novel area of research and standardized model design is currently absent, investigation is required to determine individual needs that need to be fulfilled. A study investigating potential consumer demands from PHIMS using nominal group technique and participatory design identified certain key areas of interest in this domain [Civ+06].

Primarily, PHIMS main goals according to consumers were determined to be the monitoring and assessing of health, health-related decision making, and planning and performing health-related actions. Surveyed individuals found value in the potential of PIMS in eliminating the need for introspective reconstruction of personal health history using memory which may omit critical details, hence providing a more accurate record of disease or biomarkers. PHIMS were recognized to hold potential value in the decision making and planning of treatment, by allowing individuals to participate in their own healthcare through having concentrated and comprehensible information. Furthermore, PHIMS can provide actionable suggestions, through using existing information to generate medical recommendations such as suggesting checkups, supplements, or reminders to improve compliance to treatment. Finally, PHIMS can offer secure information sharing and information integration across different platforms [Civ+06]. Taking into consideration the utility recognized in PIMS by consumers—the individuals that the frameworks aim to empower—it is suggested that PIMS will become increasingly relevant in future research and aid in facing multiple challenges in both the domain of healthcare and personal data control.

Another requirement for PHIMS to be a tool for empowerment is equality in terms of access to the services they provide. As medicine shifts towards the treatment of chronic disease and is required to adapt to an aging society, these novel technologies should be accessible as well as comprehensible to individuals of all ages in order to avoid discrimination and marginalization of older adults. Utilizing the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) framework, a review of 22 studies, assessing multiple factors such as age, socioeconomic background, and health needs, which all appear to influence their capacity to use and understand PHIMS [Tri+18]. It is therefore clear that research in the domain should take into account the socio-organizational environment and age and seek a personalized approach to ensure access and understanding of what the technologies offer. Acknowledging individual differences in design of PHIMS to augment their level of accessibility to the public as well as inclusivity renders them a tool for fair and uniform empowerment.

3.4.5 1.3 Objective and scope

The research is addressed to a dual objective: examining technical specifications for recommendation generation and data analysis in personal health, while also investigating implementation challenges from legal, ethical, and technical perspectives. This scope encompasses:

- Analysis of data management challenges in medical contexts
- Evaluation of PHIMS implementation requirements
- Assessment of patient empowerment through data control

- Investigation of regulatory compliance frameworks

The increasing prevalence of medical IoT devices, personal health apps, and electronic health records underscores the urgency of efficient PHIMS implementation. This research aims to provide a comprehensive framework for addressing both technical and practical challenges in PHIMS development and deployment.

3.4.6 Methodology

3.4.6.1 1. Comprehensive Literature Review

A systematic literature review was conducted for each research section to establish a comprehensive understanding of the landscape. Epidemiological studies were examined to evaluate the predictive algorithms underlying potential PHIMS applications. Post-review, interdisciplinary analyses integrated insights from healthcare informatics, regulatory frameworks, and predictive algorithms for health risks. These studies informed the assessment of data analysis methodologies, addressing limitations and exploring how these methodologies could be applied or misapplied in the PHIMS context.

3.4.6.2 2. Technical Evaluation

Dry lab experiments were conducted to assess the diagnostic capabilities of the large language model (LLM) Chat GPT. The methodology is listed in Section 3.2.3.

3.4.6.3 3. Legal and Social Impact Appraisal

The findings from the technical evaluation were integrated with legal and ethical considerations, using the LeADS framework to assess implementation challenges. Ethical and legal implications of the methodologies were critically evaluated, addressing potential risks and offering actionable, policy-relevant recommendations. This analysis emphasized user empowerment by exploring how PHIMS technologies can be ethically designed and regulated to promote autonomy and trust among users.

3.4.7 Research Findings

3.4.8 Risk Stratification

Utilizing real-world data to stratify patients based on higher or lower risk of disease is likely to play a great role in the future of personalized/precision medicine, especially in the age of EHR, where large data is driving medical knowledge. Risk stratification is the process of evaluating and assigning risk status for a disease to patients, hence considering them both as individuals and part of a larger community (stratum).

Stratifying patients by risk can enable more efficient management of care through prognosis of disease and guide early intervention [Red+17]. The aim of such approaches is to improve patient outcomes while reducing treatment cost, hence constantly optimizing healthcare provision [MH21]. A critical example of how risk stratification can be practically utilized is analysis of hospital readmission risk; readmission is a risk for patients, exposed to infections, adverse events, and a psychological burden and health economy. Risk stratification can then be used to evaluate both discharging patterns, as well as targeted actions for specific hospitals to optimize treatment [Gla+20]. Artificial intelligence and predictive analytics can evaluate outcomes and be informative in the identification of the relevant intervention, while also aid in determining outcome metrics and prognostic biomarkers [MH21]. Finally, risk stratification at population level can be used to guide medical research and further hypothesis testing in order to establish causal links and further comprehend disease pathology.

It has been shown that oftentimes, diagnostic tools currently used widely in clinic and medical practice can be erroneous and of low sensitivity, failing to predict patient outcomes and limiting patients benefiting from preventive measures and therapy [Hen+15b]. EHR/EMR contain metrics which can prove useful as datasets in risk stratification algorithms as they can contain patient stay duration, symptoms exhibited, laboratory/test measurements, data from monitoring and IoT devices as well as observations by the responsible clinicians [PNMS13a]. Monitoring systems can be either self-sufficient and “stand-alone” or trained to identify the patients clinicians tend to miss, or “assisted” with the source of training data displaying a direct effect on system clinical utility.

So what role can risk stratification play in personal health? We propose a twofold system through which physicians and researchers can obtain trends when patients choose to share their data, while patients whose data is tracked can obtain recommendations generated through risk stratification. Many personal health applications currently function using literature threshold values and oversimplified systems that are currently not dynamic and do not occur through longitudinal patient tracking.

However, for widespread adoption of practical and longitudinal risk stratification models, we need to identify the limitations of such models and their applications to healthcare. Through literature review some common limitations for models that could be used in longitudinal risk stratification for predictive purposes in PHIMS have been identified.

EHR limitations

Missing data

EHRs present with extreme variability across patients in terms of completeness. We can classify missing data as missing at random (MAR), missing completely at random (MCAR) or missing not at random (MNAR) [HAD21]. Missing data can not only affect the robustness of modeling and analysis of the EHR but also induce possible selection bias affecting the overall results of the analysis. MCAR data are missing due to reasons confirmed to not be associated with the objective of the analysis, MAR data could be missing due to factors correlated to an extent to the variables analyzed and MNAR data is missing due to reasons that are directly associated with the purpose of the analysis. MNAR data in particular, is of particular importance for PHIMS as it could indicate that new measurements of a patient’s health parameters are neglected due

to a deterioration in patient condition, in which case the PHIMS platform could recommend a physician appointment or notify the healthcare provider.

Particularly with MNAR, where selection bias is impossible to rule out, missing data assumptions need to be both clearly defined and be considered in the analysis [HAD21].

Imputation methods

Imputation methods have been used in literature [Pet+19] in order to perform analyses in large medical databases and particularly EHRs; however, many methods ignore the reasons due to which the data is missing. Oversimplifying and ignoring basal assumptions can lead to misperformance of the model. In order to render imputation a viable means of EHR dataset processing, we suggest multiple imputation models which, although more computationally intensive, allow for more uncertainty and flexibility regarding missing values.

Multiple imputation presents several advantages [Mur18]. All the available data is retained and used, hence increasing power of calculations. Additionally, it allows for uncertainty and assists in its accurate statistical representation by generating multiple datasets with varied imputations with higher accuracy of standard errors and confidence intervals. By providing unbiased parameters for MAR data, multiple imputation mitigates biases of traditional imputation to an extent.

Finally, using external knowledge from the clinic as well as verified sources of data regarding the sample population that provides a representation of the addressed missing variables, sensitivity analyses can suggest possible deviations from MAR [Pha+19]. A clinical resource of particular interest is genetic data, which when available can be used to generate genetic risk scores that can be used as a predictor for imputation, increasing area under curve [LCM19].

Data Provenance

One size fits all is often inapplicable when attempting to mitigate missing data issues. In these cases, it may be useful to consider the provenance of the data, which refers to the origin of missing data, as well as the conditions under which the data is collected [HAD21]. Constructing several sub-mechanisms for each relevant data item as well as the time point at which it was collected in order to correctly define what missing data assumptions are fulfilled and hence classifying the missing data on a granular level.

Correctly identifying data provenance requires a clear hypothesis, definition of variables, and a collection of data which is predesigned to consider the assessment of missing data. In a longitudinal risk stratification of a patient using PHIMS, the initial collection of data may have not been designed to be classified as easily due to the initial intended use. Hence it is important to design the forthcoming data collection with empirically based causal pathways in mind, determined by physician expert opinion and literature in order to proactively address confounding biases created due to missing data in future analyses [Pea00]. STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) [Elm+07], a golden standard defining guidelines for epidemiology, modeling, and statistical studies in healthcare, only vaguely describes missing data suggesting researchers “indicate the number of participants with missing values” and “explain how missing data was addressed”. The subject of missing data is under-addressed in multiple healthcare longitudinal studies neglecting possible biases and uncertainty factors, hence using prior knowledge, i.e., for Bayesian modeling and sensitivity analyses can provide more

reliable and justified results [DHo8]. Considering the practical applications of PHIMS, a patient will need to rely upon a constantly updated and longitudinally evolving model, hence a meta-learning approach could be used, where multiple algorithms for missingness are evaluated and used according to both the types of data sources and the assumptions of missingness.

Selection bias

While it is relatively simpler to define samples in deterministic studies, with predefined variables and specific outcomes, stochastic modeling of data that was not collected with specific intended research outcomes may present more complicated selection biases. We can identify two main sources of biases, at healthcare provider level and at research level. Healthcare providers can differ immensely in documentation practices and registering of data to EHRs and usually present with geographic intimacies; patients in two different areas will present different epidemiological characteristics [San+12]. Researchers performing analyses and creating models of disease can extract, process, and analyze data differently and interpret it in variable fashion, leading to diverse research outcomes.

The demographic of healthcare providers is biased due to the very nature of healthcare services. Higher EHR completeness, for instance, may be associated with higher incidence of disease, as individuals who have more extensive EHRs have sought medical care more often [Con+24]. Certain conditions are associated with age, gender, ethnicity leading to confounding in extrapolations to the general population. Therefore, overrepresentation of certain patients may create strong statistical biases that are not representative of the total population, which is a likely target of PHIMS. Furthermore, the aging population of modern societies has shifted healthcare to address chronic disorders more often leading to an overrepresentation of older adults. An important factor to consider is willingness to share EHR data which also complicates the demographic [Jos+22]. Finally, geographic location can create sampling biases through differences in genetic composition or through local social determinants of health (SDOH), even at a neighborhood level [BEW11]. Depending on the area, socioeconomic differences can affect access, quality, and outcomes of health.

Right censored vs. left censored

Data censorship refers to unknown values or event times in the dataset. Data censorship can affect inclusion and exclusion criteria in the analysis which can further be complicated when patients switch health insurers due to potential interoperability and data sharing consent issues; this process is difficult to automate [Raz+15], hence having a central repository where personal health data is stored in the form of PHIMS and having access control regarding third parties in an interoperable format would greatly assist secondary data usage. Left censored data is below detectable threshold while right censored data is above the detection threshold but the exact value is unknown.

Right censored data results in not knowing the exact label and is often excluded from modeling, while left censored may not suffice to derive features. In the latter case either further data collection is required, or imputation and synthetic data based on prior knowledge can be collected.

Particular data limitations when using EMR records [PNMS13b] may be incomplete observations. Left censored patients may be patients that transferred to the study or provided their

data too late to provide complete profiles while right censored patients may have withdrawn or been discharged too early. When data is collected at discrete time points leading to unknown values or times of events, we observe interval censorship. This process can be addressed using PHIMS to an extent as additional data from IoT devices and log in could provide prior information and a central repository for data is conducive to complete longitudinal records. When it occurs, interval censoring may be addressed according to literature using methods such as expectation maximization algorithms and imputation-based approaches [Hsu+07; ZDS22]. PHIMS collected data can assist Bayesian methods of analysis through providing additional contextual information and priors or parameters to assist the analysis.

Non stationarity

In the process of constant medical data accumulation changes in technology, science, and incentives can change the practice of medicine as well as the clinical use of EHRs themselves, meaning the dataset itself can change. This process is called non-stationarity. When comparing a deep learning model to the status quo, slight improvements observed in the novel model compared to standard RFs may disappear with dataset shift or non-stationarity leading to overfitting the initial dataset [JS15].

This issue can occur for a variety of reasons:

Time scale changes: Treatment, definition of the disease, and disease progression under treatment are constantly changing, affecting the predictive capabilities of the predictive model.

Multivariate predictive nonlinear interactions: Unidentified interactions among variables can not only cause confounding. Subtle shifts among multiple variables that are undetected can lead to a cumulative sum change rendering the model less effective at prediction.

Historical data overfitting: Certain models such as random forests can overfit specific data in the training set and be maladaptive to dataset shifts.

So why is PHIMS a good solution to non-stationarity and what adaptations should be made when dealing with non-stationary data?

Data

The effect of non-stationarity on a predictive model is largely affected by data, including the volume, temporal coverage (discrete vs. longitudinal), and quality of data. Large and diverse datasets can improve generalizability, but they must assess potential data shifts to be effective. Longitudinal data spanning multiple time periods is crucial for identifying long-term trends and improving robustness, and high-quality data, derived from accurate data collection, storage, and validation to produce accurate features is essential to minimize the impact of noise and artifacts that can exacerbate non-stationarity.

Model adaptations

Preemptive design of models to deal with non-stationarity, particularly in the context of healthcare where data shifts are highly dynamic, is essential. Healthcare-derived time series can often-times be heteroskedastic and non-stationary, hence traditional time series assumptions can be inapplicable [Oga+10]. One example in literature concerning the case of transformers assessing longitudinal data in time series format where data distribution shifts across time, is to create two distinct modules [Liu+22a]. One module will provide stationarization, and provide integrated

statistics for inputs and heighten predictability. The second module provides a de-stationary attention mechanism to avoid overstationarization and recover the intrinsic non-stationary information into temporal dependencies by approximating differential attentions derived from the raw series data.

Examining the case of non-stationarity due to intervention suggested by the very model is worth investigating as well, generating an intervention-tainted outcome. The ultimate goal of risk stratification is to inform and guide interventions. For example, a patient identified as low-risk might not be admitted to the hospital, but in certain cases, such interventions may have been the very reason certain patients, such as those with asthma or pneumonia, survived.

Models can adjust for censoring effects of clinical interventions on patient outcomes, as seen in the TREWScore study (Targeted real-time early warning score) [Hen+15a] for septic shock, showing higher AUC in ROC when compared to MEWS (Modified Early Warning Score), commonly used in the clinic and Routine Screening. In this study, patients who did not develop septic shock after receiving treatment were considered right-censored after treatment; however, they were accounted for in the model development process. An inefficient updating of interventions can generate biases, as an additional factor is introduced in the causal pathway, hence causing predictive variables to be used in inferring their own effect [Lil+20].

An important consideration to mitigate nonstationarity hence arises, which is causal inference. The medical community has derived fairly accurate features for identification that may be in the causal pathway and can hence be efficient predictors of disease [Pea00]. Reducing the number of features and including primarily causal factors derived by expert opinion and literature such as the Cochrane guidelines [HG12] that directly infer the cause of disease rather than infer a correlation-derived probability risk can reduce uncertainty produced by nonstationarity. A Bayesian approach, for instance, using priors derived from within a causal framework could allow a research-informed adaptation to nonstationary new observations introduced [ZZT24].

This reduction of parameters can function two-fold in the context of PHIMS. Fewer variables improves interpretability and renders the analysis more explainable for both physicians and patients. Additionally, it is in accordance with the principle of data minimization [Sha+21a], which according to the EDPS (European Data Protection Supervisor) suggests “a data controller should limit the collection of personal information to what is directly relevant and necessary to accomplish a specified purpose”. In that case, the legal framework aids data analysts to shift towards more clinically actionable modeling of disease.

3.4.8.1 A framework for EHR based risk stratification analyses in the context of personal health

Data selection to avoid biases

Integration of External Data Sources: Linking EHR data with external datasets, present in the context of PHIMS such as population surveys or registries, can provide a more comprehensive view and help correct for selection biases [KAZ24]. External data can be provided through the PHIMS platform.

Standardization of data Collection: Implementing uniform data entry protocols across health-

care providers and institutions can reduce variability and improve reliability [AS+24].

Use of Bias Adjustment Methods: Employ statistical techniques to adjust for known biases, enhancing the validity of prevalence estimates derived from EHR data [Con+24].

Generalization to population:

1. Raw frequency and exploratory data analysis
2. Data Censorship
 - (a) Right Censored: Event occurs beyond the study period.
 - (b) Left Censored: Values below the detectable threshold.
 - (c) Interval Censored: Events occur within unobserved intervals.
3. Selection Bias evaluation
 - (a) Sources:
 - Healthcare provider variability (documentation practices, geographic factors).
 - Researcher interpretation and model-building disparities.
 - (b) Mitigation Strategies:
 - Consider geographic and socioeconomic disparities.
 - Address overrepresentation of specific demographics (e.g., older adults, frequent healthcare users).
4. Missingness evaluation
 - (a) Classification:
 - Missing Completely at Random (MCAR): Data missing unrelated to variables.
 - Missing at Random (MAR): Missingness related to observed variables.
 - Missing Not at Random (MNAR): Missingness linked to unobserved factors, indicating underlying conditions related to observed variables.
 - (b) Imputation Methods:
 - Multiple Imputation: Generates multiple datasets with varied imputations to improve accuracy and mitigate biases.
 - Sensitivity Analyses: Making use of external data, such as genetic risk scores, surveys to improve imputations and define uncertainty.
 - (c) Data Provenance Analysis: Understanding the origin of data in order to confirm assumptions about missingness, supports granular classification, and reduces bias.
5. Post-stratification
6. Multiple Imputation and when possible modularisation using sub mechanisms for each variable of interest that presents with missingness patterns.

1. Causal factors and expert analysis to confirm feature selection
2. Adjust for non stationarity in the case of time series data
 - (a) Causes:
 - i. Temporal shifts in clinical practices and disease definitions.
 - ii. Nonlinear interactions among variables.
 - iii. Overfitting to historical data.
 - (b) Model Adaptations:
 - i. Incorporate stationarization techniques and dynamic modules for longitudinal data.
 - ii. Adjust for intervention-induced shifts in outcomes.
 - iii. Employ Bayesian approaches with causal priors to accommodate new data distributions.
3. Ethical and Legal Considerations
 - (a) Data Minimization: Adhere to principles of collecting only relevant and necessary data for specific purposes.
 - (b) Explainability: Simplify models to ensure transparency for both patients and clinicians.
 - (c) Compliance: Align with data protection regulations such as the GDPR to ensure ethical data use.

3.4.9 Large Language Models

LLMs, or Large Language Models refer to models that attempt to comprehend and generate speech or text using large text datasets [Zö+23]. LLMs use machine learning methods to generate the probability of the next speech fragment in a sequence effectively predicting the next token and simulating speech to an extent. Current LLMs such as GPT-4 (Generative Pre-Trained Transformer) can generate speech based on immense amounts of data and can sometimes be indistinguishable from human written content.

In the context of PHIMS we can consider several scenarios where such models could prove useful.

1. Unstructured data summation
2. Chatbots for answering medical questions
3. Usage as a diagnostic tool

3.4.9.1 LLMs for data extraction

As LLMs are designed to analyze and produce text, they can be particularly useful in data processing. One example is named entity recognition (NER). LLMs can identify medical data and classify it, producing a structured format containing drug names, disorders and performed procedures from unstructured doctor's notes or even from registered conversations [Gha+24]. The unstructured data can help with automation of registering data from multiple sources, as well as converting qualitative inputs into quantitative and categorical variables. Additionally it can be particularly useful in labeling large datasets for analysis as research suggests LLMs can be extremely efficient in the annotation of clinical data, with high accuracy and much lower human intervention. Furthermore, training LLMs in labeling using human expert knowledge significantly improves accuracy in the automated task [Goe+23]. When retrieving data from EHRs, having an additional LLM to evaluate the output greatly improved performance [Goe+23] with limited hallucinations and clinically acceptable accuracy.

It is evident that LLMs can be particularly useful in the case of PHIMS especially when wishing to produce labeled structured data from patient inputs, diverse health IoT devices, physician notes and EHRs among others.

3.4.9.2 LLM performance in differential diagnosis (Ddx)

LLMs offer the advantage that they can more readily analyze unstructured data such as patient histories, laboratory measurements etc. Google's AMIE (Articular Medical Intelligence Explorer), when confronted with challenging medical cases by the New England Journal of Medicine, diagnosed patients correctly within its top 10 choices 59% of the time [Tu+24], outpacing doctors that took part in the study (34% accuracy). As standalone models, Chat GPT-4 and Claude produced the most accurate results, while a mixed method of doctors consulting with an ensemble of LLMs produced the most accurate diagnoses [Zö+24]. In a paper that assessed the accuracy of Llama 2, GPT-3.5, GPT-4 and Google GPT-4 displayed the best performance, although all LLMs were diagnostically accurate for common diseases. For rare disorder case files LLMs though displayed underperformance [San+24]. The LLMs could provide diagnosis support as well as suggest treatment and were suggested to be valuable clinical assistance tools.

As these models have been trained on enormous amounts of data derived from both academic and layman resources, older information, derived from the internet, where rare diseases can be underrepresented in the most common bodies of text. Fine-tuning and pre-training can improve reliability to a great extent but can prove computationally intensive and can create massive costs in hardware [WZ24]. Equally important is correct prompting of the models, which can significantly improve performance in Ddx tasks [Whi+23].

Surprisingly, Chat GPT-4, despite not being fine tuned with medical data or given particular prompts, overperformed models specialized in medicine and trained on PubMed sourced data such as MedPalm [Nor+23]. Even more surprisingly GPT-4 passed all three stages of the USMLE (United States Medical Licensing Exam), indicating the capabilities of the model even without specialization.

However, due to lacking accountability and misdiagnosing rare diseases along with hallucina-

tions, recommendations by LLMs in the context of PHIMS should be provided to the patient's overseeing physician for evaluation. While a useful tool, LLMs should be used in compliance with a responsible trained professional.

3.4.9.3 LLM fairness and biases

As mentioned above, commercially available LLMs such as GPT-4 have been trained on massive amounts of data, which means that biases derived by human predispositions are not derived from scientific inputs. It is therefore essential to evaluate whether human biases seep into analyses performed by LLMs for medical purposes.

A particular case of interest is race based medicine. LLMs have been assessed in a Nature paper to promote in certain cases inaccurate, harmful, race-based medicine [Omi+23]. Since October 2023, when the paper was published, immense improvements have been made in LLMs and OpenAI, the founding company of GPT-4 have addressed to an extent certain fairness mishaps that were affecting outputs, suggesting GPT-4 presents low levels of bias [Elo+24]

3.4.9.4 Chat-GPT4 performance and biases assessment

In order to assess the diagnostic capabilities of LLMs we performed a dry lab to investigate:

1. The performance of GPT-4 compared to Isabel (www.isabelhealthcare.com), a diagnostic tool, introduced into certain practices of the United Kingdom NHS (National Health System)
2. Potential racial biases introduced in the ddx process by Chat GPT

Materials and Methods

The dataset used was sourced by appendix A of the paper "DxGenerator: An Improved Differential Diagnosis Generator for Primary Care Based on MetaMap and Semantic Reasoning" [San+22], which also assesses a Ddx tool performance and compares it to the diagnostic system Isabel. The vignettes provided were deemed a ground truth as they were derived from credible sources of medical knowledge such as high impact factor journal case studies and medical textbooks.

The symptoms and lab results for each case were fed into either Isabel or Chat GPT-3.5 and Chat GPT-4. GPT-4 outperformed in diagnostic accuracy GPT-3.5 which in turn outperformed in diagnostic accuracy Isabel for both top 1, 5 and 10 percent accuracy. We then attempted to assess the potential racial biases affecting diagnostic accuracy for GPT-4. Diagnoses that were unaffected by confounding racial factors were maintained and those associated with race were removed from the dataset. The data were then assigned a race and the diagnoses were re-assessed for 4 different races: white, black, asian and hispanic. GPT-4 did not display statistical significant differences for the four races in terms of diagnostic accuracy. This unbiased performance represents a crucial advancement in AI-driven diagnostic support systems.

3.4.9.5 Explainability in LLMs for medical reasoning

A paper on the journal of hepatology suggested LLMs offer limited interpretability and explainability of the generation process and a major limitation is that commercially available LLMs do not offer metrics of statistical uncertainty [VC24]. The black box mechanism behind these LLMs means that clinicians are unable to follow the reasoning behind the result; ultimately affecting trust in the system and hence reducing chances of implementation. Sequential prompt engineering, prompting step-by-step can steer LLMs into a specific direction and simulate a reasoning process, effectively improving accuracy in arithmetic, common sense, and symbolic reasoning tasks [Wei+22]. Prompting Chat-GPT into displaying chain-of-thought diagnostic reasoning offers interpretability for clinicians, as they can assess the “qualitative relationships between inputs and outputs” [Sav+24]. An interesting outlook was that diagnostic reasoning does not improve GPT-4’s accuracy, signifying it either does not derive the same benefits from reasoning processes that a human would or that a maximal accuracy that could not be surpassed by reasoning may have already been reached. Much more interestingly, the LLM could be generating the reasoning post hoc. In our opinion, while this would offer interpretability and ease of evaluation of the response, it is neither explainable nor necessarily accurate. While the authors of the study suggest ad hoc reasoning is unlike human reasoning, some neuroscience literature suggests humans may be reasoning in a similar fashion; the process of rationalization suggests providing seemingly logical reasons to justify behavior driven by unconscious impulses [JBL11], while the bounded reality theory suggests humans make decisions based on limited information to reach a good enough rather than optimal outcome, justifying this outcome ad hoc to suit their overall worldview and social context [GP24].

3.4.9.6 LLMs for PHIMS

LLMs offer a valuable tool in the field of personal health, especially for data extraction and summation, as well as an assistive tool for competent physicians. LLMs can function as a bridge for interoperability between providers, platforms, researchers requesting data and doctors [Li+23b], being able to convert unstructured data into interoperable formats like FHIR.

Second, in personalized healthcare applications, LLMs demonstrate significant potential through their fine-tuning capabilities using patient-specific data. This includes processing biometric and psychometric qualitative data, with demonstrated ability to detect signs of mental disorders and distress in speech patterns. This capability enables proactive healthcare intervention by alerting responsible physicians when concerning patterns are detected [Yan+24].

Third, regarding patient engagement, LLMs can facilitate direct user interaction in layman’s terms and provide customized patient education and health-related guidance. This includes the ability to respond to specific queries about personal health analytics, making complex health information more accessible and understandable to users [Fan+24].

3.4.10 Personal data protection and PHIMS

The protection of personal data in PHIMS presents multiple challenges across three critical dimensions: data handling risks, technical solutions, and regulatory compliance.

Big Data and constant training means a higher risk to personal data protection. In particular, LLMs such as Chat GPT can store and process information such as conversation history and account information (<https://openai.com/policies/eu-privacy-policy/>), and hence sensitive information, such as medical data requires special handling and local models potentially in order to avoid data leaks in the future [VC24]. This challenge is amplified in the healthcare context, where ML models require extensive personal health data, yet sufficient safeguards are oftentimes overlooked due to limited awareness in the scientific community.

3.4.10.1 Technical Solutions and Their Limitations

Several technical approaches have emerged to address these challenges. Decentralized learning techniques, particularly federated learning could provide a meaningful solution, and federated prompt and fine tuning for LLMs is currently being developed to address privacy leaks. Similarly, blockchain technology where data is stored in distributed ledgers that are cryptographically safe, authenticated, and immutable can provide a secure, private and scalable environment for machine learning in healthcare. However, blockchain's immutability poses challenges in complying with GDPR's right to erasure and applied research solutions are required to mitigate these conflicts.

Compliance with EU regulation such as the GDPR and the AI Act can mitigate to a certain extent damages to individuals. However, due to the massive rate of development of novel AI models, a proactive, privacy-by-design approach is essential, as misuse and potential privacy violations of the future may not be well defined by the regulations of today. The GDPR in particular presents ambiguous terminology in multiple articles and particularly with mobile health applications, which present multiple similarities with PHIMS, one can observe many violations in existing applications. Such are: incompleteness of privacy policy, inconsistency of data collection disclosure, and the insecurity of data transmission.

3.4.10.2 Implementation Challenges

In the case of machine learning, particularly LLMs, the black box nature of the models used in healthcare [VC24] is in direct contradiction with the transparency and explainability requirements of both the AI Act and GDPR. According to the Medical Device Regulation of the EU, a medical device is a tool used for "diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease," hence qualifying any risk stratification or LLM described above as a medical device when used and applied in healthcare [VC24]. Medical devices require strict quality, security and risk control standards. Implementation in clinical workflows requires:

- Local or decentralized learning approaches
- Enhanced explainability mechanisms

- Robust data management for transparency and quality
- Compliance with GDPR, AI Act, and MDR requirements
- Alignment with Digital Markets Act for data portability and sharing

For future policy development, interdisciplinary teams, consisting of both scientists involved in state-of-the-art research with deep comprehension of healthcare analytics and legal/policy experts need to collaborate, to account for the rapid development of the field.

3.4.11 PHIMS and user empowerment

Active patient participation into their own healthcare leads to better health outcomes and increased compliance and satisfaction. PHIMS and personal health involvement can lead to a better understanding of personal health by the patients themselves and can ultimately inform policy and improve population health through patient education. Patient engagement can lead to change within healthcare organizations through mutual learning and more decentralized power systems. Patient engagement can have an immense impact on patient education, healthcare tool development, health organization planning, and novel policy development and implementation while enhancing existing service provisions and healthcare organization governance by affecting the care process or structural outcomes. Patient engagement requires further research as a domain considering the potential impact it can have on public health outcomes; however, it is under-defined and under-researched.

Other than active participation in healthcare and a personalized approach to medicine, PHIMS can be used as a system for data sharing with researchers and a platform for personal data valorisation. The lack of control over personal data can cause users to withdraw from digital markets and assessment of personal data value is very difficult, as there is little involvement of users in the collection and processing of their data. PHIMS can function as a personalized repository where personal data accessibility is managed and treated as an asset; personal data is of extreme value and users can scarcely decide to what extent they are involved in the data economy or receive sufficient compensation for their data. Personal data valorisation is under-defined and research has suggested that the main factor influencing individuals' willingness to pay/be paid for data is the development of consciousness regarding data as a tradeable asset. The implementation of PHIMS must prioritize aspects that directly enhance patient engagement and improve healthcare outcomes. Active patient participation in their own healthcare leads to better health outcomes, increased compliance, and higher satisfaction levels. Through PHIMS implementation, patients gain better understanding of their personal health, which can ultimately inform policy and improve population health through enhanced patient education. The implementation strategy must address data valorisation aspects, recognizing that personal health data represents a valuable asset requiring careful management. PHIMS implementation should create a personalized repository where data accessibility is managed effectively, allowing users to participate meaningfully in the data economy while maintaining control over their information.

Technical implementation considerations must focus on interoperability and standardization to ensure consistency and precision in healthcare systems. This includes developing standardized data collection techniques that enable cross-platform data exchange while safeguarding user privacy and maintaining robust consent processes. For population-level impact, implementation should enable improved data management and enhanced patient engagement capabilities. This requires careful attention to patient education tools, healthcare tool development processes, and mechanisms for influencing health organization planning and novel policy development.

3.4.12 Research Analysis

The analysis of PHIMS development and implementation reveals several interconnected domains requiring careful consideration and systematic approaches.

3.4.13 Privacy and Security Framework

Promoting privacy-by-design in PHIMS development is crucial for long-term success. The integration of decentralized learning methodologies, particularly federated learning, combined with blockchain technologies offers promising approaches to enhance data safety and mitigate privacy threats. These technical solutions must align with established standards, including the GDPR, AI Act, and MDR, while maintaining focus on explainability and transparency to build trust in healthcare technologies.

3.4.14 Artificial Intelligence Integration

The implementation of Large Language Models (LLMs) in healthcare settings demands well-articulated and rigorous restrictions. Rules must emphasize bias evaluation, result transparency, and safeguards against data exploitation. Moreover, as medical devices under regulatory frameworks, LLMs require comprehensive assessment to ensure safety, reliability, and efficacy in healthcare environments. Enhanced regulatory supervision becomes crucial for ensuring these tools remain both beneficial and ethical.

3.4.15 Accessibility and User Empowerment

A fundamental consideration in PHIMS development is ensuring fair access across all user groups. System design must actively address gaps in socioeconomic position, age, and health literacy to prevent marginalization of vulnerable populations. Through inclusive design principles and configurable features, PHIMS can enhance accessibility and promote widespread adoption. The Digital Markets Act's support of data portability and valorisation frameworks further empowers users in managing and potentially monetizing their personal data.

3.4.16 Technical Infrastructure and Standards

Investment in interoperability and standardization proves crucial for ensuring consistency and precision in healthcare systems. Standardized data collection methods enable cross-platform data exchange while maintaining user privacy and robust consent processes. The interpretability of machine learning models, particularly large language models, requires special attention to foster trust among healthcare professionals and patients by clearly explaining recommendations and reasoning.

3.4.17 Healthcare Impact and Outcomes

The integration of PHIMS into healthcare systems demonstrates potential for enhancing patient empowerment, improving health outcomes, and increasing treatment compliance. These platforms serve dual purposes: as educational tools improving health decision-making and as data-sharing mechanisms advancing public health knowledge.

3.4.18 Data Ethics and Governance

Secondary data use demands strict adherence to ethical standards. Key requirements include data de-identification, transparency in usage, and informed consent processes to maintain public trust. The formation of interdisciplinary ethics committees becomes essential for monitoring the ethical implications of data-driven healthcare research and applications. Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary studies are essential for addressing the intricate difficulties presented by PHIMS. Cooperation among data scientists, healthcare professionals, legal authorities, and ethicists is crucial for creating equitable and practical frameworks that tackle the intricacies of emerging technologies. Accelerated progress in artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and blockchain technology necessitates research teams that are proactive in policy formulation rather than reactive. Engaging patients, healthcare professionals, and community stakeholders in participatory research will ensure that solutions are focused on human needs, pragmatic, and inclusive. Longitudinal studies are crucial for evaluating the practical efficacy of PHIMS and AI tools, as well as for understanding the societal and economic ramifications of personal data valorisation.

3.4.19 Conclusions

The introduction of PHIMS into healthcare enhances patient engagement, improves outcomes, and signifies a notable transition towards personalised, participatory medicine and offers potential for positive reform in the current healthcare system. Large Language Models (LLMs) and risk stratification algorithms offer advanced processing, diagnostic, and educational functions, whereas Personal Information Management Systems enable individuals to take control of their health data. The integration of these resources may effectively address ongoing challenges in healthcare, such as access disparities, diagnostic inefficiencies, and insufficient data management. Their adoption presents certain challenges. To ensure the responsible implementation of

these advancements, it is essential to address significant ethical, technological, and regulatory challenges.

The moral application of these technologies, alongside the resolution of privacy, security, and bias issues, constitutes a significant challenge. Regulations such as the GDPR and AI Act provide a foundation for ethical data use; however, these frameworks must evolve to address emerging concerns as technology progresses rapidly. Due to the opaque nature of ML models and LLMs, often described as "black-box" systems, it is essential to develop explainable AI solutions to enhance trust between patients and physicians. To eliminate inequalities in healthcare delivery and ensure that these tools benefit diverse populations, it is crucial to address biases outcomes and ensure equitable access to PHIMS. A comprehensive and multidisciplinary strategy is required to address these obstacles, uniting professionals from various fields to deliver practical, ethical, and effective solutions.

Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research is essential for the optimal utilization of PHIMS. Facilitating collaboration among data scientists, medical practitioners, legal specialists, ethicists, and legislators enables the alignment of technical advancements with societal needs and ethical standards. Research initiatives can facilitate the design and implementation of technologies that are transparent, safe, and user-focused. Incorporating end users such as patients, carers, and healthcare professionals into the development process ensures that these solutions are technologically advanced while also being inclusive and practical. This approach allows for the possibility of a future where healthcare is characterized by greater equality, reliability, efficiency, and individualisation.

3.4.20 Future work

Personal Health Information Management Systems (PHIMS) research should focus on healthcare data management and analysis difficulties to ensure robust, equitable, and useful results. Meta-learning methods for missing data and non-stationarity adaptation are crucial. Meta-learning can help PHIMS dynamically adapt to these obstacles, ensuring accurate imputation and consistent performance across varied settings. For individual patient care and population-level health planning, PHIMS must contain adaptive mechanisms to sustain relevance and reliability as the healthcare landscape and data characteristics change.

Integrating real-time IoT data to fix interval censoring in patient records is crucial. Continuous biometric data from IoT devices like wearable health monitors can fill gaps in fragmented health records with context. Adding real-time data to PHIMS can improve longitudinal health analyses, allowing for more accurate patient trajectory modelling and prompt intervention recommendations. Advances in causal modelling are needed to reduce biases in observational healthcare data. PHIMS can make accurate, ethical predictions and insights by focusing on causative linkages rather than correlations, minimising healthcare inequities and building user trust.

Large Language Models (LLMs) in PHIMS are worth studying, especially for their capacity to support specialised functions. LLMs may synthesise massive, complicated datasets and make patient-specific suggestions to supplement risk classification frameworks. They can also create synthetic data, to simulate studies and improve modeling or to fill dataset gaps, especially for

under-represented populations, to make prediction models more robust and inclusive. When carefully incorporated into PHIMS, these tools can improve efficiency and accuracy. Future research that embraces these principles will ensure that PHIMS become flexible, equitable, and patient-centered systems that can satisfy modern healthcare needs.

3.5 Privacy friendly AI: benefiting from AI without giving away privacy

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3.5.1 Executive summary

The wide adoption of Machine Learning (ML) to solve a large set of real-life problems came with the need to collect and process large volumes of data, some of which are considered personal and sensitive, raising serious concerns about data protection. Privacy Enhancing Technology (PET) are often indicated as a solution to protect personal data and achieve general trustworthiness as required by current EU regulations on data protection and AI. However, an off-the-shelf application of PETs is insufficient to ensure high-quality data protection, which is necessary to understand. To this end, a systematic analysis of the risks against data protection in modern machine learning pipelines is a must. In this project, the first focus was on elaborating these fine lines between the guarantees required by the EU data protection directives and regulations and the actual threats and defence strategies with the technical guarantees they offer. Thus, building a detailed threat model that considers stakeholders, deployment choices, and different phases of the pipeline before and after using PETs. An analysis including such a threat model, a trust model, and the different guarantees can offer a straighter-forward technique to compare the desired privacy guarantees with the obtained ones. Acknowledging that no technology is perfect, all PETs come with limitations and drawbacks that must be clearly communicated and taken into account when the practitioner in this field seeks legal compliance.

Another finding in our analysis was the limitations of the current legal framework against some complex ML settings, namely the case of transfer learning of models, where the basic aims of enabling data subjects to have a flow governance over their data may be bypassed and lost. Transfer learning is a complex setting where a repurposing of a model can be carried out without actual reuse of the original data. This practice makes it difficult to prove leakage or prevent it. In the same context, legal tools like informed consent face a real challenge, since it is impossible to cite all possible transfer learning purposes that can be achieved after a model is already trained, making the obligation to inform data subjects about all the purposes of processing impossible. The legal analysis of this context reaches explored grounds and heated points such as addressing the question of the ownership of a model and whether data subjects can share ownership of the model since their data have been used to build it. The work on this problem proved the immaturity of EU legal tools in complex AI problems and the lack of flexibility when dealing with technical AI problems using legal lenses.

Similarly in this techno-legal type of issue, one of the most stubborn problems is the terminology and how the shallow usage of terms such as “anonymisation” may be misleading. In the EU legal framework, the anonymised data does not fulfil the required criteria to qualify as personal data and therefore the processing of anonymised data becomes free from the restrictions that personal data are subject to under the GDPR. To this end, as a further step, this work investigated the usage of anonymisation and how it goes beyond the technical understanding of the

term to include many PETs depending on the purpose of the regulation and the actual threat model used. The superficial mapping between the meaning of legal anonymisation and the technical tools named using the same term, i.e., 'anonymisation algorithms', leads to a narrow application of these algorithms and a shallow attempt to achieve a lawful processing. The superficial understanding of these terms by the tech community leads to a wrong usage of PETs that may be disadvantageous to stakeholders, especially those aiming to be protected by the regulations.

From another angle, the issues of privacy in the machine learning system may be tricky to spot before an actual leakage of massive data is revealed. Even more seriously, holding a potential attacker that does not show any record of malicious behaviour remains an open question that is hard to detect, since many of the attacks against ML systems have a statistical nature and achieve a high success ratio even in black-box settings with the attacker using the system just like any other regular user. One of these attacks is membership inference attacks, which we focus on in complex settings, namely in federated learning with a malicious aggregator and under transfer learning settings for large language models. In the latter two points, our findings suggest that this kind of attack is hard to detect and defend against, especially if one wants to preserve privacy and still maintain a good model performance.

3.5.2 Introduction

3.5.2.1 Background

With the growing adoption of data-intensive tools, machine learning models became the centre of a large portion of digital innovations. General awareness of how machine learning models (ML) are spread and deployed in nearly all digital services remains limited. Although researchers and machine learning practitioners tend to have a deep understanding of the lifecycle and the presence of machine learning models, the broader public, including policymakers and lawyers, often has limited insight into the processes. This created a gap between law enforcement that aims at protecting individual rights in digital services and computer scientists and AI researchers that understand the potential of these tools in solving real-world problems.

These reasons were behind the proposal of the LeADs (Legality Attentive Data Scientists) project. The project's goal is to train the next generation of law and computer science with an interdisciplinary vision of Artificial intelligence (AI) that takes into account the technical innovations with the legal objectives of data protection regulations. Training legal experts with a technical understanding of how AI models work under the hood will enhance the flexibility of the legal directives and promote legal frameworks that are easy to implement in practice. On the other hand, equipping data science practitioners with the necessary skills to understand the legal instruments with which they must comply is a first step toward closing the already existing gap between laws and technologies.

Figure 3.12: LEADs project crossroads

3.5.2.2 Objectives and Scope

The LeADs project has four main research crossroads as outlined in Figure 3.12. ESR 15 project, which we cover in this report, falls under the crossroad two titled: trust in data processing and algorithmic design whose elements are mainly inspired by the EU Commission guidelines for trustworthy machine learning [CCNT19]. This report will mainly take the perspective of privacy preservation in machine learning workflow from both a legal and a technical perspective, inspecting the gap in a systematic manner that allows us to highlight the existing problems and propose solutions that can be implemented in practice. Privacy is considered a key element in this vision of trustworthiness that includes many other elements, namely lawfulness and ethics, transparency, robustness, and fairness. It is seen to be so because the blocking element in the lifecycle of AI adoption is the restricted access to large volumes of legally protected data due to privacy concerns. Thus, without ensuring a proper privacy strategy, data remain locked and tools cannot be built without data, so concerns about the transparency of processes and the reliability of the offered solutions are qualities to worry about when the process already started, while privacy is generally a first barrier.

Privacy in machine learning, as discussed in this project, is an interdisciplinary topic at the intersection of cyber security, machine learning, and data protection regulations. Each of these elements is affected by the other. This interconnection is more complex when processes become larger and deployment strategies spread across the lifecycle of the data flow.

To unlock the topic, the first focus was based on inspecting this intersection between law and machine learning by looking at the very core of privacy and confidentiality as properties. Then, we examine the different threats to privacy in machine learning workflows and what characterises

them along with the respective defence strategies and their roles in achieving legal compliance. Then, we inspect a legal-driven approach around privacy-preserving tools as seen by the regulators by examining the key problems that block the adoption of PETs and mainly the anonymisation requirements by focussing on assessing the flexibility of the legal instruments in ML scenarios. Keeping in mind that the flexibility of law plays a significant role in implementing it.

The final part of the research project revealed many areas of research that merit both a legal and a technical inspection. These areas concern complex data flows, namely in Federated Learning (FL)⁶ and in transfer learning⁷.

3.5.2.3 State of the Art

The work in this intersection is rapidly growing driven by the need to fill the gap between data science and law.

Research in privacy preserving machine learning is generally divided into two main directions, namely privacy attacks and defence strategies [Cri20]. Sensing potential attacks and defences is insufficient without a systematic sensing method that evaluates both risks and the performance of the respective defences [Xue+20]. Especially attacks targeting ML systems are so diverse in nature and include traditional security issues related to deployment plans, training set poisoning, backdoors, adversarial examples, model theft, and sensitive training data recovery. Despite progress, preserving privacy in ML services has many unique challenges, including limitations in detecting malicious actions and the burden of applying PET where the utility of models tends to be sacrificed at the expense of protecting the privacy of data [Liu+21] [Pap+18]. One of the key missing aspects of the research in this area is the lack of the interdisciplinary approach, thus works tend to offer a very limited sense of privacy preservation, which is often insufficient to tackle the discussion around legal compliance.

A first work in this project [EMLD24] offers a more systematic and legal-driven approach in assessing privacy threats in machine learning. Later works [DEMB23] [EMDMB23] tackled a more legal analysis in complex settings of machine learning. Other works (still in press) worked on a more technical approach of privacy threat detection and leakage prevention under complex settings of federated learning and transfer learning.

3.5.3 Methodology

The methodologies in this interdisciplinary project involve a combination of technical, legal, and ethical approaches that require expertise across multiple disciplines, including computer science, law, and ethics.

We adopted two different kinds of methodologies, one when working on technical solutions and another one dedicated to the legally driven approaches.

⁶Federated learning is a set-up in which multiple clients collaborate to solve machine learning problems, which is under the coordination of a central aggregator[Zha+21]

⁷Transfer learning is a technique that utilises a trained model's knowledge to learn another set of data[Mar+22]

The technical methodologies were mainly focused on experimental studies, where different privacy attacks were designed and tested on a set of models that were trained using publicly available datasets like MNIST and ImageNet thus no personal datasets were collected since the technical privacy studies focus on technical privacy requirements with an effectiveness that is agnostic to the legal types of data. In other words, the technical privacy guarantees do not take into account whether the data are personal or not, but rather on the presence or not of a leakage risk and how to prevent it. Thus, for a better comparison it is advisable to use datasets that are benchmarks in the field in order to be able to position the theoretical novelty of the proposed solutions.

However, legal problems follow a very different methodology of analysis incorporating different legal instruments depending on the legal type the data used in each use case including legal scholars' opinions and guidelines that interpret the legal texts and offer practical approaches to study compliance.

3.5.4 Research Findings

The intersection of machine learning, privacy, and data protection regulation is driven by the growing reliance on data-intensive technologies from one side and the increasing scrutiny of how legally protected data should be handled; from another. Our inspection of the existing gap between regulations and actual privacy risks and defence strategies showed many poorly addressed aspects that make compliance with the regulations a challenging task. That is, the lack of a strategic framework that is understandable and feasible for machine learning practitioners to evaluate the efficacy of their privacy-preserving techniques in achieving the goals of the regulations such as the GDPR. Moreover, the drawbacks of the terminology differences between lawyers and computer scientists and their effects in hindering the enforcement of the data protection directives. And finally, the technical challenges in detecting and defending against data privacy attacks in complex machine learning settings such as transfer learning and federated learning.

3.5.4.1 The legal requirements versus the technical capabilities of privacy enhancing techniques

Under the hood, building tools that make use of machine learning models involves the usage of two types of data, namely: training data and inference data. The training data are the data used to build the model, and whatever capacities the model learns, they come from the knowledge extracted from the training data. The inference data are the data that the tool user feeds into the model in order to receive a result. The two types of data undergo two completely distinguished cycles of processing and pre-processing, which implies different stakeholders, infrastructures, and deployment choices that are influenced by the economical and societal aspects of the machine learning project itself.

This complexity in design, processing, and deployment is understudied by regulators. The current data protection regulations focus on a broad legal examination of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

tools, which leads to a vague consideration of the privacy risks and shallow requirements without straightforward guidelines on how to put these requirements in practice.

We found that despite the mantra of privacy enhancing tools (PETs) that exist, an off-the-shelf application of these tools is insufficient to achieve the goal of the regulations in safeguarding the legally protected types of data. To elaborate, the current regulations often refer to the need for privacy in processing sensitive or personal data by using 'appropriate measures'; however, due to the lack of sufficient guidelines and clear tools to audit the claimed 'appropriateness of privacy measures', these regulations remain difficult to implement [EMLD24]. Furthermore, we found that auditing the appropriateness of the privacy enhancing techniques incorporated inside a specific machine learning workflow can be done by defining specific threat and trust models for each workflow and thus establishing the technical and legal guarantees that this workflow must follow prior to any integration of any PET, then comparing those necessary guarantees with those obtained in practice after adopting a privacy-preserving workflow [EMLD24].

3.5.4.2 The techno-legal terminology

The gap between data protection regulations and Privacy Preserving Machine Learning (PPML) is deepened by the terminological differences between the technical staff and the legal one. These differences arise because legal frameworks focus on protecting individual rights and regulating data use, which imply a categorisation of data and tools that is based on the source of the entities that own, govern or can be impacted by the data. However, technological frameworks emphasise the design, functionality, and implementation of systems and their structure, thus the categorisation of data by technologists follows the structure and the functionality of the systems. Therefore, we find that the regulations often refer to types of data such as "personal, sensitive, trade secret...etc.," while computer scientists talk in terms of "text, image,..etc.." Another example of these confusions in terms is the term used to refer to stakeholders in the system where the law mentions actors such as: data processor, data holder, data subject, etc. while computer scientists use terms like process unit, user, etc. We found that there is no straightforward way to map between the two types of terminologies; it is rather a case-by-case process that requires an interdisciplinary effort of all stakeholders, including engineers and lawyers [EMLD24]. We also studied some of the consequences that arise when the mapping between these two kinds of terminology is poorly done with the case of anonymisation; where the particularity of this case was the fact that there exists a set of PETs also called anonymisation algorithms, although our analysis shows that the term "anonymisation" as mentioned in the legal instruments can map up to many PETs including PETs that do not fall under the technical categorisation of anonymisation algorithms [DEMB23]. Furthermore, anonymisation or pseudoanonymisation algorithms as applied by developers and engineers may be insufficient to achieve the required privacy of data that the legal instruments aim to achieve when mentioning "anonymised data". Our paper studied an extreme case that takes into account health data and how the poor bridge between legal requirements and the technical implementation of PETs may either end up in a fake shallow of privacy protection or in cases where anonymisation can not be used due to technical or organisational limitations limiting the access to the data.

The techno-legal terminology landscape of privacy in machine learning faces another challenge

which is the one of interpretation of complex workflows like those when models are repurposed, technically known as "transfer learning". This complex setting is characterised by the possibility to repurpose models without the need to actually re-use the raw training data that were collected to build the first model for the initial purpose. Our findings show a lack of flexibility in the current EU regulations when dealing with complex machine learning workflows like the one of transfer learning settings. That is because current regulations have a broad but rather rigid approach when trying to regularise the processing of data, concepts such as statistical aggregations and knowledge are highly debatable among scientists and lawyers on whether they should be considered personal or sensitive, especially with the challenges faced by technologists themselves in proving or denying the prones of certain models to leakage attacks [EMDMB23]. The ambiguity observed when trying to ensure that the built machine learning systems are perfectly compliant with the data protection regulations in the EU causes difficulties for developers and their organisations to determine the technical privacy requirements that their AI systems must provide. We found that even legal tools, such as obtaining consent about the use of raw data prior to any processing, may be insufficient if the data are used to build machine learning models. In fact, with the possibility of repurpose models without an actual re-use of the data and the whole confusion in interpretation of this practice, the consent obtained about the data solely may fail to accomplish the actual goals of obtaining informed consent. Thus, our paper [EMDMB23] suggests that in the case where the processing for which consent is to be obtained contains statistical aggregations or the building of machine learning models that can be repurposed, this consent should cover the output of this processing as well as the input with a rough estimation of the leakage risk that the data can be subject to when the aggregations and the models are used.

3.5.4.3 Data privacy attacks in complex machine learning settings

From a pure technical perspective, a large portion of privacy attacks in machine learning settings are statistical in nature, where attackers try to push models to reveal parts of the training data [EMLD24]. The particularity of this kind of attack is that they can occur in black-box settings where attackers do not show any malicious action, since they use the models in the same way as any benign user, making detection and defence challenging and pushing system designers to opt for preventive approaches such as differential privacy [Wan+23] that harm the performance of the model; exposing the traditional trade-off of obtaining privacy at the price of sacrificing performance. Not only that, attackers can go undetected, and thus inaccoutable for their actions.

In this angle, two settings were studied: the case of transfer learning for large language models and the case of federated learning.

In transfer learning settings and contrary to previous results that demonstrated a small risk of transfer learning leakage in computer vision models [Zou+20]. Our investigation showed opposite results for large language models and demonstrated a high leakage risk for language models when they are repurposed. This exposes the poor estimation of leakage risks for these models that are becoming more widely adopted, such as ChatGpt.

Moreover, for federated learning use cases, we emphasise on the growing risk of using federated

learning; which is a PET itself; without a good estimation of the leakage risk that can occur from maintaining attacks such as data reconstruction attacks and membership inference attacks. We showed the difficulty in detecting attacks maintained from within the system, and we proposed new strategies that focus on the detection of malicious behaviours without sacrificing the utility of the model. Such detection techniques can be useful for enforcing accountability with respect to legal instruments.

3.5.5 Research Analysis

Interdisciplinary research PPML can shape legal and technical standards by unlocking the potential of machine learning innovations to solve real-world problems without sacrificing the privacy implications of feeding AI with legally protected data. The preservation of privacy is a pivotal angle in the latest framework of trustworthy AI proposed by the EU Commission [CCNT19]. These guidelines aim to prescribe how machine learning models should be built and exploited for the best benefit of the environment and the large public. Furthermore, machine learning tools are being more widely adopted and by contributing in closing the gap between lawyers and computer scientists we help in achieving the goals of the LEADs project.

Analysing the ambiguities in the terminology and proposing how to overcome the lack of flexibility in the current regulations can help developers and practitioners to be more legally aware of the way they process and build machine learning models. In addition, these efforts help to shake the legal community to the reality of the difficulties in achieving compliance in practice.

3.5.5.1 Influence on the legal and policy standards

Our first work [EMLD24] analysed the privacy and confidentiality issues faced in machine learning workflows suggested a model of designing threat models' specific to each workflow and derive the technical privacy guarantees based on the legal instruments under which the system fall prior to any processing, then incorporating a privacy preserving workflows and compare the obtained guarantees against the promised ones to establish a realistic assessment of privacy. This work can help align machine learning with current legal instruments in a more systematic way. Furthermore, we also examined the challenges faced in understanding the regulations and obtaining these technical requirements [EMDMB23][DEMB23]. Our analysis exposed the rigid nature of the legal frameworks that makes it challenging to adopt the appropriate privacy measures for each case.

Our interdisciplinary approach can help in promoting global cooperation on AI governance while maintaining privacy as a fundamental right.

3.5.5.2 Challenges faced in influencing legal and policy standards

These goals behind interdisciplinary research in PPML face many challenges. The technical complexity is often faced with a lack of understanding by policymakers, which reflects a limitation in adopting PPML solutions. Moreover, while PPML solutions promise good privacy guarantees, this privacy is often obtained at the expense of sacrificing performance and utility. For example,

differential privacy may degrade the accuracy of ML models, while cryptographic tools such as homomorphic encryption require enormous computational resources. This tradeoff may exhibit a financial burden that is difficult to bypass.

The pace of technological development of threats versus defences is faced with a slow pace of law advancements. To elaborate, new threats emerge such as adversarial attacks and novel re-identification attacks that push PPML defences to evolve outpacing the ability of regulators to respond. This dynamic landscape poses a challenge to creating stable and durable legal frameworks that can effectively govern the use of PPML in the long term. In addition to this continuous race, PPML solutions face another challenge of ensuring their interoperability in different jurisdictions. Privacy laws around the world have different definitions, requirements, and enforcement mechanisms. Aligning PPML research with these varied frameworks can be difficult, especially when cross-border data flows are involved. Policymakers must collaborate with technologists to create coherent and harmonised standards that are compatible with the global nature of data sharing.

3.5.6 Conclusions

The interdisciplinary approach to privacy in machine learning as presented in this work represents a crucial step in addressing the tensions between the growing demand for data-driven technologies and the need to protect the privacy of individuals. The main objective is to unlock the full potential of machine learning in tasks that incorporate the use of sensitive and personal information without compromising confidentiality or individual rights.

A successful implementation of privacy-preserving data flows depends on the collaboration between technologists and legal experts to balance privacy protection with the accuracy and utility of the model. As privacy concerns continue to increase, particularly in fields such as health care and finance, PPML is expected to play a vital role in ensuring that innovation does not come at the expense of human rights.

However, there is still much to overcome in this field, including the ambiguity of the legal framework and the complexity of the technical solutions.

3.5.7 Future work

Finally we quote [EMLD24], where we point out some of the open questions and research directions in this field:

- **Measurement and evaluation of privacy:** There is a need for formal evaluation tools and frameworks to measure the privacy guarantees that PPML tools provide. Measurements are needed for auditing and data protection risk assessment for accountability purposes.
- **Communication Efficiency:** Some PPML tools suffer from a high communication cost and, therefore, are inefficient to deploy for large complex machine learning models, such as secure multiparty protocols (SPMC) and federated learning. Thus, there is a large room

for optimising computational complexity, such as optimising SMPC protocols through the use of MPC compilers.

- **Computation Efficiency:** computation efficiency is one of the drawbacks of the cryptographic tools used in PPML. This established the need to reduce the computational complexity either by making ML models designed for cryptographic evaluation or by making the cryptographic schemes more computationally efficient.
- **Privacy budget versus utility and/or fairness:** When adopting perturbation techniques such as differential privacy, privacy comes at the cost of utility (thus reliability), as well as the fairness of models (since minorities in datasets are the most harmed by utility loss). Approaches that balance between privacy, fairness, and utility are needed to establish trustworthy machine learning systems.
- **The relationship between privacy and other trustworthy machine learning elements:** trustworthiness in machine learning includes many components such as preservation of privacy, fairness, transparency, robustness, etc. The enforcement of privacy can come at the cost of these other components, which makes it challenging to identify the impact of privacy-enhancing technologies on transparency, for example. Understanding how each tool may impact the other elements of trustworthiness and how to set a clear trade-off is an active area of research.

4 Legal, technical and user-centered enablers of data processing and sharing

4.1 Sharing information for the public good

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4.1.1 Executive summary

This final scientific report provides an in-depth overview of the research undertaken by ESR 7 as part of the Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) project, focusing primarily on the topic of governmental access to privately held data. The research is structured into two interlinked parts: the investigation of data ownership and control as part of Crossroad 3, and ESR 7's PhD thesis, which delves into the tensions between business-to-government (B2G) data sharing regulations and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), particularly in light of the Data Act and Data Governance Act.

Crossroad 3, took a relational and interdisciplinary approach to the concept of 'data ownership.' It critically examined the evolving notion of property rights over data, considering how private institutions—particularly Big Tech companies—had gained significant control over user data. These companies often treated data as an economic asset, despite the absence of a formal legal definition of data ownership. This has raised concerns about the negative impacts of data enclosure and extraction, such as economic inequality and exploitation of user information. Crossroad 3's investigation focused on exploring these ownership dynamics, calling for a reformed data governance model that would redistribute the wealth and resources generated by data more fairly. ESR 7's work in this area examined not only the traditional legal framework of data ownership but also how control over data could be enhanced through technological and policy-based mechanisms, ensuring that the benefits of the digital economy were more equitably shared.

Building on these insights, ESR 7's PhD research further investigates the tensions between data protection and data sharing regulations within the European Union's legal framework. Her research highlights the dual objectives of data protection, which seeks to safeguard the rights and control of data subjects, and the regulations promoting data sharing, which aim to enhance the digital economy through the reuse and exchange of data. Specifically, the study examines how the recently introduced Data Act and Data Governance Act emphasize the economic potential

of data sharing, often in tension with the GDPR's focus on protecting individual privacy and data rights.

Furthermore, ESR 7's research identifies the potential for legal fragmentation resulting from these competing regulatory frameworks. The differing goals of promoting economic growth through data sharing while simultaneously ensuring robust protection of personal data create a complex regulatory landscape. This fragmentation poses significant challenges to policymakers who are tasked with maintaining the coherence of the European data regulatory framework. The research underscores the importance of finding a balance between protecting individual rights and enabling the free flow of data, both of which are critical for the future of the EU's digital economy.

In this context, ESR 7's work offers a nuanced analysis of the protective and limiting aspects of data subject rights, exploring the complex interplay between individual control and the broader goals of economic innovation. Her research emphasizes the need for an interdisciplinary approach to address the regulatory complexities of the data economy. By integrating insights from data science, policy, and legal studies, the research offers a more holistic understanding of the tensions between data protection and data sharing. Furthermore, ESR 7's work highlights the importance of cross-disciplinary collaboration to develop effective regulatory solutions, even as her focus remained on legal scholarship rather than transitioning into a data science role. The research ultimately contributes to the ongoing discourse on how to regulate data in a way that fosters innovation while protecting fundamental rights, ensuring that the digital economy evolves in a fair and transparent manner.

4.1.2 Introduction

The Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) project was designed to bridge the gap between law and data science by training a new generation of professionals capable of navigating the increasingly complex regulatory landscape of the data economy. These professionals, equipped with a dual understanding of both legal frameworks and technical data science, were envisioned to play a critical role in shaping and refining the legal responses to technological innovation. A key goal was to ensure that laws governing data usage and sharing are not only effective but also feasible from a technological standpoint, avoiding regulations that are impossible to implement or that fail to address the realities of modern data practices. This new breed of professionals—*legality attentive data scientists*— would help advance legal systems to keep pace with rapid innovation while safeguarding rights and promoting responsible data use. In my case, as ESR 7, my role was that of a "data science attentive lawyer," bringing legal expertise into the technical domain to examine how law can and should respond to the challenges posed by the digital economy.

As ESR 7, my research in Crossroad 3 focused on the theme "*Public-private data sharing from 'dataveillance' to 'data relevance'*". This theme explores the growing practice of states, especially law enforcement agencies such as police and intelligence services, accessing data held by private entities. In particular, I sought to analyze the government access to privately held data in light of recent European legislative developments, notably the Data Act and the Data Governance Act (DGA). These regulations aim to promote greater data sharing between public

and private entities, especially in the context of business-to-government (B2G) data exchange, while also ensuring that the rights of individuals and businesses are respected. My investigation examines the implications of these regulatory changes for the balance of power between public authorities and private institutions and raises critical questions about the appropriate limits of governmental access to private data in the digital age.

This report presents the findings of my research in the Project but also of my PhD research, which constitutes one of the first comprehensive comparative analyses between the GDPR, the Data Act, and the Data Governance Act. The research delves into the intricate tensions between these regulatory frameworks, particularly in their foundational principles. The GDPR is built on a foundation of data protection as a fundamental right, placing a strong emphasis on individual control over personal data through mechanisms such as consent, the right to access, and the right to erasure. In contrast, the Data Act and the DGA emphasize the economic potential of data, advocating for its reuse and exchange as key drivers of the European digital economy. These regulations promote the idea that data should be more freely shared between public and private actors to foster innovation, economic growth, and efficiency in public services. However, this focus on data sharing can reduce the level of control individuals have over their personal data.

The core contribution of my research lies in analyzing the extent to which these regulations align—or diverge—from each other, especially in their treatment of control. While the GDPR safeguards personal data as an inherent right, the Data Act and DGA shift the focus toward the economic value of data, treating it as a resource to be leveraged for economic gain. This divergence creates a tension between the rights-based approach of the GDPR and the market-oriented focus of the other regulations. My research examines how these competing objectives can lead to legal fragmentation and regulatory uncertainty, making it difficult for businesses, governments, and individuals to navigate the regulatory landscape.

In addressing these issues, my research sheds light on the broader questions also posed by the LeADS project, particularly in terms of how to strike a balance between data protection and data sharing in a way that promotes both innovation and fundamental rights. The study's findings are significant not only for legal scholars but also for policymakers, who must grapple with the challenge of ensuring that regulations governing the data economy are coherent, effective, and adaptable to future technological developments.

The report begins by examining the coherence of the EU's legal framework for B2G data exchange, with a specific focus on the interplay between the GDPR, the DGA, and the Data Act. These legislative measures are key components of the EU's Digital Single Market Strategy and European Data Strategy, which aim to enhance data accessibility while protecting fundamental rights. The analysis highlights how the GDPR's emphasis on personal data control contrasts with the DGA and Data Act's promotion of data sharing, particularly for public sector use. This regulatory dichotomy raises important questions about how the EU can balance its economic ambitions with its commitment to privacy and data protection.

In conclusion, the report identifies two key challenges: the philosophical tension between the rights-based approach of the GDPR and the market-oriented goals of the DGA and Data Act, and the practical difficulties posed by textual inconsistencies across these regulations. These

challenges create legal uncertainty, making it difficult for stakeholders to understand how to comply with the law and for policymakers to ensure that regulations are both enforceable and effective. My research underscores the importance of resolving these tensions to foster legal certainty, promote economic growth, and protect individual rights in the evolving data economy. By examining the alignment of these key regulations, the research contributes to a clearer understanding of how the EU can navigate the complex challenges posed by the digital economy while safeguarding fundamental rights.

4.1.3 Research Findings and Analysis

4.1.4 Navigating Regulatory Complexities in the Digital Economy

In today's increasingly data-driven world, the convergence of data science and law has become more crucial than ever due to the rapid and ongoing advancements in digital technologies. These technologies, while serving as engines of significant economic growth, have also introduced a range of complex challenges related to the management, governance, and regulation of data across both private and public sectors. Data has emerged as a core asset of the digital economy, particularly within the European Union, where it plays a pivotal role in driving innovation and economic development. [Com20d] [Cou24] This surge in the value and ubiquity of data has also amplified the demand for professionals with interdisciplinary expertise—individuals who can expertly blend technical proficiency in data science with a deep understanding of legal and regulatory frameworks. These professionals are essential for ensuring that technological innovations do not undermine fundamental rights or compromise ethical standards, such as data privacy, security, and fairness.

Interdisciplinary experts in the fields of data science and law are tasked with addressing a multitude of pressing issues. These range from data protection, intellectual property, and cybersecurity to regulatory compliance, all of which are integral to the functioning of a highly digitized global economy. As data frequently crosses borders and is shared across platforms by diverse actors, the legal frameworks governing its use must be carefully navigated to ensure its responsible and ethical stewardship. In this intersection of law and technology, professionals must grapple with the challenges of legal compliance while facilitating innovation and economic growth. The ability to reconcile these sometimes opposing forces is particularly important as governments and regulatory bodies around the world, especially within the EU, seek to design policies that support innovation while upholding fundamental rights.

The EU has been at the forefront of creating comprehensive data governance policies that reflect this balancing act. Notably, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Governance Act (DGA), and the Data Act stand as major regulatory initiatives aimed at shaping the digital future of the EU. The GDPR, a pioneering regulation, establishes a strong framework for personal data protection, emphasizing individual control over data through principles of transparency, accountability, and privacy. It empowers data subjects with specific rights over their personal data and places stringent obligations on organizations that handle such data. [Bie22] [Fus14] On the other hand, the DGA and the Data Act, while recognizing the need for data protection, are more focused on promoting the free flow of data, especially between businesses

and governments (B2G), in order to unlock economic growth, innovation, and improved public services. These regulations aim to create a data economy where information is more easily accessible and can be reused to foster innovation, while still maintaining a degree of regulatory oversight. [Com20d]

However, these regulatory initiatives also bring to light inherent tensions between the goals of data protection and the objectives of data sharing. While the GDPR is centered around protecting individual rights and limiting data misuse, the DGA and Data Act advocate for the extensive sharing and utilization of data as a driver of economic and societal benefits. The delicate balance between these objectives requires a deep understanding of both legal and technical aspects to ensure that these frameworks operate in harmony rather than in conflict. Addressing these tensions is essential for developing a coherent legal framework that accommodates both the economic needs of the digital age and the protection of personal data and privacy. [CC23]

To address this growing need for professionals who can navigate these complexities, the LeADS project was established with the goal of developing interdisciplinary experts. The project seeks to train individuals in the interconnected fields of data science, law, and policy, equipping them with the skills necessary to navigate the intricate and often contradictory regulatory landscape. [CC23] Participants in the LeADS project are taught to balance the imperatives of innovation and economic growth with the need to safeguard fundamental rights and ensure ethical data use. The project's overarching aim is to create professionals capable of managing data responsibly, ensuring that its use is transparent, fair, and secure, while adhering to the legal standards set forth by the EU.

In this context, my PhD research, focuses on examining the compatibility of the legal and regulatory frameworks governing business-to-government (B2G) data sharing, particularly those outlined in the Data Governance Act (DGA) and the Data Act, with the principles enshrined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The central objective of my research is to analyze how well these new data-sharing regulations align with the GDPR's core principles, which prioritize data protection and the rights of individuals. The challenge lies in reconciling the EU's dual objectives: facilitating data sharing to spur innovation and economic growth, while ensuring robust data protection standards that safeguard individual rights.

My research as ESR 7 formed part of Crossroad 3 of the LeADS project, which investigated the concept of 'data ownership' from an interdisciplinary perspective. In particular, my research explored the idea of 'data control'—the extent to which individuals or entities should be able to control data—alongside the notion of 'data sharing.' By conducting a comparative analysis of these regulatory frameworks, I sought to uncover the legal, ethical, and technical tensions between enabling greater data sharing and maintaining the necessary controls over personal data. This analysis was crucial in understanding how the EU's regulatory frameworks could evolve to balance the need for economic integration and the protection of fundamental rights.

Ultimately, my PhD research reflects the broader tension between the goals of control and sharing in the EU's digital regulatory strategy, shedding light on the challenges faced by regulators and policymakers in creating a cohesive and forward-looking framework for the data economy. It highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in addressing these complex challenges, offering insights that are valuable not only for legal scholarship but also for policymakers

and industry stakeholders striving to navigate the rapidly changing digital landscape.

4.1.5 Research Questions

My PhD research thus focuses on the tensions between the GDPR's focus on data protection and the DGA and Data Act's emphasis on economic growth through enhanced data sharing. The scope is confined to an analysis of these three key pieces of legislation, focusing on their provisions related to B2G data sharing. This work does not delve into other sectoral data-sharing frameworks or international agreements, but it draws attention to their relevance when interpreting EU law. The following key research questions guide the analysis of this research:

To what extent do the DGA and Data Act provisions for B2G data sharing align with the GDPR's framework? What are the philosophical and legal tensions between the GDPR and the newer regulations concerning data sharing and protection? How do the GDPR's principles, such as data minimization and purpose limitation, affect the sharing and reuse of personal data under the DGA and Data Act?

These questions are answered through several chapters in my PhD, which focus on several topics, amongst them:

(i) how the GDPR, the Data Act, and the Data Governance Act have, in theory, the same twin aims of the EU's digital regulations - facilitating market integration while upholding fundamental rights. However, they have distinct conceptual ideals, namely the protection of the fundamental right to data protection and the free flow of data in the internal market; (ii) the double rationale on data, namely data as an economic asset and data as a common good; and (iii) the lack of definitive definition of "data sharing" in the GDPR and opaque definition of "data sharing" in the Data Governance Act and the Data Act.

Whilst I am still writing my PhD thesis, results emerging from my preliminary findings demonstrate that the literature lacks clarity on how the tension between protecting personal data through control and pushing for further sharing and reuse of data plays out. Therefore, this research aims to contribute to the academic discourse by undertaking a comparative analysis of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Governance Act (DGA), and the Data Act. Through this comparative lens, the research aims to elucidate and address the regulatory misalignments that manifest in the context of business-to-government (B2G) data sharing.

4.1.6 Methodology

My PhD research adopts a doctrinal legal methodology, which involves the analysis of legal texts, academic literature, and judicial decisions to understand and evaluate the existence or not of tensions and contradictions between the GDPR, the DGA, and the Data Act. The doctrinal method is well-suited for assessing legal compatibility since it focuses on interpreting and analyzing legislative frameworks, recitals, and case law. This approach allows for examining the legal principles, definitions, and terminology that shape the intersection of data protection and data sharing in the EU regulatory [TB24]

The rationale behind choosing a doctrinal methodology lies in its ability to explore the conceptual and textual (in)compatibilities between these three regulations, particularly concerning business-to-government (B2G) data sharing. Since this research focuses on legislative and legal frameworks, which are relatively new and continuously evolving, it prioritizes analyzing written legal sources to provide an authoritative basis for evaluating the regulations. This method also helps in understanding the philosophical underpinnings of each regulation—whether they are grounded in fundamental rights or economic objectives—and how these differing foundations affect the interpretation and application of the law.

While the research itself is primarily legal in nature, as a part of the LeADS project, I have profited from an interdisciplinary approach that has integrated legal, technical, empirical, and normative analysis. The methodology blended these methods to address abstract problems and apply them to real-life policy design and business needs. This approach allowed me to integrate legal rules with a technological and technical environment in a cross-disciplinary manner. I also became familiar with quantitative and qualitative methods of empirical research, particularly focusing on comparative and policy analysis. The training also provided me with technical knowledge related to data usage in the digital world, which was critical for having a comprehensive understanding of the impact of my research.

The research involves a comparative legal analysis, which is conducted to identify both textual and conceptual alignments and misalignments between the GDPR, DGA, and Data Act. The comparison is structured around crucial legal principles (such as purpose limitation, data minimization, and consent) and their application within the context of data-sharing provisions in the DGA and Data Act. In summary, the chosen methodology combines traditional legal doctrinal research with innovative interdisciplinary techniques, comprehensively analyzing the compatibility between the GDPR, DGA, and Data Act. This approach ensures that both legal and technical aspects of data sharing are addressed, offering meaningful insights into the evolving regulatory landscape for data governance in the EU.

4.1.7 Conclusions

4.1.8 Research Analysis and Conclusions

The main focus of my research, as ESR 7 and also for my PhD thesis, revolves around the sharing of data between private and public institutions and the challenges related to data protection that arise from the sharing of personal data. Additionally, my work as ESR 7 within Crossroad 3 and the LeADS project has provided me with the opportunity to delve into the concept of control in data protection law and how this notion of control conflicts with the notion of sharing data for economic development and further reuse.

Thus, research so far has revealed significant disparities between the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Governance Act (DGA), and the Data Act regarding their approaches to data protection and sharing. The GDPR places a strong emphasis on protecting personal data as a fundamental right, establishing rights for data subjects with the aim of enhancing control over the processing of personal data.[\[Bie22\]](#) [\[Fus14\]](#) In contrast, the DGA and Data Act prioritize the economic value of data, advocating for widespread sharing, particularly

for business-to-government (B2G) purposes, which falls on the complete opposite side of the spectrum of control.[EDP21] [EDP22]

This disparity creates a tension between the need to preserve individual rights and the drive to promote data-driven innovation and economic expansion. Moreover, notable discrepancies have been identified between the regulations, especially in terms of definitions and terminologies. This underscores the necessity for precise definitions and alignment between data protection and data governance regulations. Additionally, the research has found thus far that there is a visible requirement to harmonize the dual objectives of the legal frameworks. This involves advancing data-driven innovation while simultaneously protecting the fundamental right to data protection as enshrined in the GDPR.[CC23]

These findings are highly significant in the context of the LeADS project. Since my research directly deals with interdisciplinary aspects of data regulation, the LeADS experience has allowed me, as a legal researcher, to fully comprehend the technical aspects of my research and to grasp the legal and technical tensions between the GDPR, the DGA, and the Data Act. The research has identified philosophical and textual inconsistencies between the GDPR and the newer data-sharing regulations. These findings can help in understanding the data regulatory framework, particularly in developing a more harmonized legal framework that balances privacy rights with the need for data-driven innovation. Policymakers or judicial bodies can use these findings to ensure that future regulations or legal interpretations reduce legal uncertainty and improve compliance across sectors.

Moreover, emphasizing the compatibility challenges of business-to-government (B2G) data sharing highlights the need for more precise guidelines on how public and private sectors can exchange data while respecting fundamental rights. This research can influence the development of more robust legal standards for data sharing, particularly by promoting mechanisms that align with both privacy protection and economic imperatives. From a data science perspective, the research offers insights into how legal regulations shape the use and sharing of data. By identifying the challenges posed by the GDPR's limitations on personal data processing, the research underscores the importance of designing data-sharing systems compliant with legal standards, especially with the approach of data protection by design and default.

The research has provided insights into the LeADS project by examining the compatibility of the GDPR, the DGA, and the Data Act. It focuses on business-to-government (B2G) data sharing and the tension between data protection and the drive for data abundance to foster economic innovation. This analysis helps to understand how regulatory frameworks must balance data protection with the need for data sharing in the digital economy.

One of the significant issues identified thus far in this research is the lack of consistency in the terminology and in the foundations between the GDPR, DGA, and Data Act, emphasizing how the harmonization of definitions, especially concerning data-sharing practices, reduces legal uncertainty and ensures smoother implementation of these different regulations. This is especially relevant due to the growing emphasis given to the use of B2G data sharing for public benefit, which further weight to more precise and more robust guidelines that should be developed to ensure that public authorities can access the data they need without compromising individuals' data protection.

4.1.9 Future work

Despite these challenges, the research highlights the need for continued development of legal-tech tools that can help bridge the gap between data science and law. These tools could automate compliance processes, making it easier for businesses to share data while adhering to legal obligations. Future interdisciplinary work could explore developing artificial intelligence (AI) systems that automatically assess data-sharing activities for GDPR compliance or blockchain technologies that ensure data transparency and trustworthiness in line with regulatory requirements.

Moreover, as the DGA and Data Act begin to be implemented across the EU, there is an opportunity for empirical research to assess how these regulations are impacting B2G data sharing in practice. This could include case studies on how data-sharing agreements are being negotiated and enforced, as well as surveys of businesses and public authorities on the challenges they face in complying with both the GDPR and the newer data-sharing regulations.

4.2 A framework for user-centered, legal-ethical collective consent models: genomic data sharing

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4.2.1 Executive summary

Health data is sensitive and sharing it could have many benefits and risks, which is especially true for genetic data. One's genome might indicate health risks that could be used for more personalized healthcare or increased insurance premiums. These affect not only the individual who has initially consented to the collection and sharing, but also those who may be impacted or identified by the same DNA. So how can all relevant individuals consent to genetic data sharing? Collective consent offers a framework to engage multiple stakeholders, but no digital collective consent exists yet for the general public due to challenges in legal-ethical and sociotechnical properties such as transparency, legal complexity, and usability. This final scientific report provides an overview of the research taken by ESR9 as part of the Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) project, focusing on the topic of consent for genomic data sharing in the European Union (EU). ESR9 is also part of Crossroads 2, which deals with trust in data processing. Within this, transparency and usability help to build trustworthy processes. ESR9 conducted a theoretical and empirical study on collective consent processes for health data sharing. First, I explored the need for collective consent from a privacy, biomedical, and legal-ethical lens. I analyzed the transparency and user-relevancy of policies from notable Direct to Consumer (DTC) genetic testing companies to find gaps in the status quo. Then I tested methods in the framework for transparent, user-centered collective consent with a employees from a welfare technology company to better understand pros and cons in future implementation. Then I surveyed adults about their attitudes towards consent management and engaging elements within different consent mediums to better understand their needs and desires. Together, this framework shows promise for addressing end-user and business needs for collective consent, and upon further iteration could also be relevant in the future to other types of shared data in the EU.

4.2.2 Introduction

Sharing genomic data can offer many benefits, from more personalized care to a better understanding of human health. For example, genetic testing can help people to determine which medication may be most effective or those with a family history of a disease to understand their predictive risk. However, it is also sensitive and sharing it could have many risks, which is especially true for genetic data. For example, the data might reveal family member's conditions, or a genome might lead to personalized insurance premiums as well as personalized medicine. These potential harms should be addressed on an individual, group, and governance layer to protect privacy and security while also maximizing the benefits.

One of the ways to address the individual and group level is through collective consent, to offer

relevant individuals a framework to consent to health data sharing. Collective consent stems from indigenous bioethics where indigenous tribes fought for their right to consent to biomedical research as a community, not just as individuals. It has been used in research partnerships with indigenous groups to improve stakeholder involvement instead of treating indigenous populations as test subjects.

Though it has been proposed, no digital collective consent (wherein multiple individuals consent in different via different governance structures such as families or tribal leader) exists yet as there are complex issues such as the conflicting right not to know and the duty to report, the mechanism of decision making, and governance structure of the collective are undefined. Generally, different EU legal-ethical considerations, technical properties such as transparency, and core concepts such as trust that all must work together to support digital collective consent. The EU MSCA ITN Legality Attentive Data Scientists (LeADS) has been established to train early stage researchers to address these types of issues that span interdisciplinary domains. 15 early stage researchers have been divided into four different crossroads: 1) Privacy vs Intellectual Property, 2) Trust in Data Processing and Algorithm Design, 3) Data Ownership, and 4) Empowering Individuals. My research is placed within Crossroads 2 and also has connections to Crossroads 4. This research incorporates law, ethics, and computer science (privacy, Requirements Engineering (RE), Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)) and fits within the scope of Crossroads 2 because in genomic data sharing, consent is a key issue to help build trust. Some of the ways to enhance trust is through transparency of the consent, data sharing, and processing. The usability the consent process also helps build trust.

As more and more genetic data is collected, stored, and shared in addition to different metadata, the genomic privacy risks also increase. The more datasets that are available, the more re-identifiable someone can be. For example, combining different datasets (e.g. public, controlled access, population level patterns) can re-identify participants from anonymized databases and non-participants may have their genomes and traits exposed. In 2004 it was found that only 75 statistically independent single nucleotide polymorphisms, or single base pair changes in DNA, could re-identify an individual [LOA04], in 2024 the number is likely lower. With the rise in electronic health records, genomic data, and digital recordings, individual consent is insufficient to address the highly interconnected world. Both the benefits and risks should be shared between affected individuals, and everyone should have a say in data sharing that could equally help or harm them.

4.2.2.1 State of the Art

Consent can be difficult for an individual to understand and may be even more challenging for collectives. First, there are often barriers to understanding the text and many efforts to make the reading level easier and more accessible to a larger portion of the population [YHF90]. One review also found that verbal communication helped improve understanding [Tam+13]. Studies demonstrate that Informed Consent (IC) forms for genetic testing are far less comprehensible than what is commonly recommended [Nie+18]. They looked at 36 IC forms from US providers and found that the median readability grade levels were 14.75 and 12.2 (the numbers represent how many years of study that would be needed to understand the text) by two different for-

mulas which were much higher than the recommendation of 8 by the US Institutional Review Board. Second, realistic benefits of consenting to genomic data sharing may include statistics or scores that are hard to understand the relevance of. Most people also have a limited health literacy [McB+10] and data literacy [D'17] which creates barriers to understanding risks and benefits of sharing health data including how research processes work and understanding the impact of statistical results on their daily life.

This may implicate family in the context of genome data and health data [O'No1] and may lead to genetic privacy abuses [bpp19] such as the United Kingdom Border Agency's Human Provenance Pilot Project in 2009 that used genetic ancestry testing to vet asylum claims, conflating ancestry with nationality, and disenfranchising asylum seekers [Ben16]. From the system, there may be different levels of informational transparency, integrations with storage and access controls, and design. Overall, the institution that asks for consent is also a consideration for participants and can lead to trust evaluations that may influence their decision to collective consent or not. For example, if MyHeritage has historically had a data breach, then it might decrease trust in participants regardless of how transparent and usable the consent management is.

This often contrasts with the legal consent requirements from the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). IC mandates that consent to data processing be "freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous" (Art. 4(11), easily revocable and in an intelligible and easily accessible form using clear and plain language (Art. 7); explicit for biomedical and genome data because it is sensitive data (Art. 9); transparent, in terms of completeness, comprehensibility, and accessibility of the information disclosures (Art. 12, 13 and 14 GDPR); and compliant with the principles of data protection by design and by default (Art. 25 GDPR).

Another challenge is the information and communication technologies that support consent management. The e-health scenario complex and the available choices about data sharing and their significance to the user may be difficult to understand as well. The way options are presented to users can protect individuals from unnecessary risks and respect their preferences, but it can also manipulate them into mindless data sharing [Noam]. Dark patterns in cookie consents are incredibly pervasive and in a study testing how design choices affect user decisions, it was found that offering more granular control of consent on the first page decreased consent by 8-20 percentage points [Nou+20]. Conversely, the same study showed that removing the "reject all" or opt-out button from the first page increased consent by 22-23 percentage points and overall participants were frustrated by the pop-up design preventing access to a service, creating feelings of coercion and increasing consent fatigue [Nou+20]. Individuals should be able to manage their data use permissions over time and manage the level of information they are given to suit their preferences [Bur+13] and increase public trust and engagement [Wil+15]. However, more options or transparency may not necessarily be the answer, as increased demand for user engagement could make people feel overwhelmed by the numerous options and notifications and undermine their decision making [SCH14]. The implementation of consent withdrawal is also a complicated process because many parties are involved in data processing [PAP18], and also revoking data may mean different things in practice (i.e., revoking the permission to hold personal data v. the permission to use personal data) which has not been well studied or implemented [Whio9].

Dynamic consent [Kay+15a] is a flexible existing model of consent that offers a patient-centered platform for electronic consent (eConsent) management [Kir+18] and research project [Pri+20a]. Underpinning collective consent is the principle of communication and involvement of stakeholders in data governance and decision making to increase understanding, empowerment and trust [Kay+15b]. However, I have not found any that has studied group or collective decision making for genetic data in a digital context. For example, what level of transparency would be appropriate while also preserving the anonymity of individuals in a collective who share a genetic disease? What attributes are most relevant for a user? One case study of dynamic consent, CTRL in Australia [Haa+21a] had the goal of integrating genomics with its healthcare services and built a dynamic consent tool offering participants greater control over their data and data sharing, news about involved studies, and access to researchers. Instead of focusing on legal compliance, they focused on usability and data sharing using Global Alliance for Genomics and Health Data Use Ontology. Another dynamic consent platform for a longitudinal health study, CHRIS in South Tyrol, Italy [Mas+22], has also built a custom platforms to better engage users. Dynamic consent also offers solutions for withdrawing consent with the concept of "wrapping" the participant's consent preferences in "sticky policies" that are attached to data as it moves around for data processing and uses encryption techniques which allow the information to be processed while encrypted, so even the results are encrypted with new homomorphic encryption and has been piloted in EnCoRe [Enc] [Bei+14].

Ways for enhancing understanding and transparency health IC have also been explored. For example, transparency by design centers transparency-enhancing design patterns to increase the clarity and navigability of IC and enhance participant engagement in data-driven research [RL20a]. Though IC is traditionally text based, other mediums have been explored, such as comics to request consent for participation in a genomic research project to the San people in South Africa. The comic increased general understanding of the genomic research process and accordingly strengthened their ability to make fully informed decisions [BR21]. Multimedia IC with audio and visual reinforcement with simple language and visual metaphors has also been shown to improve understanding [Men93]. Given that human beings are not well versed in understanding statistics and percentages, health statistics such as risks and benefits should follow transparency guidelines [Gig+07], for example, reporting risks and benefits in comparable units instead of how they are usually reported with relative risks were for benefits, and absolute frequencies for harms (e.g. 1 in 1000 patients are at risk for a stroke, but taking this medicine may reduce risk of a stroke by 40%).

Implementations of DC can be both individual and collective, which has been suggested not implemented [Pri+20a]. Underpinning collective consent is the principle of communication and involvement of stakeholders in data governance and decision making to increase understanding, empowerment and trust [HCL19; Tak+18; Pri+20b; Hea19; Hud09; War11; Hay+21; Pri+20a], which serves as an example of how the consent processes can be more user-centered, trustworthy, and comprehensible by design if relevant stakeholders are involved.

Overall, health data has emerged as a significant source of medical and research knowledge, benefiting individuals and related groups. While there may be many shared benefits and risks, in the status quo, health data sharing largely remains individualistic (e.g., individual consent) and poorly communicated. This is because 1) much of the history of legal-ethical consent is built

on individual autonomy and in practice, collective notice and consent is ignored unless legally required, 2) consent processes are complex in the digital age with multiple parties and difficult to transparently record and understandably communicate, and 3) user-centered consent design is highly contextual and there are few studies in the field for shared health data.

4.2.2.2 Objectives and Scope

Given the challenges in consent and informational privacy, two of the main focuses of this work will be informational transparency and user-centered design of information to address the "informed" consent issue. This also ties to the unique challenge of collective genetic data, such as communication of risks and potential harms, or navigating the balancing of different opinions in a collective. Information also must be relevant and useful, or else it will fall into the transparency paradox. Thus, user-centered design is another key factor that allows for iterative research into building a system that addresses user needs. Given the limited amount of prior research in the digital collective consent for undefined groups, where there is no empirical research available, the process should be taken from the ground up. Instead of focusing on innovative technology that may not be useful or usable, I will focus on consent needs and goals of potential end-users as well as from Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) that may be motivated to implement a framework for more transparent, user-centered collective consent that abides by EU regulations. To be useful in the EU necessitates being legally-ethically aligned with EU regulations such as the GDPR.

My research objective is to explore the challenges in collective consent and tools and methods to enhance user-centered, transparent collective consent to help end users and organizations. This will be answered by these research questions.

- **Research Question 1** How is notice and consent implemented for genomic data sharing in companies and/or research, and what are open challenges?
- **Research Question 2** What are methods, tools, or frameworks can help address the challenges in digital collective consent?
- **Research Question 3** What components can enhance informational transparency in informed consent?

My thesis work focused on the identification of collective consent gaps and the characterization of methods to enhance transparency and usability in collective digital consent. Such gaps in collective consent included the tensions between collective autonomy and individual autonomy, the legal gray-area surrounding EU guidelines for genomic data, which do consider it collective data, and the legal requirements in practice, which often fail to uphold stated informational transparency requirements. These findings, combined with the small amount of existing literature on collective consent led me to combine interdisciplinary methods in an innovative context to study how privacy, usability, and collective consent interact. I used these to empirically identify the current challenges regarding informational transparency and user-relevancy for consent

in Direct to Consumer Genetic Testing Companies (DTCGTCs), characterize employee perceptions of IC methods to improve consent processes design and policy documentation, assess user needs and attitudes towards consent, and characterize user perceptions of engaging elements different consent mediums offered.

This work extends previous work on collective digital consent by adapting and testing methods from privacy [Shv+19; Niso9], requirements engineering [Moo03; GP21], HCI [Wal11], and governance [Joh+21a] in new contexts regarding genetic data and Small Medium Enterprise (SME) consent processes. This results in a new framework in which to implement future prototypes to address consent challenges. I developed new datasets throughout the different studies - beginning with DTC genetic testing company's privacy and consent policies, understanding user needs for consent, consent management, and consent design by different mediums.

4.2.3 Research Findings

4.2.3.1 Collective consent is overlooked in the status quo

In this section we discuss work related to RQ1.

Looking at the practices set by leading DTCGTCs there are no requirements to disclose collective risks and benefits despite legal-ethical guidelines in the EU which discuss those issues – so DTCGTCs fail to mention any possible collective issues. In addition, they also fail informational transparency metrics (e.g., completeness, direct language) and are not framed towards customers. In the EU, consent can be divided into legal consent for processing data and ethical consent to align with bioethical guidelines [Boa19]. Consent has been proposed as an ethical safeguard for autonomy regardless of legal bases for processing data, especially for sensitive health data [Sup23; Eur21]. However, in the case of DTCGTCs, they bypass any primary IC for sensitive data processing by using the legal basis that they are providing a contracted service and only ask for consent for secondary purposes (for research and sharing with external third parties). When looking at both the privacy policy and consent policies for secondary purposes, the text was often incomplete, vague, and too complex. The type and descriptions of risks and benefits varied greatly across the six different companies analyzed, from sharing only one general risk to sharing over 6 specific categories of risks. This is a key gap as privacy and consent policies offer a window into the internal data processing practices, which can both affect expert opinions on privacy and safety, as well as individual opinions on whether they will contract with a particular company or share data for secondary research purposes. The GDPR also sets high transparency requirements, which the companies may not meet through failing these assessments. From analyzing these industry leaders' non-transparent policies, their success in the face of disregarding informational transparency and shared risks and benefits may indicate a general trend towards lack of care regarding these issues for other DTCGTCs, even with high GDPR requirements. One example of shared risk and benefit information showed how it was framed to shield companies from any future lawsuits, not to reassure the reader that they would be protected. Internally, the companies likely have their own risk assessments and protocols to address different risks, but it is not shared. This contrasts with the goals of the GDPR's transparency requirements "A central consideration of the principle of transparency outlined in these

provisions is that the data subject should be able to determine in advance what the scope and consequences of the processing entails and that they should not be taken by surprise at a later point about the ways in which their personal data has been used. [...] data controllers should assess whether there are particular risks for natural persons involved in this type of processing which should be brought to the attention of data subjects. This can help to provide an overview of the types of processing that could have the highest impact on the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects concerning the protection of their personal data.” Sharing more information about existing protocols in a user-centered manner and including collective issues would be a step forward for informational transparency.

However, without clear guidelines, frameworks, and specific legal requirements, companies are unlikely to share such information. While EU regulations like the GDPR apply to all Member States, it also allows each Member State to enact it as they see fit. This is compounded by the conflicting rights, e.g., the *right to know* and the *right not to know* genomic information [CLS14], which may be used for positive health decisions or have negative effects on one’s mental state [Lau01; Mur+24]. Each country has specific laws surrounding confidentiality and privacy of patient information and exceptions, such as special genetic cases [VBD23], which can lead to confusion in patients about the scope of medical confidentiality [San+03]. While a guideline to suggest discussing information with family members or any type of informal collective notice and decision-making can be helpful, it would have to be tailored to each country and medical context, or else it might be more confusing than helpful. The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) acknowledges that there may be a collective data subject through genetic data [Boa19], which may identify genetic families all at once. However, due to the history of individual consent and autonomy, the implementation of collective consent and collective rights is still highly debated. The conflict of different individual’s rights is the most debated aspect, as how to balance different people’s rights can be difficult and without much precedent [Kur21; KMB22]. Regardless, DTCGTCs have been part of contentious cases where information was used unexpectedly by law enforcement to find serial killers [Wic19] or when public family trees reveal surprise relatives [Sch+24], and it is surprising that there is little useful information about these difficult situations. In the latter case, one study shared how participants suggested, “increased warnings pre-discovery and improved support post-discovery” [Sch+24] upon learning about their true genetic parents. On the reverse, it can be important to discuss information with relatives that could be useful, such as disease risk scores. There is literature that reveals that familial risk scores can be much more predictive than general population scores, even if the disease is not linked to a genetic cause [VSA18]. However, the researchers also caution against using family risk too liberally, as it may increase undue worry. In these cases, it would be helpful to refer to more testing and genetic counseling. It has been suggested before that DTCGTCs “have a responsibility to provide support” to their customers, and one of the ways is through information about genetic counseling [Mid+17]. This can make it difficult to offer specific guidelines on how to frame possible results and risks beyond directing customers to experts in genetic counseling. Though guidelines can be useful, there needs to be more research into this area to ensure useful, usable steps.

While guidelines for shared data are not well studied, how to communicate risks to highlight understanding has been a longstanding research goal. DTCGTCs have been criticized for its por-

trayal of possible harms, especially after data breaches have been revealed. For example, MyHeritage's privacy policies say, "while our reasonable security program is designed to manage data security risks and thus help prevent data security incidents and breaches, it cannot be assumed that the occurrence of any given incident or breach results from our failure to implement and maintain reasonable security." While legally the statement may be sound, it may meet customer expectations. A woman who was part of a class action lawsuit against MyHeritage due to a data breach [Nor18] stated that she would have not used the genetic services if she had known that the necessary precautions were not in place [Spi18].

Risks could be improved by addressing general fears, using graphics, and sharing more information about risk management. While consent policies may be framed to address participants using active language and with a clear subject (e.g. "you"), the risks are still varied in number and category across companies and do not usefully address concerns. For example, the company whose one stated risk of unexpected secondary findings would not address any of the top harms from a survey across 22 countries of attitudes towards genomic sharing [Mid+18]. The three most commonly feared potential harms from the study were: if friends or the government obtained information without consent and the use of the information for marketing purposes. Also, while it is difficult to convey probabilities for genetic risks, usage of simple pie charts or '100 person diagrams' was preferred by participants in a study, though the most desired option was access to a health professional for questions [Smi+16]. Directly addressing common concerns using simple graphs and pictograms with professional support may be useful for DTC genetic testing websites to share risks more concretely and assuage concerns. A solution from the EU is a Data Protection Impact Assessment [Par17a] for the purpose of delineating those risks and devising appropriate mitigation measures for those processing special categories of data (e.g. genetic data) at scale (Art. 35(3) GDPR). Not only is it good internal practice that enables organizations to manage the substantial data protection risks that arise from genetic data processing, but some of the information could be communicated to customers to increase transparency.

4.2.3.2 Interdisciplinary methods can enhance transparency and design for a better IC process

In this section we discuss findings from RQ2.

We had identified a lack of informational transparency and user-centered framing as two of the challenges regarding collective digital consent and consent for genomic data sharing in general. Previous studies have analyzed how health data sharing privacy policies are opaque and critiqued consent processes for being confusing and not protecting participants' rights. While we used Contextual Integrity (CI) for analyzing existing policies and it has been suggested for use in auditing, it had not yet been tested. I adapted the CI method for developing better notice (via privacy policies) in a welfare tech SME and studied employee perceptions about usefulness and ease of use. In addition, I also use the RE design process to develop consent process Business Process Model and Notations (BPMNs) to address transparency, privacy, and consent requirements for specific collective consent use cases with the same SME. To address the issue of consent design I also surveyed potential users about their consent needs and tested user

perception towards different mediums of consent (comic, video, text, infographic, newsletter). The study with the general public reveals several archetypes that could be used to characterize the different needs of the population, as well as the importance of specific elements across different mediums, like graphic elements or stepwise design. The user studies within the SME revealed that both methods were useful for understanding, communication, and validation of requirements, and were promising tools that employees would potentially adopt for future implementation and study.

Though many factors likely impact employee perceptions of the CI and BPMN methods, I identified how it was useful for understanding, analysis, and communication as well as easy to use. Both the CI and BPMN were perceived to be well accepted through a questionnaire and semistructured interviews. These studies used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), assessing employee perceptions of usefulness and ease of use to predict usage and acceptance of the technology. Therefore, it can be inferred that CI and consent BPMNs would be acceptable to use under the TAM. While no previous studies have been done in the same context, I look at similar studies to compare results. TAM and its extensions have been used in consent for health data sharing and related fields [ZLL22; Li20; Den+18]. One study investigated patient perceptions of different consent methods and found no functional (Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU)) or practical (perceived workload) differences between the three methods [Wil+19]. Another study regarding user acceptance of mobile medical platforms used the TAM and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) with three additional three patient-centered factors: perceived convenience, perceived credibility, and perceived privacy risk, and found that perceived privacy risk, perceived credibility, and PEOU predicted the PU of such platforms [Wan+22]. Another study focused on IC providers and tested the usefulness of an IC document tool for project managers [Swa+22]. They used PU and PEOU from TAM in addition to the System Usability Scale for usability and perceived utility. They found that project managers generally thought the tool was useful, with room for improvement in compliance or usability. While not in consent, another study looked at nurses' acceptance of electronic medical records using TAM and showed increased PU with the electronic medical records [Ald+18] but that PEOU was greatly affected by the self-efficacy of the user, support from the top management, and information quality. These results show that largely the core TAM theory can reveal useful information, while extensions can add more context. Similar to our studies, we also identified key PU elements and elicited improvements and sociotechnical concerns from the interview data. This suggests a promising start to using CI and BPMNs in SMEs.

While our work included core TAM elements, it may be interesting to evaluate extensions, such as the ones described above using perceived convenience, or to adapt findings of previous studies into new TAM extensions (e.g., support from top management). This is complex because many TAM extensions exist, and none fit the exact context but may have to be adapted. These changes to methodology may have to be validated themselves and then used to evaluate users. It may offer insights into how the leadership's attitudes affect the implementation of a technology. While the interviewees in the studies included some members of leadership like the Chief Governance, Risk and Compliance Officer (CGRCO) and the head of DevOps, it would seek them out as a demographic. While individual-level acceptance is important, the implementation of these tools at higher levels of leadership and governance can set best practices and the com-

pany culture. For example, BPMNs can be implemented in many ways, and a BPMN Governance system with executive sponsorship [VRVSS14] may ensure enough resources to successfully implement a new system.

Then the consent prototype phase, archetypes, and engaging consent medium design elements could be incorporated to meet the user's goals. To help define the goals from user interviews, we took inspiration from personas to better understand different users and needs and design fitting systems [PG03]. Research into personas for health focused on specific health-related needs like dementia [Sal+22; HTD13] or disabilities [Jim+98] but not on the overall IC process to strategically create information disclosures for different sub-demographics. The general profiles of archetypes revealed from user data showed how different demographics could receive contextualized information and concrete examples relevant to their specific needs (e.g., Fully Informed, Trust Seeking), rather than one-size-fits-all terms. More personalized systems have been the subject of much debate, and CI could also follow suit. More research is needed [Pas+08] to determine the actual benefit of tailoring information to the styles against the increased costs of its creation and implementation. Using resources wisely was also the goal of investigating the most influential design elements of the mediums (comic, infographic, text, newsletter, and video) as well as the engaging elements that attracted their attention. That way, different mediums and elements could be used to target different IC goals. Structure, readability, and a step-by-step design were the top most engaging elements. See the relevant paper [Doa+24] for an overview of positive and negative elements from each medium. The top-ranking medium, the infographic, ranked highly because it helped understanding, time-saving, and interest through the use of numbered lists, icons, bold headings, and graphic elements.

4.2.3.3 Condensed, graphical, and contextually appropriate IC and consent management

Here we address work related to answering RQ3.

Consent takes on a pivotal role in EU regulations such as the GDPR with requirements for informational transparency but there are implementation can be challenging. IC requires user-centric design elements in consent to help achieve the general principle of transparency which encompasses the “quality, accessibility and comprehensibility of the information” [Par18]. Hence the obligation contained in the GDPR for privacy and consent notices to be purposely *designed* as effective tools to adequately inform the intended audience: “transparency by design” [RL20a]. However, decades of research in the biomedical domain show that study participants' consent can rarely be deemed actually informed [ML14], often due to the complexity of language [Nie+18] and lack of health literacy [McB+10], as well as to the lack of data literacy of the individuals [D'17].

Engaging individuals in a user-friendly consent experience is thus fundamental to enable them to meaningfully and freely make decisions with a sense of satisfaction [Fer+16] and agency. Improving the readability and comprehensibility of consent notices is one aspect of this, but research is also being done to explore visual communication techniques. Current research often focuses on the effect of multimedia on understanding [Kra+17; PLJ12], which can have a varied effect based on different studies. Multimedia also spans many formats, and most studies reviewed for their effect on understanding compared 2-3 different formats [PLJ12]. The Article 29 Working

Party also refers to visual design means, such as “*cartoons, infographics, flowcharts*”, to enhance the comprehensibility of information, and specifically to “*comics/cartoons, pictograms, animations*” [Par18]. However, they do not offer further guidance about what mediums to use and for what purpose (e.g., how one might prioritize skimming while another might be better for complex information). Therefore, I experimented with five different mediums of consent in one study, building on previous studies researching the use of a comic [Ste17; BR21], video [Ant+17], infographic and illustrated text [Wan+19], and plain text as a control [SGB17].

Traditionally, engagement studies in biomedical consent refer to patient engagement with the research or biomedical process. Such engagement refers to participants interacting with the results of a study, updating information, or changing consent [Coo+13] [IK21] [Haa+21b]. However, we are interested in participant motivations to give their initial attention, consume the information, and make continued decisions about their consent in a conventionally tedious process, taking inspiration from research about the attention economy [Sim+71; CFM15]. Can consent forms be interesting and attention grabbing?

First, German adults were asked about their experiences with consent and their goals. The majority of the participants clearly indicated that they spent only as long as necessary to understand, however almost half of them also mentioned that it should not take longer than one minute. That said, time spent on consent seems to be contextual and depends on the type of data and the entity asking to share such data.

The main goal was also impacted by different emotions, document criteria, and engaging elements. The best to worst ranked mediums were the infographic, video, text, newsletter, and comic. Within those, elements that allow the visual prioritization of certain content over others, like headings, bullet points, and highlights (i.e., “surface-level cues” [Wal11]) that allow individuals to skim the document effectively and discern at first sight the most important information. Based on the ranking of engaging elements, participants preferred step-by-step documents (e.g., linear numbered lists with clear headings), instead of open or story-based formats. Structure, readability, and step-by-step elements are the top three engaging elements and could be easily integrated in most mediums. While our study only designed the infographic using four of the top engaging elements (i.e., structure, readability, color, and step-by-step element), other mediums like the text could also employ color and step-by-step elements instead of the open-format element. Importantly, context is key. While the comic had positives regarding understanding and interest, it elicited feelings of disapproval and was deemed too “unserious” for health consent for adults, and would be better suited for children, the elderly, or non-native German speakers. On the other hand, the infographic performed the best due to enhancing understanding, saving time, and being interesting while eliciting feelings of anticipation, interest, acceptance, and surprise. Contrary to [Wan+19], which surveyed adult students, comics were not appropriate for the majority of German adults surveyed, who thought it would suit children, the elderly, or non-native German speakers better. Comics have been useful for communicating medical information with children [GW+15], while another found that comics for medical IC especially increased understanding for children with lower comprehension scores [FADD21]. Understanding was one of the positive affordances given by comics and can help give insight into how strong negative emotions and bad audience fit can override any benefits within a medium. Comics have been a case study for cultural stigmas [Lop06], and while they may have been

suitable for an indigenous population [BR21], some researchers are pushing for more serious comics (similar to serious games for education) [LH18] and the comic co-design process itself as a research practice [Tav+23]. It is important to test and co-design consent with the intended audience, otherwise a negative audience fit and context may be more harmful than plain text consent.

Another key finding was how many participants wanted a centralized consent management platform in order to be able to see, manage, and track the consent they have been given. A digital management platform via a mobile app or website was the most desired way to manage their decisions, and participants also said they would like to revoke consent this way. This indicates that individual informational transparency has limits. While informational transparency can address better engagement and understanding of specific ICs, over a lifetime they become unmanageable. Due to the many different consent management platforms and lack of centralization, other researchers have focused on interoperability and standardization. Existing browser-based consent mechanisms range from Do Not Track (DNT), Global Privacy Control (GPC), Advanced Data Protection Control (ADPC), and more [Hum+22] while consent apps and platforms may use custom or proprietary tools. Dynamic consent management platforms, even if not centralized, can be beneficial to building trust, carrying out IC over time, and providing feedback to participants [Rau+20; Haa+21b; Haa+24; Mas+22]. Building upon this, the previous archetype layering methods could incorporate archetypes of general profiles to be tailored for different goals. Users of different ages may prefer different mediums, such as comics for younger audiences and videos for older audiences, or users with technical expertise could choose to see jargon.

Figure 4.1 shows a diagram of an iterative consent process from legal-ethical requirements to consent requirements and modeling to the consent prototype and evaluation, then repeating. The methods and main findings from the thesis that address different steps are shown below the different consent process steps as they apply.

4.2.4 Research Analysis and future work

Building a legal-ethical, usable framework for collective consent for genomic data sharing in the EU contributes to the LeADS project by directly addressing the interdisciplinary needs, incorporating law, ethics, and computer science (privacy, RE, HCI). This framework can help to build a collective consent system to address the true complexity of shared data. This requires understanding how law works and examining legal documents, and can be challenging without a legal background. Without being well versed in the GDPR, its recitals, court rulings, and guidelines from the EDPB and European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPB). This has made it possible for me to identify gaps and solutions from different disciplines, apply methods across disciplines, and combine solutions in a practical context with one of the LeADS industry partners, Tellu. This is an area with very little existing research, but the implications for individual and collective autonomy and rights are far-reaching. It would be prudent to address this issue before it escalates into a problem deemed too troublesome to solve.

Beyond using it for collective consent, this research used practical methods for analyzing and improving privacy policies, consent policies, and consent documents that can be helpful for

Figure 4.1: A diagram of an iterative consent process and the methods and main findings from the thesis that address different steps of the consent process. Future work should evaluate the framework and continue iterating on the process.

practitioners. Especially for organizations who struggle with transparency, who may want guidance on how to frame the information for end-users, or who deal with complex data flows, the methods used across this scientific report can help to improve internal privacy policies and consent processes and communicate consent to users using engaging design to address their needs. It can help to differentiate their products from the market and stay on the cutting edge of legal-ethical compliance and privacy measures. However, the user studies were in-depth qualitative studies investigating specific contexts and participants, so findings may not necessarily be extrapolated to other populations. While the findings were useful for detailed insights into user perspectives, it would be important to expand the sample size and context in for future works to be more generalizable. It may also be interesting to replicate in other specific use cases, as the context was found to be highly important for the user studies, with employees' perceptions tied to their day-to-day responsibilities and the German adults' perceptions of comics heavily influencing the ranking contrary to more objective uses the medium provided. While exact replications are unlikely in the field, any extensions using this work should be repeated across different populations and more diverse demographics to increase reliability and generalizability. Since this work is interdisciplinary even beyond law and computer science, another challenge was to adequately combine methods and findings from different computer science disciplines, like HCI with RE. Working across disciplines inevitably leads to a trade-off between depth and breadth, and the challenge is to combine them for the right level of abstraction to contribute

quality work. Since collective consent is a complex issue with little existing research, it can be useful to have pilot studies and such an overarching framework to continue adding to.

One of the most important areas of future work is the effect of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), which will build upon the GDPR and apply to health data. At the time of writing, the final draft of the EHDS has not been shared and the current draft (as of April 2024) uses “opt-out” mechanisms for primary and secondary uses of health data. However, it contradicts the GDPR’s requirements for explicit, specific, and affirmative consent. If Member States have already implemented GDPR compliant consent, then they may have to change existing infrastructure. In addition, there are vague roles for data intermediaries (Health Data Access Bodies, HDABs) to manage the data sharing, but they do not have any transparency requirements (e.g., notification to the data subject that data is being used) in the current draft. These HDABs may also share data with private companies for a fee, which may require an economic assessment to understand the possible impacts. Overall, This may lead to decreased autonomy and transparency in the EU unless carefully considered and implemented.

4.2.5 Conclusion

Using interdisciplinary methods, this work combined user studies, literature reviews, and privacy policy analysis for both quantitative and qualitative data to demonstrate the usefulness of BPMNs and contextual integrity methods to investigate current challenges in legal-ethical consent in the EU and DTC genetic testing company practices, improve business privacy practices, and categorize consent needs and preferences in the general population. Together, this builds the foundation for more user-centered collective consent that addresses end-user needs as well as business needs, aligned with EU regulations and ethical standards for health data. These results offer a framework for collective consent across multiple angles – ethical, legal, governance/business, and end-users for better collective consent systems. Considering how there are only speculations [Pri+20a] and no existing research on how to build a digital collective consent, this is an important step forward into a more formalized system for collective decision making and consent for all people involved. In this way, the shared risks and benefits of health data can be holistically considered by all relevant parties and informed decisions can be recorded.

These results provide compelling evidence to support the idea that more informationally transparent, user-centered consent is possible for collective data in the EU. Studying collective consent remains critical to the EU data sharing economy, individual autonomy, and collective privacy, and helping to protect sensitive data while also making it as open as possible for people to benefit from the genomic data.

4.3 Balancing Bias Mitigation and Data Protection in AI-Driven Healthcare: Insights from the European Health Data Space, AI Act and GDPR

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4.3.1 Executive summary

This research investigates the intricate challenge of balancing bias mitigation and data protection in AI-driven healthcare within the European Union's regulatory landscape. The study focuses on three pivotal frameworks: the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the AI Act, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Our findings reveal that while the EHDS aims to facilitate AI development through secondary use of health data, emphasizing anonymization and pseudonymization, the AI Act permits processing of sensitive data for bias detection and mitigation in AI systems. These approaches potentially conflict with GDPR's strict rules on processing sensitive health data. The research uncovers how anonymization and pseudonymization requirements in the EHDS may impede the creation of representative datasets crucial for bias mitigation in AI. Furthermore, it highlights how the AI Act's provisions for data re-identification in bias detection contradict GDPR's data protection mandates. This study contributes significantly to the fields of data science, law, and policymaking by illuminating the tensions between innovation, equity, and data protection in healthcare AI. It provides critical insights into the interactions between these regulatory frameworks and their implications for developing unbiased, innovative AI technologies in healthcare while maintaining robust data protection standards. The research is particularly relevant for policymakers, legal experts, and data scientists working at the intersection of AI, healthcare, and data protection, offering a solid foundation for future regulatory refinements and technological developments in this rapidly evolving field.

4.3.2 Introduction

AI use in healthcare has the potential to revolutionize the field by improving access to treatment and resources, as well as enabling more efficient and personalized care.[Alo+23; Joh+21b] AI can aid in diagnosis and precision medicine[Kri+17] and has various applications in medical imaging[Cop+21], drug discovery[Oli19], disease prediction[lqb+21; Laa+22] and telemedicine[Fer22]. However, the use of AI in healthcare also raises legal and ethical concerns, such as issues related to data protection, privacy and accountability, which require appropriate regulatory frameworks to address.[CSM18] A key question in this regard is whether AI can increase fairness in traditionally underrepresented communities or if it will worsen existing disparities in healthcare systems.[Eur22] In 2020, the Commission stated in their Communication titled "A European Strategy for Data" that: "The value of data lies in its use and re-use. Currently, there is not enough data available for innovative re-use, including for the development of artificial intelligence." [Noad] The European Health Data Space ("EHDS") is at the forefront of this challenge, as a visionary initiative aimed at facilitating the secondary use of health data to drive innovation. The

AI Act, a legislative framework designed to regulate artificial intelligence, including the processing of special categories of personal data, establishes standards for transparency, accountability, and oversight, ensuring that AI technologies are developed and deployed in a manner that respects fundamental rights and ethical principles.[Noaf] Concurrently, the AI Act introduces provisions to detect and correct biases in high-risk AI systems. This paper will explore the balance between bias mitigation and data protection in developing AI technologies for healthcare under the legal frameworks of the European Union (EU), namely the EHDS, GDPR, and AI Act. It will begin with a background on the regulatory framework and an overview regarding AI technologies. Later on, general information regarding the EHDS will be provided. Following this, bias in AI systems and real-life examples of bias will be explained. The discussion will then cover data handling in the EHDS, including anonymization and pseudonymization, and will examine the AI Act's provisions for bias detection and correction. This will lead to an analysis of conflicts between the frameworks of the EHDS, the AI Act, and the GDPR. Finally, the study will conclude with reflections on the impact of these conflicts on developing unbiased medical AI, providing insights into navigating these regulatory challenges.

4.3.2.1 Objectives and Scope

This research aims to examine the intricate balance between bias mitigation and data protection in AI-driven healthcare within the European Union's regulatory framework. The study focuses on analyzing the interactions between the EHDS, the AI Act and the GDPR. The objective is to understand how these frameworks address bias in AI technologies used in healthcare while maintaining data protection standards. The primary research question this work answers is: "How do the proposed EHDS and the AI Act address and provide solutions for mitigating bias in AI technologies used in healthcare, and how do these frameworks interact with GDPR?" This question incorporates the challenges of creating representative datasets for AI training while adhering to data protection regulations, and the potential conflicts between bias detection methods and data protection mandates.

4.3.2.2 State of the Art

The intersection of data science, law and policymaking in healthcare AI is a rapidly evolving field. Key literature in this area includes studies on bias in AI systems, such as the work by Ntoutsis et al.[Nto+20] on bias in data-driven AI systems, and Parikh et al.[PTN19] on addressing bias in AI in healthcare. The legal and ethical challenges of AI in healthcare have been explored by researchers like Gerke et al.[GMC20], highlighting the need for appropriate regulatory frameworks. In the realm of European regulation, the proposals for the EHDS and the AI Act represent significant developments. These have been analysed by scholars such as Marelli et al.[Mar+23], who discuss the implications of the EHDS for health data governance. The interaction between these new frameworks and the existing GDPR has been explored by researchers like Shabani and Yilmaz[SY22], who examine the interplay between regulatory frameworks in the secondary use of health data. This research fills a gap in the existing literature by providing a comprehensive analysis of how the EHDS and AI Act specifically address bias mitigation in healthcare

AI, and how their provisions interact with the GDPR's data protection requirements. This work contributes new knowledge by identifying potential conflicts between these regulatory frameworks and proposing ways to navigate these challenges in the development of unbiased and privacy-preserving AI technologies in healthcare.

4.3.2.3 Methodology

This research employs a qualitative, comparative analysis methodology to examine the regulatory frameworks of the EHDS, the AI Act and the GDPR. The approach was chosen for its effectiveness in analysing complex legal and policy documents. Primary data consists of official EU documents, including proposed regulations for the EHDS and the AI Act, and the existing GDPR text. Secondary sources include academic literature, policy briefs and expert commentaries. Data was collected through official EU sources and comprehensive database searches. The analysis involved a systematic review of documents, focusing on provisions related to secondary use of health data, bias mitigation in AI systems and data protection requirements. An interdisciplinary lens integrating perspectives from data science, law and healthcare policy was applied throughout.

4.3.2.4 Regulatory Background

The central role of data in the development of AI technologies brings significant attention to data protection legislation. Given the focus of this study on EU law, the GDPR, which came into force in 2018, serves as the primary legislative instrument governing data protection.^[PEU16] Although the GDPR was enacted relatively recently, rapid technological advancements and the growing volume of data have necessitated updates. The European Commission's Communication outlined their vision: "the EU should combine fit-for-purpose legislation and governance to ensure the availability of data, with investments in standards, tools, and infrastructures as well as competences for handling data."^[Noad] The EHDS, introduced in May 2022 as part of the EU's data strategy and the first of planned data spaces, aims to foster a genuine single market for electronic health record systems, relevant medical devices, and high-risk AI systems. To achieve this goal, the EHDS proposes new rules for various types of data processing.^[Par24] It is important to mention that on the 15th of March 2024, the European Parliament and the Council of the EU reached an agreement on the proposal of the EHDS.^[Noah] While the general outline of the EHDS remains unchanged, critical amendments have been introduced, such as the 'opt-out' mechanism, which allows individuals to prohibit the use of their data for secondary purposes. This study is based on the text published on March 18, 2024; however, it must be noted that this text is not the final version of the regulation, as it has not yet passed the jurist-linguistic review. Additionally, when referring to general facts such as the purposes of the regulation, the older text is occasionally referenced. In parallel to developments in the EHDS framework, the EU has also introduced the AI Act, which proposes a framework for regulating AI development and application within the EU. Its objectives are to establish uniform internal market rules for AI development, market placement, and usage; promote human-centric and trustworthy AI; and ensure high levels of health, safety, and fundamental rights protection.^[Gil24] Furthermore, the

AI Act aims to regulate AI systems based on risk levels and impose specific obligations.[Noab] Given that the EHDS references the AI Act within its provisions, and both must align with the GDPR, a thorough analysis must consider all three acts together, particularly in terms of bias mitigation.

4.3.2.5 Overview of AI Technologies

Before delving into the discussion on AI and bias in healthcare, it is crucial to establish a clear understanding of these concepts to pinpoint the core issues. The definition of an AI system in the AI Act has sparked debates for being too broad[Noag], and throughout its evolution, the definition has undergone amendments.[Bob24] The AI Act, Article 3(1), describes an AI system as: “‘artificial intelligence system’ (AI system) means software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I and can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with”.[Noap] On the other hand, in the literature, Davenport and Kalakota argue that AI technologies encompass a variety of techniques rather than a single technology. Machine learning, a foundational aspect of artificial intelligence, involves using statistical methods to construct models from data, enabling these models to ‘learn’ through iterative training processes.[DK19] Deep learning, a subset of machine learning, employs artificial neural networks with multiple layers to discern intricate patterns within large datasets.[GMC20] In this study, the term ‘AI’ is used as an umbrella term to encompass these complex systems. Occasional reference is made to ‘machine learning models’ specifically when discussing details such as the importance of the training dataset used.

4.3.3 EHDS – Objectives and Key Components

The EHDS outlines two primary objectives: firstly, to enhance citizens’ access to and control over their electronic health records (EHR) across the EU, and secondly, to promote the responsible secondary use of health data for purposes such as innovation, research, and policymaking (Recital 1, EHDS). As the first of the European domain-specific data spaces, the EHDS represents a significant milestone poised to transform healthcare governance within the EU and potentially set a new global standard.[Mar+23] EHDS provisions include aspects related to both primary and secondary use of electronic health data. The primary use of electronic health data aims to integrate EHR products and other medical software, potentially overcoming obstacles related to cross-border health data sharing. The emphasis of this study, however, is on the provisions pertaining to secondary use, which will be explained in more detail in the following sections of the paper. The EHDS has also been proposed to facilitate the utilization of health data for developing AI technologies within its secondary use framework. According to the EHDS Proposal, ‘secondary use’ refers to the processing of electronic health data, which includes both personal health data originally collected for primary use and data specifically gathered for secondary purposes.[Noah] As a result, the Proposal does not provide a detailed explanation of ‘secondary use,’ but rather describes it in general terms and refers to the purposes listed in the fourth chapter of the Proposal.[Noah] The secondary use framework introduced as a system

through which health data would be accessed by public, private, not-for-profit entities, as well as individual researchers, "for research, innovation, policy making, educational activities, patient safety, regulatory activities or personalised medicine, in line with the purposes set out in this Regulation," as stated in Recital 41 of the EHDS. Recital 41 of the EHDS also emphasizes the importance of using health data to develop AI systems that support scientific research, innovation, and the production of goods and services for the health or care sectors. This includes activities such as training AI algorithms to enhance the health and care of individuals. Excerpts from the EHDS indicate that the initiative aims to establish a unified market for electronic health records and AI systems within the EU. It does so by introducing a secondary use framework that facilitates broad access to health data for various parties involved.[Noah] While the EHDS focuses on facilitating the secondary use of health data for AI technologies, it also introduces distinct roles for actors involved in this framework. Actors within the secondary use framework must be mentioned as the EHDS introduces different roles compared to the GDPR. 'Health Data holder' described in a broad manner as, any individual or organization in the health or care sector, or conducting related research, as well as Union institutions which have the right or obligation to manage data under relevant laws.[Noah] 'Health Data user' on the other hand defined as: "a natural or legal person, including Union institutions, bodies or agencies, which has been granted lawful access to electronic health data for secondary use pursuant to a data permit, data request or an access approval by an authorized participant in Health Data@EU".[Noah] Moreover, there will be another actor which will act as an intermediary between data holders and users called 'health data access body' (HDAB) which will be established by Member States. Without providing a definition of this authority, the EHDS sets forth tasks and obligations of HDABs in the fourth chapter.[Noah] These authorities portrayed as a supervising body which will oversee applications of secondary use framework. The details of data handling under the secondary use framework are explained in the fourth section of this study.

4.3.4 Bias in AI Systems

Bias, as a general term, is not a recent problem but is "as old as human civilization." Human biases have been studied across various disciplines, including psychology and law.[Nto+20] This inherent human characteristic has inadvertently been conveyed into developed technologies and has been detected and studied extensively from the early stages. In 1996, Friedman and Nissenbaum defined biased computer systems as "computer systems that systematically and unfairly discriminate against certain individuals or groups of individuals in favor of others." [FN96] The real importance of biases in AI systems lies in a fundamental issue: AI development heavily relies on data produced by humans. Consequently, any biases present in humans infiltrate our systems and are exacerbated within complex sociotechnical frameworks. This can lead algorithms to perpetuate or exacerbate existing inequalities or discriminatory practices.[Nto+20] Bölükbaşı et al. demonstrated a clear example of this when they found that their natural language model algorithm, trained on Google News articles, exhibited sexist traits.[Bol+16]

4.3.4.1 Examples of Bias in Healthcare AI

Even though there is an abundance of studies conducted on bias, fairness and disparities of AI technologies, a commonly agreed upon definition of bias cannot be extracted from those studies.[Nor+21] Mittermaier et al.'s description of bias follows "a difference in performance between subgroups for a predictive task" can be used to understand what the term encapsulate as a broad definition.[MRK23] Bias distinguished into two by Parikh et al., namely societal and statistical bias[PTN19] and statistical bias classified as "data-driven bias" and "algorithmic bias" into two subcategories.[Nor+21] Data-driven bias refers to the bias in the training data of algorithmic models. This could appear either in data limitations or data gaps which would mean that data of some societal groups were omitted in the training data. In another saying, data-driven bias occurs in the data collection stage and thus representativeness of data cannot be provided. Similar to Parikh et al.'s distinction, Vokinger et al. make the differentiation based on the phases of the development of machine learning models. First, they describe these stages as data collection and data preparation, model development and evaluation and the deployment of the model into a clinical practice. Then they called the bias in the data collection and data preparation stage as 'sampling bias' when the data used to train the AI is not representative as the population which the AI system intended to be used. They showcased a example to the sampling bias when the model trained to detect a type of a skin cancer on people with white skin thus not having the desired results when it is used on people who has a darker skin tone. This led to a result that no matter how advanced the technology got it does not perform fully when it is used on people with darker skin tone.[AS18] Similarly, Parikh et al. mentioned the Framingham Study risk factor which has been used widely to calculate the risk for cardiovascular disease, yet the original study conducted on mostly non-Hispanic white people thus when applied on different groups of the society it didn't give the optimal results. In the words of Ntoutsis et al. "mis-represented groups coincide with social groups against which there already exists social bias such as prejudice or discrimination".[Nto+20] Underrepresenting a group of society while training an algorithm cause unfair and/or inaccurate consequences for that group. These outcomes were seen frequently as racial bias and gender bias as multiple studies prove. Norori et al. mention a skin cancer diagnosis algorithm perform with a %50 accuracy rate when tested on black people due to its training dataset was contain images of black people only %5 to %10.[Nor+21] Furthermore, another example given by them shows gender bias and how it can appear in real life. An algorithm which claims to predict heart attracts before 5 years, misdiagnosed women in high numbers. The reason of this outcome has been found that the algorithm was trained mainly on data samples of men.[Nor+21] Panch et al. identified the term algorithmic bias in healthcare as "the instances when the application of an algorithm compounds existing inequities in socioeconomic status, race, ethnic background, religion, gender, disability or sexual orientation to amplify them and adversely impact inequities in health systems".[PMA]

4.3.5 Data Handling under EHDS's Secondary Use Framework

The Proposal explains the secondary use framework in its fourth chapter, starting with 'minimum categories of electronic health data' which will be collected under secondary use frame-

work. The Proposal's description of 'health data' which will be used under secondary use framework encompasses a wide array of data. These categories include data directly connected to health, such as electronic health records and genomic data, as well as data indirectly related to health, such as information on insurance status, professional status, education, lifestyle, wellness, and behaviour.[Noah] Article 33 also dictates that health data holders will make the data available under this framework. This obligation to provide the data is detailed more in Article 41 of the EHDS. This article also obligates data holders to deliver a general description of their dataset to HDABs. (Article 41(2))[Noah] The process will start with a data permit application by data users to HDABs and their application will be evaluated based on the criteria listed in the Articles 34-36. One of the conditions to obtain data permit is to use data only with purposes listed in Article 34. In this article, subparagraph (e)(ii) mentions using the data for "training, testing and evaluating of algorithms, including in medical devices, in-vitro diagnostic medical devices, AI systems and digital health applications" together with other possible purposes were itemized.[Noah] After the data permit is granted by a HDAB, Article 44(2) states "The health data access bodies shall provide electronic health data in an anonymised format, where the purpose of processing by the health data user can be achieved with such data, taking into account the information provided by the health data user." [Noah] However, the following subparagraph introduces an important exception in this regard. Article 44(3) stipulates "Where the health data user has sufficiently demonstrated that the purpose of processing cannot be achieved with anonymised data in line with Article 46(1), point (c), the health data access bodies shall provide access to electronic health data in pseudonymised format. The information necessary to reverse the pseudonymisation shall be available only to the health data access body or a body that acts as a trusted third party in accordance with national law." [Noah] These two articles indicate that data will be open to access as anonymised format as a rule and pseudonymised as an exception within the secondary use framework. Following the setup of the system, how data users will access data is regulated in section 5 of chapter IV. According to Article 55, HDABs will inform the data users about the available datasets and their characteristics through a metadata catalogue.[Noah] Additionally, one of the new concepts introduced within the March 2024 version of the EHDS is the 'opt-out' mechanism from secondary use. Article 35f of the agreement text states that, "Natural persons shall have the right to opt-out at any time and without stating reasons from the processing of personal electronic health data relating to them for secondary use under this Regulation." [Noah]

4.3.5.1 Bias Under the Secondary Use Framework of the EHDS

The term 'bias' is mentioned only in Article 56, titled "Data Quality and Utility Label," of the EHDS. In short, the article regulates a list of criteria that health data holders must follow within datasets made available by HDABs to maintain data quality and utility. Article 56(3)(f) stipulates that elements regarding the examination of biases will be included in this data quality label.[Noah] This provision indicates that examining for biases will be a part of data quality and utility labelling. Additionally, subparagraph (d) indicates another element which will be listed in this labelling process: "... representation of multi-disciplinary electronic health data, representativity of population sampled, average timeframe in which a natural person appears in

a dataset” (*emphasis added*).[\[Noah\]](#) The last subparagraph of the same article gives authority to the Commission to issue further technical specifications to establish data quality and utility, and states that this authority will be enacted in coordination with the AI Act as indicated below. “The Commission shall, by means of implementing acts, set out the visual characteristics and technical specifications of the data quality and utility label, based on the elements referred to in paragraph 3. Those implementing acts shall be adopted in accordance with the examination procedure referred to in Article 68(2). Those implementing acts shall take into account the requirements in Article 10 of Regulation [...] [AI Act COM/2021/206 final] and any adopted common specifications or harmonised standards supporting those requirements, where applicable.”[\[Noah\]](#) The next section will examine the AI Act and its relevant provisions.

4.3.6 The AI Act and Bias Mitigation

According to Article 10 of the AI Act, there are a number of criteria which training datasets for high-risk AI systems must meet. The subparagraphs of Article 10(2) are as follows: “(f) examination in view of possible biases; (g) the identification of any possible data gaps or shortcomings, and how those gaps and shortcomings can be addressed.” [\[Noap\]](#) In addition to this article, Article 10(5) further details the conditions that must be followed when examining datasets in accordance with Article 10(2)(f) and (g). Article 10(5) follows as: “To the extent that it is strictly necessary for the purposes of ensuring bias monitoring, detection and correction in relation to the high-risk AI systems, the providers of such systems may process special categories of personal data referred to in Article 9(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, Article 10 of Directive (EU) 2016/680 and Article 10(1) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725, subject to appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons, including technical limitations on the re-use and use of state-of-the-art security and privacy-preserving measures, such as pseudonymisation, or encryption where anonymisation may significantly affect the purpose pursued.”[\[Noap\]](#) These stringent requirements for bias examination and correction in high-risk AI systems under the AI Act necessitate a thorough evaluation alongside the EHDS provisions to ensure comprehensive data quality and utility standards. Given that this process involves the handling of sensitive data, it is imperative to incorporate the GDPR into this evaluative framework.

4.3.7 Research Findings and Discussion

AI technologies are fundamentally shaped by the quality and composition of the datasets they rely on during their training phase. Bias can manifest in these datasets in various forms, including misrepresentation or underrepresentation. Wojcik highlights these issues, stating, “Underrepresentation of minorities in datasets leads to inaccuracies and produces biased outcomes.”[\[W6\]](#) This underlines the critical impact of dataset composition on the accuracy and fairness of AI outputs. Diversifying the dataset is commonly recommended to mitigate bias.[\[MSP19\]](#) However, this requires having detailed information about the data that makes up the dataset. Nevertheless, datasets formed within the scope of the EHDS will consist of anonymized data. The EHDS establishes a secondary use framework primarily based on anonymized data, with pseudonymized data being an exception. This distinction significantly impacts data protection regulations. Ac-

According to Recital 26 of the GDPR, anonymized data are not subject to data protection legislation, whereas pseudonymized data are. In this context, the distinction lies in the level of identifiability retained within the data. Anonymized data have been irreversibly transformed so that individuals cannot be identified directly or indirectly. Therefore, they fall outside the scope of data protection laws. Conversely, pseudonymized data still allow for re-identification through additional information held separately. As such, they are considered personal data under the GDPR and require compliance with data protection regulations. This leads to two main problems. First, as explained above, it is necessary to have indicators (labels) and information about the data in order to detect and reduce bias in the dataset. Having more indicators will facilitate the process of reducing bias; however, it also increases the risk of re-identification.[[JJB12](#)] This heightened risk is particularly concerning under EHDS, which is not designed to manage such instances.[[SY22](#)] Secondly, it is open to discussion whether the safeguards introduced by the AI Act would be sufficient to maintain the protection of personal health data. Vidalis highlights the challenges in this area, stating, “Nevertheless, in the context of big data, we must admit that neither pseudonymization nor even anonymization at the source of data secures protection of the data subjects. Indeed, the massive amount of multifactorial information from multiple sources allows for the development of specific algorithms that could potentially identify individuals, even when dealing with these data categories through methodologies such as ‘deep mining’ analysis, where AI plays a critical role.”[[Vid21](#)]

4.3.8 Conclusions

The European Health Data Space’s secondary use framework presents a promising avenue for advancing scientific research, innovation and the development of goods and services in the healthcare sector, particularly in the realm of AI algorithm training. However, this technological progress is not without its challenges, chief among them being the mitigation of bias in AI systems. The critical nature of addressing bias cannot be overstated, given its potential to significantly impact societal well-being and exacerbate existing healthcare disparities. This research emphasises the importance of adhering to GDPR principles, especially when handling sensitive health data or in scenarios with elevated re-identification risks. Such adherence is not merely a matter of regulatory compliance; it is fundamental to ensuring the responsible use of data in AI development. The intricate balance between promoting innovation and safeguarding data protection rights emerges as a key consideration for policymakers and AI developers alike. Moving forward, it is imperative that the implementation of the EHDS and the AI Act be carried out in a manner that harmonizes with the GDPR’s robust data protection framework. This approach will not only foster trust in AI-driven healthcare innovations but also set a global standard for responsible AI development in sensitive domains. Future research should focus on developing practical guidelines for navigating these complex regulatory intersections, ensuring that the promise of AI in healthcare is realized without compromising on data protection and ethical standards.

4.3.9 Future work

The findings of this research highlight several areas for future investigation. Further studies could explore practical methods for creating representative datasets that comply with GDPR principles while effectively mitigating bias in AI systems. This may involve examining innovative anonymization techniques that preserve data utility for AI training. Additionally, research into different techniques, such as federated learning, could offer new insights into balancing data protection and AI development needs within the context of the EHDS and AI Act. Empirical studies on the impact of these regulations on AI innovation in healthcare across EU member states would provide valuable insights into their effectiveness in practice. The ethical implications and potential of using synthetic data for AI training in healthcare, considering both bias mitigation and data protection aspects, also warrant further exploration. Future work could also analyse the global implications of the EU's regulatory approach, particularly its influence on AI governance in healthcare beyond Europe. Examining the long-term effects of the EHDS 'opt-out' mechanism on data availability and AI development could inform future policy adjustments. Lastly, investigating the potential role of regulatory sandboxes in facilitating compliant AI development in healthcare could contribute to more effective implementation of these regulatory frameworks.

4.4 Data Collaboratives - Theory and Practical Considerations

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4.4.1 Introduction

The shift from centralised to decentralised learning that occurred in the second decade of the XXI century has timely coincided with the growing public interest in the previously rather niche topic of statistical inference and machine learning. The questions posed by the academic community go two-way. Firstly, active research in the domain of ML tries to tackle the problem of effective learning from multiple data sources while preserving some pre-defined privacy-related constraints. In this regard, the paradigm of FL is one of the alternatives that are posed by the community the most frequently. The second branch of inquiry is interested mostly in *why* rather than *how* - and is rooted in domains such as personal data protection and alternative data governance.

The aforementioned research areas are wide and varied, making it impossible to cover them satisfactorily in one written work. However, this report is mainly preoccupied with the interlink of decentralised learning techniques and data governance methods. It poses a number of precise questions regarding FL and its application, as well as delivers an explanation of the connection between technology, law and governance (if one considers law and governance a separate matter). While heavily incorporating the ML theory, the work strives to deliver a more polymathic content, swiftly balancing between the application of technology and its potential consequences stemming from the regulatory layer. Given the time constraints of three-year research, it is implied that not all of those topics could be covered in vivid detail. However, this report is a diligent attempt to present very detailed output research on FL in harmony with a discussion on European data governance. It undertakes the objective of answering not only the question *how* but also *why*, as it connects abstract technological solutions with more concrete policy proposals. While it still touches only upon the top of the iceberg when discussing compliance issues, it tries to breach the gap between different disciplines, posing the proposed technological solutions in a new context of polymathic mergers of different areas of academia.

4.4.1.1 Report Overview

The goal of this report is to present selected technological issues concerned with decentralised learning, together with an explanation of how voluntary collaborative learning can support the current (European) data governance framework. It tries to distil the years of development of the European data governance policy into a manageable background, then presents a proposition of extending the current framework by a concept of Data Collaboratives that is defined herein. Afterwards, it follows with the delivery of particular technological solutions that can reinforce the implementation of the introduced Data Collaboratives. The policy remarks introduce the concept of modern data governance and tie it back to the available technology (which, in the context of this report, is mainly focused on FL). The discussion on the policy opens three distinct issues: a) collaboration measurements, b) privacy issues (with regards to collaboration metrics)

and c) personalization of models via clustering. The work on collaborative measures is presented as a last subsection of this report, while the other two are future research directions.

This work is opened with a section of formal prerequisites that may be necessary to understand its content entirely. The subsequent section introduces an array of issues concerned with European data governance. It starts with a glance at the history of the subject while briefly introducing how the concept of data commodification was mainly abandoned on the European level for the sake of a framework built on data obligations and access. Subsequently, it goes into much detail when explaining the concept of Data Collaboratives that are built upon common management problems. Finally, it presents the current European framework that strives to increase data availability and how the concept of Data Collaboration can be a complementary measure in that context.

The following material is dedicated to the presentation of solutions to the selected array of problems that may arise in collaborative learning scenarios. The section presented herein exposes the results of the work on the client contribution issue. It formalizes the problem of analysing the marginal contribution of a client, introducing a formal notion of Aggregation Masks and Collaborative Contribution Function. Afterwards, it presents the solution in the form of Alpha-Amplification functions. The subsequent work should expand this idea by analysing the possible correlation between contribution metrics and susceptibility to privacy-related attacks and exploring the issue of personalization in the FL setting, focusing on delivering a novel method of personalization via clustering.

4.4.1.2 Methodological Remarks

All experimental sections are structured in the same way. Firstly, they introduce an introduction to the topics presented therein, with a particular emphasis on a brief presentation of the related work¹ The next subsections formally present the method and its evaluation methodology. After that, an experimental setup is described, with some of the details included in the appendices to this deliverable. Results with the appropriate commentary are placed at the end of this section.

All the experiments included in this report are replicable, with the pointers to the code used for experiments placed in the appropriate section of each chapter.

Although focused on the domain of ML, this work also includes discussion on many issues that are inextricably linked to topics of compliance and policy, which makes it interdisciplinary in nature. Sections that include such a work follow their own methodology, balancing on the brink of normative and objective statements. Seldom is it a case that some pre-defined methodology exists for conducting such a task. In contrast to the ML-oriented research, one does not have a clear structural framework in which the results of such a research could be presented. Hence, each chapter will follow its own methodology that is suitable for delivering the oriented goal. Section 4.4.3 starts with a general discussion on the history of European data governance, then turns its attention to the realm of Alternative Data Governance to propose a solution that may

¹This presentation of the related work, in contrast to one performed in the second and third chapters (that is of general nature), is focused solely on the most novel and notable papers published on the topic presented in the chapter.

reinforce the current digital initiatives of the European Commission (EC). While the formalization presented in this chapter is rather informal when it comes to the rigour of proper mathematical definition, it mostly serves as a tool for conveying the concept to the reader and linking the realm of policy and technology. It is perhaps the most interdisciplinary chapter presented in the whole work.

4.4.1.3 Table of Notation

The mathematical notation employed throughout this report is a mixture of notation widely adopted and accepted in the literature on the topic of FL (see [Wan+21; Kai+21]) and one that is based on the conventional notation used in many modern textbooks on the topic of ML (see [BB24b], [Biso6], [SSBD14]). This mixture should allow for a convenient expression of the concept presented herein while still being readable to a reader that is at least partially familiar with a conventional notation deployed in the domain. Following this convention, this work employs lower-case letters with a bar overhead (e.g. $\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{\theta}$) to define vectors and upper-case letters (e.g. X, Y, Θ) to denote matrices. By default, vectors are said to be column vectors, and their transposition ($\bar{x}^T, \bar{y}^T, \bar{\theta}^T$) is meant to denote row vectors. Elements of the vectors are indexed by the lower index (e.g. θ_i), while the elements of the matrix are specified using a double index (e.g. $\Theta_{(i,j)}$). This way, the upper index is left intact and can be used to express the position of an element in a time series (e.g. θ^t and $\theta^{(t+1)}$) - an important advantage when it comes to describing iterative algorithms.

One visible redundancy that is kept throughout this work is the distinction between hyporeport functions class (i.e. $\mathcal{H} : \Theta \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$), loss function (e.g. $\mathcal{H}(\Theta) \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$) and objective function (e.g. $l(\bar{x}, y, \theta)$). It could be argued, that the distinction between the loss and objective function is repetitive, the definition of (local) objective function basically repeats that of the loss function. However, this distinction will be very convenient when describing the FL in Chapter 4.4.2, allowing an easy and readable distinction between the global objective function ($\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K l(\bar{x}, y, \theta)$) and local objective function ($l(\bar{x}, y, \theta)$).

The rest of the notation that is presented in the 4.1.

4.4.2 State-of-the-Art: Decentralised Machine Learning

The growing amount of available data, together with the increasing complexity of models, forced the data science community to readdress how it approaches training, optimisation and deployment of machine learning pipelines. Performance-wise, the advent of high-performing Graphical Processing Units (GPU) played a transformational role in advancing research on ML, but it could not offset the need to search for more expressive statistical models with millions or even billions of parameters. Storage-wise, the growing number of interconnected Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices allowed for an almost exponential growth in the amount of collected data, rendering it unfeasible to store it at one or even a few locations. To mitigate against a growing computational and storage demand, two different approaches were developed. The first one, a **scale-up approach**, aimed to increase the processing power of a single machine so it

Table 4.1: Notation Table

Symbol	Description
\mathbb{R}	the set of real numbers
\mathbb{R}^d	the set of d -dimensional vectors over \mathbb{R}
\mathbb{N}	the set of natural numbers
\mathbb{Z}	the set of integers
$\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{(1 \times d)}$	a column vector over reals
$\bar{x}^T, \bar{y}^T, \bar{\theta}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{(d \times 1)}$	a row vector over reals
$X, Y, \Theta \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$	$n \times d$ a matrix over reals
$\bar{x}_i, \bar{y}_i, \bar{\theta}_i$	an i^{th} element of a (row or column) vector
$X_{(i,j)}, Y_{(i,j)}, \Theta_{(i,j)}$	$n \times d$ an $i^{\text{th}}, j^{\text{th}}$ element of a matrix
$Vec(\cdot)$	$Vec : \mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d} \rightarrow \bar{\mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times (n \times d)}$ (vectorization operation)
$ S $	cardinality of the set S
$\ \bar{x}\ _1$	$\sum_{i=1}^d \bar{x}_i $ (manhattan norm)
$\ \bar{x}\ _2$	$\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^d \bar{x}_i^2}$ (euclidean norm)
$\ \bar{x}\ _p$	$[\sum_{i=1}^d \bar{x}_i^p]^{\frac{1}{p}}$ (p-norm)
φ_i	a probability distribution $\varphi_i : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$
$D_i \sim \varphi_i$	a dataset generated by φ_i
\mathcal{X}	instances domain (a set)
\mathcal{Y}	labels domain (a set)
Θ	parameters domain (a set)
\bar{x}	a (vector) of features $\bar{x} \sim \varphi_i$
y	label $y \sim \varphi_i(y \bar{x})$
$\theta \in \mathcal{R}^{1 \times d}$	model parametrization (column vector)
$\Theta \in \mathcal{R}^{n \times d}$	model parametrization (matrix)
\mathcal{H}	$\mathcal{H} : \Theta \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ (hyporeport functions class)
$h(\bar{x}, \theta)$	$h(\bar{x}, \theta) \rightarrow y$ (hyporeport function)
$h(\bar{x}, \theta)^*$	$\text{argmin}_{\theta \in \Theta} l(h(\theta), \bar{x}, y)$ (optimal hyporeport function)
$h(\bar{x}, \theta)_{D_i}$	$\text{argmin}_{\theta \in \Theta} l(h(\theta), \bar{x}, y), \bar{x} \in D_i$ (fitted to $D_i \sim \varphi_i$)
$l(\bar{x}, y, \theta)$	$\mathcal{H}(\Theta) \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ (loss function)
$F(\theta)$	$\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K l(\bar{x}, y, \theta)$ (global objective function)
$f(\bar{x}, \theta)$	$l(\bar{x}, y, \theta)$ (local objective function)
P	population of clients $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$
C	population of clusters $C = \{c_1, \dots, c_2\}$
$\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$	Multivariate Normal Distribution
$Dir(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$	Multivariate Beta (Dirichlet) Distribution
$\mathcal{U}(a, b)$	Univariate Uniform Distribution on interval (a, b)

would be better suited to handle more complicated tasks. Although efficient to a certain extent, the efficiency of this approach suffered from a substantial decrease in efficiency once a certain threshold was reached, which could be suitably illustrated by the inability of modern GPU to meet certain demands regarding the tremendous computational power required to train more expressive models. Considering this physical limitation, an orthogonal *scale-out approach* was developed, as distributing the whole process on two or more units could result in lower equipment costs, better mitigation against the risks and severity of possible failures and increased I/O bandwidth. [Ver+20].

Figure 4.2: Graphs presenting the topology of networks originally presented in 1962 by P. Baran in [Bar62]. The picture presents an example of (from left to right) a fully centralised network, decentralised network and distributed network.

Under the **scale-out approach**, one could further distinguish between two sub-approaches, namely the **data-parallel** and **model-parallel** [PBGBn13; Ver+20] methods. In the **data-parallel** approach, we are trying to partition the dataset into different subsets and then distribute those subsets on available working nodes. In the **model-parallel**, every node (agent) possesses the exact copy of the dataset, but different agents work on different parts of the shared model. Under certain circumstances, those approaches can be combined into one **data-model-parallel** approach [Xin+16; Ver+20].² It can be rather intuitive that the data-parallel approach is suitable for performing tasks where high-volume data is being processed, rendering it impossible (or at

²Intuitive graphs presenting parallelism in distributed machine learning from J. Verbraeken et al. are presented in 4.3

least unpractical) to gather it in one place and process it by one unit. On the contrary, the model-parallel approach is required when a training or inference phase is computationally demanding, and it must be parallelized between different computational units (while each computational unit can independently store the exact identical copy of the dataset). This report mostly concerns mixed **data-model-parallel** approaches that require both decentralized storage and parallel computation, often performing those operations over a large-area network with varying degrees of stability.

Figure 4.3: An overview of some of the distributed machine learning topologies based on the degree of the distribution presented in [Vep+18].

Given that the terms **centralised**, **decentralized** and **distributed** will appear frequently throughout all chapters of this report, a short paragraph should be dedicated to making a proper distinction between them. This work will adapt the **system topology** developed by P. Baran in 1962 in relation to types of topologies that can be used to connect different nodes over a network. Said topology distinguished between centralised, decentralised and distributed systems [Bar62]. Centralised systems share one central hub that links all the stations connected to the network (sketch A in Figure 4.2). Decentralised systems assume the existence of multiple central hubs that link only a subset of stations to the network (sketch B in Figure 4.2). Distributed systems provide an architecture where stations are connected directly to each other, creating a peer-to-peer network without the use of any intermediary hubs (sketch C in Figure 4.2).

One can easily make a correspondence between the general (basic) topological types presented by P. Baratan [Bar62] and architectural propositions made in the literature on the data-model-

parallelization. **Centralised architecture** can take the form of an ensemble (Sketch A in Figure 4.3), where the communication is limited to upward-downward streams of data from a centralized hub. Decentralized architecture can take the form of either Trees (sketch B in Figure 4.3) or Parameter Servers (sketch C in Figure 4.3). Trees provide for the parallelization of upward-downward tasks but still assume the existence of one central hub (root). Parameter servers provide for a more flexible architecture, with distinguished entities (parameter servers) distributing the workload between the stations. Finally, a distributed architecture is possible, with stations communicating peer-to-peer to assess and carry out the workload.³

Although the topologies are always consistent, the employed vocabulary may differ from field to field and from author to author. Since the work of [Bar62] was centred around the topic of networks, individual (atomic) entities were called *stations* and their connection a *linkage* (*link*). In modern decentralized (or distributed) machine learning, it is common to refer to atomic entities as *nodes* and the central hub as *orchestrator* or *parameter server*.

The research performed under the PhD will concern mostly decentralised systems - and even more specifically - those that can be categorized under the term of **parameter servers**. While there are a lot of domain-specific problems when it comes to distributed learning, the sub-chapter is limited to the general overview of the possible topologies, mainly to provide some background for further discussion on so-called "*no peek*" *approaches*. It is also done so in order to clear any possible misconceptions arising from the usage of words such as *distributed* and *decentralized* in relation to a system's architecture. More often than not, those terms seem to be used synonymously by some authors, which may create unnecessary confusion.

4.4.2.1 Scaling-out Stochastic Gradient Descent

The large-batch Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) can be seen as a *technical predecessor* of FL - a paradigm of learning that will frequently appear on this work's pages. In fact, those techniques are similar enough to be considered together in one of the crucial surveys invoked throughout this report [Vep+18]. However, it must be pointed out that work on parallelization of SGD was chronologically preceding publications on FL [Ver+20]. This section will overview basic concepts related to Synchronous and Asynchronous SGD.

4.4.2.1.1 Synchronous SGD The main motivational factor that drove the development of large-batch SGD was the need to parallelize the process of training deep neural networks given the hardware constraints of that time. Up to 2012, a number of authors have experimented with the idea of scaling up ML algorithms through **parallelization and distribution** [Dea+12], thus building up the field of **Synchronous and Asynchronous SGD**.⁴

Under the general umbrella of those terms, the main objective is to distribute the training process using n worker machines that are in charge of computing the stochastic gradient that is

³The overview of different propositions made under each paradigm is beyond the scope of this document, but some points of reference for further reading can be found in the work of J. Verbraccet et al. - the most up-to-date survey on the distributed systems [Ver+20].

⁴Much of this research had focused on linear and convex models [Dea+12].

received by m parameter servers. Let $W \in \mathbb{Z}$ be a finite set of integers identifying the workers, and let $P \in \mathbb{Z}$ be a finite set of integers identifying the parameter servers. In the case of the Synchronous SGD, there exists a function $\mathcal{I} : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ that assigns each worker $i \in W$ to a corresponding parameter server $j \in P$. Given the nature of the task (distribution of the workload), it is additionally reasonable to assume that $m \leq n$, i.e. $|P| \leq |W|$, since one parameter server should be able to service at least one worker.

For now, assume that $\bar{\theta}$ is a complete parametrization of the model and that $\bar{\theta}$ can be split in a number of disjoint parameter sets, i.e. $\bar{\theta} = \bigcup_{\bar{\theta}_j \in \bar{\theta}} \bar{\theta}_j$. Each parameter server $j \in P$ stores a subset $\bar{\theta}_j$ of the model, using received gradients to update the model's j^{th} parameter. Therefore, given n workers, m parameter servers and a dataset $X = \{\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_i\}$ of size $|X|$ the objective is to find such parameters of the model θ that will minimise the objective loss function f defined as:

$$\min F(\bar{\theta}) := \frac{1}{X} \sum_{i=1}^X f_i(\bar{x}_i, \bar{\theta}) \quad (4.1)$$

where f_i is a conventional loss function taking form $l(\bar{x}_i, \bar{\theta}, y)$. Although the loss function is shared across all the nodes, the use of lower-case i (i.e. $f_i(\cdot)$) is employed to highlight the fact, that there exist n different local functions that output is averaged in the global loss function.

As denoted by the very name of this method, the objective will be achieved by a first-order stochastic optimisation algorithm that iteratively updates a model θ using a stochastic gradient $G := \nabla f(x_i; \theta)$ computed either at a randomly sampled x_i or at a mini-batch containing B randomly sampled data points from the set X . Therefore, we will obtain a sequence of models $\theta^{(0)}, \theta^{(1)}, \dots, \theta^{(m)}$ where m is the number of iterations of Gradient Descent (GD) [Che+17].

Remark 4.4.1. *The fact that the parameters θ are indexed both by a lower index (position in a union of sets $\bigcup_{\theta_j \in \theta} \theta_j$) and an upper index (to denote the next iteration of parameter θ) can cause confusion, especially if the notation is inconsistent. This work will employ consistent notation, using a lower index to denote the position of an element and an upper index to present the chronological order of the elements. Following this notation, θ_i^t will denote a j^{th} parameter at round t . When it comes to the use of brackets $(\cdot \cdot \cdot)$ at the higher index, they will remain purely esthetical choices, being employed when they can add additional clarity. This implies that θ^t and $\theta^{(t)}$ will remain an equivalent objects. Sometimes, it will be necessary to introduce additional notation (e.g. when describing Contribution Masks in later Chapters). However, each time a new notation appears, an appropriate explanation will be provided. Moreover, this new notation will be used only within the chapter in which it is necessary to do so.*

Remark 4.4.2. *The overline sign over the parameters (i.e. $\bar{\theta}$) will be omitted if it does not cause any ambiguity. It is purely an esthetical choice to avoid too cluttered notation.*

Under the large batch SGD, two possible approaches are often featured: **synchronous** and **asynchronous** descent [Che+17; Dea+12]. The main difference between them concerns how we update the model located on the parameters servers - whether we update it as soon as we receive

the gradient from the first worker (Asynchronous Large Batch SGD) or wait for gradients from all the workers to update the model (Synchronous Large Batch SGD). The exemplary implementation of Synchronous SGD was introduced by [Che+17]. The Algorithm 2 presents the intended behaviour of the parameter server, while the Algorithm 3 presents the behaviour of the worker.

Algorithm 2: Sync-SGD Parameter Server by [Che+17] adopted to the needs of this work.

```

input  $\gamma_0, \gamma_1$ , learning rates.
input  $\alpha$  decay rate.
input  $N$  number of mini-batches to aggregate.
input  $\theta^{(0)}$  model initialization.
for  $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$  do
     $G = \{\}$ 
    while  $|G| < N$  do
        Wait for  $(g, t')$  from any worker.
        if  $t' == t$  then  $G \leftarrow G \cup \{g\}$ 
        else Drop gradient  $g$ 
    end
     $\theta_j^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \theta_j^{(t)} - \frac{\gamma_t}{N} \sum_{g \in G} G_j$ 
     $\theta_j^{(t)} = \alpha \theta_j^{(t-1)} + (1 - \alpha) \theta_j^{(t)}$ 
end
    
```

Algorithm 3: Sync-SGD worker by [Che+17] adopted to the needs of this work.

```

input Dataset  $X$ 
input  $B$  mini-batch size
for  $t = 0, 1, \dots$  do
    Wait to read  $\theta^t = (\theta_0^{(t)}, \dots, \theta_M^{(t)})$  from parameter servers
     $G_k^{(t)} := 0$ 
    for  $i = 1, \dots, B$  do
        Sample datapoint  $\bar{x}_{(k,i)}$  from  $X$ 
         $G_k^{(t)} := G_k^{(t)} + \frac{1}{B} \nabla f(\bar{x}_{(k,i)}, \theta^t)$ .
    end
    Send  $G_k^{(t)}$  to parameter servers.
end
    
```

The Synchronous SGD can be seen as a two-layered optimization problem where an outer objective function $F(\theta)$ is optimized using local gradients $\nabla f(x_i, \theta_i)$ that are calculated with respect to i^{th} parameter of the model. Because of the double optimization, we could denote the central function $\nabla F(\theta)$ a **global objective function** and further distinguish each **local objective function** $f_i(x_i, \theta_i)$ - a notation concept that will be employed with FL. The central server dispatches

tasks to all workers and awaits a response. If the received gradient is, in fact, calculated with respect to the $i^t h$ parameter from the round t , then it is included in the union of all received gradients. Otherwise, it is discarded as a straggler. This behaviour ensures that the delayed subpart of the system will not halt the whole process. The name *synchronous* comes from the fact that the gradients are updated synchronously at each iteration after the server receives a complete set of gradients G . This remains in contrast with *asynchronous* version of the same algorithm that is discussed in the following subsection.

4.4.2.1.2 Asynchronous SGD Asynchronous (large-batch) SGD is very similar in nature to its synchronous counterpart. The main difference is rooted in how the central entity behaves in relation to the gradients received from the server. In the synchronous version, the server collects tuples of local updates (g, t') to average them before the formal aggregation. The asynchronous version aggregates updates instantaneously without the need to validate the timestamp. This forces one fundamental change in the client, which does not track iterations as in the synchronous version. Similar to the synchronous counterpart, the intended behaviour of the parameter server is presented in the Algorithm 4, while the Algorithm 5 presents the behaviour of the worker.

Algorithm 4: Async-SGD Parameter Server by [Che+17]

```

input  $\gamma_0, \gamma_1$ , learning rates.
input  $\alpha$  decay rate.
input  $\theta^0$  model initialization.
for  $t = 0, 1, \dots$  do
     $\theta_j^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \theta_j^{(t)} - \gamma_t G_j$ 
     $\bar{\theta}^{(t)}_j = \alpha \theta^{(t-1)}_j + (1 - \alpha) \theta_j^{(t)}$ 
end
    
```

Algorithm 5: Async-SGD worker k , where $k = 1, \dots, N + b$ by [Che+17]

```

input Dataset  $X$ 
input  $B$  mini-batch size
while True do
    Wait to read  $\theta^t = (\theta_0^{(t)}, \dots, \theta_M^{(t)})$  from parameter servers
    for  $i = 1, \dots, B$  do
        Sample datapoint  $\bar{x}_{(k,i)}$  from  $X$ 
         $G_k^{(t)} := G_k^{(t)} + \frac{1}{B} \nabla f(\bar{x}_{(k,i)}, \theta^t)$ .
    end
    Send  $G_k^{(t)}$  to parameter servers.
end
    
```

The change between synchronous and asynchronous versions of the algorithms seems to be minor, but it has significant consequences for theoretical and empirical convergence [Che+17] rate. The following section will inspect how those algorithms relate to FL.

4.4.2.2 Private Decentralized Machine Learning

Previous sections were mainly concerned with scaling out the whole training process to ensure scalability. From this point onward, privacy and availability issues also will be considered. In order to do this, it is necessary to transform learning algorithms presented in Algorithm 2 and Algorithm 4 to comply with stricter requirements.

One of the first surveys on the set of techniques that would fit the presented purpose was drafted by Vepakomma et al. in 2018 [Vep+18] and it referred to them as the *no peek* approaches. The term *no-peek* refers to the fact that we do not disclose raw data directly, but we use some intermediate results of the local training.

The work of P. Vepakomma adopted the division between **Large Batch Synchronous SGD**, **FL** and **Split Learning (SL)** and then assessed a number of properties characterising each method in terms of privacy and security (some of the features of relevance were: whether the data is revealed, whether the hyperparameters are revealed and whether the intermediate representation is revealed). The following results are reported as they were presented in the original article of [Vep+18].

<i>No-peek</i> deep learning	Data revealed	Hyperparameters revealed	Intermediate representation revealed
Large Batch Synchronous SGD	No	Yes	Yes
Federated Learning	No	Yes	Yes
Split Learning	No	No	Yes

Table 4.2: A division between different *no-peek* distributed deep learning techniques, originally presented in [Vep+18].

The subsequent paragraphs will introduce the idea that Large-batch SGD, FL, and SL are highly interconnected, and one can introduce slight transformations to one of the paradigms to easily arrive at the other.

The one last thing that must be addressed is the difference between *no-peek approaches* and the *privacy protection* itself. FL and SL were designed with strong privacy constraints incorporated into their assumptions. However, those constraints primarily target limitations in sharing clients' data directly. Indirect results are still shared, and those indirect results may or may not be considered a *personal data* depending on the chosen legal regime that is applicable. This concept will be explored in the last chapter of the report - but it is important to highlight that avoiding disclosure of the raw user's data is not rendering privacy protection regulation inapplicable.

Method	100 clients	500 clients
Large Batch SGD	29.4 TFlops	5.89 TFlops
Federated Learning	29.4 TFlops	5.89 TFlops
SplitNN	0.1548 TFlops	0.03 TFlops

Table 4.3: Results of experiments presented in [Vep+18]. The table shows computation resources consumed per client when training CIFAR 10 dataset over VGG.

Method	100 clients	500 clients
Large Batch SGD	13 GB	5.89 GB
Federated Learning	3 GB	2.4 GB
SplitNN	6 GB	1.2 GB

Table 4.4: Results of the second experiment presented in [Vep+18]. The table shows the computation bandwidth required per client when training the CIFAR 100 dataset over ResNet (in gigabytes).

A contrari, there are cases when sharing the raw data will not fall under those regulations, irrespective of the method of transfers⁵. The common misconception is that *no-peek* approaches render a given data collection process exempted from the appropriate regime of personal data protection.⁶ Taking that into consideration, maybe a more appropriate name for *no-peek* approaches would be *no-transfer* approaches, as they block direct aggregation of data but do not necessarily imply that privacy-leakage is in the realm of implausible.

⁵Assuming that the method of transfer itself does not create any additional metadata that can be used as an identifier as defined under an appropriate legal regime

⁶(...) or any other applicable regulations. What concerns this report mostly focuses on personal data protection regulations. However, it is highly possible that one would need to take into account other legal goods that are appropriate. Providing an example, it may happen that the data leakage would amount to infringement of Intellectual Property regulations.

4.4.2.2.1 From Large-batch SGD to Federated Learning FL (sometimes also interchangeably called Federated Optimisation) is a widely discussed technique of *no-peek* learning deployed on multiple agents simultaneously. The main purpose of FL is to train one global model using a decentralised network of agents, each holding only a small subset of the local data [Wan+21]. Therefore, while the local loss function is the same across all the devices, the local distribution may vary greatly, which further leads to different results yielded by each local loss function. This scenario is further reinforced by additional assumptions [Wan+21; Kai+21; KMR15; McM+17], namely:

- The number of clients varies greatly, from 10 in the cross-silo scenario to 10^6 in the cross-device scenario. Accordingly, the subset of available clients is dynamic - with clients dropping out of the training to an extent unknown prior to the disconnection.
- The data is not independent and identically distributed (non-i.i.d. data). Some devices may hold a multitude of samples, while others may hold none or close to none. This further results in many problems while trying to optimise local loss functions. Some of them may yield a result that is non-representative for the whole population, get stuck on local minimum⁷, or drag the whole training process due to the issues with local optimisation.
- The communication bandwidth is strictly limited and can be a bottleneck for the whole training process. Depending on the FL setting, we may or may not have one central orchestrating server that must act as an intermediary between every agent participating in the training. While the communication burden may be easier to assess in the cross-silo scenario, in the cross-device scenario, it is not always possible to fully assess how the network consumption will be distributed over time.
- Each agent's dataset starts as a concealed and must remain concealed during and after training. This implies that neither any other agent nor the orchestrating server itself can access the raw data used in the training process. This also further implies that the distribution of local datasets is not only non-i.i.d. but also that they are generally unknown to the orchestrating server. In my opinion, it generally does not imply that the agents could not be re-identified and their datasets wholly or partially reconstructed. So-called "no-peek" approaches owe this name to the fact that they do not access the "raw" data stored at each device participating in the training. We generally should distinguish between a simple *no-peek* approach and the privacy-risk evaluation - otherwise, we may run into terminological and methodological Babylon.

Depending on the data split, we distinguish between **Horizontal Federated Learning (HFL)** and **Vertical Federated Learning (VFL)**. HFL envisages split in a sample space, with feature space shared across all local clients. VFL provides for a scenario when the sample space is the same, but the features are split between different clients.

⁷Ultimately, we are interested in large-scale non-convex optimisation

4.4.2.2.2 Horizontal Federated Learning HFL is the first presented formulation of the problem [McM+17] and, up to the date of this report, perhaps the most researched one [Kai+21; Li+23a; Wan+21]. It envisages that the split occurs in the sample space while the feature space is identical across all of the nodes. Formalising described above, the decentralised supervised objective can be formulated as follows:

$$\min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} F(\theta) \text{ where } F(\theta) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K l(\bar{x}_{i \sim \varphi_i}, y_{i \sim \varphi_i}, \theta) \quad (4.2)$$

where additionally:

- $F(\theta)$ is the global objective function that we want to optimise indirectly;
- θ denotes the parameters of the global model that are also used in local optimisation;
- $l(x_{i \sim \varphi_i}, y_{i \sim \varphi_i}, \theta)$ is the local loss function that is universal for all agents;
- x_i and y_i are the samples gathered on the i^{th} client;
- sample $x_1 \sim \varphi_1, x_2 \sim \varphi_2, \dots, x_i \sim \varphi_i$ - we expect that some samples may be distributed similarly, but they will never be distributed identically. The same applies to labels;
- $K = |k|$ where $|k|$ denotes the size of the whole population.

This is the simplest formulation of the problem. To further increase the optimisation efficiency, one may want to attach weights to each loss function at the i^{th} client and introduce those weights directly into the problem formulation. Therefore, one would obtain:

$$\min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} F(\theta) \text{ where } F(\theta) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K l(x_{i \sim \varphi_i}, y_{i \sim \varphi_i}, \theta) \quad (4.3)$$

where additionally:

- $\sum_{i=1}^K = 1$ - the weights must add up to 1 across all agents.

It is also possible to sample only a subset of clients from the population K . This generally follows intuition, as it is seldom possible to train on the whole population of devices. Therefore:

$$\min_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} F(\theta) \text{ where } F(\theta) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K l(x_{i \sim \varphi_i}, y_{i \sim \varphi_i}, \theta) \quad (4.4)$$

where additionally:

- $k = \binom{K}{n}$, where K is the total size of the population and n is the sample size, while the frequent assumption is that we are sampling without replacement.

As noted above, we have introduced a set of labels y_i corresponding to each set of samples x_i gathered on the i^{th} client. If we want to generalise the objective further, we can simply rewrite the above objective as [Wan+21]:

$$\mathbb{E}_{i \sim P}[F_i(x)]F_i(x) = \text{where } \mathbb{E}_{\zeta \sim D_i}[f_i(x, \zeta)] \quad (4.5)$$

where additionally:

- $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes the parameters of the global model;
- $f_i(x) : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denotes the local objective function at client i ;
- P denotes the distribution of the population of clients Γ ;
- $f_i(x, \zeta)$ is a generalised local loss function;
- φ_i denotes the distribution of data used to optimise the local loss function $f_i(x, \zeta)$.

Given the general problem formulation presented above, it is not a mistake that this sub-chapter has started with a more narrow formulation, introducing the loss function $l(i \sim \varphi_i, y_i \sim \varphi_i, \theta)$. Most of the tasks solved by distributed learning are formulated as supervised learning tasks where additionally to the subsets of data $[\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_i]$, one must possess a corresponding set of labels $[y_1, y_2, \dots, y_i]$ to optimise the local loss functions. The availability of those labels, especially in the context of multi-device learning, is a tremendous academic and practical challenge that is highlighted as one of the research directions in [Li+23a].

The most straightforward solution to the problem is to use Stochastic or Mini-Batch GD to solve the problem [Wan+21; Kai+21]. Since it is impossible to compute $\Delta F(x)$ directly, we must first compute all $\Delta f(x)$ and then use those gradients to approximate global loss and fine-tune the model's parameters. Because of the communication constraints, it is natural to execute n steps of local-SGD before communicating the results back to the Server. Another natural extension comes from the work of [Red+22] where an Adaptive Federated Optimization was proposed according to which the local model's dispatch pseudo-gradients in the form of difference between the received and updated model. This version of the algorithm is presented in the Algorithm 6. The properties of dispatched pseudo-gradients will be matter of examination a few times in this report, as they provide for an intuitive and natural interpretation of the learning process.

An attentive reader could easily spot the similarities between the Algorithm 6 and Synchronous Large Batch SGD presented in Algorithms 2 and 3. Indeed, if one would initialize only one parameter server j for the whole model θ and make a further assumption that each worker works on the whole model θ holding its own dataset, one would arrive at the general Federation Optimisation presented above. The similarities are so extensive that even in the [Vep+18], the authors cite the work on FL to describe the Synchronous SGD. Yet - FL comes with a number of assumptions, such as data heterogeneity or privacy constraints - that perhaps justify distinguishing it as a different sub-field. It is also worth highlighting that in the literature on FL, the server-less approach is proposed when no central orchestrating entity aggregates the gradients - but the clients are communicating peer-to-peer. This has given rise to a distinction between

Algorithm 6: Adaptive Federated Optimization Algorithm [Red+22].

```

input: Initial model  $x^0$ ; ClientOpt, ServerOpt with learning rate  $\eta, \eta_s$ 
for  $t \in \{0, 1, \dots, T - 1\}$  do
  Sample a subset  $S^{(t)}$  of clients
  for client  $i \in S^{(t)}$  in parallel do
    Initialize local model  $\theta_i^{(t,0)} = \theta^{(t)}$ 
    for  $k = 0, \dots, \tau_i - 1$  do
      Compute local stochastic gradient  $\nabla f_i(\theta_i^{(t,k)})$ 
      Perform local update  $\theta_i^{(t,k+1)}$ 
    end
    Compute local model changes  $\Delta_i^{(t)}$ 
  end
  Aggregate Local Changes  $\Delta^{(t)} = \frac{\sum_{i \in S^{(t)}} p_i \Delta_i^{(t)}}{\sum_{i \in S^{(t)}} p_i}$ 
  Update global model  $\theta^{(t+1)} = \text{ServerOpt}(x^{(t)}, -\Delta^{(t)}, \eta_s, t)$ 
end

```

Server-based Federated Learning (SFL), and Peer-to-Peer Federated Learning [Ngu+22] (P2PFL). However, this report will mostly rely on Server-based FL.

4.4.2.2.3 Vertical Federated Learning Previous subsections overviewed the classical approach to FL- one, which envisages the split of the sample space. However, a different (vertical) split is possible - where the samples are shared among all the clients, but the feature space is split between them, with a particular client (often labelled as a *active party*) possessing a label corresponding to each sample [Liu+24]. The difference between horizontal and vertical FL is presented in Figure 4.4. A general VFL Training Procedure is outlined in the Algorithm 7.

In contrast to the general FL case, the similarities between vanilla Large-batch SGD and VFL may be slightly more challenging to spot. Each VFL algorithm generally follows a similar pattern [Liu+24]. The first step is to perform a feature alignment. Since the sample space is shared and the feature space is split, a subset of common samples must be identified, and individual samples in that subset must be aligned with each other. This is commonly achieved by Private-Set-Intersection techniques [PSZ14; PSZ18; LCo4] that were initially developed for inter-database operations. However, in recent years, we have observed a number of successful attempts at transferring them to the realm of VFL. [Sun+21] presented an algorithm for the VFL framework that is based on Private Set Union (PSU) to generate the union of samples for training purposes. [ZTP21; LD20] proposed a multi-party general framework for finding a subset of common samples under the privacy guarantees defined therein. [Liu+24] presents a most recent comparison of PSU techniques and methods that are being developed in order to allow align the feature subspaces without breaking privacy guarantees.

Once the samples are aligned, the active party can initiate the general training procedure. Since each node has information about different features, all of them must utilize their local prediction function $G_K(\cdot, \cdot)$ to compute the corresponding output H_k . Once the outputs are computed, they are dispatched to an active party K , that firstly updates its own prediction function (ψ_K^{j+1}) and then calculates loss in respect to all the local models' parameters from θ_1 to θ_K . Only after that the parameters are sent back, and the process repeats.

This work will be predominantly focused on the HFL as the baseline realization of the decentralized learning paradigm. However, it is important to highlight that the vertical approach is also a developing area of study, with recent surveys delivering an overview of promising results presented over the last few years [Liu+24]. Moreover, a third (mixed) approach is emerging - one where both the feature and sample spaces are split between the nodes. This approach, sometimes referred to as *Transfer Federated Learning (TFL)*⁸ that combines techniques from both approaches to tackle both scenarios simultaneously.

4.4.3 Data Collaboratives in Context of the European Data Governance

The following chapter contains work published in the article: Data Collaboratives with the Use of Decentralised Learning (Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, Chicago, USA, 2023) available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3593013.3594029>.

⁸It is worth pointing out that the keyword *transfer* here refers to the split feature and sample space and is differs in meaning to what is understood as *Transfer Learning* in the main ML literature.

Algorithm 7: Generalised VFL Training Procedure as Presented in [Liu+24]

```

input : learning rates  $\eta_1, \eta_2$ 
output: Model parameters  $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_K, \psi_K$ 
Party  $1, 2, \dots, K$  initialize  $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_K, \psi_K$  for each iteration  $j = 1, 2, \dots$  do
    Randomly sample a mini-batch of samples  $x \subset D$ 
    for each party  $k = 1, 2, \dots$  do
        Party  $k$  computes  $H_k = G_k(x_k, \theta_k)$ 
        Party  $k$  sends  $\{H_k\}$  to party  $K$ 
    end
    Active party  $K$  updates  $\psi_K^{j+1} = \psi_K^j - \eta_1 \frac{\partial l}{\partial \psi_K}$ 
    for each party  $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$  in parallel do
        Party  $k$  computes  $\nabla_{\theta_k} l = \frac{\partial l}{\partial \theta_k} = \sum_i \frac{\partial l}{\partial H_{i,k}} \frac{\partial H_{i,k}}{\partial \theta_k}$ 
        Party  $k$  updates  $\theta_k^{j+1} = \theta_k^j - \eta_2 \nabla_{\theta_k} l$ 
        Send back  $\theta_k^{j+1}$  to party  $k$ .
    end
end
    
```

4.4.3.1 Sketch of European Data Governance

As indicated in the introductory chapter of this work, a substantial part of it will be dedicated to the issues related to collaborative learning and self-organization as a method of obtaining knowledge about the environment without directly exposing one's data. This is strictly related to a (broad and variously defined) topic of Data Governance. This chapter of the presented report will focus on selected issues and approaches of European Data Governance, with a particular emphasis on Data Access and Common European Data Spaces. However, current approaches and propositions with regard to appropriate frameworks for data governance do not come out of the void. Instead, they build upon previous discussions and proposals that equally attempted to find solutions on how conflicting interests in data could be resolved. It is, therefore, necessary to briefly summarize the said discussion, as without proper context, one may find it difficult to properly localize the further remarks regarding Data Access and Common European Data Spaces. The following subsection follows that objective, briefly sketching how the debate on Data Governance unfolded during the last twenty years on the European level. It is heavily implied that the *sketch* can not be treated as an exhaustive description of all the topics presented therein, as it would require another manuscript to follow this topic's nuances in more detail. However, its main objective is to present two key highlights. Firstly, it aims to present how Data Governance became a key policy concern on the European level. Secondly, it elaborates on how the policymakers gradually abandoned the idea of data commodification to arrive at *softer* measures that stand in opposition to the data as commodity approach. Finally, it arrives at the original concept of the Data Collaborative, a collective and self-organized entity that could potentially support the current European data governance framework.

Figure 4.4: Visualization of the simplified Vertical Federated Learning setting provided by [Liu+24]. As presented in the figure, the sample is split between a number of clients by different features, while the active party (in green) holds all the relevant labels. Since the labels must be somehow paired by IDs, the first stage of Vertical Learning consists of private entity alignment - finding common samples for all the interacting parties. The natural scenario that may employ VFL is based on the assumption that a number of different entities may possess different information about the same sample (e.g. the same patient has records in different hospitals or the same insured has records across different insurance companies). In such a case, it would be a natural translation of the federated learning process to combine information about the sample without revealing what exactly each entity knows about it.

4.4.3.1.1 Data Governance as a Key Policy Problem Whereas the European Commission does not offer a comprehensive definition of its *European way of data governance* [Com22a], data governance has, in general, been defined by scholars as the exercise of authority and control over the management of data, whilst its purpose would be to increase the value of data and minimize data-related costs and risks [ASB19]. Von Grafenstein differentiates between three analytical layers that are equally mentioned by the legislators, with each having its own challenges: (i) the regulatory layer, (ii) the organisational layer, (iii) the technological layer [Gra22a]. Since the Juncker Commission identified the creation of a Digital Single Market as a critical policy objective in 2014, the EU has been highly active in proposing regulation for a digital economy that ensures a high level of data protection while, at the same time, boosting competitiveness and innovation capacities. With the recognition of data as an essential resource for economic growth, job creation, and societal progress [Com24], the interest in data governance has spiked over the last years, gathering worldwide attention of policy-makers and research communities. Whereas the regulation of data flows originated in attempts to protect the fundamental rights to privacy and data protection, regulatory perspectives evolved with the growing understanding of benefits that result from data-driven innovation that relies on data as a resource [OEC]. Since

data would not have any intrinsic value, but its value would rather depend on the context of use as well as the extent to which it can be reused [OEC], ensuring availability and access to quality data has become a key concern.

Whilst the European Data Protection Framework has been conceived in fundamental rights terms, it has a dual purpose also to ensure the free flow of personal data [Mad20]. EU policy of the past years, therefore, equally aimed at adding a fifth to the four existing freedoms of the European Single Market (free flow of goods, capital, services, and labour): the free flow of data.[CM22; VE19] However, in addition to growing concerns about the internal consistency of this patchwork of rules and regulations [DH23], the question comes up if the current path to data governance taken by the EU in its Data Strategy is capable of achieving its objectives. How a framework should look that ensures both the availability of personal and non-personal data to a wide variety of actors as well as the protection of fundamental rights of different stakeholders is far from clear. Whilst substantial gains are expected from exploiting the non-rivalrous character of data by increasing its availability, neither companies nor individuals would necessarily want their data widely available due to potential threats to privacy, intellectual property rights, or trade secrets if data is disclosed [CM22] Resolving these tensions lies at the heart of discussions on how to design a framework for the data-agile economy. It, therefore, comes as no surprise that commentators described the regulation of data markets as *shaping up to be one of the major challenges of the twenty-first century* [Tay+22].

4.4.3.1.2 From Property Rights to Data Access and Sharing Obligations A frequently used example for the explanation of the necessity of property rights in society constitutes the *tragedy of the commons* elaborated by Hardin [Har68]. Scarce resources that are accessible to all members of society would ultimately end up being overexploited and depleted – freedom in a commons would bring ruin to all [Har68]. This tragedy could only be averted either with the introduction of a system of private property rights that should enable efficient resource allocation according to market mechanisms or via government regulation that defines rules for the use of that resource. Whilst the characteristics of data as an intangible, non-rivalrous resource that does not get depleted upon consumption make it a difficult fit for traditional economic and legal categories [Ker22], debates emerged about how property rights in data could contribute to the preservation of the *privacy commons* which might otherwise degrade due to concerns about an (over)use of personal information [Scho4]. As described by Thouvenin et al., data propertization gave *hope to those wishing to unlock the potential of the data economy and to those trying to re-empower individuals that have lost control over their data* [FA17].

Whereas a certain degree of legal protection can already be offered by non-property regimes such as trade secrets or contracts and *de facto* ownership positions via technical protection measures, none of these regimes create rights *erga omnes* – i.e. enforceable rights against the world [36]. It is property law that confers exclusive rights that can be invoked against more than a number of specific persons, and it is precisely this universality that has been described as the touchstone of property rights [Bri24]. The existing European intellectual property rights regimes, however, do not provide for a comprehensive property right in data as such. Instead, they offer different degrees of protection based on criteria such as creativity, investment, or secrecy. Some commentators have, therefore, rightfully used the metaphor of a patchwork to

describe the protection offered by existing intellectual property regimes in data [Zec21]. Furthermore, neither the Data Protection Directive nor its successor, the General Data Protection Regulation, grounded in the unalienable fundamental right to data protection, created any property rights for data subjects over their data.

Whether or not the introduction of a new comprehensive unitary property rights regime might be the appropriate approach to solving diverging interests in data has been subject to a long-lasting scholarly debate. Early proponents in the US argued that property rights in data would empower individuals to regain control over their data and to value their privacy according to their preferences [Les99b]. The protection of data would thereby be linked with the incentives of the market by using the laws of property as a control mechanism [Les99b]. Others, however, feared that a property rights approach would ultimately erode existing levels of privacy if individuals simply traded away their personal data [Cohoo]. Market solutions based on a property rights model might thus not cure any of the problems related to control but only legitimize them [Litoo].

Particularly in Europe, where information privacy is considered a fundamental right and where personal data should consequently not be considered as a commodity that could be bought and sold on a market, a property rights approach appeared problematic. At the same time, critics observed that maintaining the argument that personal data should be nobody's property would be illusional in a data-driven economy [Pur15]. Instead, the status quo devoid of well-defined property rights in data would result in a *de facto* assignment of (economic) property rights to the information industry, eroding the data subject's autonomy, privacy and informational self-determination [Pur15].

Other scholars discussed the introduction of property rights in data not from the angle of the empowerment of the individual but from the creation of data markets [Zec16a]. Property rights in non-personal data might create incentives to generate and disclose data – thereby enhancing the general availability of data for other market actors. Whilst the proposition was taken up in the proposal by the European Commission on the possible introduction of a data producer's right [Comb], criticism prevailed. The reliance on Big Data for permanent, dynamic access to real-time data sources could hardly be aligned with individual ownership [Dre16b]. Instead, creating an additional layer of rights in data might cause disruptive overlaps with existing copyright and the *sui generis* database right [36]. Consequently, competing claims of ownership would risk resulting in a "tragedy of the anticommons", i.e. an underuse of data due to complex interrelations of overlapping ownership claims [Ste20].

With the European Strategy for Data, a turning point in the EU's approach to the regulation of the data economy has been reached. After decades of discussions, the creation of property rights in data seems to have been discarded as a suitable mechanism that is capable of resolving conflicting interests in data. However, the rationale behind its proposition, i.e., empowering individuals and companies with regard to *their* data as well as enabling the emergence of a data-agile economy, is still existent. As the academic debate shifted away from conceiving property rights in data as a potential legal solution to resolve conflicting interests in data, a similar tendency could be observed in EU policy. Whilst the goal of the European Strategy for Data remains to realize a *genuine single market for data*, any reference to (legal) data ownership rights disap-

peared from the European Commission's communications and proposals. Commentators hence described the strategy as a *paradigm shift* in EU policy from data ownership towards facilitating data access and sharing [MA21b].

Since data would constitute an essential resource for companies to develop new products and services or train AI systems, a regulatory environment should enable stakeholders to have easy access to an almost infinite amount of data. Regulation should enable data to flow easily while at the same time ensuring that European rules and values are fully respected. Key pillars of the European Strategy for Data thereby attempt to enable precisely the creation of such a regulatory environment that ensures *better access to data and its responsible usage* [Com24]. Regulating data access instead of creating property rights in data has thus become the new instrument that should solve conflicting interests in data.

First, the Data Governance Act (DGA) [Com22a] intends to facilitate access and encourage the use of data held by public sector bodies. Whilst the Open Data Directive already established minimum rules governing the re-use of data that is not subject to, for instance, intellectual property rights or commercial confidentiality, the DGA harmonizes access conditions for the reuse of protected categories of data. Moreover, the DGA puts in place a framework for *data intermediation services* and *data altruism organization*, which should play a key role in the data economy by supporting, facilitating, and promoting (voluntary) data sharing by bringing demand and supply of data together. A notification scheme for data-sharing services should thereby increase trust in these data intermediaries (and hence in data sharing) by companies and data subjects.

Second, the European Commission intends to create Common European Data Spaces [Comc] in strategic sectoral fields [Com22c] that bring together relevant data infrastructures and governance frameworks to facilitate data pooling and sharing. Key features of these data spaces should be that they provide a secure infrastructure to pool, access, share, and use data while ensuring the protection of European rules. The structure should thereby provide access to and use of data in a fair, transparent, and non-discriminatory manner via trustworthy data governance mechanisms. The DGA is thus supposed to play a fundamental role in the creation of data spaces as it should create the foundation for the establishment of trustworthy, neutral data intermediaries.

Third, the Data Act proposal [Com22b] constitutes, together with the DGA, the second horizontal legislative instrument of the European Data Strategy. Whilst the DGA aims at opening up data held by public sector bodies, the Data Act proposal creates mandatory access rules to data held by private actors in B2C, B2B as well as B2G relations. The data access rights are thereby supposed to fulfil the twofold purpose of empowering individuals and companies over *their* data while at the same time ensuring that data is available for other stakeholders. It is still unclear, however, how mandatory data access rights would have to be designed in practice to comply with, for instance, the requirements of the current Data Act proposal. Whether they would have to be designed as *ex-situ* rights that enable the porting of data directly to another platform or as *in-situ* rights that would require external algorithms to be transferred to the data location to perform data analysis [Ker].

Since the Data Act proposal merely demands that data should be *made available* or to implement the principles of data minimization and data protection by design by using technology

that *permits algorithms to be brought to the data*, it seems likely that in many instances, it might favour in-situ access rights that do not require the transfer of data.

Finally, this paradigm shift towards fostering data access is not only visible in the European Strategy for Data but has also been observed in other new European digital regulations [OEC]. Provisions in the Digital Markets Act (DMA) [Comd], the Digital Service Act (DSA) [Come], and the AI Act [Com21] would also contain provisions that reflect the EU's attempt to open up data while at the same time finding a balance between new access and transparency obligations and competing interests in data. New access and/or portability obligations in the DMA, DSA, and the AI Act would, therefore, equally constitute part of the latest regulatory effort of the EU to end data enclosure while departing from a *single-minded rights-based and data ownership approach* [58].

At the same time, however, authors have been critical of approaches based on access rights alone. Focusing exclusively on the problem of whether a company should get access to data would be insufficient. The *data as a resource* framing of the European Strategy for Data that regards *data abundance* as desirable would necessarily continue to conflict with the purpose limitation and data minimization principles in European Data Protection law [Tay+22]. This tension would not be automatically resolved in a regulatory governance model that merely proscribes data access and sharing obligations. Viljoen argues that a common flaw in existing data governance frameworks based on propertarian or fundamental rights-based approaches would be its consistent focus on attempting to reassert individuals instead of more collective forms of control over ones *datafication*. Since data processing practices by major companies would primarily aim at deriving population-level insights, data governance approaches would have to move beyond individualist claims and develop institutional responses to represent the relevant interests at stake on a more collective level [Vil20]. Other scholars insist that a broader analytical approach would be necessary, for instance, by the use of data trustees or technological solutions that impact the allocation of *de facto* control of data [Ker20].

Given the insights regarding management on the collective level [Vil20], one may find it tempting to seek solutions based on some voluntarily self-governed schema that allows individuals to harvest the advantages of inferential statistics performed on large bodies of data while also preserving a form of decentralized and voluntary nature of commons government. Indeed, the never-ending popularity of data crowdsourcing [citation] is valid proof that self-organization can support existent data governance schemas. As tempting as it would be to stop at crowdsourcing as a desirable and final measure of such supportive action, it is necessary to point out its instantaneous and irreversible nature that may act in a prohibited way towards undecided *data holders*. Once the data is transferred to a global pool, it is hardly the case, that it can be guaranteed that it will be (physically) discarded when requested so. In this sense, crowdsourcing may be seen as a binding method of cooperation between independent actors.

Although Data-based Collaboration is not a substitute for data ownership or sharing obligations under a current framework, it is a complementary remedy that can solve some of the tensions and issues that previous approaches could possibly not. Hence, the following section thus presents a model of data collaboratives based on decentralized learning techniques that might remedy some of the existing shortcomings by moving beyond individual data control. In-

stead, it employs a more collective approach that enables participants in the collaborative to access different datasets and collectively train one model without the need for transferring any raw data. It exemplifies how a solution on the technological layer could contribute to reducing tensions that the regulatory layer alone could not solve, i.e. enabling control over data while at the same time making it available to other stakeholders. Furthermore, the following proposition equally mirrors the demand of the Data Act to conceive data access rights in a way they implement the data protection by design and data minimization principle.

4.4.3.1.3 Data Collaboratives

4.4.3.1.4 Data Governance and the Commons Management Problem When Hardin saw either a market-based approach via property rights or government intervention as the only possible solution to prevent the tragedy of the commons from occurring, scholarship on the commons [Sab92] argued that an alternative approach was possible. This approach would rely on collective resource management, i.e. the institutionalized sharing of resources among members of a community [MFS10]. Commons thereby consist of three elements: (i) a resource (ii) a community that has access to and takes care of the resource (iii) collective action of creating, maintaining, and governing in common [Mar17]. Since they are based on the idea of access rather than exclusion, they would challenge the dominance of private property [Mar17] or even constitute the opposite of property [MQ17]. The main function of commons would, therefore, be to institutionalize freedom to operate within symmetric constraints, free of the particular risk that any other can deny the use of that resource set [Ben14]. The commons framework, therefore, does not imply unmanaged access to a particular resource but requires that groups engage in managed resource sharing [Mad20].

Ostrom famously defined eight design principles [Sab92] [Sab92] that enable successful collective resource management, such as collective-choice arrangements that allow groups to adapt governance conditions to their needs and local circumstances. Whilst initially conceived for the management of natural resources whose characteristics are evidently very distinct from data, they would still be highly relevant with regard to data governance as they could provide insights for assessing the types of institutions needed to govern access and use of data [MFS10]. How data could be subject to regulation via commons governance institutions has been subsequently further analyzed within research on governing knowledge commons that have been defined as *institutionalized community governance of the sharing and, in some cases, creation, of information, science, knowledge, data, and other types of intellectual and cultural resources* [FMS14]. Its key insight would be how information resources are governed as a shared resource via a collective and not in markets via intellectual property rights regimes or state intervention [Mad20]. New technologies thereby would have played a vital role in the possible development of knowledge commons as they facilitated the ability to capture the previously uncapturable and to draw value from it by means of advanced data analytics [Pur17].

Studies, therefore, attempted to adapt Ostrom's design principles for collective self-managing institutions and translate them to and extract valuable insights for data governance [Ins21a; Coy+20; Pra19]. This further resulted in discussions and analyses, [Ins21a; WHB22] on various

models of data stewardship, such as data trusts, data foundations, data cooperatives or data collaboratives [WHB22]. Data collaboratives thereby have been described as new emerging forms of partnerships where privately held data is made accessible for analysis. The collaboration between participants that is facilitated within these structures aims to result in new insights and innovation and to unlock the public good potential of previously siloed data [Ver20]. Our approach to data collaboratives and collaborative data sharing is based on many advancements in the technological field that were presented in the span of the last 20 years. We draw from such solutions as personal data stores [Sha+21b], distributed learning [KMR15; Ver+20], or even data licensing [Bas00]. What we propose is a mild formalization of the set of existing technological solutions adjusted to mitigate the issues arising from the current data governance methods. For the sake of better generalization, we limit ourselves to the method-agnostic notation, not to exclude any new or existing technological solutions that may be adopted to serve as a building block of new data collaboratives. Our method of defining the boundaries and goals of data collaboratives is based on the identification of common principles and basic computational operations that the participants can perform. In the following, we introduce the goal of data collaboration and the four essential principles that define it. Next, we elaborate on the notation of collaborative computing that is a baseline for the presented structure. Lastly, we introduce the current limitations of the proposed approach.

4.4.3.1.5 The goal of the Data Collaborative The proposed approach is based on applying decentralized learning for better data governance and could provide a substantial leap towards independent and self-sovereign data management inside trusted communities.

The main goal of data collaboratives is to allow trusted parties to establish a private or hybrid (public-private) collaboration and train one shared model without transferring the raw data beyond the local storage. In this sense, the data collaborative is an applied case of data access and data sharing - because each party is allowing only access to derivative aggregates of its resources - and does not consent to any transfer of raw data. It, therefore reflects demands set by the Data Act proposal with regard to access rights that should implement the data protection by design and the data minimization principle (in-situ instead of ex-situ access right). The trained model is then shared between all parties. We deliberately do not define here the notion of a party or a participant to the collaborative. We assume that it may be a physical person or an organisation and that the shared data may or may not constitute personal data. All these scenarios will require different legal approaches, as different types of rules may or may not apply, depending on a specific use-case. However, any approach to data governance in the technological layer requires a degree of abstraction that would allow for a fine generalization of the presented method, and any synthetic definition of a participant may be harmful to this objective.

The main objective of the data collaborative is to always perform at least one collaborative computation (which is abstractly defined in the next section of this paper). At the same time, the collaborative may be capable of tracking the individual contribution of all participants with regard to the final output. Although this is a distinct problem on its own, that is overviewed as an open challenge, a data collaborative might therefore strengthen control over data in several ways. First, by not requiring participants to transfer raw data which is directly embodied in the

four essential principles that define the data collaborative. Data access within our data collaborative would therefore be less invasive with regard to potential privacy, intellectual property, or commercial interests the stakeholders might have with regard to their data. Second, if we assume that the data collaborative is able to track and evaluate the contribution of each participant, this could enhance trust in the collaboratives as it empowers individuals to understand their contribution and thereby promotes the participation and collaboration to the collective model. Furthermore, one might envision the possible implementation of rules that enable proprietary or contractual claims with regard to the trained model that are made dependent on the proportion of the registered contribution by participants. At the same time, the collaborative could succeed in breaking up previously siloed data and thus ensuring its availability to other stakeholders. Where previous regulatory approaches failed, data collaboratives might contribute to reconcile conflicting interests in data.

As briefly mentioned in the previous paragraph, we define our commons management system through the set of four essential principles that are used to classify it as a data collaborative and which are loosely connected to previous attempts to transpose Ostrom's principles on managing the commons to data governance frameworks. Firstly, the data collaboratives should provide an accessible infrastructure for performing various analytical tasks without the necessity to transfer raw data beyond the participants' devices. Consequently, the proposed architecture strengthens control of participants over their local datasets. [**Decentralised Data Storage**]. Once the model is trained (or once an analytical task is accomplished) it should be governed by all the members (in proportion to their marginal contribution). Shared governance is a key guarantee that all the members will benefit from joint participation in the analytical tasks. Collective-choice arrangements could be realized by allowing participants to the collaborative to create their own rules and governance conditions. What's more, it can be envisaged that during the establishment of the collaborative, parties establish operations and actions that require a certain number of votes and can only be initialized if a certain quorum has been reached. [**Shared Model Governance**]. The formal structure of a data collaborative should be mostly implementation-agnostic. This is because any structure or implementation that satisfies the baseline definition and four essential principles can be treated as a data collaborative - irrespective of the implementation details [**Universality**]. Finally, data collaboratives can be established and executed in many different ways, combining the available technology with local needs. However, each data collaborative should be able to perform at least one analytical operation in a distributed environment [**Minimal Utility - Collaborative Computation**].

These principles can be fulfilled by the utilization of many already existing technologies. The last decade has seen the development of large-batch synchronous distributed learning [Dea+12], federated learning [[Ane+19; Beh+21; Che+19; Kon+17; Mä; McM+17; Ram+19; TBF22; Wan+21; ZLG20; Zha+22]] and other "no-peek" approaches such as split neural network [Vep+18] that allowed us to develop a completely different mindset regarding machine learning, escaping the dogma of collecting the whole data in one centralized location in order to develop a model based on the chosen objective. Although many challenges regarding those methods are still open [Kai+21], decentralised learning has seen a number of use-cases that may be seen as a showcase of the potential hidden in that approach [Che+19; Har+19; Ram+19]. Most importantly, decentralised learning may serve as the backbone of a different approach to data gover-

nance, where the data “owners” are able to establish closed communities of high and medium trust and then collaboratively participate to the training of ML models.

4.4.3.1.6 Problem Statement and Basic Definitions for Collaborative Computations The data collaborative is established between three or more parties that share an interest in performing one or more collaborative computation and retaining controls of outputs of those computations throughout the existence of the partnership. The principle of **Minimal Utility** requires the parties to be interested in performing at least one collaborative computation throughout the existence of the collective partnership. Therefore, we need to define – at least briefly – the notion of this term. For this, we use mostly the notation used in the theory of decentralised machine learning [Ver+20; Wan+21]. We assume to have a set of available clients (that are synonymous to the notion of parties of participants) $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ and each client C_i stores a set of data $X_i = \{(\bar{x}_1, y_1), (\bar{x}_2, y_2), (\bar{x}_3, y_3), \dots, (\bar{x}_p, y_p)\}$ where each (\bar{x}_i, y_i) is a one sample, \bar{x}_i is a vector n-dimensional vector containing all features and y_i is a label that is attributed to the vector \bar{x}_i . The objective is to estimate a surrogate for a hidden function $h(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$, that assign a label y to the observation \bar{x} . Machine Learning training method recreates a hyporeport function $\hat{h}(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$ as a proxy of $h(\bar{x})$ such that $\hat{h}(\bar{x}) \sim h(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$. We want this approximation to be the closest to the unknown function $h(\bar{x})$ as possible. We can generally express that idea as:

$$\min \mathcal{P}[\hat{h}(\bar{x}) \neq h(\bar{x})] \leq \epsilon \tag{4.6}$$

where ϵ is some previously defined margin of error that we can tolerate given the projected task. The generalised error on distribution D and in relation to some underlying function $h(\bar{x})$ can be defined as generalization error: $\mathcal{L}(\hat{h}(\bar{x})) = [\hat{h}(\bar{x}) \neq h(\bar{x})] \leq \epsilon$ Equation 4.6 describes the generalization error that our hyporeport function is making on the given population. During training, we don't have access to the whole population, but only to the training sample that we have gathered for that particular purpose. In a centralized scenario, the dataset will be defined as a collection of data gathered from all available clients, i.e. $\mathbf{X} = X_1 \cup X_2 \dots \cup X_i$, where X_i is data stored at the client C_i . In such an environment, we can directly train one hyporeport function $\hat{h}(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$, and then evaluate it on the possessed data:

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{h}(\bar{x})) = \mathcal{P}[(\bar{x} \neq h(\bar{x}))] \tag{4.7}$$

Equation 4.7 samples from a dataset, comparing the output of the function to the original label (independent) variable attached to the feature vector \bar{x}_i Equation 4.7 also assumes that we can gather the whole dataset X in one (or few) centralised locations, irrespective of the number of clients that have generated said data. Although this is a common assumption for a centralised scenario, such an action devoid independent actors of any control over their own data.

Therefore, we assume that clients do not want to consent to direct data transfer and are only considering engaging in a collaboration which does not require them to take such steps. Given that the participants have limited knowledge about the information coming from other distributions than their own, they still may be interested in information that could help them better

understand the whole population. In such cases, all the actors may engage in a collaborative activity of collaborative computation (e.g., distributed analytics or distributed learning): in the first case (distributed analytics), they are interested in a single statistic regarding samples from other distributions; in the second (distributed learning) they participate to learn a hyporeport function $\hat{h}(\bar{x})$ that minimizes the local loss functions on the datasets distributed differently than their own. Both distributed computations, as well as the notion of **collaborative computation** in general, can be formalized as the composite function:

$$F(\hat{X}) = F(\hat{X}_1) \oplus F(\hat{X}_2) \oplus \dots \oplus F(\hat{X}_i) \quad (4.8)$$

$F(\hat{X}_1) \oplus F(\hat{X}_2) \oplus \dots \oplus F(\hat{X}_i)$ are functions computed locally at each client, such that $F(\hat{X}) : R^d \rightarrow R$, and equation 4.8 denotes the composition of all local contributions. Providing an example let us assume we have n clients each one possessing a dataset $X_p = \{(\bar{x}_1, y_1), (\bar{x}_2, y_2), (\bar{x}_3, y_3), \dots, (\bar{x}_p, y_p)\}$ that may be distributed differently, and the maximum length of the dataset $|X_p|$ may differ from client to client. Let us also assume that each vector \bar{x}_i contains n different features. In such a case, one may be interested in statistics regarding the selected features across the population. The function $F(\hat{X}_i)$ may in that case, locally compute the mean of the sample:

$$\bar{X}_i = \frac{1}{|X_i|} \sum_{i=1}^{|X_i|} x_i \quad (4.9)$$

Where for each dimension n we obtain one scalar describing the mean of the local samples. Such results can be then aggregated and once again averaged before returning the final vector:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{\bar{X}} \sum_{i=1}^{\bar{X}} \bar{X}_i \quad (4.10)$$

is calculated and returned to all participants of the collaborative. Another example of distributed computation is a collaborative approach to establishing the common hyporeport function $\hat{h}(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$ that is indirectly trained on data from all the clients. Given that the random variables are not independent and identically distributed, each local client can compute $F(\bar{X}_i) : \hat{h}_i(\bar{X}_i) \rightarrow y$ and send back only the aggregate representing the final hyporeport function \hat{h}_i the other members of the collaborative. Compound function function 4.8 will be then a global hyporeport function that is made from composition of the local hypotheses functions. One simple algorithm that can be utilized to perform such aggregation is FedAvg – a vanilla baseline for Federated Learning [Kon+17].

The following definitions are independent of any particular implementation design. It may be possible that all the local aggregates are send back to the Central Orchestration Node (CON) that is deployed by a third-party as a service [KPK22]. The universal notation of compound operations denoted as \oplus was employed specifically, not to limit the domain of possible implementation designs. Hence, collaborative computation can be defined as any function $F(\bar{X})$ that accepts

aggregates of the local functions and broadcasts the output to all the members who provided some aggregates of their local data.

Considering the multitude of circumstances under which the aforementioned methodology of data collaboratives can be used, it is advisable to define this concept as a set of principles that are fundamental to its existence, while the particularities of implementation may vary from case to case. Given an example, the personal data stores [Mon+14] may be seen as data collaborative, although their real implementation is quite different from what was presented here. On the other hand, existing solutions based on federated learning can be turned into data collaboratives. This flexibility is something that the concept of data property was devoid of. Hence, we believe, that the concept of data collaboratives is something that may fill up a gap in the current system of data governance.

4.4.4 Collaborative Contribution Function and Alpha-Amplification on the Example of Federated Learning

The following chapter contains work published in the article Amplified Contribution Analysis for Federated Learning (Advances in Intelligent Data Analysis XXII, Springer LNCS, Stockholm, Sweden, 2024), available at: [\(link\)](#)

4.4.4.1 Research Placement

The work on the family of functions that are able to detect the marginal contribution of a data collaborative member stems directly from the *rationale* behind the institution. Although not placed directly in the formal prerequisites quantifying a relationship as a *Data Collaborative* (as defined in Chapter 4.4.3), a tool to assess the marginal utility of a participant seems to be one of the open issues that are strictly connected to an idea of sharing a common burden of model training (data and resource wise). As explained in the previous Chapter, collaboratives try to take a different approach to the problem of property rights in data by establishing a consensual and mutually beneficial relationship that is based on data sharing. However, there may still be a need to employ some kind of incentive mechanism, that is able to separate contributing members from non-contributing members. During the search for such a mechanism, I tried to bypass the methods based on Game Theory, such as Shapley Value [Sha52] for two reasons. Firstly, they generally tend to be expensive in terms of time complexity, especially including the problem of externalities [Ski20]. Even assuming a polynomial time complexity that can be achieved via sampling [CGT09], the issue of calculating marginal contribution can possibly escalate to a main computational task performed by the collaborative (which would be contrary to its non-shareholding structure). On the other hand, those types of solutions often tend to quantify the precise marginal contribution based on the transferable utility. Once again, taking Shapley Value as an example, it generates a total surplus generated by the coalition of all players. While such calculation could be useful for establishing individual shares in the profit generated by collect endeavour, as explained before, creating a proprietary structure is not a goal of Data Collaborative.

Because of the aforementioned reasons, the search for an appropriate class of functions has turned towards (computationally) inexpensive evaluators that are better suitable for detecting non-contributing or polluting members than for specifying a precise pay-off vector, as in the case of Shapley Value [Sha52]. The goal was to find an alternative version of Leave-one-out function that shares the same (or - at least - similar) computational complexity but is more effective when it comes to detecting malicious clients (while the precise meaning of the word *malicious* will be elaborated on in the experimental section). The following chapter introduces advances in this regard.

4.4.4.2 Related Work

The issue of quantifying the marginal impact of the particular subset of the dataset on the general model has been under examination for several years up to this date. In the current literature, the majority of available solutions are based on the Shapley Value [Sha52]. In 2017, [CL17] introduced the idea of using cooperative games theory to evaluate personal data in networks. Similarly, [GZ19] introduced Data Shapley - a method for assessing the impact of each observation on the final model's performance. This was later expanded by [Jia+19]. Works of [Wan+20; Liu+22b] employed this approach to the FL scenario. By labelling each client as a player and using the loss function as a value function, the whole learning process is structured as a cooperative game and the client's marginal contribution is embedded in the final pay-off vector. This approach comes with several issues, such as relatively high computational complexity that can act as a prohibitive factor, even if a sampling schema is employed to decrease the number of subsets that must be considered (calculating Shapley Value requires calculating all the $\mathcal{O}(2^N)$ subsets).

Some authors seek solutions outside the realms of cooperative game theory. In the [Lv+21], authors propose using pairwise correlation for detecting malicious clients. This approach can work efficiently, given that the group of unwanted models will always share some degree of similarity in parameters, which was not proven to be always guaranteed in the case of deep learning models. A data-driven approach was presented in [SKK21], where authors propose constructing a separate model for grading the marginal contributions of clients. The most similar method to our work was presented in [ZWP21], where authors also observe the usefulness of employing the cosine similarity between different vectors of parameters of local clients. However, they employ a different approach to this problem, as the contribution is calculated at the end of the whole training cycle, comparing the route of optimal gradient descent to a proposed one. Conversely, this chapter presents a dynamic schema that can produce contribution vectors each round without considerably slowing the training process. Another work that is similar to the work presented within this Chapter was included in [STW19], where the observation that gradients received from clients can be (temporarily) preserved to assemble and compare the efficiency of different models. However, this technique was limited solely to Shapley Value, which, once again - was ruled out due to reasons presented at the beginning of this chapter.

In addition to a novel method of quantifying the client's marginal contribution, this chapter presents a uniform notation that scales to every method of calculating the marginal differences between the assembled clients. While surveying the current State-of-the-Art, it became evident

that there is no consensus on how to (abstractly) approach the problem of marginal evaluation in FL scenario. While the works using Shapley Value [Wan+20; Jia+19; Liu+22b] are using notation directly inspired by [Sha52], the other articles [Lv+21; SKK21; ZWP21; STW19] often present one of its own origins, hence making it complicated to relate one method to another - while in fact - most of those methods express the exact same things. This chapter was, therefore, a nice opportunity to present a unified and simplified notation.

4.4.4.3 Methodology

4.4.4.3.1 Notation and Aggregation Masks The term aggregation mask is used to describe a process of manipulating the client's weights before the actual aggregation in order to detect the difference in performance between the global and marginal coalition of clients. Hence, the sole usage of masks neither influences the actual aggregation of the clients nor impacts the sampling schema. However, results of comparing different coalitions can be used to either adjust the weighting or sampling schema or simply blacklist some clients from attending the training.

Definition 2 (Aggregation Mask). *Given the aggregation procedure*

$$\theta_{(m)}^{t+1} = \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j \theta_j^t = \theta^t - \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j (\theta^t - \theta_j^t) = \theta^t - \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j \Delta_j \quad (4.11)$$

aggregation mask is a set of weights $\{\phi_j | \forall j \in S\}$ such that it fulfils $\sum_j^{|S|} \phi_j = 1$ and $\theta_{(m)}^{t+1} \neq \theta^{t+1}$.

In other words, a mask is an auxiliary weights aggregation that does not serve as a direct update. The need to define an auxiliary mask comes from the possible confusion that may arise when mixing the notation used in FL with the notation used to denote the process of client evaluation. It is essential to understand that the mask (as defined in 2) is used only to express the weights used during the evaluation process, not the actual weights aggregating process. Confusion may arise from the fact, that in FL, it is not uncommon to use auxiliary weights while aggregating the parameters.⁹ Using the concept of aggregation mask, it is possible to define the two most important masks used throughout this work. Namely, the Leave-one-out Mask and the Alpha-Amplification Mask, denoted respectively with $\theta_{(L,i)}^{t+1}$ and $\theta_{(\alpha,i)}^{t+1}$.

Definition 3 (Leave-one-out Mask). *The Leave-one-out mask denoted by $\theta_{(L,i)}$ is an aggregation mask that fully conceals the contribution of client i . Formally:*

$$\theta_{(L,i)}^{t+1} = \theta^t - \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j \Delta_j \quad (4.12)$$

$$\text{where } \phi_i = 0 \text{ and } \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j = 1 \quad (4.13)$$

⁹Even more confusing, the weights parametrization is sometimes referred to as *sampling*.

Figure 4.5: Visual representation of the mask concept. Each time a set of agents (small rectangles at the bottom of the infographic) sends gradients to an orchestrator (large rectangle at the top of the infographic), the orchestrator can prepare a corresponding mask that will be used for evaluation, irrespective of the weighting schema used for performing an actual update. Leave-one-out mask zeros the contribution of the i -th client, while the alpha-amplification reinforces it by alpha factor. Those masked gradients may then be used in specific evaluation functions.

Definition 4 (The Alpha-Amplification Mask). *The Alpha-Amplification Mask denoted $\theta_{(\alpha,i)}$ is an aggregation mask that amplifies the contribution of client i by the parameter α . Formally:*

$$\theta_{(\alpha,i)}^{t+1} = \theta^t - \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j \Delta_j \tag{4.14}$$

where $\phi_j = \alpha$ **and** $\alpha + \sum_{j \in S} \phi_j = 1$ (4.15)

Remark 4.4.3. *The L (e.g. $\theta_{(L,i)}$) is a constant signaling use of the leave-one-out mask. However, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ is a parameter that controls the amplification. If α is less or equal to one, it should be treated as a weight multiplier. If the α is larger than one, then it should be treated as preserving α copies of the client's i gradient during the weight's aggregation. This provides an intuitive interpretation of the mask and allows us to convert between those two interpretations. Hence, if $\alpha > 1$, $\phi_i = \frac{\alpha}{n}$ and $\phi_j = \frac{1-\alpha}{n-1}$.*

Remark 4.4.4. *The parameter α allows us to control the sensitivity of the analysis. More precisely, it allows us to decide to what extent we want to amplify the contribution of the evaluated client. Setting the parameter α to 0 reduces the alpha-amplification mask to a leave-one-out mask, i.e. $\theta_{(\alpha=0,i)} = \theta_{(L,i)}$. On the other hand, an increase in the alpha parameter will result*

in the marginalisation of other clients. At the limit, the aggregation mask will provide weights that are identical to those of an evaluated client.

In addition to what was presented above, the loss function will be denoted with $\mathcal{L} : \theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. To simplify the notation, shorthand notation omits the concept of the hyporeport function while defining the loss function, substituting just the matrix of weights in that place. We often omit the dependence on data matrix X and the corresponding label vector \bar{y} .

4.4.4.3.2 Collaborative Contribution Function and Universal Masking

Definition 5 (Collaborative Contribution Function). *The Collaborative Contribution Function Ψ , given the previous matrix of weights θ^t , set of gradients $\{\Delta^t | \forall \Delta_j^t \in S\}$ and a loss function $\mathcal{L}(\cdot)$ returns an n -dimensional vector $\bar{\psi} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ that maps every client to its respective marginal contribution calculated by using a selected mask (m). Formally:*

$$\Psi_{(m)} : \mathcal{L}, \theta^t, \Delta^t \rightarrow \bar{\psi} \in \mathbb{R}^d \quad (4.16)$$

$$\text{where } \forall i \in S : \bar{\psi}_i \approx \mathcal{L}(\theta^{t+1}) - \mathcal{L}(\theta_{(m,i)}^{t+1}) \quad (4.17)$$

is called a **Contribution Index** of a client i .

This definition implies that the contribution index of each client should always be bounded by a co-domain of a loss function. Hence, two collaborative contribution functions are always expressed in the same units as long as they are calculated using the same loss function.

Definition 6 (The Leave One Out Function). *The Leave-one-out Function is a Collaborative Contribution Function Ψ that calculates the contribution of the client i using the leave-one-out mask:*

$$\Psi_{(L)} = \mathcal{L}(\theta^{t+1}) - \mathcal{L}(\theta_{(L,i)}^{t+1}) \quad \forall i \in S \quad (4.18)$$

Definition 7 (The Alpha-Amplified Function). *The Alpha-Amplified Function is a Collaborative Contribution Function Ψ that amplifies the possible contribution of the client i by parameter α using an amplification mask and is defined as:*

$$\Psi_{(\alpha)} = \mathcal{L}(\theta^{t+1}) - \mathcal{L}(\theta_{(\alpha,i)}^{t+1}) \quad \forall i \in S \quad (4.19)$$

Remark 4.4.5. *Both functions calculate client contribution, but the yielded contribution indices will have an opposite sign. For the leave-one-out function, if the client has a positive impact on the training, masking its presence will result in a lower score. Because of that, positive scores returned by the leave-one-out method are evidence of a positive contribution, while negative scores are on the contrary. For the alpha-amplification function, the difference will be positive if the client is deemed to be harmful to the training while remaining negative if the client is positively contributing. For this reason, alpha-amplification can be interpreted as a threat score.*

Remark 4.4.6. *It is essential to highlight the importance of noticing the difference between the score returned by the collaborative contribution functions and the score of the model that was updated using masked weights. The score of a model is simply a loss value returned when evaluating this model against a given dataset, i.e. $\mathcal{L}(\theta_{m,i}^t)$. The contribution function is always a difference between the loss of the baseline model and the masked model, i.e. $\mathcal{L}(\theta^t) - \mathcal{L}(\theta_{(m,i)}^t)$.*

A remark must be made about the time complexity. Without the loss of generality, we assume that forward propagation through the neural network (without backpropagation) constitutes one computational unit. The complexity of the baseline leave-one-out is $\mathcal{O}(N)$, as it is required to perform exactly $N + 1$ forward propagations through the network. Similarly, alpha-amplification requires testing only $N + 1$ combinations, so its time complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N)$. However, as evidenced by the next section, it tends to capture better the behaviour of the malfunctioning sensors (clients).

4.4.4.4 Experiments

The following experiments were designed to explore two hypotheses specifically:

1. The *Alpha-Amplification* function, in relation to the leave-one-out baseline, can better detect a set of weights that is harmful to the general training, i.e. the average scores of such clients exceed one standard deviation of the sample.
2. In the case of local splits being non-IID, the collaborative contribution function (be it LOO or alpha-amplification) exhibits lower confidence in clients with original data, which was not subject to any transformation or dilatations.

4.4.4.4.1 Datasets In order to test formulated hypotheses, six different simulations using three different datasets are performed, namely: MNIST [Noal], FMNIST [XRV17], and CIFAR10 [Noac]. The datasets are split using two different methods to obtain heterogenous and homogenous label distribution across the clients. Homogeneous distribution assumes that the labels are distributed uniformly across all the clients. Heterogenous distribution is generated using Dirichlet Distribution, as this method was employed before in some papers concerning FL e.g., [Red+22] uses Dirichlet Distribution to create highly heterogeneous splits. While the homogeneous and heterogeneous splits are being employed, the total number of data samples at each node is assumed to be the same. The exemplary split is visualized in figure 4.6.

To simulate clients whose participation is detrimental to the training, a set of transformations and dilatations is performed on the first five clients in each split. Three types of data modification are distinguished: Gaussian noise addition, blur transformation and image rotation. All clients affected by those modifications are labelled as *malfunctioning sensors*. The remaining five clients are labelled as *valid sensors*. Noise addition is performed by firstly sampling a noise matrix from a Gaussian Distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ that is multiplied by a scaling constant c and then adding it to the original image. For client number 0, the scaling constant equals 0.4, while for client numbers 1 and 2, the constant equals 0.15 and 0.10, respectively. Client number 3 is blurred by using a 3×3 Gaussian kernel, while the rotation on client number 4 is performed by first selecting a random angle from the interval 0 to 45 and then applying the rotation. Transformations are illustrated in Figure 4.7.

4.4.4.4.2 Experimental Setup To solve the MNIST classification problem, a convolutional neural network with three convolutional layers and another four fully connected layers is em-

Figure 4.6: Showcase of the data split using homogeneous (left column) and heterogeneous (right column) for all three datasets in the form of an inverted histogram. The number of examples placed on a particular client is displayed on the x-axis. Each colour corresponds to a different label. Clients from 0 to 9 are placed on the y-axis. As evident from the figure, the homogeneous split assumes that the distribution across labels is uniform. On the other hand, heterogeneous splits are generated with Dirichlet Distribution.

ployed. Both types of layers use Rectified Linear Units. Additionally, the fully connected layers employ neuron dropout at a rate of 20%. FMNIST classification task is solved by a modified version of ResNet34 with a changed classification head. The CIFAR10 problem is solved with a modified version of ResNet101. To solve the federated problem, a generalized version of FedAvg - the FedOpt [Red+22] is employed. The global learning rate is set to $\eta = 1.0$, and the number of global epochs is equal to 80. During the local training, we use Stochastic Gradient Descent, with a learning rate equal to $\hat{\eta} = 0.01$ and batch size equal to 32. This is kept constant across all of the three benchmark datasets.

4.4.4.5 Results

This section presents the results of the experiments. The subsection 4.4.4.5.1 showcases individual training progression and contribution values registered for particular nodes each round. Subsection 4.4.4.5.2 presents average contribution values registered for each node. Section 4.4.4.6 presents commentary on the results. The leave-one-out and alpha-amplification values were calculated simultaneously in the same simulation run to keep all the constant fixed. While

Figure 4.7: Examples of data transformations used on all three datasets. The first row contains a sample of unchanged data. Such data is located on half of the deployed sensors. The remaining five rows showcase different types of malfunctions, resulting in rotation, blur, light noise, moderate noise and heavy noise, respectively (from left to right).

the leave-one-out is impossible to tune by default, the alpha parameter in alpha-amplification was set to $\alpha = 5$.

4.4.4.5.1 Individual Contribution Values Using the functions defined in Definition 6 and 7, it is possible to register a marginal contribution value for every client each round. Figure 4.8 showcases those values for a selected simulation run (run no. 3). The same results obtained for the heterogeneous split are presented in Figure 4.9. The Leave-one-out values are placed in the first column, while the Alpha-Amplification values are placed in the second column of the Figure. Values registered on malfunctioning sensors (sensors on which the data was transformed) are highlighted in red. Please take into consideration that the Leave-one-out function and Alpha-Amplification functions are reversed wrt to each other. It implies that a positive Alpha-Amplification value will denote a detrimental marginal effect of a participant on a selected model, while a negative will imply a positive marginal influence. On the contrary, a negative Leave-one-out value will signalize the detrimental influence of a client, and a positive will indicate that the client enhances the general performance of the aggregated model. This section contains only values registered for the third simulation run.

4.4.4.5.2 Average Contribution Values While the previous subsection presented values registered for each round, this section presents contribution values averaged across the iterations.

Figure 4.8: Leave-one-out (as defined in Definition 6) and Alpha-Amplification (as defined in Definition 4) values registered for each of the clients every round (Training Run No. 3, Homogeneous Setting). The Leave-one-out values are placed in the first column, while the Alpha-Amplification values are placed in the second column of the Figure. Values registered on malfunctioning sensors (sensors on which the data was transformed) are highlighted in red. Please take into consideration that the Leave-one-out function and Alpha-Amplification functions are reversed wrt to each other.

Given five different simulation runs, it was additionally possible to average obtained values across all simulation runs - obtaining one global outlook on the performance on of the Alpha-Amplification in comparison to the Leave-one-out methods. The results were displayed in Figure 4.10. The left-hand side of the Figure contains five plots representing Leave-one-out and Alpha-Amplification values obtained during MNIST, FMNIST and CIFAR 10 simulations run in an IID (homogeneous) setting. The right-hand side of this figure contains six plots representing the leave-one-out and alpha-amplification values obtained during the simulations run in a Non-IID (heterogeneous) setting. The identification numbers of nodes are plotted on the x-axis, while the average score is plotted on the y-axis. The *malfunctioning sensors* are coloured red, while the *valid sensors* are coloured green. The solid black line represents the baseline value at point 0.0 (no visible contribution), and the dotted black line represents the *cut-off* value at the level of one standard deviation of a sample. Once again, please note that the Leave-one-out and alpha Amplification Scores are sign-flipped by definition: a negative Leave-one-out score indicates a negative impact on the trained model, while the positive Alpha-Amplification value represents the same situation. The numerical form of those results is presented in Table 4.5.

Figure 4.9: Leave-one-out (as defined in Definition 6) and Alpha-Amplification (as defined in Definition 4) values registered for each of the clients every round (Training Run No. 3, Heterogeneous Setting). A heterogeneous setting implies that the split is generated using the method described in Subsection 4.4.4.1 and visualized in Figure 4.6.

4.4.4.6 Commentary

Examination of the presented results allows one to draw several conclusions about the behaviour of the Alpha-Amplification function and, as a consequence, allows to formulate a preliminary answer to the hypotheses. Firstly, the Alpha-Amplification serves well when used as a threat detection tool. In almost every of the simulation runs (except the non-IID CIFAR10 dataset), the tested function can detect all three clients with excessive noise, often also detecting clients with datasets transformed by blur or rotation. On the other hand, the Leave-one-out fails in the majority of the cases, often detecting no more than one *noised* client. Hence, it seems that the Alpha-amplification can handle better the task of *malfunctioning clients* detection than the Leave-one-out baseline. This provides an answer to the first hypothesis. The empirical evidence suggests that the Alpha-Amplification score of *malfunctioning sensors* exceeds one standard deviation of the sample, while the Leave-one-out score of the same sensors often fails to do so.¹⁰ Secondly, in the case of Alpha-Amplification, there is no observable detrimental effect of the data heterogeneity on the *malfunctioning sensor detection*. Although Alpha-Amplification

¹⁰The placed threshold was defined in relation to the standard deviation of the sample, but it is possible to test both functions against a different detection threshold. Standard deviation was chosen, as it is fairly straightforward to interpret and present..

CLIENT ID	MNIST				FMNIST				CIFAR10			
	HOM		HET		HOM		HET		HOM		HET	
	LOO	ALPHA	LOO	ALPHA	LOO	ALPHA	LOO	ALPHA	LOO	ALPHA	LOO	ALPHA
0	-0.043	0.208	-0.028	0.756	-0.904	3.871	-0.648	3.888	-1.520	8.705	-1.449	10.251
1	-0.064	0.256	-0.039	0.541	-0.892	3.512	-0.740	5.027	-0.677	2.926	-0.523	2.899
2	-0.073	0.314	-0.042	0.858	-0.789	3.266	-0.811	3.329	-0.277	1.295	-0.187	2.043
3	0.017	0.043	0.104	0.036	0.647	-0.962	0.705	-0.728	0.731	-1.004	0.750	-0.333
4	0.009	0.136	0.033	0.462	0.362	-0.439	0.630	-0.071	0.312	-0.309	0.379	0.043
5	0.068	0.014	0.112	0.277	0.514	-0.863	0.541	-0.378	0.483	-0.753	0.597	-0.027
6	0.052	0.036	0.117	0.346	0.448	-0.879	0.521	-0.202	0.487	-0.778	0.509	-0.224
7	0.073	0.032	-0.004	0.182	0.468	-0.882	0.449	0.073	0.511	-0.816	0.629	-0.179
8	0.049	0.021	0.173	0.056	0.558	-0.903	0.603	-0.040	0.486	-0.753	0.522	-0.195
9	0.042	-0.003	0.094	0.366	0.467	-0.858	0.734	-0.098	0.500	-0.780	0.550	-0.426

Table 4.5: Averaged Contribution Values portrayed in Figure 4.10 presented in a numerical form.

works well for threat detection, it generally does not penalize the clients with healthy data, even in the case of a heterogeneous environment. It can be explained by the fact that while increasing the impact of a *malfunctioning sensor* is detrimental to training, the amplification of weights provided by a *valid sensor* does not affect the training to that extent in the homogeneous scenario or may cause drift of weights towards values that better fit the local (client's) distribution in the heterogeneous case. This also implies, that while Alpha-Amplification is a promising threat-detection tool, it may now be always advisable to use it as a method of universal contribution quantification. However, this depends also on the chosen sensitivity. As the alpha parameter was set to $\alpha = 5$ during the experiments, the Alpha-Amplification function tends to heavily amplify the signal from the tested client. A lower value of alpha would allow us to build a more universal contribution index (capturing also the positive behaviour of valid sensors), but would not yield such conclusive results for the *malfunctioning* batch. This also portrays well the flexibility of the presented method, which is not present in the Leave-one-out baseline.

4.4.5 Conclusions

This work has been carried on undeniably an extensive topic, merging the empirical ML research with normative constructs derived from either current regulation on personal data processing or policy issues on data governance. It would simply not be feasible to gather all the necessary remarks under the umbrella of one report. What could be achievable - and what this work tried to do - was to provide a fundamental breach between the concept of data collaboratives and federated learning and then to advance the start-of-the-art on the second topic (with respect to the problems that may be relevant to the notion of data collaboratives).

The research started with a very general sketch of European Data Governance and how it shifted from data property to data access within the last few years. The modern debate on the commodification of data has been going on for at least three decades, so it was never the goal to depict it in full detail, as this issue is just too vast and complicated to be narrated in one contained chapter (or paper). However, this sketch allowed the author to introduce a bridge

between the policy endeavours on one side and the rising technology on the other. From the author's perspective, it was necessary to tie the proposed technological solution to a real normative need - and the introductory remarks on the (failed) concept of data property served that purpose. As the legislators are looking for new methods of governing the data, a natural connection between the methods of decentralised machine learning and data can be exposed and utilized.

Beyond any doubt, that connection between data sharing and methods of learning is not entirely a new concept, as the last two centuries have provided many examples of work delivered exactly on that conjecture - from the concept of data licensing to Personal Data Stores, naming a few. However, for any technological policy to be implementable, two prerequisites must take place: a new normative concept must be rooted in the axiomatic structure of the system, and the technological framework must be complete and mature in the state to be widely adopted by the private and public sectors. More often than not, only one of those points is fulfilled, leading to an incomplete statement of intent expressed on behalf of the legislator, either failing due to a complete lack of placement in the current normative system or the inadequacy of the technology that is being presented as a solution to a problem. The first example can be illustrated by the case of Federated Learning - and the misunderstanding that the sole usage of it makes the system GDPR-compliant. As it was argued in the course of this research, this is not always the case - from the perspective of the GDPR, the usage of a specific learning algorithm remains irrelevant as the Regulation does not deal with precise methods of processing the data, as instead with the abstract process itself, placing emphasis on the rights and obligations that arise if the minimum criterion of applicability is fulfilled. The second example can be encountered while reading numerous policy briefs on the topic of a specific technology from a normative perspective. It is seldom a case that those documents dedicate much attention to the comparison of how the overviewed technology fits the current state-of-the-art. Probably caused by a shallow understanding of the state-of-the-art itself, those documents tend to follow a closed pattern of proposing the same technological solutions but distinguished under a different name. This is highly unproductive, as it never leads to achieving rational outcomes - an overarching goal of every policy. The battle for Alternative Data Governance has been going on for years, with many exotic proposals, such as Personal Data Stores, never fully realized.

The author's search for a more actionable result was based on the assumption that whatever will be proposed will fulfil those two prerequisites. The shift towards data access and data sharing has coincided with the advancements in decentralised machine learning. Perhaps for the first time in the history of modern data governance - every such proposal was rooted in the normative axioms of the system. In the last decade, a legal debate over the property of personal data has been taking place, with contesting sides arguing whether the legal constructs related to property can be - at least by extension - applied to personal data. While this debate can not be entirely referred to here, as explained in the chapter on data collaboratives, it is highly probable that the debate will be decided in favour of data access and sharing. This validates the proposal of Data Collaboratives, as it places in in the context of desired normative changes. Concerning the second prerequisite, a mature and implementable technology, the advent of decentralised learning methods has rendered concepts such as Data Collaboratives fully realizable. Previous technological proposals - even if rooted in the current normative regime - often lacked

the maturity that would allow them to be implementable on a larger scale. Providing example, Personal Data Stores was an innovative proposal that could potentially allow for license-based personal data processing. However - they were never in a state that would allow them to be widely adopted by the private and public sectors. Moreover, since the enactment of GDPR and other popularisation of consent-based approaches to personal data processing, the proposal has lost its normative relevance.

The second example - one concerning Personal Data Stores - is also why the author has tried not just to propose Federated Learning as a tool for promoting data availability and accessibility. The *Data Collaborative* is just a name, and *Federated Learning* is just another method of Decentralised Machine Learning. It is entirely possible that the name of Data Collaboratives will not be recognizable in years to come, while the advancements of Decentralised Machine Learning will expand the state-of-the-art algorithms far more efficiently than Federated Averaging proposed by McMahan et al. However, the goal here was to present an abstract entity - a concept that is not confined to just a name and a single algorithm. That is why much time and effort was dedicated to first distinguish the characteristic features of each Data Collaborative - and then to place them in the context of the actual Machine Learning formalisation. This way, the concept could outgrow its name and original proposal - adjusting to available policy needs and technological capabilities. Until we learn to speak about technology-related policy in this way - focusing on an abstract and general concept but heavily rooted in the mathematical formulation - we will hardly arrive at any satisfactory conclusion.

The rest of the work carried out during this research focused on specific technological issues connected to Federated Learning. While it was still connected to the idea of Data Collaboratives, it was also strictly connected to specific areas of the current state of the art on the topic. The friction between the need to present a solution with a sufficient level of concreteness while presenting technological research with the need to generalize concepts while presenting studies on the normative system was undeniably one of the most challenging parts of this work, putting to the test the author creativity when it comes to merging incongruent methodologies.

In relation to all the precise technological solutions presented so far, the problem of marginal client contribution and personalization via clustering should be highlighted. The answer to the first one was presented in the form of the Alpha-Amplification for Federated Learning.

Regarding marginal client contribution in a federated setting, the solution is most often sought in the realms of Game Theory - directly employing Shapley Value as one of the most popular tools. However, the author's search for an appropriate tool went beyond the realms of Game Theory, seeking an appropriate solution instead in the natural properties of the (federated) gradients. As shown in the relevant section, by manipulating the gradient of each client, one can better detect the possibility that a certain client is harmful to the process while still retaining the computational complexity of a Leave-one-out (LOO) method. This is certainly good news, as an inexpensive tool for filtering the *noise-makers* and *data-polluters* is an existential issue for Data Collaboratives.

The other technological issue that was explored during the author's research was connected to the model's personalization via gradients-based clustering. Once again, manipulation of the (federated) gradients yielded satisfactory results when compared to the State-of-the-Art. This

research was not directly presented in this report as it is still a work in progress. However, in relation to the upcoming endeavours, the issue of personalization is one of the keys to future research directions, as the ability to personalize models is another vital issue that should be resolved on the level of Data Collaboratives - as the lack of satisfactory personalization may discourage members from participating in the collaborative in the future.

Figure 4.10: Averaged contribution values across all the five simulation runs. The left-hand side of the Figure contains five plots representing Leave-one-out and Alpha-Amplification values obtained during MNIST, FMNIST and CIFAR 10 simulations run in an IID (homogeneous) setting. The right-hand side of this figure contains six plots representing the leave-one-out and alpha-amplification values obtained during the simulations run in a Non-IID (heterogeneous) setting. The identification numbers of nodes are plotted on the x-axis, while the average score is plotted on the y-axis. The *malfunctioning sensors* are coloured red, while the *valid sensors* are coloured green. The solid black line represents the baseline value at point 0.0 (no visible contribution), and the dotted black line represents the *cut-off* value at the level of one standard deviation of a sample. Note that the leave-one-out and alpha amplification scores are sign-flipped by definition: a negative leave-one-out score indicates a negative impact on the trained model, while the positive alpha amplification value represents the same situation.

4.5 Boundaries of data ownership: from concept to practice

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4.5.1 Abstract

Striving to find the most effective data governance system in the European Union over time not only does not lose its relevance, but on the contrary is gaining momentum. One of the frequently proposed models was the concept of data ownership, which, after being abandoned, seemed scientifically unattractive for a while, but now continues to be discussed among legal scholars and policymakers. Initially, the research aims to study the concept of data ownership in the classical legal doctrine with the analysis of data as an object of civil law, absolute and relative rights, and the possibility of introducing this approach into the legislation of EU countries. The research is then based on the transition from the classical legal doctrine in the usual perception of the concept of "property" to new approaches. This transition also leads to a different perception of the concepts of "owner" and "user".

The very concept of "property" may not be the most accurate and appropriate formulation to describe the requirements of data subjects. However, proposals to reform the data governance landscape have merit, especially in terms of access rights and data portability, which reinforce data rights.

Today, a fresh perspective on data ownership is essential, placing the greatest emphasis on personal data ownership in order to empower data subjects and expand their capabilities and control. In this area, the practical side and the improvements that individuals and companies with an awareness of data ownership can get are significant.

When it comes to the boundaries of data ownership, first of all it is necessary to look at the existing gaps and problems "from the inside", and find out what is generally considered problematic for the data subject itself? What are the expectations of the data subjects themselves? What level of control over their data do they consider acceptable and sufficient?

Along with efforts to find answers to these pressing questions, there is an obvious need to provide suggestions for improving the level and quality of personal data management, which could be satisfactory for data subjects. The issues of privacy, access to data, as well as the ability to use and benefit from their data by individuals can not be overlooked. Scientific research has been relatively little developed regarding individuals' perception of the value of their own data, while this provides new opportunities and makes it valuable for the possibility of understanding the views and needs of data subjects.

The solutions to all the problems voiced in the study in modern realities cannot be purely legal. The level of the law plays a crucial role, but the sphere related to data, in particular, personal data, should also find solutions in technical mechanisms.

Keywords: personal data, data ownership, information property, data subject, GDPR, data governance, information

4.5.2 Executive summary

Some time ago, solid scientific hopes were pinned on the so-called "data ownership" approach. Data ownership was supposed to "unlock the potential of the data economy and to those trying to re-empower individuals that have lost control over their data" [HP20]. However, the approach has not found legislative consolidation in the European Union, which has led to a situation where data is not recognized as property, including personal data. In addition to studying data ownership as such, the research is aimed at understanding the needs and requirements of individuals. The issue of the value of personal data is underestimated, as well as the opportunity to benefit from your own data. However, individuals, at least intuitively, feel they are in some way the owners of their personal data. However, not in all situations can they know exactly how this right of possession manifests itself. "They collect our personal data for creating a mosaic of human behaviors used to extract valuable knowledge for marketing purposes: our personal data is the new gold. On the other hand, individuals do not have the tools and capabilities to extract useful knowledge from their personal data." [Gui17].

The most important goal is to provide individuals with security and protection in relation to their data, including from third-party encroachments." Ownership of data and real control over it give hope for control over integrity and a guarantee that data will not be changed or destroyed without the consent of the owner. Increasing the level of control mechanisms on the part of data subjects increases their level of confidence in the data management system as a whole. Data subjects want to be able to securely share data with other data subjects, as well as businesses and corporations. People, especially in recent years of active digitalization, want to meaningfully exercise their rights and be aware of the processes of data collection and processing.

Furthermore, existing approaches for personal data valuation mostly neglect the individual perspective. [RE16] In this study, an attempt to see the problem through the "eyes" of the individual himself is made. Are lawmakers and policymakers taking into account the real wishes of the key stakeholders today after all?

4.5.3 Introduction

The issue of data ownership has no ambiguity in the economic sense in the world of market relations and the development of new technologies. In legal science, there is a clash with many complex obstacles, including the difference in approach of different legal systems, the stability of the civil law system, the intangible nature of data, etc. All these questions take place in the study for the best analysis of the concept of data ownership as a legal phenomenon.

Next, an analysis of this phenomenon is elaborated, taking into account modern realities and going beyond data ownership. The study examines the actual needs of data subjects, as well as their perception of the definition of personal data ownership, and also develops the issue of understanding the value of their own data.

There is also an analysis of the extent to which the expectations of data subjects are met in practice. An extensive analysis of the existing inconsistencies between the desires of individuals and the existing reality is given. Attempts have been made to analyze the main problems in this area on the basis of other studies and current legislation.

The practical side of data ownership plays an important role, attention is focused on offering solutions to the identified problems. Some provisions of the Data Act and its impact on the state of things for individuals are being analyzed.

The leitmotif of the study is the idea that data subjects do not want to have the status of data owner in a legal sense. It is important for them to have real control over their data and the opportunity to benefit in clear and simple ways. The issue of trust of data subjects is also important and is considered in the study.

Thus, efforts have been made to consider the issue of personal data ownership from the point of view of data subjects from different angles, as voluminously and fully as possible. It is mentioned that it is possible to solve existing problems with the help of technical measures, but due to the fact that the article is not of a technical nature, this remains a matter of "keep in mind".

4.5.3.1 Background

The theoretical basis of the research is the legal concepts and views of scientists and researchers who have analyzed various legal aspects of data ownership and related objects: data and its impact on legal processes, intellectual property law, competition law, legal aspects of personal data protection, and contract law. Among the researchers, one can point to such authors as Reiner Schulz and Dirk Staudenmayer, «EU Digital law»; Mark Burdon «Digital Data Collection and Information Privacy Law», Artsiom Nazaranka "Legal protection of personal data in Public Opinion"; Reiner Schulze and Fryderyk Zoll «European contract law», Łukasz Tomczyk «Protection of intellectual property rights in Poland from the perspective of polish youth», Oishika Banerj «Guide to intellectual property law in Germany»; Stanley Greenstein «Elevating Legal Informatics in the Digital Age» Zenobia Henge «Privacy and data ownership as a European Business Advantage», Kunbei Zhang «Can Chinese legislation on informational privacy benefit from European experience?».

Of particular interest are the works of Andreas Boerding, Nicolai Culik, Christian Doepke, Thomas Hoeren and Tim Juelicher «Data Ownership—A Property Rights Approach from a European Perspective», Dr. Mor Bakhoun, Dr. Beatriz Conde Gallego, Dr. Mark-Oliver Mackenrodt, Dr. Gintarė Surblytė-Namavičienė «Personal data in competition, consumer protection and intellectual property law. Towards a holistic approach?».

The connection of various aspects of property rights with data that acts as new knowledge in the field of human activity has become the subject of research by many authors, among whom it is possible to distinguish Michal Bernaczyk «The constitutional right to information in Poland. theory and practice», Birkinshaw, P., Varney, M. «Government and Information: The Law Relating to Access, Disclosure and their regulation», Mir Puigpelat «The access to public information in accordance with the Spanish legislation of transparency: a chronicle of a change of paradigm», Stefano Comino and Fabio Maria Manenti « Intellectual Property and Innovation in Information and Communication Technology».

Researchers pay enough attention to data as an object of national and international legal regulation. In this case, considering the legal nature of property, Adriano Zambon, in his work «Property: A conceptual analysis». He notes that the term "property" can be used to refer to

something that is not a commodity but has a commodity as an object. For example, intangible things that are registered under the name "information" are not designated by the term "property", but they are the object of something that is designated by the term "property". The work of V. Talimonchik is interesting in terms of the international aspect, which established that international treaties in the field of intellectual property protection do not take into account the peculiarities of the protection of complex objects, which the author relates to information and communication systems.

Herbert Zech considers information as an object of property rights, unlimited intellectual property. It manifests itself in personal aspects and even in property law. Therefore, the author classifies information, highlighting semantic, syntactic and structural information.

The works devoted to cross-border issues in accordance with the legislation of the European Union on the protection of personal data deserve attention. Thus, Shakila Bu-Pasha focuses on such problems as the interrelation of the global digital world, which objectively assumes the universality of various operating systems. «Cross-border issues under EU data protection law with regards to personal data protection». However, the legal regulation of relations referred to the activities of the Internet is still governed by national legislation. In this regard, the author believes it is important to find out the relationship between the EU case directives and the legislation of the EU member states on the protection of personal data.

The study also uses the works of such scientists as Belykh B.C. «Information as an object of legal regulation», Kopylov V.A. «On the model of civil turnover of information», Dozortsev V.A. «The concept of exclusive right, Nasonova E.N. «Information as an object of civil law». Considerable attention is paid to the analysis of the system of regulatory and legal requirements existing in the field of regulating information as an object of property right in the EU policy documents and the legislation of the member states of the European Union.

The main documents that are considered as an important scientific basis for the research are Regulation 2016/679 (The General Data Protection Regulation) - on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data; "Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe", which was approved at the meeting of the European Commission on May 6, 2015; Directive (EU) 2019/770 on certain aspects concerning contracts for the supply of digital content and digital services; Directive 2000/31/EC on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce, in the Internal Market. The European Commission working Paper "Guidelines for Private Sector Data Exchange in the European Data Economy"¹⁷ (SWD/2018/1) establishes a set of tools for companies that are data owners, data users or both at the same time. For this purpose, it provides guidance on the legal, technical and business aspects of data sharing, which can be used in practice when considering and preparing data exchange between companies from the same or different sectors. Directive 2016/1148 on measures to ensure a general high level of security of information systems is aimed at achieving the stability of essential communication services, pays attention to maintaining the confidentiality of information while ensuring information security, proceeds from the general principle of applying a risk-based approach to ensuring information security. Regulation 2018/1725 - on the protection of individuals in the processing of personal data by institutions, bodies, institutions and agencies of the Union and on the free movement of such

data; Directive 2017/1128/EC on cross-border portability of online content services in the internal market; Directive 2002/58/EC - on personal data processing and privacy protection in the electronic communications sector, and others.

4.5.4 Methodology

In order to conduct a qualitative study of the issues raised, an expanded review of the literature devoted to the problems of property rights in the system of absolute rights, including those related to the legitimate collection, preservation and accessibility of personal data, was conducted. An in-depth theoretical analysis of scientific sources, the norms of the legislation of the European Union and foreign legislation has been carried out in order to achieve the goals set out above. The ESR used a comparative legal method to compare the norms of EU legislation and international agreements in the field of ownership of intangible objects, intellectual property and copyright, as well as a systemic structural method in order to identify the relationship between the achievements of scientific doctrine and the degree of its reflection in legislation.

4.5.5 Research Findings

4.5.5.1 Information revolution and the origins of data ownership approach

The information revolution was the impetus for a completely new approach to the ownership of intangible objects, with its revolutionary impact of information technology on all spheres of society in the last quarter of the XX century. As the influence of information technologies, computers, and other equipment becomes more and more accessible to the public, the issue of protecting a fundamentally new category of rights - data - has become acute.

It is known that we refer information and the results of intellectual activity to intangible objects, despite the fact that the distinction between tangible and intangible property in the modern world is becoming increasingly blurred and the category of intangible property is expanding more and more.

However, even though intangible objects are more difficult to recognize than material objects, they have their external expression, are objectified externally, and this peculiar form is fixed on one or another material medium (electronic books, electronic information resources, etc.).

The most ancient references to data and information relate to Ancient Egypt, Greece and China, but in a completely different context than we have today. Back in ancient times, the concept of data was limited to the number of people, labor, livestock, agriculture, houses, animals and food. Over time, the similarity of databases began to form, which took into account more and more factors, such as marriages and the number of soldiers in the army. Gradually, primitive calculations were transformed, people began to come to understand the importance of the information being collected. With the further digital revolution, a new era in the field of data application has begun. The types of data collected have expanded and the scale of data collected has become globalized. The data began to transform into completely new semantic loadings. New terms have appeared, such as data collection, data processing and storage, data privacy,

etc. Data flows rapidly became more and more complex, and entire databases and powerful information industries were created, which, in turn, required a new legislative regulation.

Data protection legislation has gone through an evolutionary path, since the “data protection law has always had to conform to both quantitative and qualitative changes of relationships within the data flow. Quantitative because the number of actors collecting, analyzing, and using personal data has been constantly growing, as did the number of relationships. Qualitative because the relationships were becoming more complex. For instance, at the beginning of the Information Revolution because the computers very expensive and available only to a small number of actors, there were expected to be only few databanks. As a result, the first-generation data protection norms targeted those few databanks individually and did not contain generally applicable data protection rights”. [Puro7]

The striving to effectively protect personal data and to create the most effective legal regime has generated a lot of scientific discussions about the property rights over personal data. The important thing to understand is “that property is not an entirely straightforward concept. It has many faces and bears more than one function, among others, facilitating market exchange... or a mere protective function (performed by invoking other than market qualities of property). Therefore, the answer to the question whether or not propertization of personal information might be a good idea for Europe cannot be simply yes or no, but requires further deliberations on what approach to data protection – market or non-market – we are prepared to take, what ‘face’ of property suits best for it, and, most intriguingly, if the approach is non-market, do we have to go through the trouble of introducing a new model of data protection via property”. The fluidity and tendency to change of the institution of property rights have already been mentioned above, which is perfectly applicable to personal data.

The information revolution created a situation of uncontrolled collection, use, sale, profit from personal data, all this happened in opaque, non-transparent ways. The significance of personal data, and most importantly, their commercial value, were realized by large players and smaller companies and used by them for their own purposes. Thus, “the private ownership paradigm often emerges as a reaction once the data collection has been unveiled, and individual data ownership rights are increasingly enforced with data protection policies such as the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With the emergence of the Internet of Things (IoT), the debate about individual data ownership has gained a new face because it remains unclear who owns personal data produced by machines” [V18] The “heart” of the personal data protection system became the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which established strict rules and high fines for violations and non-compliance with them. The regulation was put into effect on May 25, 2018. The document is based on the principle of personal data security and is one of the world examples of how personal data should be respected and protected. In this study, a thorough analysis of GDPR in the position of the topic of the dissertation is to be carried out.

Thus, the widespread development of the Internet has led to a “heated debate about how data should be used and controlled” [AD20], in most cases, meaning personal data. And one of the most significant questions in the context of digitization is “whether the fundamental rights of individual subjects are respected and what is required to protect them from interference”

[PH20] Scientific debates eventually led to the conclusion that "these issues arise against the background of disputed property relations, that is, the relationship between the owner and his property" [PH20]

However, the information revolution has touched not only personal data, expanding the borders of the economies of countries through digitalization. As noted above, the evolution of technology is directly related to and affects the concept of data, and as humanity advances in the field of computing, the deep meaning of the concept of data evolves. Today there are a large number of data types, as well as subcategories, however, they do not fully reflect what is happening today. Also, we must not forget that as technology develops in the future, new types will appear, and today's definitions will constantly evolve.

In this regard, in accordance with the needs of today, it is important to consider the massive flows of economically significant data, which have also become difficult to control.. "The changes caused by digitization will ultimately lead to the entire economy becoming digital. At present, there is a global race to reap the benefits of emerging digital technologies or developments such as artificial intelligence, quantum computing or the growth of the Internet of things. There is a clear and strong political willingness and momentum around the world to harvest the growths advantages of digitization ". [RS20] The response of European legislation to the extensive digitalization of the economy has become "Digital Single Market Strategy", Digital Content Directive, Sale of Goods Directive, Portability Regulation, Geo-blocking Regulation and others.

The development of artificial intelligence, machine-generated data directly led to a dilemma about the owner of such data. Given that they often have potential and economic value, setting rules about who they belong to has become acute. "Machine-generated sensor data have enormous value, for example, for developing self-driving automobiles. But it is as yet unclear who owns these data: the automobile manufacturer; the car owner; the producer of the sensor equipment; or no one at all? What we need, concludes the Commissioner, are rules at EU level that establish data ownership ". [GO16] Self-driving cars are just one example, almost every home today has "smart appliances", personal devices, medical devices, which are inherently powerful "collections" of information.

In view of issues of this kind, there were proposals from the scientific community that "with respect to the proceeding digitalization, a common European framework is needed to provide specific rules for the marketability of data " [Boe+18] And often such a "framework" means exactly the approach of data ownership, as able to cope with the tasks currently facing.

Taking scientific research as an example, Arrow's information paradox [Arr62] brilliantly explains the need to introduce ownership of information. Due to the special nature of the information, when concluding a transaction about it, if the buyer wishes to evaluate the value of the information for him, then knowing its content, the need for acquisition will disappear. If the ownership of this information is established, then the buyer, even knowing its content, will not be able to use it for any purpose. With such a guarantee, disclosure can be safely made prior to the conclusion of a contract. In our opinion, this makes a lot of sense in light of the growing "information fever".

Thus, the concept of data ownership appeared as a possible solution to control the increasing volume of data, both personal and economically significant. Data propertization gave "hope to

those wishing to unlock the potential of the data economy and to those trying to re-empower individuals that have lost control over their data” [FTF17] However, we must not forget that any structure used to classify data types carries limitations and cannot cover the actual volume. Therefore, when considering methods of data ownership, a certain legal regime of ownership may be required for each type of data, and these regimes may differ significantly from each other.

An important issue is the transfer of data rights. According to legal doctrine, before property rights can be transferred, they must first appear. Let’s correlate this provision with the property rights over data. The question immediately arises, at what point do property rights over data legally arise? It is extremely important to focus on the prerequisites for acquiring property rights of the specification, since the creator of the data is comparable to the creator of the product in a broad sense. Specification means that the creator creates a new material thing from one or more components and acquires its ownership. Basically, the creator is a person who directly executes the specification. This legal consequence takes effect regardless of who owned the manufactured components earlier, provided that the value of the new thing is no less valuable than the components. Consequently, at the moment when the creator acquires property rights according to the specification, the previous rights expire.

From the standpoint of the theory of civil law, the transfer of information from one person to another is unacceptable – only the transfer of property rights to information is possible. It is possible to reveal this statement based on the example of intellectual property. Civil legal relations are also becoming more complex and evolving in accordance with today’s realities. Many researchers note that it is necessary to recognize the presence in real civil relations of new intangible objects that are not named, not reflected in the legislation, but give rise to subjective civil rights and obligations. Such new intangible objects should be called big data, big user data, domain name, virtual objects, artificial intelligence, robots, etc. [I.Z21] All of them are directly related to the concept of data ownership, giving rise to questions about who is the owner of the data from a legal point of view, how he exercises his right and how he can transfer his right of ownership to other subjects of civil legal relations. All these issues will be discussed in more detail in the relevant part of the study.

The legal status of data ownership remains disputed, but it does not cease to be discussed. On the one hand, data is a dynamic concept, and it is difficult to define and fit it to a specific model; on the other hand, the concept of data ownership continues to promise control and focus on data protection. The concept of data ownership is especially important in terms of access rights and data portability, which strengthen data rights.

4.5.5.2 Existing legal concepts in relation to data property

A review of the most common and significant concepts and interpretations of the concept of information and information property in the legal literature shows a pronounced tendency to a contradictory approach to the definition of this legal phenomenon.

Herbert Zech considers information as an object of property rights, unlimited intellectual property. It manifests itself in personal aspects and even in property law. Therefore, the author

classifies information, highlighting semantic, syntactic and structural information.[Zec15b]

V.S. Belykh argues that many legal concepts have epistemological roots in the field of natural sciences and in some cases, it is generally inappropriate to form a definition of certain concepts in the Civil Code, because they are generally intersectoral in nature and cannot be limited to the sphere of civil law regulation of public relations.[B.Co1] Undoubtedly, the author is right that information is a multidimensional concept that is the subject of various forms of human consciousness and activity: natural sciences, philosophy, political science, history, law, etc. However, it is impossible to fully agree with the above statement, since intersectoral concepts, as a rule, are specified in the relevant branch of law with the identification of its narrowly focused specifics to improve legal regulation.

Some authors believe that information is a very special object that requires a special legal regime that differs from the legal regulation of classical objects, in particular, intellectual property rights. The argument is based on the statement that the essence of relations regarding information as an object of civil rights is not in the traditional use of the result for economic turnover, but in its cognition. The use of information turns into familiarization, and it is no longer carried out by virtue of the right to an object belonging to a certain person, but by virtue of a general permission to get acquainted with publicly available data and information.[V.Aoo]

The above definition clearly shows the author's desire to expand the scope of the concept of information by using general categories, without taking into account the fact that not in all cases information can acquire the properties of an object of civil rights.

Since it seems impossible to mention all existing legal concepts, it is most effective to do this by dividing scientific fabrications into adherents of the concept of data ownership and opponents of it.

This section first examines the point of view of scientists who support and promote the data ownership approach, with arguments and arguments for its effectiveness. Next, the opposite opinion is studied, equally well-reasoned.

4.5.5.3 Argumentation of proponents of the propertization approach

Speaking about data ownership, it is necessary to understand why this approach has been so actively proposed by prominent scientists? What improvements and effective solutions can propertization offer? And finally, why did the policy makers also consider this concept as one of the likely ones?

This proposal takes place for obvious reasons. Firstly, due to the traditional nature of this approach and the development of the institution of property rights in the legislation of all countries. Data property is hoped to be able to settle a large number of emerging legal relationships in the field of data, in which it would be possible to secure ownership of specific entities, thus streamlining them and bringing specifics to sometimes chaotic and poorly controlled processes.

Herbert Zech's research on data ownership is deep and valuable, and in his opinion, data ownership will increase the incentive for data collection. His argument is partly based on the assumption that data as such is subject to the disclosure paradox.[Zec15a] He offers many positive aspects of propertization, this is just one of them.

The purpose of privacy protection is one of the priority goals of propertization of the personal data. The same control over data that allows an individual to feel reliable and respect personal boundaries. It is assumed that “data ownership right would not replace the legal foundations of privacy protection but strengthen it”[Lau96] . “Possibly there is something more to that protective function of property that Europe can also use. The first thing which comes to one’s mind is that status of property rights may give data protection rights an extra set of enforcement mechanisms” [Pur16]. Thus, securing data ownership rights can really be useful in this aspect, because “most importantly, people feel responsible, act in their self-interest, and take care of data” [Leg21] . The argument about personal responsibility and self-interest takes place and is fully justified, since ownership rights to any objects entail this increased responsibility of subjects, which in most cases has a positive effect on the market.

Personal data can be changed, stolen, and even destroyed. Propertization, thus, gives hope that “control over integrity, that is, the assurance that the data will not be altered or destroyed without consent of the owner”[NK93] . The above, according to the authors, can be considered as the fundamental force of the data ownership right.[NK93]

One reasonable argument has similar arguments to the Hardin tragedy. Non-creators of information “are always at an advantage over the information-creator. The information commons are overused in such a way which results in the absence of new information creation”[Har67] Thus, by privatizing information and granting property rights, an incentive is provided for the future creation of information, the goal of not overusing information is achieved. This is a principle applied in intellectual property law. It is possible to find a rational grain in it, protecting the creators of information. The information protected by property rights really gives hope for the observance of the rights of the creator of the information, but the question arises again - how to accurately identify him? How to determine that this particular subject created this or that information? These reflections will be discussed in more detail in the next part.

Continuing the theme of the public good “when information is owned it is no longer a public good. Instead, owners use legal and technical means to restrict access to the information, thereby making it excludable. The result is a private good (the information is available to others only at the discretion of the owner) or a club good (the information is available to the members of a group but all others are excluded from access” [MB22] This may concern, for example, commercial information. A company can start creating its own database by collecting the names and addresses of its customers. This protection mechanism is seen as reliable and strong. Access to such a database on the basis of ownership rights allows you to make the data exclusive more valuable. Considering the paradigm of the common good from this point of view, we tend to agree that this opinion makes sense.

One of the significant arguments is that data as a property fully meets the market challenges of today’s realities. Data as a commodity, data as a real market currency and value, what, if not property, can better meet these challenges? Data has naturally become an integral part of the economy and this process is irreversibly gaining momentum. “Propertization would acknowledge the existing phenomenon of commodification of, or a high market value attributed to, personal data, and could offer a solution to the data protection problem – a result of the 20th century rise of private and government databases”[Pur16]

Speaking about the economic potential of data, it should be noted that industrial data is of great value. “The value of the EU data economy was estimated at EUR 257 billion in 2014, or 1.85% of EU GDP. This increased to EUR 272 billion in 2015, or 1.87% of EU GDP (year-on-year growth of 5.6%). The same estimate predicts that, if policy and legal framework conditions for the data economy are put in place in time, its value will increase to EUR 643 billion by 2020, representing 3.17% of the overall EU GDP” ¹¹. Consequently, with such a high cost of industrial data, the question of income distribution becomes acute. In “ensuring a fair allocation of the profits generated by analyzing the data... a clear property rule can provide the framework for a functioning data economy” [Zec15b]

Today, industrial data is protected mainly by database rights and intellectual property rights. However, what if these data are not collected in a single database and do not represent the result of creative activity? The introduction of ownership rights to raw, machine-generated industrial data would go far beyond the main intellectual property regimes currently existing in Europe in the field of data and information, copyright and database rights.[Hug17]

Continuing the topic of intellectual property, for instance, “copyright does not protect individual pieces of data. This claim is based on the idea/expression dichotomy, which lives at the core of copyright theory. Namely, ideas are not protected by copyright” [Hug17]. It is impossible not to agree with this point of view, since raw data, ideas and knowledge really cannot become the object of copyright. At the same time, data protection in the form of databases is possible with the help of copyright. At the same time, databases should be organized creatively and in an original way. Databases using technologies like IoT or AI may well fall under copyright protection. However, again, the raw data remains behind the legal board. In general, the introduction of the right to raw data would go far beyond the main intellectual property regimes currently existing in Europe in the field of data and information, copyright and database rights. Accordingly, there is a need for such a method of their protection is formally justified, and therefore proponents of the approach based on data ownership offer it. However, we are in no hurry to conclude that such an approach is the only possible and correct one. Thus, data ownership was proposed with the hope of successfully solving the problems that appeared with the development of the active phase of digitization and the circulation of large amounts of information.

Thus, data property was supposed to firstly, simplify and fragment these very volumes of data, making it easier to manage them. The ability to organize and fragment data is needed for a reason, it was and it is an crucial task. Information flows are huge and incredibly confusing, they cannot be regulated by any single mechanism. Many problems that arise with data, such as data leakage, misuse of data, illegal disclosure of data, any unreasonable disposal of data, are difficult to control and find out all the relationships, reaching the true responsible party. It was assumed that they could be ordered using propertization. This is the so-called “erga omnes” effect, which entails that property rights apply to all persons, creating negative obligations for them without their consent. [Erp19] A certain ability to track relationships, the direction of data, protect data from misuse using the privileges of ownership rights is at the heart of this approach. The erga omnes effect could indeed, at least theoretically, ensure data security and

¹¹European Commission, Staff Working Document on the free flow of data and emerging issues of the European data economy, Brussels, 10 January 2017

impose responsibility for unjustified actions with "other's" data.

When talking about data structuring and fragmentation, we are talking not only about information security, but also about data control. To a greater extent, despite all attempts at legislation, "we have no real control over our personal data. And data property was declared a measure capable of regaining this control. Thus, if property rights are structured in a certain way, even after transfer of some control also by "selling" a fraction of rights an individual would always retain essential control over his personal data, e.g. allowing and defining the goals of data processing" [Puro7] Data control is important not only in relation to personal data, any data that is uncontrolled is a huge block of unresolved issues. And the data ownership was supposed to solve these issues, giving control over the data to individuals and organizations.

Propertization, in addition to the above goals, of course, pursued the task of optimizing economic processes. Data ownership as a tool for regulating economically significant data was seen as an adequate response to the widespread processes of expanding firms' work with data, making profits from data, selling and buying a variety of types of data. As Anastasios Dosis and Wilfried Sand-Zantma note in their study, "we define property rights as the ability to control the amount of data collected and to monetize it. In this setting, we highlight a central trade-off between two forms of contractual incompleteness: the first linked to the firm's decision to process the data and the second related to the limit to data monetization"[AD20]. In addition to monetization and profit from data, the authors also mention data control, but in the context of data control by large firms with massive amounts of information. "If the firm owns the rights, it has full control over the collection and use of the data of all consumers".[AD20].

Moreover, an economic forum in 2011 made the resounding conclusion that ownership of personal data already exists in the EU, if not expressly enshrined in law. that actually. "As EU data protection law evidently allows for the transfer of personal data between parties, we might conclude personal data is certainly a commodity, and thus can be considered property-like"¹². . It is noteworthy that opponents of the approach under consideration have the opposite opinion that data protection law is incompatible with data ownership, which will be discussed in the next part.

In addition, "the more data property rights are concentrated to large levels of subjects, the greater the value produced and the higher the efficiency" [Li22] The authors are confident that it is the ownership rights to data that can increase the profits of companies, and it is necessary to involve an increasing number of subjects in this structure. The propertization of data is supposed to fairly distribute the roles and will enable each subject to achieve higher efficiency. Summing up, propertization pursued several main tasks. First, information security, the possibility of being held accountable for illegal actions with data, systematization of the information space in such a way as to be able to follow the chain of actions with data and "find" the responsible party. Secondly, data fragmentation was aimed at facilitating control over them, simplifying their management system. Also, data ownership implied the return of the possibility of personal management of their personal data. And of course, one of the most important goals is to expand the boundaries of the data economy and monetization of information. Like other objects of civil turnover, the data were supposed to be involved in civil transactions, bringing

¹²World Economic Forum, "Personal Data: The Emergence of a New Asset Class", 2011

income and profit to their owners.

4.5.5.4 Argumentation of opponents of data ownership

Opponents of the concept of ownership in relation to data appeal with many arguments and, first of all, the immaterial nature of data. “One primary reason for legal scholars to be critical of data ownership is that there are important differences between data and paradigm cases of property”[Zec12]

First, unlike tangible entities, possession of data does not imply that one is the sole possessor and exclusive user. Data can be duplicated, and several people can use it at once. Second, it is difficult if not impossible to exclude third parties. Unless one manages to keep data secret, it can be duplicated and used by others. Due to being nonrival and non-excludable, data are public goods (as the term is used in economic theory, and contrasts with private goods, club goods, and common-pool resources). Moreover, data are non-depletable: they can be used more than once without losses in quality.[HP20]

Some are convinced that the very idea of data exclusivity, necessary for the functioning of property rights, is questionable. And they refer this not only to data, but also to other goods. “Alienability of any object of some public significance, e.g. food, medication, children’s products, homes with minors as residents etc. – is heavily regulated by the state. Free alienability inherent in and necessary for the market function of property may be limited since property is never absolute”.[Puro7] Undoubtedly, data is of great public importance, but it is difficult to agree with the opinion that limited expropriation can affect the system of property rights, including in relation to data.

From practical side there are explanations in the scientific community why the approach to data ownership is not able to solve specific practical problems. Many scientists are convinced that there is no practical need to own data, for example, there is a belief that even without data ownership, data would be produced, used, licensed, sold [HP20].

One of the issues of concern to policy makers is the issue of data availability. As far as we know, there are many ways to restrict access to data, there are doubts - will data ownership play a sharply negative role? This raises doubts “about the need to introduce a new ownership right to data due to the problem of data access. The access rights provided by the European Commission to facilitate the data market can indeed be implemented to a large extent by making changes to the existing rules. If the right of data ownership had been introduced, these access rights would have to take the form of restrictions on such a right”[FTF17] These doubts seem reasonable and justified, since it is known that one of the goals of the European Union is the availability of data. Data ownership implies very strict restrictions in this regard, which suggests that it is incompetent.

The theory of great opportunities for data control using data ownership is being questioned, since such fragmentation can lead to even greater confusion. Many scientists are of the opinion that this approach could lead to the opposite effect and an even greater loss of control over the data. “We return to the unavoidability of death facto data control through both technological and legal means. When we consider these two aspects cumulatively, an additional layer

of property rights did not seem like a sufficiently attractive incentive which would dissipate de facto control, thereby ensuring greater circulation and use” [Gan] This point of view has been reflected in the works of many researchers. They express concerns that the creation of ownership rights, in particular, to personal data, is likely to create new regulatory problems. These reflections lead to the conclusion that “any benefits that could be obtained from the appropriation of personal data would be outweighed by the risk of potential harm” [Po4]

It is hard not to agree that property rights will potentially be the cause of many conflicts and litigation. Obviously, it will only increase the risk of unintentional violation of rights, thus complicating legal certainty.

In the right of ownership, the key figure is the owner of the object of ownership. As mentioned above, it is not so easy to determine the original owner of the data. And in general, the number of participants involved the chain of information is often incredibly large, and the relationships between them are so intertwined that they are difficult to reflect in data protection measures. Speaking about data, it is difficult to say who each subject is in relation to specific information. And how to "assign" this or that status to subjects in relation to this information. All these difficulties are real obstacles to the data ownership approach.

As mentioned above, some of the proponents of the data ownership approach appeal to the fact that this approach can make a more effective system of personal data protection. On the one hand, this sounds promising, however, won't the powers conferred by the ownership right "overlap with the protection provided by the data protection act"? [Tho17] Since the data owner and the data subject will have the competence to mutually prohibit the use of data, this is quite a logical concern.

Another issue is the dynamic nature of the development of the economic market. Data ownership does not seem to be a flexible enough approach to adapt to the fast pace and character of the economy. At least, in the continental system, property rights are already a “hardened” and well-established system that is not capable of rapid response.

Reasoning more deeply about the inflexibility of the data ownership approach, such a characteristic of data as its dynamic nature comes to mind. It makes it "difficult, if not impossible, to determine a stable object of protection. The subject of law is simply too volatile" [P.B17] It is necessary to take into account the often rapid obsolescence of data, the constantly updated flow in databases, some instability in the right of the data producer. All these factors lead to the conclusion that creating a mechanism called “data ownership” is a challenging, if not impossible task.

Not only economic, but also technical "trends" require an approach that can change and adapt to them, which is obviously not typical for data ownership. Thus, data ownership in the legal sense is not a suitable and working approach to data governance. Hugenholtz put forward an idea against property rights based on the lack of legal certainty of the approach. He gives an example of data generated by machine processes. In his opinion, it is extremely difficult to imagine a right to data that is “sufficiently stable in terms of subject matter, scope and ownership rights”. [P.B17] As for the subject matter, if “the right extends to data generated by machine processes, what data will it protect? All the data that the machine outputs during a given period of time (for example, an hour, a minute or a second)”? [P.B17] It seems that the right of ownership

alone is not able to answer these questions.

Among other things, the data ownership approach can become a threat to the confusion of overlapping rights with respect to data. Assuming data ownership as a working system, this "would seriously jeopardize the system of intellectual property law that currently exists in Europe. It would also contradict the fundamental freedoms enshrined in the European Convention on Human Rights and the EU Charter, distort the freedom of competition and the freedom to provide services in the EU, restrict scientific freedoms and generally undermine the prospects of big data for the European economy and society" [P.B17] It turns out that in addition to the "legal confusion", we are even talking about the violation of fundamental rights and freedoms, of course, according to the aforementioned author, but still this opinion takes place and seems not unfounded. We are of the opinion that data ownership is really capable of creating confusion and problems, for example, with intellectual property rights. In addition to intellectual property rights, enterprises and organizations also have a sufficient number of legal, factual and technical tools to protect their data. Speaking of the latter, when using technical protection measures, access to data is closed to any unauthorized persons and attempts of illegal interference and fraud that involve criminal liability. In addition, there is a database protection law that is able to effectively protect large databases. It is impossible not to mention the contract law, because in many cases it can "replace" the right of ownership, while taking into account the most detailed interests of the parties. We will return to contract law later dwell on it in more detail. These mechanisms offer a number of ways to ensure data protection, they are an established system, and despite the fact that each of the mechanisms has its weaknesses, "mixing" them with property rights is highly undesirable.

Also, a legal inconsistency may arise due to a potential conflict with the ownership of the data carrier. "Since data can easily be copied, modified, and transferred to other storages, the entitlement to use and access the storage and data may diverge. A contractual agreement with a cloud operator usually does not mean that the operator receives legal ownership on the stored data assets. Instead, the user merely intends temporary retention and requests for exclusive access to the information. In this context, the agreement of the parties has to be cultivated" [Boe+18]

The next potential conflict is data producer's right. "The 'data producer's right' would lead to extensive overlaps. As a consequence, the new right might give rise to multiple competing claims of ownership in the same content" [P.B17] It should take into account all existing mechanisms for the protection of copyright, related rights or the right to a database. The author gives an example that both copyright and database rights in the EU allow users to copy or extract data from databases for non-commercial research purposes. "The "right of the data producer" should include all the existing exceptions, and if we imagine the right of ownership, it will bring even greater difficulties.

Thus, property rights cannot be considered as a separate independent category, without taking into account all related rights and the risk of conflicts with them. And these conflicts are inevitable, as illustrated above. Is there a need for such a complication and intersection of rights in the legal system? It seems obvious to us that there is a need to simplify it as much as possible, and apparently, the right of ownership is not able to cope with it.

4.5.5.5 Legal obstacles to data ownership approach

To consider legal obstacles to the possession of information, first of all it is necessary to turn to the very concept of ownership. “The right of ownership is the most complete property right. According to its purpose, the right of ownership gives over a thing the full power compatible with the law. Its exclusivity means that no other person can have the same right to the same thing - property rights. The owner always excludes all others from ownership of this thing”.[\[V.P09\]](#)

The theory of property rights focuses on absolute rights. The key question becomes how these absolute rights should be distributed in order to eliminate negative externalities, subsequently increasing efficiency. It follows from these that significant and socially useful resources must belong to someone, and this right must be guaranteed at the legislative level. The next thing we see from the definitions is that property rights must be distributed exclusively so that the owner can exclude others from the good. Otherwise, the distribution itself loses its meaning. And also an important point is the possibility of transferring of property rights.

Speaking of the exclusion of third parties, it is necessary to mention the principle of “erga omnes”, almost “all systems of private law adhere to distinction between personal rights that apply between a chosen number persons and property rights that have consequences for third parties, sometimes even against the whole world. Property rights are special rights because they have effect against third parties, usually against everybody else”.[\[Akk15\]](#)

However, the above definition suggests the impossibility of data ownership, as it faces the first obstacle on the way to this. By its very nature, a complete monopoly on information is difficult or completely impossible. Information “remains” with both the previous owner and the new one. This violates the very concept of property rights. The ability to exclude others from the field of ownership becomes a key issue in potential data propertization.

The next principle to consider is the “numerus clausus” principle. It is interpreted differently in different legal systems, but the essence of the principle is that the content of the property rights is already predetermined, and the parties are limited to this already existing content and “thus are limited in the creation of new types of property rights”.[\[Akk15\]](#) This principle of property rights has both a substantive and procedural side [\[Erp\]](#), since this principle limits not only the number and content of such rights, but also how these rights are created, transferred and terminated. Following the principle of numerus clausus, next to full ownership, only property rights smaller than the property right (secondary or so-called “limited” property rights) can be created.

Since we are talking about the classical understanding of property rights as an absolute right in legal doctrine, one can see from the concept discussed above that it is impossible to own, dispose and use information in the classical sense. And this is largely due to the contradictory nature of the information. It has much in common with material goods, while being an intangible object. Also, the right of ownership of information does not correspond to one of the leading principles of ownership - transparency. “The principle of transparency in a classical sense only had two aspects: the object as to which a property right was claimed had to be clearly described and delineated and it had to be made public”.[\[Erp\]](#) It is obvious that the principle of transparency did not imply the possession of information and is more directed towards material

objects. Thus, the data can be said to be inconsistent with the basic principles of property rights as such.

“When looking at the characteristics of a potential data ownership right, most parameters are still very unclear. Academics have only just begun to think about the possible subject matter of protection (be it data on the syntactic level or information on the semantic level) and whether data or information should be protected as unitary asset (attributing rights irrespective of how others have obtained the subject matter of protection) or as a commodity asset (allowing others to use independently obtained data or information)” [FTF17]

Speaking about different levels of information, this issue was thoroughly studied by Zech. [Zec16b] He distinguishes between three conceptual levels of data. The first is the semantic level or content level, which encapsulates human-understandable information that carries the essence and meaning. At this level, we can talk about the value of information as such. The second level is syntactic, where information is presented in the form of signs and symbols, also called the code layer. The semantic level is made up of the syntactic level, creating a third level, which is located on the physical storage medium. It is also called the physical level, which can be tangible by a person.

This classification was a bright success in the scientific community, as it facilitated the understanding of the essence and nature of information. In addition, it is of great importance in relation to the question of this study, since “as it is crucial which layer will be the object of the property right. Granting the property right at different conceptual layers can have vastly different consequences for the law” [Ste23]

Zech also formulated his definition of data ownership, which is based on the concept of property rights. “Building on the standard categories of property rights: use (usus), enjoying the benefits of the use (usus fructus), changing form and substance (abusus) and transfer of the property three basic categories of rights to information can be distinguished: possessing information, using information and destroying information” [Zec15b] This definition seems to be the closest to reality and accurate, since it reflects the capabilities of a potential data ownership system to the greatest extent.

Continuing the question of the controversial legal nature of the information, the difficult question arises of how to determine their original owner? It can be said with certainty that “there is no consensus about the criteria on how to originally attribute the right to a right holder”. [FTF17] Since the data does not lose properties while simultaneously satisfying the needs of, say, hundreds of subjects, it is difficult to determine the original owner.

However, it is quite certain and obvious that the familiar doctrine ceases to work. Many authors call today to “to avoid unnecessary and non-productive academic debate based on sterile dogmatic analysis and preconceived 19th century paradigms” [Erp] After all, the right of ownership is initially focused on the possession of physical objects that are fundamentally different from the object considered in this study. And when the object is something else, then there is no point in relying on the usual classical dogmas entirely.

4.5.5.6 Legal analysis of GDPR provisions from the angle of the data ownership approach

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is one of the most important legal framework that establishes guidelines for the collection and processing of personal data of individuals. It was approved in 2016 and entered into force in 2018. Its peculiarity lies in the fact that its power extends to all websites used by EU residents.

In law, data ownership is mostly associated with the privacy of individuals. “With personal identifiable information being collected in an ever-increasing volume by large tech companies, this discipline aims at defining the actual owner of this data collection and the extent of control that remains with the data’s subjects. This legal perspective is particularly important as companies must be held accountable when it comes to data leakages or alienation...”[Leg21]

The GDPR provisions are interesting to us from the point of view of the data ownership approach. What is personal data according to GDPR? According to the Article 4 personal data means “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is a one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such a name, an identification number, location data...”¹³.

The GDDR is, first of all, about the basic human rights and freedoms, their right to dispose of information about themselves. Is it possible to say that we "own" information about ourselves? According to Pearce, “data protection rights could prima facie be regarded as either personal or proprietary rights. Both kinds of rights share their orientation towards economic efficiency, civil liberties and avoidance of unjust interferences. But while proprietary rights do so on the basis of assigning transferable rights in external things, personality rights are internal, not directed at external things, relate to an individual’s personhood, character, and identity, and are inalienable”[H18]

The important point is that the legislation does not directly address the issue of ownership, and firms and regulators circumvent many obstacles by avoiding direct references to ownership; instead, they focus on the potential control exercised by the data subject or the limitations of the data controller.[JM17] It should be noted that personal data in principle cannot be the subject of property protection. “The GAP in accordance with the European Charter of Fundamental Rights defines personal data as rights subject to special consideration, in respect of which no property rights can be exercised” [Ste23]

Article 1(2) of the DR defines the purposes of the document, according to which it protects fundamental rights and freedoms and, in particular, the "right to personal data protection" ¹⁴., therefore providing a definition of the right separately from property. However, “This view is not necessarily shared in the US. Some privacy conscious academic advocate the propertization of privacy as the model for increasing privacy protection [Ste23] Different legal systems have different approaches, but we are focused on the EU approach.

However, there is a directly opposite opinion that the European data protection system can be considered a regime similar to the property regime. This is explained by the legal powers vested in individuals, and the most striking arguments are the provisions of the Regulation on the right

¹³The General Data Protection Regulation, 2018, Article 4

¹⁴The General Data Protection Regulation, 2018, Article 1 (2)

to be forgotten and the right to data portability. Such control and management resembles the scope of property rights. “Significantly, some have suggested that despite the GDPR prima facie being premised on human rights rhetoric and the fact that it employs no explicit property terminology, its substantive provisions function remarkably similarly to regulated property regimes” [J] There are surprisingly a considerable number of adherents of this opinion, some of them even make such bold statements as “more specifically the GDPR appears to implicitly acknowledge that the concept of personal data itself has become akin to a commodity that is capable of changing hands and being traded” [J13]

Another argument in favor of this point of view is the protection of personal rights, similar to the protection of property interests. Property rights protect the interests of an individual in relation to a particular object or resource, whether it is a tangible or intangible object. What is especially remarkable, “an interest will be protected from an unwanted use or taking by another party, under the assumption that property can only legitimately change hands if the consent of the right holder is given. The interest of rights holders in this context tend to be protected by courts and legislatures by way of fines, punitive damages or injunctions” [H18] Do we support this point of view? In part, yes, legal mechanisms do resemble the protection of property rights. And then we will try to show in more detail why.

An important provision of the GDPR is the right to deletion (the “right to be forgotten”), which gives the data subject the right to receive from the controller the deletion of personal data concerning him without undue delay. The data subject also has the right to withdraw his consent to the processing of his personal data. The “right to be forgotten” is of interest from a legal point of view, which gives the data subject a special right to information about him. Thus, “the individual is granted a power of exclusive disposition concerning the processing of personal data that is—to some extent—comparable with the power of the owner over his property. In terms of property law, this could be understood as a negative dimension of an exclusive right, i.e., the power to exclude others from using one’s property”. [Boe+18] This point of view is quite justified, since it really resembles the regime of property rights and the exclusion of others from the possibility of owning an object. However, in the case of the right to be forgotten, it is not the exclusion of all others by the subject, but the deletion of the object itself. And if in the ownership right the owner continues to satisfy his ownership right over the object, then the same cannot be said here. Thus, although the “right to be forgotten” resembles the legal regime of property rights, they still cannot be correlated as identical.

The following provisions of the Directive, in the opinion of some scientists resembling the regime of property rights, is the right to data portability. The data subject must have the right to transfer his personal data “to another controller without hindrance from the controller to which the personal data have been provided”.¹⁵ This provision gives the subject the right to dispose of his personal data almost in full, independently determining the place of their storage. This is a direct opportunity for the subject of personal data to make a decision on further processing and access, it goes far beyond consent to the processing of their data. “Therefore, it can be seen as another step towards a (privacy-based) concept of data ownership.” [Jü16]

¹⁵The General Data Protection Regulation, Art 20 (1)

4.5.6 Research Analysis

4.5.6.1 Data as an object of civil law relations

One of the key positions is the consideration of data as an object of civil rights. Civil law relations are most closely related to the daily needs of people and should cover at least the most important aspects of their lives related to civil law. This analysis provides an opportunity to get closer to the needs of individuals and to see gaps in the law regarding data. This is especially important, since today huge flows of economically valuable information circulate in civil turnover, and the question of its regulation arises.

“In the big data era, data is an emerging object of civil rights” [Li22] It is impossible to deny the influence of data and their circulation in civil turnover as a new object of civil law, although not yet legally designated in the legislation of many countries. But in practice, data have long and firmly entered the system of civil legal relations, which is the need to consider them in more detail from this angle.

“The civilian idea of ownership is an absolute dominion... over the relevant object”. This is indeed the case, and in the context of data means the most comprehensive property rights over the data. “From a comparative viewpoint, a main distinction can be drawn between the civil law and common law understanding of ownership” [Gra17] Data in the context of civil law is a different category, which needs to be delved into more deeply.

Firstly, data as an object of civil rights is a very important category for the business sphere. As Teresa Scassa notes in her research “data ownership can play a role in commercializing data: It is common for companies and organizations to seek to control the data they collect through their activities in order to commercialize them. An ownership right can support various techniques for control, including contracts/licensing and technological protection measures”¹⁶.

The economic value of data is growing day by day, and it is quite possible that in the future they will take a dominant place in the system of economic goods. Currently, the exchange of information and its storage and accumulation can already be called ubiquitous phenomena. However, when it comes to selling information as a commodity, it is a more unexplored and relatively new type of activity in the global economy. The data has unique characteristics as an inapplicable product. “In contrast to most other goods, data thereby are infinitely usable and are the source of increasing returns for companies” [JC19]. The non-susceptibility of data to physical wear is an important characteristic of them. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the possible obsolescence of data, potential irrelevance or their ability to cease to be necessary as disclosure. All these are characteristics that distinguish data from other objects of civil law.

It is necessary to understand the concept of the object of law as such. Indeed, while it is not difficult to determine the subject (it can be both an individual and a legal entity), some difficulties may arise with the object of law. Under the legal objects of civil law, most legal systems usually recognize tangible assets, such as land and movable property, and intangible assets, such as monetary claims, personal benefits, honor and dignity, etc. Regarding property rights “civil law

¹⁶CIGI Papers No. 187 — September 2018 Data Ownership Teresa Scassa, page 2

recognizes a limited number of property rights and a limited number of legal objects that can be subjected to these property rights (the so-called *numerus clausus*)” [Jo6] In many legal systems, property rights apply strictly to material objects, some recognize ownership of electricity, natural resources, etc.

Speaking about data as an object of civil rights, we must again return to the topic of possession of intangible objects. Since it seems impractical to consider narrowly only data, and we are talking about a whole massive group of objects that require a full-fledged legal regime. Such a civil law regime, first of all, requires clarity in determining the content of the arising property rights, which consist of the rights of the right holder. Taking into account the immaterial nature, the possession and disposal of these objects differs significantly from such actions with material objects.

In our opinion, the absolute property right to intangible objects consists of the right holder’s ability to have property rights to this object at his disposal and, accordingly, to demand proper behavior from obligated persons; the use of this object itself for its own purposes of practical application and satisfaction of its own needs; and, most importantly, the disposal of the absolute right to an intangible object. This absolute right gives the right holder the opportunity both to alienate the rights to this object and to provide other entities with opportunities to use this object, that is, to transfer ownership rights to it. These legal possibilities are the defining foundation for the possession of any intangible object, and they are also applicable with data.

When studying this issue from the perspective of civil law, a reasonable question arises about the owner of the data. This question, in particular, is relevant when it comes to raw data that goes beyond the classical ownership schemes. In fact, the answer to this question is very difficult to find, especially when the same data is used in several terms and when the data lifecycle is difficult to construct. Considering the data as an object of civil rights, it should be borne in mind that only property rights can participate in the turnover, but not the data itself. Thus, property rights to data can become the subject of civil law transactions and pass from one person to another. Today, the concepts of a subject with access to data and a legal owner of information are often equated. However, these are completely different concepts, because it is possible to have full access to data without having any legal rights. Any illegal theft of data gives access to them, but not the rights to the data. Although technically, with illegal theft, the subject becomes the owner of the data. It can be concluded that the possession of information does not mean the existence of legal rights to it.

Studying in what cases data can act as an independent object of law, we will again return to the teachings of Zech about different levels of information. “The distinction between content layer, code layer and physical layer provides a powerful tool for defining information which can be treated as an object: it reveals that information can be defined on the semantic level (information with a certain meaning), on the syntactic level (information represented by a certain amount of signs), or even by its physical carrier (information contained in a certain physical carrier or in a wider sense information represented by the structure of a physical object)” [Zec15b] He also makes the important clarification that whenever information serves a specific use and can be shared, it can also be treated as a commodity. “The definition of such goods is achieved in the same way that information can be defined as an object in general. Therefore, information

goods can also be divided into semantic, syntactic and structural information goods” [Zec15b]. Thus, the author mainly focuses on the levels of information that make it possible to classify it as an object of law.

Sjef van Erp, in turn, does not consider the levels of information that define it as an object of law, but highlights very interesting elements for defining it as such. Among these essential elements, the author refers “nature of the content, the person creating the content and purpose and use of the content” [Erp] The author explains that the content, in turn, may be directly related to the human body, or be user-generated content for personal use, or user-generated content targeted at a particular group or person. In addition, he mentions massively distributed user-generated content and open source content.

But the most important, in our opinion, contribution lies in his conclusion that “once information (data) is specific enough to be considered an object of property law, it can be qualified as a virtual asset” [Erp]. The property regime, as mentioned above, covers real and exclusive rights. But what about the category that was singled out in the previous part, what regime should be attributed to it, and is such a consolidation necessary in principle? We believe that such consolidation is necessary, because “different types of property rights are associated with the establishment of a special civil law regime for certain types of property – objects of civil rights. Of course, such a regime is actually established not for the objects themselves, but for persons who perform legally significant actions with them” [E.A17] Obviously, each object, depending on its properties, requires a special legal regime.

Thus, the properties of the object are important, and considering the object of civil law, the following question arises. What properties should data have in order to be a full-fledged object of civil legal relations? Taking the classical doctrine into account, the answer might be that it must carry a meaningful significance, satisfy someone’s private need, which is inherent in the category of good. Secondly, it should carry economic value and interest, and this is the main characteristic that allows us to classify data as property, even if “disembodied”, and therefore as objects of civil legal relations.

In order to add data to the list of civil law objects, it seems that they must initially have the purpose of commercial use. After all, if the data is “fit” for further trade, this means that they can be compared with another product, even material things. The value of any thing involved in civil circulation is estimated by its tradability. If there is no turnover ability, then it makes no sense to include in the list of objects of civil law. So, the ability of data to be sold is critical. And it can be argued that “tradability is the key aspect of treating something as a commodity, that you have a market, a primary market, a secondary market and then we can talk about whether the law has to keep these markets open or not” [Zec16b] Obviously, today a huge flow of information is not only able to be sold but is also a valuable resource. Service company databases, with information about customer preferences, for example, are a goldmine.

Also, it should also be noted that the object of legal regulation included in civil circulation, data can become only after objectification in any form that allows other persons – potential subjects of civil legal relations - to directly or indirectly perceive this information. Such a form can serve, for example, fixing on various material carriers, transmission over communication networks, oral communication, encoding in the form of signs, symbols, color images, sounds, etc.

Only through this material carrier can access to data, as well as their structure, sequence and integrity, be provided. This physical carrier is, of course, subject to proprietary rights, and in turn, “the deletion or modification of stored data arguably means a violation of ownership of the data medium” [SKS21]

Objects of civil law fall under the principle of *numerus clausus* of property rights. According to Sjef van Erp, “in the civil law strengthened by the unitary concept of ownership, the number and type of legal objects can also be characterised as a *numerus clausus*” [Erp] In some legal systems, the list is quite open and involves the location and acceptance of new objects, but in fact it is strictly regulated and enormous efforts are required to supplement or change it. That is why it is not at all easy to include data directly in the list of objects of civil law. They may circulate in civil circulation under veiled terms such as “other property”; and despite its specificity, the presence of a material carrier, the ability to be sold, are still practically nowhere included as objects.

In another study, Sjef van Erp, analyzing the legal systems of European countries, emphasizes that “the new article 567, part 2, of the Luxembourg Commercial Code, it seems that – perhaps more implicitly than explicitly and more hesitatingly than boldly – data have been accepted as a new legal object”. [Erp]

To summaries, data as an object of civil law are an intangible good, including the result of intellectual activity, existing in a certain objective form in the form of information fixed on a material carrier, capable of satisfying the property and personal non-property needs of subjects of civil legal relations.

Based on the above, we can conclude that in the conditions of the data and digital society, it is necessary to recognize the real economic significance of data. Data today is one of the most important intangible objects of property rights that need careful theoretical study and the creation of an appropriate civil law regime, as this is directly related to a huge number of private legal relations.

4.5.6.2 Going beyond data ownership

Studying the concept of data ownership from the standpoint of classical doctrine is necessary for a legal understanding of the phenomenon. At the same time, this study provides a clear vision that the familiar system cannot provide answers to burning questions about real control over data, especially personal data. Is there in principle a need to recognize the ownership of data and why? Such a significant “expansion” and even “distortion” of the scope of the property right needs a concrete and reasoned justification. First, it is necessary to specify the subject of protection itself as such. The legislation should give a specific interpretation of what is meant by “data” in the context of ownership of them, and is it possible, taking into account the diverse and complex nature of the data. And even if the legislation, hypothetically, copes with this task and is able to formulate the essence of the subject matter, then naturally a new question will arise about the scope of protection, real existing threats, which interests are we trying to protect? And, of course, the resulting practical side will be the means legal protection granted to the newly minted data owner. And even after mentally doing this gigantic work, the economic and

legal need to reinvent the bicycle remains open.

Also, it seems completely impossible to formulate uniform norms that take into account all sorts of factors and circumstances related to social relations arising and circulating in the field of data. "...legislation on data ownership would have to respond adequately to very diverse circumstances in which data is generated and used in the future. The data economy and the use of smart products are predicted to enter all different fields of modern life. However, data collection as regards the operation of smart cars is very different from the processing of data in the healthcare sector. Whether it is possible *ex ante* to conceive uniform rules on the subject-matter of protection, the person owning the rights and the uses that will be covered by the right, while the peculiarities of different sectors are delegated to exceptions and limitations, remains rather doubtful" [Dre16a]

However, also the question remains how to anyway link these two concepts of property and data for the most effective regulation of this sphere, as well as preserving the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

The idea is to move towards finding alternative ways of "owning" data, perhaps not in the most classical and familiar sense, and at the same time, without departing far from the legal doctrine.

So, not only property can be a right, we want to make an attempt to go beyond ownership, thereby introducing flexibility and compliance with the rapidly changing realities in the field of data.

If we think deeply about what the proponents of property rights want to achieve with respect to data, then we will understand that in many cases "when people in politics, the media, the industry, and academia refer to data ownership or to privacy as property, they have largely not proposed to establish a new type of right, but a transfer rule... When people have proposed establishing property over data, they have discussed the implications of having data protected solely by property rules, and not necessarily by ownership".[Cof17]

Now more and more scientists are inclined to believe that "...transferring rights over data only by consent and on an agreed upon compensation is a property rule over something that one needs not have ownership over. Individuals do not need to hold a property right (ownership) in data in order for the transfer of whichever rights they have over it to occur via property rules... Ownership—also called property rights—is different than property rules. Property rights (ownership) are a set of rights over a thing. ... The right of ownership right (or a property right) is a type of right that can be protected by any transfer rule: property rules, liability rules, or inalienability rules. In contrast—in an unfortunate ambiguity—property rules are a transfer rule based on consent that can be used for any type of right" [RE16]

The study analyzes data ownership approach from different angles. An important factor is how this approach manifests itself in reality in relation to individuals. The question is what advantages policy makers assumed for individuals with the approach. The key aspect is an attempt to look at this approach from the individual himself. In everyday life, data subjects face accumulated problems and solve them automatically.

The ESR is of the opinion that data ownership in the legal sense is important, but is not of the

main interest to data subjects. For them, practical problems and real control and awareness of their data are much more relevant. For data ownership do not necessarily demand the introduction of new forms of ownership, but something rather different. To see why, not that ownership can be taken as a proxy for certain cases, usage and control rights.^[HP20] The ESR is of the opinion that discussions on the topic of data ownership are nothing more than a search for legitimate ways to achieve the goals of personal data regulation.

The ESR argues that the priority of the data controller, first of all, should be the trust of the data subject. Building a trustworthy system and providing leadership, informing citizens about the purposes of processing their data, striving for transparency - all these factors strengthen the trust of data subjects. Unequal negotiating opportunities should be minimized in ways that are beneficial to individuals, such as access to their data at any time. The ability to correct your own data, correct any inaccuracies, delete irrelevant or unwanted data. The principle of data minimization described in the GDPR is important.

During the collection of information, the consent of an individual is usually requested for the storage, processing and sharing of this data. Each step of this process must be recorded and integrated into technical systems to comply with the principle of transparency. The manner in which consent is requested should be understandable, readable, and convenient for each data subject. In addition, everyone should have the right to claim damages for unauthorized use of their data. The method of communication with the data controller should be as accessible as possible to the data subject.

Thus, the personal data governance policy should give individuals the opportunity to distribute, revoke, share their data for various purposes, as well as receive benefits from their own data. The data subject must have the right and be informed of this right to access, use or delete their data. Data integrity must also be protected from third parties. Technical measures play a great role in this. Therefore, ESR 12 argues that a symbiosis of legal and technical measures is necessary.

4.5.6.3 Data Act and data ownership

The GDPR approach to personal data management and protection has been discussed above, but this does not apply to data obtained as a result of using connected devices and the Internet of Things. The Data Act¹⁷, which was published in the Official Journal of the European Union on 22 December 2023, makes it possible to control and "own" such data. It should be noted that the Data Act does not apply to data that the user already controls, such as data on PCs or smartphones. The Data Act is very important in the context of data ownership, as it contains provisions on who can create value from data and under what conditions.

The Data Act applies only to raw data, which is explicitly stated in the text. The processed data is not subject to the Regulation. Thus, we can talk about big data, artificial intelligence, which companies can exchange, but they cannot make this exchange without the user's knowledge.

¹⁷Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act)

An appropriate request is required for such an exchange.

The Data Act is interesting for its approach to the phenomenon of the user and the data holder. According to the Data Act a user of a connected product is a natural or legal person or even a public sector body, who has a legal right on a connected product. Where multiple persons have such a 'stable right', there can be more than one user with regard to the same connected product. Data holders are those who control the access to the readily available data. This may be the original equipment manufacturer of the connected product, software companies, providers of sensors and providers of other electronic equipment, to the extent each of these have access to the data.

It is important to note that the Data Act does not prejudice the General Data Protection Regulation. The protection of personal data is not compromised in any way due to data exchange obligations under the Data Act. The difficulty that needs to be emphasized and which can bring confusion is the separation of personal data from non-personal data. In some cases, it is in practice that this may be questionable. The user in the Data Act and the data subject in the GDPR are different concepts that cannot be identified.

Technically, providing access to users can occur as direct access or indirect access. With direct access, the user gets access to the data without first contacting the data owner, which can happen, for example, with mobile applications. With indirect access, the user must request access from the data owner. Data holders have an important right to choose between direct and indirect access, which largely confirms their "ownership" in the legal sense.

Thus, connected products according to the Data Act must be designed and manufactured in such a way that users can easily and securely access, use and share the generated data. This means that data is becoming more available, as well as an increased incentive for data owners to invest in high-quality data generation. Facilitating the transfer of data between data holders and data users in a secure way will undoubtedly have a positive impact on the data economy as a whole.

In Article 11 of the Act "Technical protection measures on the unauthorised use or disclosure of data" a data holder "may apply appropriate technical protection measures, including smart contracts and encryption, to prevent unauthorised access to data, including metadata...". This strengthens the control over the data of the data holder and brings back the concept of ownership.

In the legal relationship between the data holder and the user of the connected product and the recipient of the relevant services, the Data Act strengthens the position of the user. If the user shares this data with a third party, then the third party is limited by the fact, for example, that it cannot use them to create competing Internet of Things products. In general, the Data Act to some extent allows you to go beyond two-way data usage models, and provide the user with more extensive control over this data.

Due to the provisions of the Data Act, device manufacturers must build a new data processing strategy that includes more than just data protection requirements. All this combined will have a positive impact on the data economy and modernize its processes.

The Regulation gives users of connected products more control over data. This suggests a new approach to "ownership" as such, more access, more value benefit, more mobility and conve-

nience for data chain participants. The expansion of the concepts of data user and data holder leads to a concept beyond the boundaries of data ownership. Such a concept is necessary today, when in the world of the Internet of Things there are a huge number of devices that interact with each other. Data should not only be collected and stored properly, but also transmitted and used by enterprises to improve the quality of their products and services. Moreover, the data itself becomes a commodity with its own value, and the Date Act reduces the obstacles to their transfer. Thus, without recognizing the data as property, the Date Act nevertheless opens up new possibilities comparable to ownership as such. It will not be possible to completely get away from the concept of ownership, because control, access and security are inextricably linked with it.

4.5.7 Conclusions

The significance of the research findings in the context of the project objectives is crucial, as it can influence the development of data policy, especially personal data. The study focuses on the practice of working with data and empowering individuals. They are not always able to fully understand the processes that occur with their data, but they must be confident in transparency and the ability to get the data they need at any time.

However, there is an opinion that “data protection is on the bottom of the list of priorities for the IT companies” [T07] Of course, this is unacceptable because only a synergy of legal and technical measures can ensure the most complete data security and protection.

Data encryption, data anonymization, all these processes are closely related to computer science and legal science alone cannot overcome them. Reuniting the legal side with computer science is a powerful tool that can bring real benefits, including economic ones. When talking about privacy or intellectual property today, the introduction of technical measures and guarantees are timely responses.

With respect to sensitive data, they are a direct necessity. Health data, genetic data should be processed in ways that are especially protected from external attacks.

At the same time, the European data governance system should ensure the interests of other stakeholders. That is, each stakeholder should be able to control "their" data. In this way, the goal of increasing the value of the data and minimizing the associated costs can be achieved.

The legal status of data ownership is difficult to determine, it is disputed by many scientists and has a different approach in different legal systems. This is due to the dynamic nature of the data, which is difficult to determine. The study provides a detailed analysis of the data as an object of civil rights, examines the positions of supporters and opponents of this approach with a legal justification. The legal obstacles to data ownership are also considered and the GDPR provisions regarding the concept of data ownership are analyzed. After conducting the study, the need for a new approach to data ownership that takes into account the interests of all parties, namely, a more flexible and modern one, is outlined. To a large extent, the research is aimed at the possibility of extracting benefits for data subjects from this concept and the possibility of its application in practice. Although ownership may not be an appropriate category for formulating and recognizing the requirements of data subjects, the proposals of owners to reform the data

management system have their merits, especially in terms of access rights and data portability, which strengthen data rights. Data-related suggestions can also raise important issues of ownership, equality, equity and dispossession, trust of data subjects and consideration of the interests of all stakeholders.

The idea that not only property can be a right is argued in the study, and attempts are being made to go beyond ownership, thereby bringing flexibility and compliance with rapidly changing realities in the field of data. The study provides arguments in favor of data governance with the help of technical measures.

The research is largely elaborated at the issue of personal data management, which will provide individuals with real control over their data. Thus, the personal data management policy should provide individuals with the opportunity to distribute, revoke, forward their data for various purposes, as well as benefit from their own data. The data subject must have the right to access, use or delete their data and be informed of this right. Data integrity must also be protected from third parties. This whole spectrum involves the concept of ownership, legal rights to data, as well as technical capabilities for their implementation.

The data controller plays a significant role in this chain. The priority of the data controller, first of all, should be the trust of the data subject. Building a reliable system and providing leadership, informing citizens about the purposes of processing their data, striving for transparency - all these factors strengthen the trust of data subjects. In addition, everyone should have the right to claim damages for unauthorized use of their data. The method of communication with the data controller should be as accessible as possible to the data subject

5 Trustworthy development and deployment of AI

5.1 A Sociotechnical Approach To Revealing The Invisible Hand That Guides the Adoption of AI in Public Administrations

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5.1.1 Executive summary

The race for digitization by government bodies (Public Authorities), facilitated through the adoption of technical solutions aimed at benefiting public administrations through the inculcation of practices such as task automation, processes streamlining, intelligence augmentation through data based analyses. These practices are often observed to be rooted in the deployment of disruptive and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligent (AI) systems which comprise of machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms etc. This adoption of AI systems as a part of government digitization efforts has been observed across multiple European Union (EU) member states and has proven to be a challenging and intricate endeavor as there are various technical, organizational and social elements (collectively 'sociotechnical elements') associated with such efforts. These sociotechnical elements (STS) are often observed to be in conflict with each other, when not aligned adequately. This is where the first wave of tensions emerge that this research study aims to identify and resolve. In doing so, this research study is focused on simplifying the various, often invisible, sociotechnical elements that guide the interaction between humans and algorithms. In an effort to delineate the aforementioned elements, this research study converges into the specific context of the application of AI systems in the administrative and quasi-judicial sphere i.e. within government bodies such as the offices of public administrations performing decision-making functions such as the dispensing of public benefits, adjudication of licensing applications etc. A majority of the AI systems investigated within this research study are modeled as Automated Decision Making Systems (ADMS) fueled by predictive optimisation techniques that synthesis vast amounts of data and providing insights to the user. These data-driven insights may be relied upon by the user in order to make important decisions as mentioned previously such as the dispensing of public welfare funds, approving tax benefit requests, making a decision on license and visa applications etc. The use of these predictive optimisation fueled ADMS by public administrations is defined as Automated Governance for the purposes of this research study.

The research study begins with identifying the different types of underlying algorithms (whether ML, DL or NLP) which fuel the AI systems being used in Automated Governance systems. This allows for the examination of the potential shortcomings associated with these technical solutions (such as algorithmic opacity, skewed fairness metrics etc.). The acknowledgement of these technical limitations allows this research study to shift the focus of digitisation efforts from focusing on a solely technology oriented solution towards the acknowledgement of the social and organisational elements which may act as relevant guardrails to plug the limitations observed with the technical solutions. This shift from technical elements only digitisation approach to the inclusion of non-technical elements as core elements affecting digitisation efforts allows for a sociotechnical synchronisation. This synchronisation, in turn, adds to the benefit of Public Authorities seeking to successfully deploy and scale Automated Governance systems. This research study identifies the three primary sociotechnical elements (STS Elements), as follows- (1) Technological Elements such as the Automated Governance algorithms, the technical infrastructure within which the Automated Governance algorithms are housed etc., the data privacy, data governance requirements associated with the use of AI systems; (2) Organisational Elements such as the flow of information within an organisation, the hierarchal structures, internal policies governing the organisation within which the Automated Governance algorithms is deployed (whether rooted in self-regulation or legal compliances) etc. and; (3) Social Elements such as human behaviour, end-user requirements, collaboration, levels of AI literacy etc. The combined consideration of these STS Elements creates an operational labyrinth that providers and deployers must navigate in order to put in place crucial practices that allow for the creation of a safe, reliable and trustworthy Automated Governance system. The research study peers through the lens of these sociotechnical elements while directing its focus on the three broad crucial building blocks associated with the development and deployment of Trustworthy AI systems, namely- (1) Meaningful Transparency, (2) Algorithmic Accountability and; (3) Human Oversight. The careful inclusion of these building blocks, allows for providers and deployers to not only create a solid foundational basis for the development, deployment and subsequent use of the Automated Governance system but also allows for compliance with ethical and regulatory guidelines that are applicable to the Automated Governance systems.

However, this need to preserve the harmony amongst the broad crucial building blocks (Meaningful Transparency, Algorithmic Accountability and Human Oversight) while ensuring the trustworthy development and deployment of Automated Governance systems is where the second wave of tensions emerge. For example, the use of privacy preserving techniques, rooted in the legal requirements focused on risk management and algorithmic accountability require that public administration organisations deploying AI systems analysing personal data must undertake adequate precautions focused on data protection through the employment of privacy preserving techniques (PPT). In turn these PPTs are noted to have an adverse effect on the ability of the Automated Governance algorithms to display adequate and meaningful algorithmic transparency since most PPTs work towards masking of the datasets used by AI systems for their computations. This PPT led obfuscation of datasets, while protects personal data, ultimately impedes the efforts of the providers and deployers to ensure meaningful transparency. The vacuum of meaningful transparency vis-à-vis Automated Governance systems, subsequently hampers the efforts of deployers and users to exercise adequate human oversight on the Auto-

mated Governance system.

Finally, the research study in its efforts to advocate for a dynamic yet reliable form of algorithmic governance practices vis-à-vis Automated Governance systems turns its attention to use-cases where Automated Governance systems have been adopted by Public Authorities. The research study observes a total of five use cases of Automated Governance systems (where quasi-judicial functions are performed using ADMS) to carry out high-impact decision making with a direct effect on members of the public. This is done to identify the core aspects associated with the development, deployment and subsequent use of the Automated Governance systems. The study then juxtaposes these use-case based observations against the ethical and regulatory guidelines held within the EU's High Level Expert Guidelines on Ethical AI (HLEG Guidelines) and the EU's AI Act. Following this analysis, two primary vacuums emerge, namely (1) the lack of operational precision when providers and deployers envisage the need for automation with most Public Authorities acting as deployers of Automated Governance systems electing to embrace unorganised and spontaneous deployment plans focused solely on the race of first adoption vis-à-vis digitisation solutions. The fallout from this spontaneous and consequently unstructured automation approach often leads to catastrophic effects vis-à-vis fair and equitable treatment towards decision-subjects that cause considerable setbacks to health, safety and fundamental rights and also contribute to the wastage of considerable public funds on digitisation projects which fail in their pilot stages and; (2) the exclusion of the decision-subjects of the Predictive Justice system from the conversation surrounding the use of Automated Governance systems. The conscious exclusion of decision subjects ultimately leads to an irreversible erosion of the principle of human agency as well as the rule of law. This in turn is counterproductive to the promise of efficiency as well as a fair and speedy resolution that are the core pillars of administrative functions sought to be automated by Public Authorities through the adoption of Automated Governance systems. Finally, the research study concludes with recommendations split across ex-ante and ex-post algorithmic accountability driven requirements focused on enabling the adoption of reliable and trustworthy AI systems that may function to preserve health, safety and fundamental rights.

5.1.2 Introduction

5.1.2.1 Background

The core objectives associated with the development, deployment as well as the subsequent (and continued) use of Automated Governance systems across Public Authorities are focused on the efficient and effective delivery of public services. This parable of AI driven efficiency within a Public Authority while may seem straightforward, is an innately complex endeavour that is affected by a gamut of sociotechnical intricacies associated with these Automated Governance systems. [Mol+21a] However, in contravention to this complexity, Public Authorities are often observed to be hyper focused on the technical elements such as the ADMS empowering the Automated Governance system [Mol+21b] while the organisational and social elements imperative to the successful deployment and subsequent use of Automated Governance systems are met through a strategy focused on minimal planning or neglect [Mol+21c]. Further, this techno-

logical hyperfocus manifests itself through the Public Authorities' pooling of a large amount of digitisation funds available within their organisations towards perfecting technological elements (such as datasets arrangements, algorithmic variables, user interfaces etc.) associated with Automated Governance systems while overlooking the importance of streamlining practices across organisational and social sociotechnical elements[Mol+21c]. This lack of balanced disbursing of digitisation funds available to the Public Authority coupled with a lack of planning for sociotechnical streamlining causes irreversible damage to the digitisation efforts undertaken by Public Authorities, which is observed through a plethora of Automated Governance projects within Public Authorities across Europe which are never scaled beyond their pilot stages, termed by experts as the “ever-pilot” projects,[Mol+21c], a term that is used to describe Automated Governance projects that are adopted by Public Authorities with great gusto and superlative promise, however, due to their inability to function smoothly and be scaled sustainably, they are eventually scrapped[Ara+23]. The failure of these Automated Governance systems deployed through a solely relying upon technology-centered approaches further cements the premise that the successful technology-enabled transformation includes social and organizational challenges as opposed to a mere technical requirements. This paradigm gives rise to the need for a research study focused on the development and deployment of Automated Governance systems which focuses in equal measure on the various sociotechnical elements such as technical elements, organisational elements and social elements that have a direct and material impact on the successful adoption of the Automated Governance system. The objectives of this research study and the need for an equilibrium between sociotechnical elements is a perfect melody for interdisciplinary research which is focused on balancing the technical realities associated with Automated Governance systems (such as use of specific AI algorithms, meaningful transparency, technical robustness etc.) and the practical user focused requirements [Nov+24] (such as the human-behaviour focused on algorithmic accountability vis-à-vis the successful adoption of Automated Governance systems) all the while focusing also on examining the sufficiency of the AI focused regulatory requirements [Wac24] applicable to the Automated Governance systems in order to ensure trustworthiness within the Automated Governance system.

5.1.2.2 Objectives and Scope

The specific objectives of this research are rooted in ensuring trustworthy and safe adoption of Automated Governance systems by Public Authorities, through creating actionable practices across the AI value chain i.e. the providers, deployers and the decision-subjects. These actionable practices are focused on ensuring transparency, accountability and human oversight and are created through the identification and exploration of the sociotechnical elements that emerge from the intersection between AI systems and their adoption within the public administration ecosystem. The research study creates a specific focus on Automated Governance algorithms that perform functions with a material role on human-decision making practices within these public administrations, which ultimately are observed to have materially impacted the health, safety and fundamental rights of the decision-subjects. [Wan+24]The study begins by identifying the different types of AI systems used to create Automated Governance algorithms, which rely on predictive optimization to support decision-making through risk-indicator metrics

or projections of future conduct based on historical data patterns.[Wan+24]

Further, the research examines the sociotechnical framework within which these algorithms operate, analysing the interaction between technological, organizational, and social elements.[CS18] As discussed previously, central to this research analysis are three key building blocks for ensuring trustworthy AI systems: Meaningful Transparency, Algorithmic Accountability, and Human Oversight (“Key Building Blocks”). The research aims to address the tensions that arise between these building blocks. For example- ensuring algorithmic accountability through the upholding of data protection obligations through privacy-preserving techniques may conflict with algorithmic transparency efforts[DH23] and in turn hinder human oversight.[Li24] Therefore, a balanced matrix of sociotechnical considerations is crucial for mediating the tensions that arise from the interplay amongst the Key Building Blocks associated with Trustworthy AI systems. Further, in addition to these sociotechnical considerations, the study explores the issues vis-à-vis the development and deployment of Trustworthy Automated Governance systems, drawing on case studies focused on using AI systems in quasi-judicial and public administration settings. The research identifies two primary challenges: the lack of organizational precision in automating administrative processes and the exclusion of individuals affected by AI-driven decisions from discussions revolving around the deployment of automated Governance systems. Further, the research study juxtaposes these findings against the EU’s regulatory and policy landscape governing the use of AI systems which primarily comprises of the EU AI Act[Eur24a] and the High-Level Expert Group on AI’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (HLEG guidelines)[AI19a]. These legislative and policy instruments are relied upon in tandem with supporting legislations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)[gdpr], the Product Liability Directive (PLD)[DL23] and the draft Artificial Intelligence Liability Directive (AILD)[Zio+23]. the study identifies operational gaps that adversely affect the reliance on Automated Governance systems and subsequently formulates ex-ante and ex-post recommendations to foster trustworthy AI systems. By way of explanation, this study anchors its legal and policy research in the EU’s regulatory landscape inspired by the EU’s longstanding and keen focus on the ethical, human-centric and trustworthy AI practices. This focus is further illustrated through the EU’s continued attempts to streamline AI policy focused on ethical and trustworthy use as demonstrated through the publication of the HLEG Guidelines, the longstanding and spirited discussions focused on the adoption of the AI Act- a legislation focused on encouraging the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy AI systems, while striving to preserve health, safety and fundamental rights. Further, the intricate correlation of the PLD, the draft AILD and the GDPR vis-à-vis the adoption of AI systems and their impact on the rights of the public that is primary governed by the AI Act, is a powerful indicator of the EU’s vision to not only ensure the encouragement of technical innovation through the development and deployment of AI systems but also the preservation of the rights of the decision-subjects through the introduction of liability structures through the PLD and the draft AILD.[Gra24] Further, while there have been various criticisms associated with the sufficiency of the PLD and draft AILD,[Hac24] these directives still focus on ensuring a holistic view towards AI regulation that is essential in the context of regulating Automated Governance systems, where a delicate balance is required between the adoption of AI based solutions and their impact on the rights of the decision-subjects.

Additionally, the thesis focuses on the use-cases of Automated Government systems within pub-

lic administrations based on the severity of their impact on the users and decision-subjects as well as the amount of information available in the public domain, this allows the research study to narrow down five (5) case studies includes the use of Automated Governance systems deployed across Europe including the instances of the use of Automated Governance systems from the EU and the UK. While offering valuable insights into the challenges of AI adoption in quasi-judicial and public administration sphere, it does not cover AI deployment in other sectors or jurisdictions (such as the use of AI based Fintech products or credit rating algorithms in the US), and while its findings may have limited direct applicability outside of European jurisdiction, the sociotechnical perspectives which this research study employs ensures that these observations can still be considered reliable lessons in the development and deployment of AI systems in deployed in high-stakes scenarios to perform functions that may have a direct impact on health, safety and fundamental rights and therefore be potentially classified as high-risk AI systems under the EU's AI Act.

The primary research questions considered in this study are as follows:

(1)About The Technology:

What are the technical requirements of an artificial intelligence system which are valuable for designing an Automated Governance algorithm in order to comply with the delicate balance of ensuring fairness and meaningful transparency while complying with data protection requirements?

(2)About the Deployment: What is the deployment framework (regulatory and institutional) that is critical to the deployment of the AI systems in the quasi-judicial and administrative automation sphere to assist in performing administrative functions?

(3)About the Decision-Subject: How can Automated Governance systems be regulated to provide adequate rights to decision-subjects who are directly affected by these artificial intelligence systems?

The research study complies closely with the project goal of the LeADS project with ensuring interdisciplinary research focused on technology and law aimed at producing pragmatic and reliable results to issues faced in the domain.

5.1.2.3 State of the Art

The understanding of ADMS is a wider construct which is fuelled through a decision making system. This “system” can be modelled on a simple strategy such as a rule-based[[Hu+23](#)] data flow or employ the use of complex and self-learning algorithms[[Iva23](#)] to achieve the said “automation” vis-à-vis decision making. To clarify, the concept of automation, per say, lies not in the ability of an ADMS to function without human oversight or supervision, but rather in its ability to reach an accurate and usable output with minimal human intervention. [[Ara+23](#)] The scope of algorithmic decision making can be further nuanced into (1) the use of algorithms which follow a dedicated rule-based methodology in order to carry out their analysis. This rule-based methodology is best understood as a nexus of multiple “if-then-therefore” statements, that have been defined by human-experts based on their knowledge and experience, in order to (as the name rule-based methodology suggests) to create rules which are used to analyse datasets in order

to identify specific patterns and consequently trigger event based actions [Kor+23] and; (2) the use of advanced analytics such as AI systems based decision making which comprises of the self-learning and self-adapting machine learning and deep learning algorithms.[HDo5] Owing to the advanced capabilities of AI algorithms, these algorithms are capable of analysing complex patterns with multiple defined and undefined variables across large and ever-growing datasets. This ability of an AI algorithm to identify patterns within datasets beyond what has been defined by a human-expert, allows for AI algorithms to be an ideal solution when dealing with complex and multi-variable predictions which are often seen to drive ADMS systems.[GC19] Previously, non-AI-based advanced analytics algorithms such as regression analysis, cluster analytics, linear programming, statistical forecasting etc. were seen to be commonly used across the board for augmentation of decision making exercises, however, the self-learning capabilities of AI algorithms and the reduced human intervention at computational stages have since superseded these methods, with AI algorithms being used to incorporate the underlying methodologies of these (previously) non-AI analytical techniques within itself.[DK19] As discussed above, there are varying levels of human involvement in both the decision making using rule-based algorithms and the use of advanced analytical techniques, primarily focused on the use of AI algorithms, based decision making with the former allowing for a high level of human involvement in all aspects of the algorithm's design and subsequent function such as the specification of rules associated with the decision making process as well as the re-tuning of the algorithm in order to ensure compliance of the computational framework and the evolving needs associated with the decision making process. On the other hand, AI algorithms require minimal human intervention in the actual computational efforts, once the algorithmic constraints have been defined and operationalised. The self-learning attributes associated with artificial intelligence, allow for the substitution of human-costs associated with continued algorithmic modifications and supervision as observed in non-AI algorithms.[EMS19]

Finally, while technological prowess dictates the computational abilities associated with an algorithm, the primary consideration is to identify the decision-making aspects which must be automated and the intensity of technological intervention that is required to adequately accomplish the tasks at hand. Therefore, it is noted that often the use of expensive and time consuming AI algorithms in relatively simple situations is an overkill and may not produce results which are significantly different than what may be achieved through the use of non-AI algorithms.[Che+23]

The type of algorithm which should underline the use of ADMS may be decided based on a two-pronged analysis (1) The domain or the subject matter within which an ADMS is deployed and; (2) the level of complexity associated with the analysis carried out by the ADMS.[Gri23] A combined consideration of these two factors may be used to create an impact-profile associated with the use of an ADMS, which may allow organisations to identify the level of automation or analytical computation they desire, which consequently dictates the measure of time, money and resources they are willing to invest in the adoption of technological tools. For example: The use of ADMS to identify simple tasks such as the optimisation of work calendars across a company (a low-impact task) may not need AI based ADMS and the use of a rule-based algorithm may suffice, however, the use of an ADMS to decipher the course of surgical action based on the chances of survival during a medical procedure (a high-impact task) may warrant the use of

AI based ADMS.

This primary differentiation which dictates the type of algorithm to use for ADMS is based on the impact and risk profile and the type of tasks that ADMS may be able to perform. Rule-based algorithms are suited for clear and well-defined tasks, whereas AI driven ADMS showcase the capabilities of tackling uncertain, complex or dynamic tasks. The advent of the internet revolution which acted as a catalyst for the creation of large volumes of data, has cultivated various high-impact situations within which ADMS are being used since these decision making practices require the assessment of historical activity of persons contained within large datasets a task which is usually performed using AI systems in various scenarios such as credit score assessments, loan approvals, selection for jobs etc.[Ara+23]

5.1.2.4 AI technologies for ADMS

The rising use of AI based ADMS to assist and augment decision making driven by their ability to generate insights backed by not only large but also dynamic datasets against the background of ever evolving societal, organisation and regulatory norms, is a tall order. However, there are various AI algorithms that may be used to create robust and reliable ADMS based on the domain within which they are deployed and the tasks that they are expected execute. This section focuses on providing a bird's eye view of some of the most common AI algorithms used as the underlying technology for high-impact ADMS, that are tailored into Automated Governance systems. These AI algorithms span across three main categories i.e. (1) Machine Learning Algorithms; (2) Deep Learning Algorithms and; (3) Other AI Techniques. Understanding the intricacies associated with these algorithms, allows for deciphering their strengths and limitations associated with each type of AI algorithm. A keen assessment of these strengths and limitations is crucial in the development and deployment of a trustworthy AI system as it sets the stage for creating the guiding principles that are used to implement regulatory and algorithmic accountability measures. A short overview of these technologies is presented below:

(1) Machine Learning Algorithms

Machine learning is a sub-set of AI technology that is focused on mimicking human behaviour through utilising large datasets and self-learning algorithms.[Biso6] The algorithms associated with machine learning are further classified into two sub-categories i.e. Supervised Learning and Unsupervised learning, which are discussed at length in the upcoming sections.

(a) Supervised Learning:

Supervised learning can be best understood through the example of a child being taught about shapes and colours. The common practice in teaching is to show the child different shapes and colours, tell them of the names associates with such shapes and colours. Over time, and with repetitive exposure to different shapes and colours, the child learns to recognise them on their own, without the teacher having to assist the child every single time. Similarly, supervised learning in AI is focused on the algorithm being shown lots of examples of things (which is the data), that are already labelled with the correct answers (borrowing from the previous example, this may be a shape or a colour). Through this continued exposure, the computer learns to identify things on its own accord through either identifying previously shown shapes or combinations

of the two, for example: A red circle placed inside a green square.

This is of course a rudimentary example of the capabilities of AI through supervised learning, various categories of supervised learning algorithms are used to perform a wide array of tasks. These sub-categories of supervised learning are separated into two broad categories focused on problem solving, [Biso6] these are discussed below:

(i) Classification methodology: Classification methodology in supervised learning is focused on the use of algorithms to accurately identify the different categories within which data points of a specific dataset may be placed. This classification based algorithm may be used to carry out low-impact tasks such as acting as a spam filter or high-impact tasks such as fraud detection mechanisms used in the banking and finance industry, However, it is crucial to note that even though there are significant upsides to using classification methodology of supervised learning such as its inherent efficiency and consequent accuracy, as well as the comparative ease of scalability, there are certain issues such as its dependence on data sets and the observed opacity which may deter reliability and trustworthiness vis-à-vis this methodology. A few examples of widely used algorithms backed by classification methodology of supervised learning are decision trees, support vector machines, linear classifiers and random forest.

(ii) Regression Methodology:

The use of regression based analysis is a common practice in designing algorithms which are focused on the utilization of a vast volume of numerical data. The algorithm based on regression methodology is trained to identify the relationship between two types of variables held within a dataset i.e. (i) dependent and (ii) independent variables. Through the process of decoding the relationship between these two types of variables, the algorithm is able to deduce and predict outcomes which may find meaningful applications across the banking and finance industries or the study of environmental patterns; another use case of such a regression analysis is the ability of the algorithms to spot patterns across the interdependent variables by employing the use of mathematical formulas. [Biso6] Finally, regression analysis, through its combined ability to decipher patterns across the data and also its ability to emulate predictive analysis may also be used to assist in complex investigations such as forensic or financial audits, by unearthing suspected wrongdoings as well as procedural anomalies. This cements the place regression analysis holds in the use of AI based ADMS across various domains. Some common techniques used within the umbrella of regression analysis are models incorporating linear regression, polynomial regression and logistic regression model

(b) Unsupervised Learning

To understand unsupervised learning, the example of a child's exposure to shapes and colours takes centre stage again. Imagine the child is being tested for cognitive abilities such as perception and logical reasoning, as a part of the test, the child is provided with a box of toys where many toys are of the same colour and each toy has an associated box shaped like the toy. There are no instructions provided to the child. The child may showcase the ability to deduce patterns based on the colours and shapes of toys through either clustering the toys with the same colour together or putting the toys in their correct boxes, thus showcasing adequate cognitive abilities and learning based on the correlation between the variables presented before them. Similarly, unsupervised learning is the ability of a machine learning algorithm to

deduce patterns and insights across unlabelled data points contained in wider dataset, thus the name unsupervised learning, emerges from the minimal human intervention associated with the algorithm. The vast majority of unsupervised learning algorithms may be classified into the following categories:

(i) Clustering Algorithms:

The use of unsupervised learning algorithms can be used to group similar data points together based on shared characteristics. Techniques such as k-means clustering algorithms are focused on classifying similar categories of datapoints together to create discernible patterns within a larger dataset. A common example where k-means clustering is used in everyday life can be the recommender systems on OTT platforms which analyse viewer behaviours and recommend potentially interesting movies.[XLNo6]

(ii) Dimensionality Reduction Algorithms:

The use of unsupervised learning is often observed to analyse large datasets, therefore, often the number of variables or features within a dataset is too high. This is when the use of dimensionality reduction algorithms comes into play as the algorithm is focused on reducing the data inputs to a controllable size in order to reduce the 'noise' within a dataset, while preserving the quality of the dataset. This dimensionality reduction algorithm is used for principal component analysis and as the name suggests, is focused on the identification and reporting of key or principal features within a dataset. This analysis of key features allows for the dataset to become manageable and therefore, application of recommendation systems or other forms of supervised learning might be made possible. Additionally, dimensionality reduction algorithms allow for the reduction in processing time associated with vast datasets.[VDMPVDHo9]

(iii) Association Algorithms:

The use of association algorithms, as the name suggests, employs the use of rule based classifications to identify (often hidden) relationships between different data points within a dataset. The main feature of association algorithms lies in their ability to trace these associative patterns without any prior instructions, this often leads to deeper insights within a dataset, which may not be apparent to even human-experts at first glance. These algorithms are widely used across various commercial activities ranging from e-commerce platforms which use large datasets to identify consumer trends and make product recommendations based on associations within the dataset to streaming services which rely on recommender systems to showcase content based on not just user history but associated patterns.

(2) Deep Learning

Deep learning is a niche subset of machine learning within the AI universe; Deep learning algorithms are focused on deploying algorithms which simulate the human brain's learning process through the use of neural networks (which are also called artificial neural networks or simulated neural networks).[HMP20] Neural networks are algorithms or a set of algorithms that is programmed to simulate neurons of a human brain in order to engage cognitive reasoning and arrive at conclusions. The deep learning algorithm uses multiple neural networks typically defined as "deep neural networks" which is a collective noun for three (3) or more neural networks. These deep neural networks are, much like other AI applications, trained on a large volume of data in order to hone their ability to identify, classify data points, recognise patterns within a

dataset, engage in predictive analysis based on the patterns identified within a dataset. The use of deep neural networks within a deep learning algorithm allows for the multifaceted processing of a dataset, which may lead to optimisation of results based on greater accuracy.[Has95] This is especially useful in the case of AI driven expert systems acting in their capacity as ADMS in high-impact and high-stakes domains such as medical sciences, law enforcement, public administration etc.

(i) Natural Language Programming: This technique is focused on harnessing the combination of computational linguistics and the rule-based processing of human languages with statistical and machine learning models, through the use of deep learning techniques. NLP algorithms is used in helping computers learn, understand and generate text and speech which mimics human linguistics.[Eis19] This is an especially complex tasks as human language does not follow a singular approach but is in fact multi-dimensional with various complex features which are characterised by the use of idioms, metaphors, sarcasm, homophones, homonyms, grammar rules (which vary across regions) and the composition of vocabulary.[WM22] There are a wide array of applications for NLP algorithms such as named entity recognition, sentiment analysis and text classification to name a few. Currently, one of the most popular use cases of NLP is its application through natural language generation to create large language models (LLMs). Essentially, LLMs use NLP driven natural language generation to learn the statistical relationships between words and therefore, are able to generate human-like text. The use of LLMs has been widely observed across various domains from their use as chatbots and virtual assistants to question answering systems that are used to convey complex concepts through simple language, or presenting the results of complex analysis in a succinct manner to the user. The relative ease of use accompanied with LLMs owing to the ability for human-users to understand their computations with ease owing to their simplified ability to present results by generating human-like texts has cemented their place within the Generative AI ecosystem (Generative AI is an umbrella term used to define a branch of AI which is focused on creating new data such as texts, images, audio-visual content, machine code etc.).

This widespread popularity of LLMs within the generative AI universe and the ease of adoption associated with them couple with their inherent malleability, has also led to the recognition of a new type of AI model – the foundation model.

(ii) Foundation Models

The clamour of private and public entities driven by the race of AI adoption has created an increasing need for the AI providers to create solutions which are flexible and can be deployed across various sectors, domains and assist in the performance of a wide array of tasks. These task-specific models that are trained on a particular dataset and are designed to perform specific tasks, have ruled the roost across the AI landscape so far. The creation of task specific models is time and resource intensive, where each model takes many months if not years to not only create but deploy and subsequently fine tune. However, with the increased fervour towards AI adoption imposes the need for a more malleable AI system, this is where the foundation AI models come into play.[SMK24] The term foundation models was popularised by the Stanford Institute for Human Centred AI and is used to describe large AI models which are trained on a vast volume of data which contain text, images, codes, audio-visual content or a combination of

these.[Yan+23] This developmental strategy combined with the deep learning capabilities associated with these models allows them to act as a foundational layer upon which specialised AI applications can be built.[Bom+21] For clarity, it is noted that Foundation Models are also known under key legislations such as the EU's Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) as General purpose AI systems which include Generative AI models (GenAI)[Eur24b] built through large AI models. A well-known example of Foundation Models are the LLMs such as ChatGPT (based on the GPT3 LLM), Gemini (based on the LLM Bard) and the Llama 3.1 (an LLM by Meta) which have been used as the baseline technology across various sectors, with many organisations using their own datasets to train these models for specific applications. These foundation AI based applications are used for a wide array of tasks such as chatbots, content moderation, personalised recommendations etc. The use of LLM based foundation models are a popular choice when it comes to the creation of ADMS, since they are not only able to be converted into specialised applications and scaled based on requirements, but also because the output generated by them mimics human-text and is therefore easier for a user to decipher or question, therefore winning points on the AI adoption scale.

There is much debate about the impact levels of foundation models upon their use within a potentially high-risk AI system especially across critical domains such as health, law enforcement, public administration and education. These concerns largely stem from the fact that foundation models are trained on large volumes of data and therefore can imbibe the bias present in those datasets. This presence of bias and the inherent opacity associated with the complex inner workings of the AI algorithms raises many questions around the reliability and accountability of foundation models. Another problematic observation which has recently come to light with regard to the use of LLMs is their tendency to hallucinate in order to create answers to the questions which may be posed to them. This is problematic as many conversational AIs powered by LLMs display an inherent anthropomorphism in their responses which may lead to an added degree of user trust.[Coh+24] Therefore, the deployment of these LLMs as a part of ADMS systems may create over-reliance triggered obstacles, that may render the users of the ADMS blind to hallucinations within LLMs.[Lin24]

5.1.2.5 Automated Governance and Sociotechnical Systems

Following the intricacies of the technical landscape of ADMS, the research study progresses towards the recognition of the concept of sociotechnical systems. The deployment of an AI based algorithmic model in its capacity as an ADMS requires a careful calculation which is focused on many factors such as an internal assessment of the stage of decision making within which the ADMS may to be deployed, the information pipeline which informs the ADMS's output, the human oversight requirements, the levels of risk associated with the task expected to be performed etc. [MA21a] Consequently, the primary currency that drives decision making within an ADMS is information married to context; in keeping with this understanding, the process of decision making within an organisation is a complex task achieved by multiple considerations involving several stakeholders that are connected with technical, social and organisational elements that may have either have a direct or an indirect impact on the decision outcome made by an ADMS or are in turn being affected by such decision. This combination of the technical,

social and organisational components creates a larger interdependent system referred to as an STS. The theory of STS was first developed as an organisational development approach that is focused on identifying the complexities associated with workflow and work design. These complexities are largely driven through the interaction between social (such as persons, levels of education and technical skills), organizational (such as processes, timelines and task flows) and technological elements (such as hardware and software components) within an organisation (collectively the 'STS Stakeholders').[CS18] In the recent past, given the fast-growing landscape of emerging technologies, the understanding of the theory of STS has gained prominence as it significantly impacts the understanding relating to the interplay between a technical element (such as algorithms, datasets, AI architecture etc.) and social elements (such as users, supervisors, persons exercising human oversight etc.). In the present context of Automated Governance systems, this interplay informs the context modelling that is applied within technical elements (ADMS algorithms), ultimately allowing for effective human- AI teaming.[CS18] The context inculcated in the technical elements (ADMS algorithms) is harvested through the social and organisational elements within the STS such as the persons who may use the ADMS, the level of skills they have, the placement of the ADMS within the organisation etc. Further, the vital task of ensuring parity in contextual awareness across the various levels of the organisation can be accomplished through the implementation of normative and (if applicable) regulatory standards that govern the social and organisational elements of the STS. Additionally, technological constraints may be applied on ADMS algorithms to ensure compatibility of the technical elements of the STS vis-à-vis the applicable normative and regulatory boundaries. This synchronisation is instrumental in ensuring adequate transparency, human oversight and accountability.[Lis+23]

The algorithmic governance canopy[JIV19] associated with an STS spans across the STS Stakeholders in an effort to enable a coherent and interdependent ecosystem wherein the roles, regulatory mandates and normative responsibilities associated with each of the STS stakeholders carried out adequately. Further, to ensure a synchronized governance across STS stakeholders, scholars advocate for a three step approach[CS18] focused on (1) Designing the STS system such that all STS stakeholder are adequately involved in the functioning of the STS, (2) Enactment of such well-designed STS (as expressed in (1)) wherein the STS stakeholders act in their expected capacity to perform technical functions, organisational coordination or social tasks and (3) The focus on the ability of an STS Stakeholder to adapt based on the growing or diminishing normative and regulatory requirements imposed on them as a part of (1). This dynamic and ever evolving governance outlook allows for the STS to function as a malleable and self-sustaining organism as opposed to a rigid technology-heavy framework which may be prone to making unfair adjudications that ultimately affect the accountability of the ADMS and consequently its deployment within an STS.

The complexity of these considerations is contingent on the context in which they are applied, therefore the need to justify and carefully deliberate on the various (micro and macro) elements encompassed within these STS considerations that assume significance when reaching a decision. The use of ADMS without human involvement to analyse context driven elements as a part of the deliberation process, materially impacts the overall decision-making process within an STS.[GC19] However, the scope of automation within ADMS can be varied and is achieved on a need-based basis by the utilisation of appropriate technology. For the purposes of this section,

the principal focus lies on the use of AI based ADMS, which rely on one or a combination of the various algorithms as those discussed previously (section 5.1.2.4). This distinction is made owing to the fact that the technical nuances such as learning capabilities, scalability, transparency considerations associated with AI based ADMS are significantly different and more complex than algorithms rooted in advanced analytics and therefore are required to be crafted carefully when being developed for a specific use case and being deployed within an organisation.[MCGK21]

For example: government departments and Judicial bodies tasked with performing complex and time consuming judicial, quasi-judicial, administrative and investigative functions have in recent years turned to the use of artificial intelligence in order to perform various tasks which are both simple (such as file management tasks, data grouping tasks etc.) and complex tasks (data mining based tasks, analytical tasks, predictive tasks which may be used to predict behavioural patterns of data subjects etc.) and are in many cases operating without sufficient transparency and meaningful human oversight[GC21] that lead to these ADMS and their associated succumbing to risk factors associated with the use of AI algorithms.[Hof23] Consequently, these shortcomings and socio-technical gaps in the ADMS directly affect the trustworthiness, fairness and often adaptability of the ADMS within an STS.

Further, in the case of the deployment of the ADMS within an STS, it is important to acknowledge that an STS is not a singular ecosystem, it is possible that the ADMS is deployed at an overlapping junction of multiple STS.[CS18] This is the junction where an organisational STS evolves into a societal STS and therefore has an added responsibility to ensure transparency and abide by human oversight requirements.

5.1.2.6 Meaningful Transparency and Automated Governance Systems

The common theme across the various types of AI algorithms which are used to create ADMS and their place within an STS as discussed in the previous section points towards the inner complexity and opacity associated with them. The task of creating an ADMS by using these algorithms either by themselves or in tandem with each other often leads to their inner complexity and opacity being reflected outwards.[SKM22] This outward reflection of the intricacies associated with an AI based ADMS may lead to confusion, mistrust or accountability concerns [SBT20] in the minds of the human-user of an AI driven ADMS, therefore, the focus on meaningful transparency remains crucial.

This approach is cemented by the regulatory compliances that are focused on ensuring meaningful transparency within the scope of application for AI systems such as ADMS carrying high-impact computations associated with high-stakes, high-impact activities.[LWM24] This concern is also mirrored by researchers, lawyers, technologists and computer science professionals across multiple jurisdictions who advocate for the swapping of opaque AI systems with interpretable AI systems for ADMS deployed in high-stakes scenarios.[GR23] Similarly on the regulatory front, the EU's AI Act devotes special attention to the transparency and human oversight principles that high-risk AI systems must ensure in order to function in the public domain. These new legal rules held in the AI Act seek to eliminate, or at least minimize, the risks associated with the opacity of algorithms, which is a feature in AI systems that does not allow for a full understanding of the processes that lead to the final output.[Lau23] Therefore, to increase the

users' trust in these systems and the accuracy of their training by the providers of these systems, it is necessary to enable AI systems to provide ad hoc explanation of their decisions in an intelligible and meaningful way for human-users.[Ped+19] It is precisely for these reasons that computer science research is focusing on the development of methods capable of illuminating the inner workings of opaque AI models through explainability mechanisms to ensure transparency, facilitating understanding and, above all, human control over the AI model. Against this background, it is also crucial to acknowledge that technical or algorithmic transparency is not enough when it comes to the use of ADMS within high-impact and potentially high-risk scenarios such as healthcare, public administration, law-enforcement etc. A collaborative and multi-dimensional approach between STS Stakeholders needs to be taken in order to truly achieve meaningful transparency vis-à-vis the AI system. Scholars note that this effort to ensure meaningful transparency includes within itself three crucial transparency components, namely (1) Algorithmic Transparency[Lon+24] ; (2) Interaction Transparency [Vös+22] and; (3) Social Transparency.[HLH23b] This section focuses on the elaboration of these components and the relevant sub-components encased within them.

(1) Algorithmic Transparency

The fulcrum of using AI based ADMS to assist or augment human decision making in high-stakes scenarios across a diverse set of domains such as healthcare, public administration, finance, is the ability to justify not only the use of the technology but also advocate for the reliability associated with the decision-influencing output generated by the ADMS. This want of trustworthiness and reliability from the ADMS becomes stems from the understanding most ADMS are processing humanely unmanageable amounts of data to reach their conclusions, therefore, human verification of each result is not only time-consuming but rather counterproductive to the narrative of efficiency surrounding the use of ADMS. However, the claims of analytical superiority associated with the use of AI based algorithms is seemingly thwarted by their opacity. In the context of their use within high-stakes scenarios to carry out high-impact computations, the primary deterrent to the perception of algorithmic accountability, trustworthiness and fairness lies with the inability of the human-user to understand the inner workings of the AI algorithm and therefore raises questions regarding not only their output but also their use within a high-impact and high-stakes use case.[GNB21] The inner complexities, especially when an ADMS is driven by underlying technology that uses techniques such as unsupervised learning, deep learning, natural language processing etc. cannot be retracted using linear measures of explainability, especially since the internal evaluation mechanisms followed by the ADMS are exceedingly complex and therefore difficult to mimic. In addition to the technical complexities associated with the transparency focused endeavours surrounding the use of ADMS, the use of explainability techniques to decipher proprietary algorithms also faces many legal and operational hurdles, allowing companies to feign intellectual property rights protections to block access to the ADMS therefore, impeding the deployment of explicability measures.

For example, many the AI based ADMS deployed within public administrations are constructed as opaque AI models[GNB21] which make it difficult for their users, who may have varied levels of AI literacy, to trust their computations and rely on their outputs. This is problematic for one of two reasons, namely (1) In cases where the AI system is performing computations which are potentially discriminatory in nature, it is difficult to represent these skewed values and

ascertain the presence of inherent discrimination in the AI model, thus, reliance on them may propagate this bias and adversely affect the decision subjects and; (2) The absence of a viable explanation accompanying the output of the AI based ADMS system that may be relied upon by the public administration makes the order legally unviable as it does not meet the basic requirements associated with the Right to an Explanation enumerated in both administrative law [Eur12] as well as the regulations governing the use of automated decision making from the perspective of both data protection as well as algorithmic transparency [Eur24a] within AI systems.

(2) Interaction Transparency

The theory of STS elucidates the correlation between the STS Stakeholders within an organisation and how such interactions between the social, organizational and technical elements within an STS affect the implementation of technology within a specific domain. In keeping with the knowledge generated through these interactions, by the interpretation and contextualisation of data by social and organisational elements while utilising technical tools within an STS, the concept of interaction transparency emerges. [Mil19] The notion of interaction transparency is rooted in the understanding that knowledge i.e. is the quantifiable and actionable impact generated by the deployment of an AI system are co-created through the interaction between and object which in this case is the technical component within an STS i.e. the AI system through which the information is processed and the subject i.e. amalgamation of the social and organisational components within an STS namely the user of the AI system that perceives the information relayed by the object (AI system) and contextualised it based on normative and organisational standards. [Pol90]

Therefore, the knowledge so perceived or created by the subject based on its reliance on the object is directly impacted by how well the subject can understand the logic associated with the output created by the object. In addition to the same, the ability of the subject to interact, critically analyse, question and where required disregard or correct the knowledge thus created becomes crucial. In the case of AI system with human-users, this translates into the ability of the user to understand the logical reasoning followed by the AI system to reach a certain conclusion. This harmony is achieved through two importance facets, namely (1) meaningful algorithmic transparency and; (2) the ability of the user to understand the algorithmic explanation or interpretation so provided to them. [HLH23a] Therefore, the responsibility of interaction transparency lies on the shoulders of both the providers as well as the deployers of the AI system. The fulcrum of interaction transparency is therefore the engaging interaction of users with an AI system designed to be human facing and oriented around providing clear concise communication tailored to the audience, whether experts or non-experts. [Lei+23] In the previous sections (Algorithmic Transparency), the technical solutions to create an AI system with meaningful levels of algorithmic transparency have been explained at length- therefore, in this section, the central focus remains the ability of a human-user of an AI system to comprehend the information presented to them. Although there is vast literature pertaining to the creation of meaningful algorithmic transparency that is focused on the translation of complex algorithmic variables into simpler factors which allow the users to comprehend and trust the internal functions of the AI System, it remains crucial that the users of such systems are well versed in, the elements of algorithmic functioning for AI systems so that they are equipped to critically

analyse the AI system in question. It is at this point where the significance of AI literacy within the social and organisational elements of an STS surfaces. Policy makers across jurisdictions have debated the importance of AI literacy, with the EU's HLEG Guidelines enumerating the efficacy of AI literacy [AI19a] as a crucial non-technical method to ensure trustworthiness in AI systems. Similarly, the EU's AI Act through its Article 4b [Eur24b] sets out the indispensable and mandatory requirement towards providers and providers of AI systems to ensure a sufficient level of AI literacy for the persons dealing with the operation and use of AI systems. However, AI literacy is multi-faceted, it is context specific and the ability to ensure AI literacy is based on the user's technical knowledge, experience, educational background. Thus, a one-size-fits-all approach falls short in the matter of ensuring AI literacy.

(3) Social Transparency

Social transparency is irrevocably intertwined with the tenets of AI for social good (AI4SG) [Flo+21] and plays a pivotal role in accomplishing the endeavour of trustworthiness associated with AI systems, especially those deployed in high-risk scenarios. Experts define social transparency in AI as the extent to which AI systems and their decisions are open to scrutiny and understandable by human beings, including both the experts within the technical, policy and interdisciplinary communities and non-experts such as the general public. [Flo23] This understanding and the ability to understand AI Systems and their decisions is rooted in the understanding of Technical and Interaction transparency as has been discussed in the previous sections, however the access to AI Systems and their decisions is dictated by the principles of social transparency, thus making social transparency the crucial final piece of the algorithmic transparency puzzle. [HLH23b]

It is noted that the combined elements of regulatory mandates and ethical guidelines focused on ensuring transparency in the context of ADMS between the object i.e. the ADMS algorithm and the subject i.e. the decision subject and the impact population at large (subjected directly or indirectly to the ADMS) create the foundational basis of social transparency. Further, social transparency, as indicated before is achieved through the fulfilment of technical and interaction transparency requirements, therefore, the regulatory and ethical mandates that ensure social transparency vis-à-vis an ADMS must be fuelled by a collective adoption of algorithmic transparency and interactive transparency principles while focusing on actionable compliances that are aimed at inculcating transparency requirements as a mandatory facet within AI systems. [KR21] These regulatory and AI ethics based efforts are supplemented by policy developments at an international level [Eur] that are strongly rooted in the development of fair and trustworthy AI systems while recognising the importance of the adoption of transparency requirements vis-a-vis AI systems and their subsequent impact in achieving fairness and transparency goals. [AI19a] Furthermore, experts view AI regulation focused on transparency and AI ethics as a collective toolkit to ensure social transparency. This synchronized uptake between AI ethics and regulatory mandates is crucial as it creates a cohesive framework through which meaningful transparency including algorithmic, interaction based or social transparency, is applied. This cohesive framework not only binds the providers through the employment of best practices but also helps deployers in ensuring algorithmic accountability across the AI value chain through mechanisms such as auditing of AI systems, risk assessment and mitigation policies etc. [WMM23]

While AI ethics is a research area that is dedicated to the identification of algorithmic accountability focused best practices for the development, deployment and use of AI systems, the ethical principles governing AI systems such as sustainability etc. are essentially non-binding in nature. Further, the adherence to AI ethics may help organisations in defining future-proof [WTS24]self-regulation practices that may not yet be reflected in the regulatory mandate applicable to the providers and deployers of emerging and fast developing technology such as AI systems. The state of the art for emerging technologies evolves rapidly and are often not inculcated in the legislative mandate until later, this threatens to create an accountability gap vis-à-vis the development and deployment of such technologies, however, the same may be mitigated through the application of self-governance mechanisms focused on ensuring algorithmic accountability, transparency, reliability etc.[HQ24]

On the other hand, legally binding regulations create actionable compliances upon providers, deployers and users of AI Systems to ensure the facilitation of trustworthy, fair and reliable AI systems, there are various legislative mandates ensured within the regulatory frameworks. Further, unlike the obligations enumerated under Algorithmic and Interaction transparency requirements (as discussed previously), the ethical and regulatory principles associated with ensuring social transparency span uniformly across the AI value chain. This exhaustive compliance mechanisms required to ensure social transparency is associated with the need to ensure that the transparency measures are incorporated within the AI system as a deliberate and ex-ante requirement as opposed to an ex-post measure. The creation of social transparency measures involving the various stakeholders across the AI value chain have manifold benefits, however, the three main purposes which this practice accomplishes are as follows: (1) Transparency by design requirements (which include social transparency) ensures that the providers create their AI systems in order to ensure that compliances vis-à-vis social transparency will be met and consequently allow for the users, decision subjects and the impact population to have a robust interaction with the ADMS. This is especially crucial as many leading providers and organisations are primed to hide their internal practices against the three-facet shield of trade secret protections, non-disclosure agreements and inherent technical complexities.[MP24] (2) Upholding algorithmic responsibility through social transparency tools is the cornerstone of ensuring that there are mechanisms in place to not only deter future violations and instances of AI failure but also to ascertain the defaulting party and consequently hold systems, providers, deployers and users responsible for any instances of AI failures.[KM24] Social transparency becomes a crucial part of the AI liability matrix and is a key aspect in ensuring judicial action and subsequent reparations in case of any damages caused to a decision-subject(s) or the impact population at large owing to the use of an ADMS. (3) Lastly, the social transparency mandate incentivises the alignment of AI behaviours and human values, ensuring that AI systems and their subsequent use is not in contravention to societal norms and expectations.[Flo+21] For example, the principle of neutrality is the cornerstone of judicial conduct, therefore, the use of a biased ADMS as an intelligence augmentation tool by a judge would be in contravention to this principle and therefore in contravention to the legal mandates and societal expectations pertaining to the decision-making practices undertaken by a judicial or quasi-judicial body. . Trustworthiness in an ADMS is not only a technical requirement but also a human-facing and crucial characteristic which affects the manner in which a human-user engages with an algorithm, therefore, social

transparency enforced through an outward and human-facing transparency vis-à-vis the inner working of the ADMS becomes a crucial piece of the trustworthy AI puzzle.[Cow+21]

The compliance with social transparency requirements, which creates a channel for public participation vis-à-vis the use of AI systems and public contestation to the use of AI systems, is also an essential mechanism of risk identification and risk mitigation within the AI landscape, wherein the public's (including experts and non-experts) access to the AI system and its decisions acts as a balancing force when it comes to the development of new technology, therefore ensuring that the providers and the deployers tread with caution while developing or using AI systems in high-risk scenarios.[KM24] This may facilitate an organised development route for the AI System and supplement the careful implementation of the technology focused on ensuring the adoption of trustworthy AI systems as opposed to rampant, uncontrolled use in high-risk scenarios that may potentially lead to incidents of AI failure and cause damage by way of discriminatory practices towards the decision-subject and the impact population at large.

While meaningful transparency is crucial to ensure trustworthiness within an AI system, another essential component for ensuring fairness and trustworthiness vis-à-vis an ADMS is the human-oversight regimen attached to its use and deployment. Meaningful transparency aids the endeavour of effective human-oversight which in turn acts as a deterrent to unfair conduct of an ADMS or callous reliance on the decisions meted out by the ADMS. It is crucial at this point to differentiate between the concept of social transparency which is rooted in the concept of access to an AI System and Human-oversight which is rooted in the concept of not only access to an AI System and its decisions but the principle of exercising human autonomy which may be facilitated by the ability to supervise or engage with the AI System in a primary capacity, without the need for judicial intervention. The crucial requirements remain focused on the human-in-the-loop who must exercise such oversight as well as the importance of ensuring contextual robustness, freedom to exercise human-agency and finally, the ability to intervene in cases where AI based harms may be caused to the decision-subject or the impact population at large.

5.1.2.7 Human Oversight and Automated Governance systems

Trustworthiness has emerged as a central feature associated with the use of AI Systems, with the endeavours towards ensuring trustworthiness spanning across legal, ethical, technical and social perspectives vis-à-vis the use of AI Systems. However, there are a plethora of risks and vulnerabilities associated with the use of AI systems as intelligence augmentation tools in high-risk scenarios; addressing these vulnerabilities to maintain trustworthiness vis-à-vis the AI System require a synchronised collaboration across the various social, legal, ethical and technical elements which impact the development, deployment and use of AI Systems. This has led to the development of risk identification, risk management and risk mitigation practices (collectively the 'Risk Management Framework'). This Risk Management Framework includes within itself a bevy of tools focused on ensuring the controlled development, deployment and subsequent use of the AI System such as transparency protocols, impact assessments both technical and focused on fundamental rights, conformity assessments, algorithmic supervision, transparency requirements etc.[Nov+24] The employment of the Risk Management Framework becomes in-

creasingly important in the cases where AI Systems are used to carry out high-impact computations such as Automated Governance systems, therefore, the practice of exercising supervision through human oversight becomes a central practice within the Risk Management Framework. The practice of human oversight finds its influence through its advocacy by various policy frameworks and legal regulations within the Key Jurisdictions.

However, in its position as a central tool within the Risk Management Framework, human oversight is closely correlated with the concept of exercising human agency. The exercising of human oversight is not merely an observation-based technique, instead, human oversight ensures that AI Systems function as intended while adhering to prescribed regulatory and ethical standards, this helps in supporting human agency instead of undermining or delegating it to an algorithmic agent.[BB24a] The instilling of human agency within the AI value chain by means of human oversight becomes a central facet to promoting and maintaining trustworthiness vis-à-vis the AI System.[Wag19] The practice of decision making is central to exercising human agency, with that in mind, the use of ADMS as a part of a decision-making practice, runs the risk of disrupting or at the very least, influencing the exercising of discretion or human agency. Therefore, the use of human oversight mechanisms within the realm of Automated Governance practices becomes a crucial practice.[Pru24] Human oversight is exercised within the contours of the AI value chain as an indispensable process which further informs the actions which may or may not be taken by the relevant stakeholders. For clarification, the requirement for the human agency focused human oversight measures within the AI value chain span across the development, deployment and use of AI Systems, thus encompassing within its purview the technical, organisational and user-based behaviours associated with the use of AI Systems.

The practices associated with the exercising of human oversight have been classified into three broad methodologies based on the methodology adopted by the EU's HLEG Guidelines [Al19a], namely- (1) Human in the loop (HITL)[Mun21]; (2) Human on the loop (HOTL)[Cre22] and; (3) Human in control (HIC)[Kou20] (collectively the 'Human Oversight Methods').

In addition to the Human Oversight Methods as discussed above, the combined concepts of human oversight and human agency evolve into the understanding pertaining to meaningful human control. Meaningful human control is best understood as the ability of the human supervisor performing human oversight functions to understand, oversee and when required intervene in the functioning of the AI System.[Rob23] The exercising of meaningful human oversight requires the human supervisor to not only have the technical background required to understand the inner functions of the AI System but also the relevant organisational credentials and power to intervene in cases of deviation by AI Systems which may lead to violations of legal rules, ethical guidelines and societal norms.[Dav23] Another crucial feature required to exercise meaningful human control is relevant domain expertise and a strong correlation with the contextual requirements associated with the use of AI Systems in the applicable environment.[CS+23] However, this is an evolving concept and much like the discussions relating to meaningful transparency, is heavily influenced by the developments in technology and the context within which it is applied.

While human oversight may be touted as a one stop solution to the issues pertaining to algorithmic discrimination and trustworthiness, this approach has been criticised by many scholars

who call into question the innate usefulness of human oversight regimens.[Gre22] The lack of empirical evidence illustrating the benefits of the results produced by the human supervision of algorithms as opposed to the results produced by the human and algorithmic entities in isolation is a crucial point of apprehension towards the presumed benefits of human oversight mechanisms.[Ban+21] The overreliance on algorithmic abilities especially in scenarios which use AI Systems within a high-reliability contexts such as predictive modelling or anomaly detection, may lead to (in many cases unavoidable) automation bias, where the human users and supervisors may perceive the decision output of an AI System as “as a heuristic replacement for vigilant information seeking and processing”.[Mos+96] In keeping with this perception, human supervisors may overly rely on the decision outputs produced by AI Systems which may deter them from detecting erroneous or unfair outputs.[Ste+24] Conversely, human supervisors may be distrustful of the decision outputs produced by an AI Systems or overly confident in their own expertise and consequently may end up overriding or disregarding decision output which in reality are fair and accurate. The summarised paradox of the issues associated with human oversight of AI Systems is that most AI Systems are designed to supersede human intelligence or aide human users in complex activities, however, the same human user who is supposed to be benefited by these AI Systems assumes the role of their supervisor. This irony perpetrates the shortcomings of human behaviour within the human oversight mechanisms governing AI Systems, therefore, regular human supervisor trainings, assessment and AI audits must accompany human oversight mechanisms in order to ensure the balance of powers within the various stakeholders within the AI Value chain.

The dialogue concerning human oversight assumes vital importance in scenarios where the AI systems is developed and deployed as an intelligence augmentation tool to be used for decision making purposed by another human user. This overlapping of responsibilities and the possibility of contradictory human agency raises concerns regarding many nuanced concepts such as the relevance of domain expertise, supervision dynamics vis-à-vis the human supervisor and the human-user, the internal power structure between user and supervisor and whether this power structure allows for over-riding of decisions become crucial.

5.1.2.8 Overview of Automated Governance and Algorithmic Accountability

The domain of Automated Governance requires a high level of algorithmic accountability as the provider and deployer institutions i.e. the Public Authorities are bound by their own set of accountability requirements[MM19] which (depending on the jurisdiction) may or may not be enforced through regulatory provisions such as operational neutrality, transparency in conduct, freedom from corruption, compliance with public information requests etc. These institutions, as an effort to uphold their duties and obligations require a robust combination of self-regulation, operational transparency across their key stakeholders and public scrutiny. Algorithmic Accountability in the context of Automated Governance borrows many features from these pre-existing standards of accountability while also making case specific additions to address the finer nuances of the situation such as the issues of fairness, algorithmic transparency, human oversight requirements etc. However, the key distinction in this research study’s approach to algorithmic accountability is that it does not focus solely on the actions which must

be undertaken to ensure algorithmic accountability but focuses on the question of who takes the responsibility to justify the development and deployment of an Automated Governance system while also investigating the liability structure attached to it by enumerating stakeholders within the AI Value chain responsible for the negative consequences of these systems.[Bov07] This focus towards the liability framework has proven to be an effective tool in streamlining algorithmic accountability practices and allows for the progression from what was previously a principle-based approach [Mit19] to a more action plan oriented framework. This liability-based approach within algorithmic accountability is derived from the theory of relationality which advocates for the responsibility of stakeholders within an AI value chain to go beyond attributability but towards actual accountability where defaulting stakeholders are held accountable for their faults or their underperformance within an ecosystem [Coo+22] which in the present case is the AI Value Chain. Further, building on the theory of relationality, the theory of responsibility makes a distinction between *being responsible* and *being held responsible*,[Sca00] this distinction informs the current understanding of accountability [Sho11] which is cornerstone to the discussion revolving around algorithmic accountability especially since the dual trend in the computer science industrial complex is (1) strengthening of property rights associated to digital products (such as through intellectual property rights) and; (2) avoiding [HL23] Algorithmic accountability in the context of Automated Governance is a tall order, which requires a systematic approach while roping in the key stakeholders across the AI Value chain. This requires a robust and dynamic combination across many socio-technical facets associated with the development and deployment of Automated Governance systems. Therefore, algorithm accountability in the context of an Automated Governance application can be enforced across four crucial avenues with specific focus on the disbursement of algorithmic accountability across the STS stakeholders. Algorithmic accountability is focused on the demands that shape these requirements and the accountability measures that key stakeholders can incorporate to fulfil them.[HL23] Further, algorithms are not value neutral but in fact incorporate the norms, intentions and prerogatives of the persons involved in developing them. Therefore, it is impractical to hold algorithms themselves accountable and consequently, the liability shifts towards the providers and the deployers of the algorithms.

Against this backdrop of the crucial building blocks associated with the Automated Governance systems- i.e. (1) Meaningful transparency, (2) Human Oversight and; (3) Algorithmic Accountability, this research study shifts its focus towards the real-life instances where the use of Automated Governance systems were observed.

5.1.2.9 Comparative Case-based Analyses of Automated Governance Systems

This research-study is focused on examining five cases of the deployment of Automated Governance systems across Public Authorities across the EU and the UK with focus across seven key constrains as derived from the EU's AI Act and the EU HLEG Guidelines. The five use cases of Automated Governance systems were chosen based on the severity of their impact on the decision-subjects and the impact populations, the amount of information available in the public domain regarding their internal functions and workings, the level of government and judicial responses associated with them and finally their relevance to the three research questions fo-

cused on; (i) the development variables associated with the Automated Governance systems (with a crucial focus on meaningful transparency and human oversight); (ii) the deployment framework within Public Authorities deploying Automated Governance systems and finally (iii) the degree of human agency and intervention capabilities accorded to the decision-subjects as well as the wider impact population.

Finally, these use-cases are as follows: (i) Systeem Risico Indicatie (SyRI), Taxation Authority, Netherlands [DTLVC] (ii) ADMS for Income Support Benefits, Trelleborg Municipality, Sweden.[OECa] (iii) Horizon IT Inquiry, The Post Office Limited, United Kingdom [Sha] (iv) The Fraud Risk Model for Universal Credit Applications, Department for Work and Pensions, UK [Off23] (v) Visa Application Screening Model, The British Home Office, UK [Fox22]

These use-cases are examined across seven investigatory parameters. These investigatory parameters are broadly divided across three segments with each investigatory parameter corroborating with the research questions investigated in the research study i.e. (i) Components associated with the development of AI systems such as Data Management, algorithmic transparency metrics and contextual clarity associated with the Automated Governance system; (ii) Components associated with the deployment and subsequent use of AI system such as the internal governance mechanisms, human oversight requirements, exercise of meaningful human control, interaction transparency etc. and finally, (iii) Components associated with the rights of the decision-subjects and the wider impact population subjected to such Automated Governance systems such as the social transparency requirements, disclosure requirements (or lack thereof) to the decision-subject regarding the use of an Automated Governance system, compliance with existing laws focused on the preservation of fundamental rights, data protection etc.

The exhaustive list of the seven key investigatory parameters, including a bird's eye overview, is as follows:

1. Data Management Framework

Data to an AI system is what fuel is to an engine and much like how any compromises with the fuel can adversely and materially affect the health, reliability and safety of the engine, the same holds true for data and its impact on the robustness and trustworthiness of an AI System.[BM17] This holds especially true in the case of Automated Governance systems owing to their technical mandate to rely on data driven insights in order to aide and assist the delivery of public services such as the dispensing of public welfare, investigating for fraudulent claims for public benefits, streamlining of internal operations for Public Authorities and assessing risk vis-à-vis applications made to the Public Authorities. In keeping with the complexities of the tasks and the impact that the decision-outcomes of Automated Governance system on the fabric of public administration, the requirement of robust and enriching data management practices becomes a key pillar in the development of Automated Governance systems.[Aga18] This investigatory parameter focuses on identifying the sufficiency of data management framework undertaken by public authorities deploying Automated Governance systems.

2. Internal Governance Mechanisms

The successful deployment and subsequent safe use of Automated Governance systems are a direct result of robust, yet dynamic internal governance mechanisms positioned within a Public Authority. This section directly correlates to the concepts of algorithmic accountability as

discussed previously. Experts versed in the best practices associated with internal governance framework focused on ensuring trustworthy and safe deployment of complex AI systems (such as the Automated Governance systems) advocate for the internal governance framework to be viewed as a sociotechnical endeavour[Asa+21] rooted in ethical practices.[WFB19] In doing so the internal governance framework encompasses various STS stakeholders associated with the Automated Governance system deployed within a Public Authority. This includes various tasks such enforcement of meaningful transparency and meaningful human control vis-à-vis the algorithmic agent, periodic auditing of Automated Governance systems etc. The peculiarity associated with the creation and enforcement of internal governance mechanisms is involving the vertical levels across the Public Authority and establishing the correct chain of command to ensure compliance across all levels, the rigidity of Public authorities and the bureaucratic red-tape may often slow down this endeavour. This investigatory parameter focuses on the sufficiency and the viability of the internal governance mechanism undertaken by the public authority deploying Automated Governance systems.

3. Risk Assessment and Mitigation Mechanisms

The risk assessment and mitigation mechanisms are tied closely with the internal governance practices and follow the risk based regulation mechanisms prescribed within the EU's AI Act.[Eur24b] While the use of Automated Governance systems may not be considered high-risk AI systems by default, especially where the Automated Governance systems may fall under the narrow task exemption under the AI Act or may utilise tactful self-determination to exempt themselves from being classified as high-risk AI systems,[Wac24] the investigatory parameter looks to identify the risk-levels associated with each of the use-cases (as per the prescriptions of the EU's AI Act) and trace their compliance with risk-management and mitigation requirements which may be applicable to them.

4. Human Oversight Requirements

The nuances pertaining to human oversight, the role of AI literacy[Eur24a] in adequate performance of human oversight obligations as well as the combined impact of human oversight and AI literacy on meaningful human control vis-à-vis the deployment of ADMS have been discussed at length, previously. In this investigatory parameter, the scope is expanded beyond the previous sections to include the regulatory obligations governing the establishment of human oversight regimen vis-à-vis high-risk AI systems under the AI Act.[Eur24a] Tied closely with the risk management sections, the investigatory parameter looks to identify the human oversight requirements based on the risk-levels of the various Automated Governance mechanisms as observed in the use-cases.

5. Contextual Clarity

Context in artificial intelligence has long been investigated as a core pillar associated with the successful development of intelligent AI systems [CDS23] that may be equipped to produce decision outputs that are relevant and appropriate.[Bre99a] While the definition of context within the field of computer science varies, the endeavour to adequately translate relevant background factors such as cultural, situational, historical or social elements which must be measured by an AI system while computing a decision output has been identified as the practice of context modelling.[Bre99a] Context modelling is focused on the effective use of background factors

associated with an AI system, in order to ensure adequate accuracy, precision and fairness vis-à-vis an AI system and reliability associated with the use of the AI system, especially in complex cases.[Bre99b] However, experts have been quick to warn against the perceived infallibility associated with context-aware AI systems[Erio2] and encourage a shift towards human-AI partnership focused on imbuing and preserving context within an AI system instead of relying solely on the technical encoding of context within an AI system.[Sch+18] This shift in perspectives is crucial in order to ensure that the context programmed within an AI system can evolve to adequately meet the challenges of dynamic evolution vis-à-vis background factors.[Jia+23] The same may be achieved through tools such as feedback loops, regular human monitoring etc. The central premise of inviting humans into the fold of contextual awareness stems from the increasing reliance of AI systems within sensitive yet dynamic fields which may have a direct impact on the health, safety and fundamental rights of persons such as finance, law enforcement, government administration, medicine etc. Therefore, contextual awareness within these fields becomes a core consideration for the development as well as deployment practices associated with AI systems, correlating their presence with meaningful human control.[Kwi22] This investigatory parameter therefore focuses on whether specific contextual parameters were enforced during the development and deployment of the Automated Governance systems.

6. Meaningful Transparency

The investigatory parameter focused on meaningful transparency derives its scope from the concept of meaningful transparency as discussed in the previous sections. In addition to the same, the regulatory prescriptions held under the EU's AI Act[Eur24a] and the EU GDPR [PEU16] are also included as a part of the investigatory scope in order to adequately assess the sufficiency of the Automated Governance system's ability to uphold and exercise meaningful transparency.[WM18] [HLH23b]

7. Rights of the Decision-Subjects

Automated Governance systems are integrated across Public Authorities as essential technical components aiding administrative procedure with the aim to promote efficiency and skills of the Deployer-User.[Mol+21a] However, while these systems may be used by Deployer-users within Public Authorities the final audience of their decision-outputs are the decision-subjects.[Mol+21c] These decision-subjects, in the case of a traditional interaction (sans the use of Automated Governance systems) with Public Authorities would be subjected to the full protections of administrative law as well as fundamental rights, however, often the same protections are found diminished in the face of the Public Authorities' use of Automated Governance systems. In addition to the procedural safeguards provided by administrative laws, decision-subjects affected by Automated Governance systems (who are also data subjects whose personal data is processed by these Automated Governance systems) have the legal right to opt out of being subjected to automated individual decision making involving the use of their personal data as per applicable data protection laws.

The HLEG guidelines[Al19a] and the AI Act [Eur24a] advocate for importance of trustworthy AI and are aimed at the adoption of AI systems that are focusing on ensuring the protection of health, safety and fundamental rights. Both the HLEG guidelines and the AI Act, employ a number of methods to reach their goals, namely (1) the HLEG guidelines which taken an ethical

guidelines based approach to AI systems identify core requirements pertaining to trustworthy AI and relying on (i) technical methods including but not limited to being focused on testing and validation, explanation methods, ethics and rule of law by design approaches etc. and; (ii) non-technical methods such as regulatory and standardisation requirements, accountability, stakeholder participation (including social dialogue) to ensure the development and deployment of trustworthy AI that are focused on ensuring the flourishing of technology and supporting the agency of individuals. On the other hand, (2) the AI Act undertakes a risk based approach focused on prohibiting AI systems which pose unacceptable levels of risk and mandating a complex legal compliance framework associated with the use of high-risk AI systems.

An in-depth analysis of the HLEG guidelines reveals that the under the aegis of its non-exhaustive requirements for trustworthy AI (which is applicable to both individual and societal aspects) lie two crucial components, namely- (1) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, operationalised by (amongst other things) stakeholder participation and; (2) Societal and environmental well-being, operationalised by inclusion of considerations relating to AI systems on social impact, society and democracy.

These requirements reveal the HLEG guidelines' vision towards the commitment to principles of fairness and prevention of harm through the careful assessment of the AI system's impact on society and democratic processes and the acknowledgement of detrimental effects associated with the ubiquitous exposure to AI systems on society at large. Further, the HLEG guidelines encourage accessibility in the design of AI systems instead of a one-size fits all approach, so as to not alienate vulnerable groups in the digitisation process. Finally, the HLEG urges the involvement of persons directly or indirectly affected by the use of the AI system in its development process. This is envisaged as a bridge building endeavour, focused on allowing providers and deployers of AI system to acknowledge the unique requirements which may be necessary for trustworthy AI systems to be deployed in specific contexts. In keeping with these requirements, the HLEG guidelines in Chapter III [Hle] of their provisions, offer an assessment checklist which is focused on examining whether the AI system is trustworthy. From the perspective of stakeholder participation and inclusivity, these trustworthy AI assessment parameters include considerations pertaining to whether the providers and deployers of AI systems used any stakeholder participation mechanisms in the deployment and use of AI systems, in cases where the AI system directly interacts with humans, are there adequate disclosures made to the users and decision-subject that an AI system is being used (as explained in the subsection above detailing Meaningful Transparency), whether broader social impact of the AI system's use beyond the direct decision-subject, such as indirectly affected stakeholders, have been considered?

The AI Act cites the importance of involving stakeholders which include the persons or representatives of person who may be affected by the use of high-risk AI systems in the process of conducting the fundamental rights impact assessment (FRIA).[Eur24b] This has been noted as a crucial requirement in the context where AI systems are deployed in Public Administrations, however, while this has been reflected in the recitals to the AI Act, the same does not find a specific mention in the provisions pertaining to the FRIA. In addition to these stakeholder participation requirements in high-risk AI systems, the providers and deployers of GenAI[Bar+23] systems are also required to disclose the artificial manipulation of content through an AI system.

However, while the HLEG guidelines make multiple recommendations to include stakeholder participation and accessibility as a core component associated with trustworthy AI, the same is not adequately reflected under the provisions of the AI Act, where the regulatory compliance span largely across providers and deployers of AI systems, while leaving decision-subjects to whom the decision output of AI Systems has been administered are often kept out of the frame. Therefore, this investigation parameter is focused on acknowledging the direct and material impact the deployment of Automated Governance system has on its decision subjects and the rights of such decision subjects (if any) as alluded to in the policy and regulatory framework governing AI Systems.[Nov+24]

5.1.3 Methodology

The methodology employed in this research study involved a comprehensive literature survey to explain the fundamental technical, policy, and legal concepts pertinent to high-risk AI systems, with a specific focus on their application in Automated Governance scenarios. Subsequently, five case studies utilising Automated Governance systems were meticulously selected. Secondary research was conducted through the examination of government reports, investigative studies, and other relevant documents, without the inclusion of any primary data.

These case studies were then rigorously analysed in the context of the ethical and regulatory frameworks governing AI systems within the European Union namely the HLEG Guidelines and the EU AI Act, with specific nods to the GDPR framework governing automated individual decision making which relies on personal data.

This approach provided a detailed assessment of how these Automated Governance systems align with established ethical standards and regulatory requirements, facilitating an in-depth understanding of their compliance and operational impact.

5.1.4 Research Findings

This research study details the methodology adopted in order to delineate the research findings based on a comparative analyses of five seminal use-cases of Automated Governance systems based on seven key investigatory parameters. This analyses against the backdrop of key building blocks of sociotechnical systems i.e. meaningful transparency, human oversight and algorithmic accountability have led to the formulation of the following research findings vis-à-vis the development and deployment of the Automated Governance systems across public administrations. This section focuses on using examples from the case-bases analyses (where required) to detail the research findings.

5.1.4.1 Broad Motivations and Inadequate Planning

A majority of the Automated Governance use-cases observed under this research study were launched as the Public Authorities' response to their government's visions focused either on the digitisation of public services or the prevention of fraud vis-à-vis public benefits. This has been

noted as a matter of public records in the cases of the Dutch Ministry's use of the SyRI algorithm,[DTLVC] the British Post Office's reliance on the Horizon software[Sha] and the Trelleborg Municipality's introduction of the Social Benefits ADMS.[OECa] These broad goals set at a government level trickle down to particular Public Authorities as a clarion call for kickstarting the race for first-adopter status for technical solutions to broad problems.[Mol+21a] Therefore, this race may often result in Public Authorities reaching for technological overkill and adopting AI systems for instances where other technological solutions (such as advanced analytics) would've sufficed.[Mol+21c] Further, the broad mandate of innovation focused merely on adoption of new technology may distract the Public Authorities from duly acknowledging the inner complexities and opacity associated with these AI systems.[Rud19] Needless to say, this approach proves to be counterproductive to the efficiency based premise of AI adoption since the Public Authorities are observed to not have adequately defined the problem they are keen on solving using AI systems but instead focusing on the mere adoption of AI technology as a part of their operations pipeline.[Rud19] This absence of clear goals may lead to a plethora of issues such as the inability to judge the right type of AI system for specific needs, the inability to define data management requirements vis-à-vis the Automated Governance systems which may lead to an excessive collection and subsequent processing of data (including personal data) for the training and development of Automated Governance systems. This data excess may not only be in contravention to the data protection regulations but may cause Automated Governance system to operate in want of qualitative datasets refined to meet particular problem solving goals the AI system is tasked with, the absence of which may lead the Automated Governance systems to incorporate bias from the large volume of unfiltered data that may ultimately lead to algorithmic discrimination. This absence of planning vis-à-vis problem statement identification and the subsequent adherence to haphazard data management strategies is observed in the use-case pertaining to the adoption of the SyRI algorithm, where the Dutch DPA stated that the use of personal data related to 'nationality' of the decision-subjects by the SyRI algorithm was excessively invasive and maintains that the process of risk-classification pertaining to taxation fraud could have been carried out without using information pertaining to nationality. Additionally, the UK's Visa ADMS has also been noted to rely disproportionately on the nationality of the visa applicant as a material aspect in deciding the risk classification attached to the visa applications. Both of these instances point towards a lack of attention towards the actual goal for which the Automated Governance system was adopted as well as the lack of tailoring the data management plan when supplying information vis-à-vis the development and training of the Automated Governance system thereby compromising on data quality. Lastly, the same pattern has also been observed across the British Post Office's Horizon software where a whistleblower describing the electronic point of sale (EPOS) feature of the Horizon Software noted that the EPOS was built with no design documents, no test documents, no peer reviews, no code reviews, and no coding standards.[Wal21b] These shortfalls amongst many others were recorder as "Issues with EPOS" as a part of a list of Outstanding Issues for resolution in Annex D of Montague Report.[CTC99] Concrete details of the mitigation efforts - besides the on-site software support framework which was operationalised post-facto are not available. Considering the central importance of the EPOS element to the financial integrity of the Horizon software, the haphazard development and deployment of the EPOS was a core detrimental feature associated

with the issued emanating from the use of the Horizon software.

5.1.4.2 Inadequate Internal Governance Mechanisms

Public Authorities seeking to develop and deploy Automated Governance systems in their capacity as intelligence augmentation tools designed to support the decision making practices have been observed, in the past, to view the introduction of an AI system within the organisation akin to the introduction of an IT innovation.[RN16] However, this understanding has evolved in the recent years with the acceptance of the disruptive impact AI systems have within organisations owing to the fast paced evolution of their capabilities.[MA23] Further, Automated Governance systems fuelled by AI systems do not require intense human-intervention (unlike IT solutions) to learn and modify their internal logic structures,[AI19b] therefore, deployer users within Public Authorities may not be able to fully understand and adequately monitor these Automated Governance systems.[MSV24] This vacuum within Public Authorities may lead to material implications on the accountability and reliability of Public Authorities and Automated Governance systems. Therefore, a dedicated internal governance mechanism (comprised of techniques such as risk management plans, standard operating protocols, AI literacy efforts, human oversight protocols, a dedicated issue escalation matrix etc.) is required to adequately oversee these Automated Governance systems,[SK24] however, owing to the fast evolving technological aspects related to AI systems and their towering impact on the organisational and social components within Public Authorities, this internal governance mechanism may benefit from being rooted in a sociotechnical approach.[Nov+24] However, as per the observations focused on internal governance mechanisms, risk management frameworks and contextual clarity vis-à-vis the case-based comparative analyses, the Public Authorities across the five cases prove to be deficient in not only employing adequate internal governance frameworks but also fall short of assessing and mitigating risks associated with the use of Automated Governance systems. This has been observed in the case of the SyRI algorithm, where the Parliamentary Investigation Report noted that while the Deployer-Users within the Dutch Ministry sought directions on how to proceed in cases where the SyRI algorithm displayed high-risk metrics for possible fraud or illegalities, no material working instructions or guidance was provided[DTLVC] This vacuum pertaining to instructions of use is further highlighted when the information pertaining to the use of the SyRI algorithm being limited to assess only the 'problem districts' comes to the fore, this further elucidates the absence of standard operating procedures, working instructions and other related internal governance mechanisms when it comes to the deployment of the SyRI Software by the Dutch Ministry. Similarly, in the context of the Social Benefits ADMS, researchers conducting interview based surveys across the Trelleborg municipality offices focusing on the adoption of the Social Benefits ADMS observed an ambivalent nonchalance towards the use of the Social Benefits ADMS which was categorised as mundanization of the technology.[OECA] Further, while the case workers (Deployer-Users) were provided with a software training module focused on the helping them navigate the software, the same does not necessarily amount to an effort to ensure adequate AI Literacy vis-à-vis the use of Automated Governance systems. Similarly, in the case of the British Post Office's use of the Horizon software, to a plethora of inadequacies related to the internal governance mechanisms of the deployment and contin-

ued use of the Horizon software have been observed. These include the inadequate training modules pertaining to the Horizon software, the insufficiencies of the software support system for the Deployer-Users, the use of the decision outputs generated by the Horizon software, the decisions made by the British Post Office and its employees based on the data generated by the Horizon software.[Sha] Further, It is noted that basic in-house training pertaining to the use of the Horizon software. The Horizon software training format was divided in three namely (i) Classroom training imparted to a wider group of individuals, (ii) on-site support provided to new Postmasters and sub-postmasters in the use of the Horizon software for their first week of using the software and; (iii) intervention training where in the event a branch was identified to have any issues with the Horizon software they were re-trained or specifically trained in certain problem areas. However, this training was limited to the basics of navigation vis-'a-vis the Horizon Software, and did not focus on how to handle or even identify algorithmic anomalies or mistakes, in fact, it has been noted that the feedback by Deployer-Users pertaining to the Horizon Software's malfunctioning were not taken seriously by persons in charge. Another issue vis-'a-vis internal governance mechanisms which appears is the inability of Public Authorities investigated under the comparative case based analyses to acknowledge the sociotechnical nature of the Automated Governance system deployed within a Public Authority and its key spanning across technology, the organisational and the social stakeholders. The internal governance mechanism across Public Authorities seems to hyperfocus on the technological components of the Automated Governance systems which disregarding the crucial organisational and social components. This has been observed in the DWP's internal governance mechanism's focus solely directed towards assessment of their machine learning algorithm and its impact on decision-subjects through a weekly algorithmic fairness analysis[Off23] while completely disregarding the need to re-configure the need to weave in the AI system within its organisational processes in a sustainable manner through relying on employee upskilling, investment towards AI literacy, human oversight protocols creation of a risk identification, management and escalation matrix etc.

Conclusively, this research study notes that the lack of adequate internal-governance mechanisms within Public Authorities seeking to deploy Automated Governance systems is an expected fallout triggered by the failure to narrow down the problem solving parameters for which the Automated Governance system is deployed and the adjacent failure to recognise the inherent complexities associated with the use of AI systems. Building up on the abovementioned subsection (Broad Motivations and Inadequate Planning), the vacuum of internal practices focused on internal governance mechanisms, is a problematic oversight on behalf of the Public Authorities seeking to deploy Automated Governance systems.

5.1.4.3 Lack Of Meaningful Transparency Vis-'A-Vis Automated Governance Systems Within Public Authorities

The premise of meaningful transparency has been elucidated at length in the previous section, these sections adequately establish the central importance of meaningful transparency vis-'a-vis trustworthy AI, the core sub-components associated with meaning transparency i.e. algorithmic transparency, interaction transparency and social transparency and finally, the specific impact

of meaningful transparency in establishing trust vis-à-vis the Public Authority's deployment of Automated Governance systems and the core requirement of meaningful transparency which includes not only an outward disclosure of algorithmic processes but also adequate and timely sharing of relevant and accessible information that may allow decision-subjects of Automated Governance systems to advocate for themselves. This is reflected across ethical guidelines, regulatory framework and judicial pronouncements.[EU24]

The comparative case based analyses reveal numerous shortcomings associated with the Public Authorities' practice of meaningful transparency. The primary observation is that across the five use-cases, each of the AI systems deployed as a part of the Automated Governance system were opaque models and no particular explanation, whether pertaining to the processing constrains or through xAI techniques were shared. This tone of the Public Authorities' subservience to algorithmic opacity within Automated Governance systems has been observed to set the tone pertaining to other sub-components of meaningful transparency (interaction and social transparency). The lack of algorithmic transparency in turn affects the ability of Deployer-Users to critically engage with the Automated Governance system, thereby falling prey to either over-reliance or under-reliance. Similarly, the lack of social transparency fuelled by algorithmic opacity, hinders the ability of decision-subjects to engage with the decision-outputs of the Automated Governance systems, which ultimately inhibits the ability of decision-subjects to advocate for themselves even in the cases where algorithmic discrimination is suspected. Further, the lack of meaningful transparency while deploying Automated Governance systems also completely disregards the core beliefs associated with investigatory conduct such as the presumption of innocence.[Wie23a]

The SyRI algorithm is identified as an intentionally opaque AI model,[DTLVC] additionally this algorithmic opacity coupled with the Dutch Ministry's unclear deployment strategies of the SyRI algorithm, which led to its application across specific low-income, immigrant dense neighbourhoods led to a serious lack of algorithmic accountability and trust vis-à-vis the deployment of the SyRI Algorithm. Further, the investigation by the Dutch DPA also revealed the lack of transparency vis-à-vis the SyRI algorithm that subsequently led to violation of the applicable data protection framework.[Aut24] Further, the Hague District court in February 2020 rendered its judgement in the case of NCJM et al. and FNV v The State of the Netherlands[Den20] where it categorically stated that neither the Dutch domestic legislations governing SyRI nor the development, deployment and subsequent use of the SyRI software respected the principle of transparency. The Hague district court further specified how the lack of such transparency led to the inability of the data subjects (also in their capacity as the decision-subjects of the SyRI algorithm) to advocate for themselves in the observed cases of discriminatory actions fuelled by the SyRI algorithm led investigations. Similarly, in the case of Social Benefits ADMS, the details pertaining to the technical aspects of the Automated Governance systems were not readily available in the public domain and were released only after multiple freedom of information (FOI) requests and an appeal before the Swedish Administrative Court of Appeals which concluded in the court directing the Trelleborg Municipality to release the source code in public domain in compliance with the administrative principle of access to public records. However, while the source code was released in the public domain, it was not streamlined to convey meaningful information pertaining to its inner mechanisms as this disclosure was provided akin

to a data-dump which contained both relevant and non-relevant information pertaining to the Social Benefits ADMS. This further illustrates the lack of meaningful transparency vis-à-vis the Social Benefits ADMS and consequently raises concerns pertaining to algorithmic accountability, adequate human oversight and meaningful human control which are further amplified by the complexity of the sociotechnical systems such as the Social Benefits ADMS.[Wie23a]

Further, the cases pertaining to the British Post Office's use of the Horizon software as well as the UKVI's deployment of the UK Visa ADMS, meaningful transparency remains a weak spot with little to no information available to indicate the disclosure of meaningful information pertaining to the inner workings of these Automated Governance systems either vis-à-vis its Deployer-Users or the public at large.[Sha] [Fox22]

Finally, in the use-case of the UK DWP's adoption of the Universal Credit Automation System, despite several FOI requests having been submitted to the DWP, no viable or meaningful information has been shared in the public domain save the acknowledgement that the Universal Credit Automation System uses an opaque ML algorithm as its underlying technology. The importance of this disclosure and its harm to premise of meaningful transparency is further illustrated when coupled with the DWP's recognition of its limitations vis-à-vis discovering the presence of algorithmic bias in the Universal Credit Automation Systems, and its inadequate precaution in shielding the Deployer-Users against succumbing to automation bias by sharing reduced information pertaining to the details of the algorithmic computations which lead to a particular case file being flagged as potentially fraudulent. This combined reading of these observations clearly indicate the lack of algorithmic, interaction and social transparency vis-à-vis the use of the Universal Credit Automation System by the DWP, which ultimately culminated into a lack of meaningful transparency.[UK 22]

The continued disregard to meaningful transparency across the five use-cases points to a significant systemic deterioration of organisational accountability standards which have resulted in the promulgation of algorithmic bias as an onslaught on the trustworthiness of the Automated Governance systems.

5.1.4.4 Exclusion of decision subjects vis-à-vis the development and deployment of Automated Governance systems

This research study in its investigations regarding the human-facing effects of Automated Governance systems views the treatment of decision-subjects through the lens of algorithmic accountability and meaningful transparency requirements. The human-facing components of these requirements such as social transparency, social accountability and regulatory accountability are indispensable to the development of a fair and trustworthy AI system. In addition to these components, the ethical and regulatory framework governing the rights of decision-subject is also discussed at length in the previous sections. Building on that premise, upon investigation of the case-studies a patterns of material deficiencies vis-à-vis the Public Authorities' treatment of decision subjects are observed. These deficiencies include issues such as the exclusion of transparency and grievance redressal requirements within the regulations driving the adoption of Automated Governance systems within Public Authorities, the exclusion of decision-subjects from the purview of stakeholder participation exercises such as impact assessments and social

dialogues, the lack of contextual awareness within the Automated Governance systems therefore rendering them unviable to be used to create decision-outputs which impact vulnerable groups, ineffective feedback loop mechanisms within Public Authorities and finally, the lack of meaningful explanations for the decision-subjects vis-à-vis the use of Automated Governance systems.

The first use-case we observe is the deployment of the SyRI scandal where the underlying legislative instruments (SyRI Legislations) used to deploy such an algorithm, empowered the Dutch Ministry to rely on a large volume of personal data for the operation (including developing, training and subsequent use) of the SyRI Algorithm, do not prescribe any provisions focused towards safeguarding the interests of the decision subjects (who are also the data-subjects of the personal data used by the SyRI algorithm) such as a duty of disclosure regarding the use of personal data in order to carry out automated decision making through the SyRI software.[\[Dis20\]](#) These SyRI Legislations were heavily criticised owing to their contravention of the principle of proportionality and subsidiarity [\[Aut12\]](#) in that a public good should not disproportionality affect or harm the stakeholder and that in order to practice proportionality in the event there are multiple options for accomplish a specific goal, the option with the least adverse impact on the stakeholder should be employed.[\[Aut13\]](#) Further, while in use, the SyRI algorithm functioned as an opaque, arbitrary and discriminatory algorithm with no meaningful explanations pertaining to the inner workings of the SyRI algorithm or disclosures about its use were provided to its decision subjects.[\[Wie23b\]](#) The SyRI algorithm was retrospectively found to have been focused only on investigating vulnerable decision-subjects residing in low income neighbourhoods. Finally, upon being subjected to large fines based on the decision-outputs of a discriminatory algorithm, the decision-subjects were faced with an increasingly frustrating complaints mechanism.[\[Wie23a\]](#) This complains procedure was found to be increasingly time consuming and bureaucratically challenging for persons who are either financially vulnerable or culturally distant, owing to their immigration status, from Dutch administrative rules and procedures governing the complaints mechanism that was used in the context of the SyRI algorithm.[\[DTLVC\]](#)

Similarly, in the use-case of the British Post Office's deployment of the Horizon software, the Deployer Users who were accused of theft and embezzlement and subjected to criminal prosecution and eventual imprisonment because of phantom transactions created by the hallucinations within the Horizon software.[\[Sha\]](#) The deployment methodology and internal governance framework for the Horizon software was riddled with inadequacies such as disorganised feedback mechanisms that prevented the Deployer Users from conveying timely, adequate feedback to the Post Office regarding the issues associated with the Horizon software and requesting relevant information concerning the technical features of the Horizon software. Additionally, during a whistleblowing survey conducted as a part of the Post Office Horizon Inquiry, a large portion of responses indicated low levels of confidence associated with the manner in which complaints against the Horizon software were handled.

Finally, in the use-cases of the Social Benefits ADMS (used by the Trelleborg Municipality in Sweden) and the UK Visa ADMS there are no records of any meaningful information or opt-out conditions being provided to the decision-subjects. Furthermore, in the use-case of the Universal Credit Automation System developed and deployed by the UK DWP, the department in a response to an FOI request disclosed its use of an ML algorithm to assess fraud risk metrics as-

sociated with universal credit applications, however, no further information which could prove to be meaningful vis-à-vis the internal operations of this algorithm were provided.[Cen22]

This vacuum of meaningful information, automation disclosures and safety protocols within the Public Authorities coupled with legislative disregards vis-à-vis the decision subjects are illustrative of the significant shortcomings associated with Automated Governance systems. While these shortcomings point out the defects vis-à-vis the algorithmic accountability metrics, they also illustrate the one dimensional and opaque approach taken by Public Authorities in their adoption of complex AI systems within their administrative processes timeline through their categorical exclusion of crucial stakeholders i.e. the citizens who are the decision (and data) subjects of these Automated Governance systems. This exclusion of decision-subjects points towards deeper governance, ethical and regulatory challenges associated with AI systems, therefore raising concerns about the realities of Automated Governance systems that are advertised as safe, fair and trustworthy.

5.1.5 Research Analysis

The Research Findings as elucidated in the previous sections clearly indicate a lack of synchronisation amongst the sociotechnical elements of the Automated Governance systems which ultimately create adverse outward effects which either affect the decision-subjects of the Automated Governance systems or the success, sufficiency and scalability of the Automated Governance systems itself. Both of these scenarios create a lose-lose situation for both the public authorities as well as the citizens affected by the Automated Governance systems. Therefore, the research findings make a strong case for the interdependency of sociotechnical robustness and trustworthiness of human-facing AI systems such as Automated Governance systems. However, in order to achieve this synchronisation amongst technical, social and organisational elements of the Automated Governance system, adequate acknowledgement of how these elements affect each other is required. This brings forth the point raised in the previous sections about this research study being a perfect interlude for interdisciplinary research as the proverbial wheels of a successful Automated Governance system are comprised of (1) technical robustness; (2) social adoption; (3) Organisational scalability and; (4) adequate regulatory compliance.[Mol+21a] [Mol+21b] [Mol+21c]

Thus, the in-depth analysis of the Automated Governance landscape within the EU is benefitted through the sociotechnical[CS18] approach undertaken by this research study and consequently advocates for the improvement of the digitisation efforts involving disruptive technology such as AI systems as observed to have been undertaken by public authorities across various jurisdictions.[KM24] This approach highlights the need for interdisciplinary collaboration amongst lawyers, deployers (organisations) and providers of AI systems.

5.1.6 Conclusion

This research study significantly advances the LeADS project's goal of integrating the collaborative spirit amongst data science and law by demonstrating the critical role and operational significance of interdisciplinary expertise in the deployment of complex and intricate AI systems

such as the Automated Governance systems. By combining technical proficiency with legal insight, the study addresses gaps in the ethical and regulatory deployment of Predictive Justice algorithms (as discussed in Section 4 (Research Findings)). Further, this research study highlights the necessity for both technical soundness, social and organisational compatibility and legal compliance to ensure Automated Governance systems are successful, scalable and trustworthy. The research study further highlights the importance of a collaborative approach, where data scientists and legal professionals are recognised as crucial pieces of the sociotechnical puzzle i.e. Automated Governance systems. This contribution not only supports the LeADS project's objectives but also provides valuable insights for enhancing the intersection of data science and law, promoting more ethical and effective AI solutions across various high-risk domains.

5.1.7 Future work

The future work associated with this research study could be focused on gathering primary data based on organisation wide interviews in courts and public authorities where AI systems are deployed to adequately trace the methodology adopted by these institutions in order to carry out their automation practices and subsequently use the automation solutions they adopt. The same would provide granularity to the analyses and may allow for identification of further nuances associated with the reliable and trustworthy deployment of AI systems in high-risk scenarios with adequate focus on safety, health and fundamental rights.

5.2 The Complexity of Value Alignment: Justice and Discrimination in Automated Decision-making Systems

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5.2.1 Background

[The use of first person is reserved solely for the background and methodology sections.]

The goal of the Legality Attentive Data Scientist's project (LeADS) was to train data scientists to think more like lawyers, and lawyers to think more like data scientists, attempting a mutual understanding across disciplines. We received training in various fields related to digital legislation and emerging technologies with significant societal impact. The intention behind this training was to equip us with the knowledge required to offer informed, policy-relevant advice to decision-makers throughout our employ and to continue making meaningful contributions to society thereafter. The essence of the LeADS project was to produce researchers who are capable of competently assessing whether, and how, emerging technologies interact with legal frameworks and societal values in ways that can inform both technological design and regulatory development.

As part of the LeADS initiative, I had the opportunity to join the National Doctorate in Artificial Intelligence for Society at the University of Pisa. The AI for Society specialization focuses on issues like explainable AI, AI for personal assistance, and AI for social good. The ethos of AI for society is ethics-by-design: prioritizing sustainability, human dignity, inclusiveness, and respect for autonomy in the development of socially acceptable technologies. In my role at LeADS, I had the pleasure of working with Crossroad 2, an interdisciplinary team focused on 'Trust in Data Processing and Algorithmic Design,' grounded in the EU's Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. This research, in many ways, is a direct outcome of that framework. I also co-authored a LeADS Working Paper on a particularly complex subject, titled 'Borders Between Unfair Commercial Practices and Discrimination in Using Data.'

These projects were impactful on my research. However, the research topic I was originally assigned was 'neuromarketing and mental integrity, between market and fundamental rights.' As my work evolved, I shifted focus toward what I saw as more foundational problems in algorithmic policy-making and technical design. I increasingly recognized that moral aims were being prioritized over fundamental rights considerations within the socio-technical design of automated distributive systems, a realization that eventually led me to exclude neuromarketing from my research altogether. The market and fundamental rights analysis still underpin my work, but my focus has moved toward addressing deeper issues at the intersection of algorithmic systems, the governance of artificial intelligence, and the rule of law.

5.2.2 Methodology

The reader may have a legitimate concern about epistemology and the relation I make with the written derivatives of the concept of truth in prose. In a way that is what the entire manuscript

is about, understanding what is true and practical. The assumption that the world is real and that we are reasoning about it should be considered a prerequisite to giving advice about AI governance. A nuanced understanding of bounded rationality should be sufficient. What should also be assumed is that legal facts exist, because we are giving technological and regulatory design advice. A nuanced understanding of legal certainty should be sufficient. If one is to be practical, one cannot live under the burden of a Cartesian demon. Now that I've loosened those epistemological constraints a bit so that a path of reason may flow to real-world fact scenarios, I should tighten them again.

Design is where social theory meets society. In the most general way, which will become precise overtime, my goal in this work is to walk a line of axiomatic conflicts related to truth and justice, using as the basis of my judgments (to generate competent advice): (1) established law where legal propositions are put forward, using legal methods; and (2) where a legal proposition is not being put forward, I will use reasoned argumentation—in the nomenclature of the field referenced—with explanatory footnotes and citation, which is characteristic of legal, scholarly work. All normative judgments are based on common sense, satisficing, or proportionality.

Methodologically, this research is analytical and theoretical in nature. It focuses on evaluating the design architecture of automated, distributive decision-making systems through the lens of legal principles, cases, and legislation with a particular emphasis on factual equality as understood within the European Union. This is not an empirical study concerned with gathering data but rather an exploration of the legal, technical, and philosophical underpinnings of the systems that use and manipulate our data for distributive decision-making. The analysis follows a first principles approach. Hopefully, in that way, the reader may follow my journey over the past three years, spotting my errors and identifying points of doubt to later be contested in thought or writing.

I am a foreigner who was trained in a different legal system. That fact does not and should not stop me from giving the informed opinion that I was paid for the past three years of LeADS to develop. But, I will constrain myself to the black-letter interpretation of legal texts. Where questions that go out of my scope of expertise are required, I will rely on other EU legal scholars more familiar with the EU legal system than I am after the taking of courses and the reading of relevant books and articles. I have never practiced in an EU member state, nor am I intimately familiar with member state legal histories. I do not pretend to have intuitions about the intricacies of Continental law.

Therefore, I make a handful of relevant points that are part of established and previously commented on law. It turns out they were impactful for my research goals. If they have been applied within the field of AI governance and fair machine learning, I have not seen it done. There are a few exceptions I shall comment on later. It is not my goal to repeat the same story being told by everyone else within AI governance. I spent most of my time away from the field finding new and impactful insights relevant to AI governance and technical design.

I am a firm believer in learning from the past—both from what one considers wise or foolish, just or unjust, lawful or unlawful. That spirit is contrary to the one of algorithmic fairness, maybe not as it was conceived and intended, but at least by the recent trends in ethical-by-design practices and policy proposals; and as recently implemented and relied on by major international

corporations and standardization efforts. I am interested in where those designs conflict with EU Artificial Intelligence policy. Of course, there are natural alignments but there are also less talked about and often completely ignored misalignment's. As a community we are far behind the speed of innovation. In trying to catch up, I believe we have forgotten the firm-ish footing we started from.

5.2.3 Beyond the Law or Back Again?

Fundamental Rights Instruments

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union 2012 (OJ C)

Cases

Bilka - Kaufhaus GmbH v Karin Weber von Hartz [1986] ECJ Case 170/84

Commission of the European Communities v French Republic [1988] ECJ Case 312/86

Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen [1995] ECJ Case C-450/93

Frédéric Hay v Crédit agricole mutuel de Charente-Maritime et des Deux-Sèvres [2013] ECJ Case C-267/12

Georg Badeck and Others, interveners: Hessische Ministerpräsident and Landesanwalt beim Staatsgerichtshof des Landes Hessen [2000] ECJ Case C-158/97

Hellmut Marschall v Land Nordrhein-Westfalen [1997] An Chúirt Bhreithiúnais Case C-409/95

Johnston v Chief Constable of the Royal Ulster Constabulary [1986] ECR 1651

Katarina Abrahamsson and Leif Anderson v Elisabet Fogelqvist [2000] ECJ Case C-407/98

Lommers v Minister van Landbouw, Natuurbeheer en Visserij [2002] ECJ Case C-476/99

P v S and Cornwall County Council [1996] ECJ Case C-13/94

Wolfgang Glatzel v Freistaat Bayern [2014] ECJ Case C-356/12

Regulations

Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts 2021

Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts

Directives

Council Directive 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin 2000

Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services 2004

Other Authorities

84/635/EEC: Council Recommendation of 13 December 1984 on the Promotion of Positive Action for Women, vol 331 (The Council of the European Communities, 1984)

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Union of Equality: Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Artificial Intelligence for Europe 2018

Directorate-General for Communication (European Commission) and Ursula von der Leyen, Political Guidelines for the next European Commission 2019-2024; Opening Statement in the European Parliament Plenary Session 16 July 2019; Speech in the European Parliament Plenary Session 27 November 2019 (Publications Office of the European Union 2020)

Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (Publications Office of the European Union 2019)

European Parliament Resolution on a Framework of Ethical Aspects of Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and Related Technologies (2021/C 404/O4) 2020

White Paper on Artificial Intelligence: A European approach to Excellence and Trust 2020

5.2.3.1 A Demarcation between Law and Ethics

The Artificial Intelligence Act is a product of the European strategy towards regulating artificial intelligences which has developed over the past six years and has always embodied a peculiar relationship between law and ethics.¹ In 2018, the European Commission released their Communication outlining the beginnings of a European strategy for AI. A key aim of the strategy was to “[e]nsure [the existence of] an appropriate ethical and legal framework, based on the Union’s values and in line with the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU.”² Around that time, the High-Level Experts Group on AI (HLEG) was established with the goal of advising the Commission, and their 2019 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, which took the fundamentals rights of the Charter³ to be the subject matter of both their ethical and legal approach, became central to the EU strategy.⁴

In 2019, Commission President Ursula von der Leyen vowed to put forward legislation offering a coordinated European approach on the human and ethical implications of AI in her Political Guidelines.⁵ Then in 2020, the official White Paper on Artificial Intelligence was released, stating that the European approach “aims to promote Europe’s innovation capacity in the area of AI while supporting the development and uptake of ethical and trustworthy AI across the EU economy.”⁶ Later in 2020, the European Parliament formally requested the Commission to submit a

¹[Aia].

²[Coma, p.3].

³[Cha].

⁴[Hle, p.2].

⁵[Ley, p.13].

⁶[Noar, p.25].

proposal for a regulation specifically addressing ethical principles for the development, deployment, and use of artificial intelligence.⁷ And finally, in 2021, the Artificial Intelligence Act was proposed, and the Commission asserted that the Regulation ensures the protection of ethical principles.⁸

A potential issue arises regarding the demarcation between legal obligations and ethical principles within this regulatory framework. The European Parliament's Resolution C 404 distinguishes between "legal obligations" and "ethical principles," advising that high-risk artificial intelligences should comply with both.⁹ However, the Resolution also observes that "ethical principles are only efficient where they are also enshrined in law...".¹⁰ This is an important point that will be explained in a moment.

The Parliament called for the development of common criteria for granting European certificates of ethical compliance.¹¹ This suggests that a separate ethical analysis, distinct from a legal analysis, may still be necessary for compliance purposes. This demarcation may present a problem: how should entities navigate the space where legal obligations and ethical principles intersect within Trustworthy AI, especially when ethical principles extend beyond legal requirements? **In cases of conflict between legal and ethical design, which should have primacy?** But first, where does the demarcation come from?

5.2.3.2 Trustworthy AI and the Rule of Law

As described above, the consensus in the European Union has largely been that AI should meet both a legal and ethical requirement. In the HLEG's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, they state that AI should be legal, ethical, and technically and socially robust.¹² The HLEG derived their ethical principles from the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.¹³ Distinguishing between the legal and ethical requirements, the HLEG explained that after legal compliance is achieved, "ethical reflection can help us understand how the development, deployment and use of AI systems may implicate fundamental rights and their underlying values and can help provide more fine-grained guidance when seeking to identify what we should do rather than what we (currently) can do with technology."¹⁴ The HLEG cited Florida's soft ethics approach, asserting that there "adherence to ethical principles goes beyond legal compliance [emphasis added]."¹⁵

Yet, the question of which direction one should go beyond fundamental rights jurisprudence remains and is striking. Accordingly, the HLEG advised that AI practitioners "should approach ethical dilemmas and *trade-offs* via reasoned, evidence-based reflection rather than intuition or random discretion [emphasis added]."¹⁶ Further, the HLEG stated that "methods of accountable

⁷[Res, p.84].

⁸[Ecp, p.18].

⁹[Res, p.69].

¹⁰[Res, p.67].

¹¹[Res, p.82].

¹²[Hle, p.2].

¹³[Hle, p.10].

¹⁴[Hle, p.10].

¹⁵[Hle, p.12].

¹⁶[Hle, p.13].

deliberation to deal with such tensions should be established.”¹⁷

Luciano Floridi, in the paper cited by the HLEG on this very point,¹⁸ entitled “Soft Ethics and the Governance of the Digital,” posits that effective governance should consist of institutional governance, regulation, and ethics. He argues, along with others, that while legal requirements are necessary, they may not always be sufficient to guide society toward beneficial outcomes. Ethics, therefore, should play a role in governance by acting as an anticipatory mechanism to identify and respond to the impacts of emerging technologies. Floridi introduced the concepts of hard ethics and soft ethics to delineate how ethics interacts with the law within the governance of artificial intelligence:

- **Hard Ethics:** involves changing or creating law through the implementation of ethical values in legislation or judicial opinions. In this case, compliance is a legal question, answered using legal methods and content specific to a jurisdiction. Compliance with the law equates to compliance with the hard ethical values that shaped it.
- **Soft Ethics:** pertains to considerations of what should be done “over and above the existing regulation, not against it, or despite its scope, or to change it, or to bypass it.”¹⁹ Soft ethics does not influence the law directly. Instead, it guides behavior beyond legal obligations, suggesting that additional methodologies are required to determine compliance with these ethical considerations.²⁰

Figure 5.1: Floridi created this graphic to help understand the distinction.

The relationship between ethics and law is characteristic of how scholars typically understand the cyclical nature of normative values being translated into regulation: similar to how the EU data protection acquis developed from shifts in the perceptions about privacy in the public, or how medical professional ethics developed in response to bioethics. During the last few years,

¹⁷[Hle, p.13].

¹⁸“For further reading on this subject, see for instance L. Floridi, Soft Ethics and the Governance of the Digital, Philosophy and Technology, March 2018, Volume 31, Issue 1, pp 1–8.” [Hle, p.12].

¹⁹[Flo18a, p.4].

²⁰The graphic below can be found at [Flo18b, p.5].

AI ethics researchers have mostly been concerned with the development of principles and have struggled with their practical application to the problems of AI.²¹ While others have taken the problem of application to be an irredeemable flaw with the principle-based approach, and so have called for a virtue ethics²² or question-based approach to be developed instead.²³

Underpinning AI ethics is the idea that law can benefit from ethics for various reasons. Yet, the author of this research wishes to suggest the opposite, that the above mechanism (which is, itself, the rule of law) shows how ethics can benefit from law. To maintain the integrity of the rule of law while embracing the benefits of ethical considerations, the Trustworthy solution lies in modeling ethical design on legal judgments, **first**. By adopting legal methodologies for ethical analysis, organizations can apply normative propositions to specific fact scenarios, enhancing the practical application of ethical principles without undermining **legal clarity**.²⁴ By engaging with the law first, ethicists might come to understand the nuance of legal facts and reasoning. And, where the balance of a legal judgment rests on conflicting fundamental rights or fact-scenarios that lead to the internal tension of a legal doctrine, one might come to realize that there is no space to go beyond in a mapping of fundamental rights. Relying on established law as a common basis, regardless of ethical or moral persuasion, is the only way to avoid conflicts.²⁵

5.2.3.3 Realized and Potential Systematic Violations

Are moral aims being prioritized over fundamental rights considerations in the design of artificial intelligences? Recent work suggests so,²⁶ taking note of a study²⁷ which concluded that automated hiring software for pre-screening and interviewing candidates 'debias' in accordance with the 'disparate impact' or 'adverse impact' metric; arguing that such practices would likely be in violation of Article 21 of the Charter, because the Court of Justice of the European Union (Court) has found differential treatment in the hiring context to be (1) limited to tie-breaking scenarios,²⁸ where a **saving clause** ensures (2) the candidates are measured in relation to an **objective standard**.²⁹

²¹For context and arguments against principlism, see [CG90]; for the application of similar critiques in AI ethics, see also [Mit19].

²²[Hag20].

²³[Maa22].

²⁴[Com20a].

²⁵[Whi+19].

²⁶[PEM24].

²⁷[Rag+20].

²⁸"... contains a saving clause does not exceed those limits if, in each individual case, it provides for male candidates who are equally as qualified as the female candidates a guarantee that the candidatures will be the subject of an objective assessment which will take account of all criteria specific to the individual candidates and will override the priority accorded to female candidates where one or more of those criteria tilts the balance in favour of the male candidate. In this respect, however, it should be remembered that those criteria must not be such as to discriminate against female candidates." *Hellmut Marschall v Land Nordrhein-Westfalen* [1997] An Chúirt Bhreithiúnais Case C-409/95 [para. 33].

²⁹"The scope and effect of that condition cannot be precisely determined, with the result that the selection of a candidate from among those who are sufficiently qualified is ultimately based on the mere fact of belonging to the underrepresented sex, and that this is so even if the merits of the candidate so selected are inferior to those of a candidate of the opposite sex. Moreover, candidatures are not subjected to an objective assessment taking account

Automated hiring systems based on machine learning are becoming increasingly commonplace, concerns about algorithmic **indirect discrimination** in employment decisions are front-and-center due to a potential lack of access to the feature space of automated systems, and the technical solutions provided by the research community often systematically deviate from the principle of equal treatment. Such practices involve ‘debiasing’ datasets to achieve statistical independence of varying degrees between **protected features** and a target variable in the outcomes of automated systems. The study of algorithmic discrimination and the corresponding solutions fall under a multi-disciplinary domain known as fair machine learning. Legal scholarship on algorithmic discrimination has predominately focused on analyzing the **training data** of automated systems for features that, if used, may constitute direct or indirect discrimination and the corresponding decisions of those systems for disparate or adverse outcomes.³⁰

Designers of such systems are aware that criteria which cause a disparate impact related to a protected feature can potentially be deemed discriminatory.³¹ The all too often proposed solution: require group equality or similarity in decision outcomes.³² Limiting guidance on bias and fairness can be found in the Ethics Guidelines on Trustworthy AI itself:

“Equality, non-discrimination and solidarity - including the rights of persons at risk of exclusion. Equal respect for the moral worth and dignity of all human beings must be ensured. This goes beyond non-discrimination, which tolerates the drawing of distinctions between dissimilar situations based on objective justifications. In an AI context, equality entails that the system’s operations cannot generate *unfairly biased* outputs (e.g., the data used to train AI systems should be as inclusive as possible, representing different population groups) [emphasis added].”³³

What does “*unfairly biased*” mean for going beyond non-discrimination law? As will be explained later, bias can either be referring to (1) bias as a deviation from the true value of a parameter or variable, or (2) bias as a deviation from group equality or similarity in outcomes. In the quoted paragraph, bias is in reference to the former. The latter, fairness metrics which seek statistical independence between the protected feature and the target variable in decision outcomes of an automated system—what have also been referred to as ‘non-conservative’ group fairness metrics.³⁴ The fair machine learning techniques described in this Chapter are limited to these kinds, often simply referred to as **group fairness** metrics and techniques, and should not be confused with those fair machine learning metrics and techniques, described later, which seek to ensure accuracy regardless of group membership.

of the specific personal situations of all the candidates. It follows that such a method of selection is not such as to be permitted by Article 2(4) of the Directive.”Katarina Abrahamsson and Leif Anderson v Elisabet Fogelqvist [2000] ECJ Case C-407/98 [para. 53].

³⁰See [WMR21]; but see e.g., [Tho+21];[MWR23].

³¹See [Fel+15]; [BS16].

³²For evidence of such ‘ethical-by-design’ practices, see [Rag+20]; for access to the toolkit to use such fairness metrics and techniques, see this GitHub library [Noaq] ; for a description of the policy behind the toolkit, see IBM [IBM]the legality of use depends on the jurisdiction and fact-scenario related their use.

³³[Hle, p.11].

³⁴[Rä21].

"Unfairly biased" in the context of Trustworthy AI means the use of an artificial intelligence whose predictive performance varies unfairly based on group membership—in other words, the goal would be to remove bias, where bias means a deviation from the true value of a parameter or variable. These technical aspects of fair machine learning will be explained, very precisely, in the framework presented in the Distributive Decisions chapter. This chapter examines the use of 'debiasing' techniques, where bias means a deviation from group equality or similarity in decision outcomes. The bias distinction will be further explained in the Non-Discrimination and Algorithmic Fairness section.

Thankfully, it is widely recognized that automated hiring systems must not discriminate. Often fair machine learning and the tool set it provides is seen as the answer to creating non-discriminatory automated systems. However, the fact is that the implementation of group fairness machine learning metrics and techniques can ensure a discriminatory effect, depending on the context or **fact-pattern** related to their use, which may have differing considerations for a **proportionality test** safeguarding the fundamental right of **equal treatment**.³⁵ An automated hiring system that, in an effort to achieve 'fairness,' eliminates differences between groups based on a protected feature while disregarding the base-rate differences between those groups, can potentially discriminate against individuals belonging to either the 'privileged' or 'unprivileged' groups, and the severity of that potential discrimination would be dependent on the strength of the correlation between the protected feature and the target variable in the original, unprocessed data sample. The next section is dedicated to explaining that, while 'fairness' and non-discrimination are often used synonymously or at least in the same breath, the estimation and preservation of **model generalizability** *must not* be ignored when determining the legality of such systems with non-discrimination law, nor *should* it be ignored when determining the ethical compliance of such systems with the Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

5.2.3.3.1 From Hiring to Substantive and Factual Equality In employment decisions, equality is sought in opportunity or outcome. Equality of opportunity can be defined as formal or substantive.³⁶ Formal equality of opportunity requires that applicants be assessed according to their qualifications, that those qualifications be appropriate,³⁷ and that the most qualified applicant receives the position.³⁸ Selection processes that enforce formal equality of opportunity result in inequalities in outcome between groups when the individuals of a given group are, on a whole, less qualified than another in a given field.³⁹ While substantive equality of

³⁵See Art. 21 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

³⁶'Opportunity' is used after formal and substantive equality to reflect the employment context, where equality of opportunity has been emphasized. Differing fact-scenarios will require differing proportionality considerations, even within hiring, i.e., disability, to ensure factual equality via substantive equality rather than the unmitigated pursuit of equality of outcome.

³⁷Where appropriateness is defined in relation to moral relevance or to the lawfulness of desiderata in accordance with indirect discrimination doctrine.

³⁸[Arm15].

³⁹For early remarks on the trade-off between "accuracy" and "fairness", see e.g. Plato's *Laws* discussing the notion of equality, "[W]hen equality is given to unequal things, the resultant will be unequal . . ." [Pla+14]; see also "Hayek on Equality, Value and Merit, "From the fact that people are very different it follows that, if we treat them equally, the result must be inequality in their actual position . . ." [Hay76].

opportunity requires all that formal equality of opportunity insists upon during the **comparison** of applicants, it is first and foremost an effort to ensure that each individual in society, regardless of their group membership, has the same **opportunities** to gain the prerequisite qualifications for positions so that differences between groups are minimal or nonexistent.⁴⁰ Equality of outcome is group equality or similarity in results, irrespective of the differences individuals of those groups may have in terms of qualifications for a given position—generally for the purpose of providing a shortcut from opportunity to representation when factual equality has not yet been fully realized via proportionate, substantive equality.⁴¹

In the European Union, *positive action* is an umbrella term used to describe soft measures like the pruning of facially neutral employment criteria that may lead to disparate impacts to ensure feature proportionality with indirect discrimination doctrine, mainstreaming initiatives, accommodations, the use of impact assessments, and outreach programs for achieving substantive equality of opportunity for members of groups that deal with the consequences of past or present **discrimination or disadvantages**⁴² so that they may compete on an equal footing with others.⁴³ Those soft measures become hard when disproportionate—what is often referred to as *positive discrimination*, a term used to describe strong measures for achieving equality of outcome through differential treatment in the comparison of applicants, in a given field of employment, where members of the previously discriminated against groups are not yet, on the whole, equally qualified.⁴⁴ Employment decisions that use differential treatment during the comparison of applicants are controversial, and the practice has been repeatedly restrained by the Court whenever employment selection processes move from the goal of ensuring substantive equality into the pursuit of equal outcomes. The Court's case-law pertaining to such practices in employment have been settled for nearly two decades, and legal scholars have repeatedly concluded that the Court systematically rejects selection processes that turn towards equality of outcome.⁴⁵ Member states have made additional nuances in the line between factual equality via proportionate substantive equality and equality of outcome that the Court has not yet made,⁴⁶ which is based on a further distinction that limits such practices only

⁴⁰"... action taken should be not only continued but also intensified at national level and Community level with a view to promoting the achievement of equal opportunities in practice through the implementation of positive actions, more especially in the fields of equal pay and equal treatment as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion and working conditions." '84/635/EEC: Council Recommendation of 13 December 1984 on the Promotion of Positive Action for Women', vol 331 (The Council of the European Communities, 1984) <<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/1984/635/oj/eng>>; See also, Art. 5 of Council Directive 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin 2000.

⁴¹"Furthermore, in so far as it seeks to achieve equal representation of men and women in all grades and levels within a department, such a system substitutes for equality of opportunity as envisaged in Article 2(4) the result which is only to be arrived at by providing such equality of opportunity." *Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen* [1995] ECJ Case C-450/93 [23].

⁴²See e.g. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Union of Equality: Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030 2021.

⁴³[Com+07, p.11].

⁴⁴For a detailed explanation of the difference between positive action and positive discrimination in EU non-discrimination law, see [VC19].

⁴⁵See [VC19, pp.462, 587]; [BCo7, p.6]; and [O'Co6, pp. 351, 356–9].

⁴⁶That is not to say whether it should or should not.

for those positions that do not require expertise.

Equal treatment means that there shall be no discrimination, either directly or indirectly, based on a protected feature laid out in a given directive. Any derogation laid out in a given directive from the principle of equal treatment needs to be interpreted strictly.⁴⁷

5.2.3.3.2 Equal Treatment Direct discrimination⁴⁸ shall be taken to occur where one person is treated less favorably than another is, has been or would be treated in a comparable situation on grounds of a protected feature or an **indissociable proxy**⁴⁹ of a protected feature, **unless**⁵⁰ such differential treatment is justified by purposes such as public security, the maintenance of public order, crime prevention, health, or the protection of the rights and freedoms of others, where the **means**⁵¹ of achieving that *purpose* are *appropriate* and *necessary*.

Indirect discrimination occurs when an **apparently neutral** provision, criterion, or practice puts people possessing a **protected feature** at a particular **disadvantage** compared to others in a comparable situation, **unless**⁵² it is objectively justified by a *legitimate aim*, and the means of achieving that aim are *appropriate* and *necessary*.

Indirect discrimination is fundamentally aimed at achieving substantive equality.⁵³ Repeating, indirect discrimination takes place when a neutral provision, criterion, or practice results in a

⁴⁷"a derogation from an individual right laid down in the Directive, Article 2(4) must be interpreted strictly." Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen (n 43) citing, Johnston v Chief Constable of the Royal Ulster Constabulary [1986] ECR 1651, [36].

⁴⁸The path taken is inspired by thematic and temporal characterizations of EU non-discrimination law found in these texts: [Noaj]; [WO21]; [Bel21]; [BCo7].

⁴⁹"Such discrimination is based, essentially if not exclusively, on the sex of the person concerned. Where a person is dismissed on the ground that he or she intends to undergo, or has undergone, gender reassignment, he or she is treated unfavourably by comparison with persons of the sex to which he or she was deemed to belong before undergoing gender reassignment." P v S and Cornwall County Council [1996] ECJ Case C-13/94 [21].

⁵⁰"In that connection, it must be recalled that the Court has already held, as regards the general principle of equal treatment in the context of grounds such as age or sex, that a difference of treatment which is based on a characteristic related to such grounds does not constitute discrimination—that is to say, an infringement of Article 21 (1) of the Charter—where, by reason of the nature of the particular occupational activities concerned or of the context in which they are carried out, such a characteristic constitutes a genuine and determining occupational requirement, provided that the objective is legitimate and the requirement is proportionate." Wolfgang Glatzel v Freistaat Bayern [2014] ECJ Case C-356/12 [49].

⁵¹"Moreover, as the discrimination is direct, it may be upheld, not on the basis of a "legitimate aim" within the meaning of Article 2(2)(b) of Directive 2000/78, as that provision covers only indirect discrimination, but only on one of the grounds referred to in Article 2(5) of that directive, namely public security, the maintenance of public order and the prevention of criminal offences, the protection of health and the protection of the rights and freedoms of others, where the means of achieving that purpose are appropriate and necessary." Frédéric Hay v Crédit agricole mutuel de Charente-Maritime et des Deux-Sèvres [2013] ECJ Case C-267/12 [45].

⁵²"It is for the national court, which has sole jurisdiction to make findings of fact, to determine whether and to what extent the grounds put forward by an employer to explain the adoption of a pay practice which applies independently of a worker's sex but in fact affects more women than men may be regarded as objectively justified economic grounds. if the national court finds that the measures chosen by Bilka correspond to a real need on the part of the undertaking, are appropriate with a view to achieving the objectives pursued and are necessary to that end, the fact that the measures affect a far greater number of women than men is not sufficient to show that they constitute an infringement of article 119." Bilka - Kaufhaus GmbH v Karin Weber von Hartz [1986] ECJ Case 170/84 [36].

⁵³[DV20].

disparate impact on a protected group, “unless that provision, criterion or practice is objectively justified by a legitimate aim and the means of achieving that aim are appropriate and necessary.”⁵⁴ Thus, using a hiring criterion that causes a disparate impact is not automatically discriminatory. Instead, such criteria are only discriminatory if the principle of proportionality is violated. The proportionality test, therefore, “opens the path for the legality of using a factor that correlates with economically or otherwise favorable traits even though the choice of that factor also leads to the unfavorable treatment of a protected group.”⁵⁵

5.2.3.3.3 Special Measures Each equality directive moves from formal to substantive equality by providing for Member States to adopt *special measures* to prevent or compensate for disadvantages linked to a protected feature. Thus, while the exception to the individual right of equal treatment must be interpreted strictly, measures which take advantage of the derogation, while discriminatory in appearance, “are in fact intended to eliminate or reduce actual instances of inequality which may exist in the reality of social life.”⁵⁶ For instance, in *Badeck*, the Court drew a distinction between training opportunities and employment opportunities. The Court applied a substantive view of equality of opportunity, allowing for the reservation of training slots for the underrepresented sex, because training opportunities are precisely where the underrepresented sex can receive the qualifications required for employment positions.⁵⁷ The *Badeck* Court also allowed, under the derogation, a national rule that guarantees that qualified women, who satisfy all the conditions required for the position, are called to interview in sectors in which they are under-represented, because such provisions do not “imply an attempt to achieve a final result.”⁵⁸ In other words, such provisions do not sacrifice equal treatment for the sake of equal outcomes.

Before moving forward, two caveats should be noted. First, the Court has only analyzed gender-based provisions in the employment context through the exception under Art. 2(4) of Directive 76/207 and Art. 141.4 of the TEC. To what extent the exceptions of other equality directives will be treated similarly is a matter of academic debate.⁵⁹ Second, while the Court has held that direct horizontal effect can be found in Article 21 of the Charter, that legal issue will not be discussed here.⁶⁰

5.2.3.3.4 Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen In *Kalanke*, two candidates were short-listed for the position of Section Manager at the Bremen Parks Department in Germany. Mr.

⁵⁴ See Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services 2004 art 2 (b); Council Directive 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin (n 43) art 2 (1) (b).

⁵⁵ [*Hac18*, p.17].

⁵⁶ See *Hellmut Marschall v Land Nordrhein-Westfalen* paras 26–7; *Georg Badeck and Others*, interveners: Hessische Ministerpräsident and Landesanwalt beim Staatsgerichtshof des Landes Hessen [2000] ECJ Case C-158/97 [19]; *H Lommers v Minister van Landbouw, Natuurbeheer en Visserij* [2002] ECJ Case C-476/99 [32].

⁵⁷ *Georg Badeck and Others*, interveners paras 52–5

⁵⁸ *ibid* 60–3 citing Opinion of Advocate General Saggio delivered on 10 June 1999, [41].

⁵⁹ [*O’Co6*, p.355].

⁶⁰ [*Mol11*].

Kalanke, one of the two candidates, had a diploma in horticulture and landscape gardening, had worked for the Parks Department since 1973, and had been acting as the permanent assistant to the previous Section Manager before the position was vacated; Ms. Glibmann, the other candidate, also had a diploma in landscape gardening, granted in 1983, and had worked in the Parks Department as a horticultural employee since 1975. The Parks Department management put forward Mr. Kalanke for the position, but the Staff Committee refused its consent to his promotion.⁶¹

The Staff Committee refused its consent for the promotion of Mr. Kalanke in accordance with the Bremen Law on Equal treatment for Men and Women in the Public Services (LGG) passed in 1990, which stated that women who have the same qualifications as men, applying for the same post, are to be given priority where women are underrepresented in the sector. Mr. Kalanke was successful in arbitration, but the Staff Committee appealed to the conciliation board where the two candidates were found to be equally qualified, and priority was to be given to Ms. Glibmann. The case made its way through the labor courts, and eventually the Bundesarbeitsgericht sought a preliminary ruling from the Court clarifying the scope of the exception under Article 2 (4) of the Directive from the principle of equal treatment.⁶²

The Court began by stating that the purpose of Directive 76/207 is to put into effect the principle of equal treatment for men and women regarding access to employment and promotion within Member States, and that the principle of equal treatment means that there shall be no discrimination whatsoever, either directly or indirectly, on the grounds of sex. The exception under Article 2 (4) of the Directive 76/207 permits national measures which, although discriminatory in appearance, are intended to eliminate or reduce actual instances of inequality and consequently give a specific advantage to women with a view to improving their ability to compete on the labor market and to pursue a career on an equal footing with men.⁶³ Since Article 2(4) is a derogation from an individual right, the Court determined that the exception must be strictly interpreted.⁶⁴

The Court found that national rules that guarantee women absolute and unconditional priority go beyond promoting equal opportunities and overstep the limits of the exception. The Court reasoned that such measures take a shortcut from ensuring substantive equality in fact to mere equality in outcome:

“Furthermore, in so far as it seeks to achieve equal representation of men and women in all grades and levels within a department, such a system substitutes for equality of opportunity as envisaged in Article 2(4) the result which is only to be arrived at by providing such equality of opportunity.”

Thus, the Court ruled that Art. 2(1) and (4) of the Directive 76/207 precludes national rules which automatically give priority to women in sectors where they are underrepresented.⁶⁵

⁶¹Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen, paras 4–5.

⁶²ibid 3, 5, and 6–11.

⁶³ibid 17–19; citing Commission of the European Communities v French Republic [1988] ECJ Case 312/86 [15]

⁶⁴Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen [para. 21]; citing Marguerite Johnston v Chief Constable of the Royal Ulster Constabulary [1986] ECJ Case 222/84 [36]

⁶⁵Eckhard Kalanke v Freie Hansestadt Bremen, paras 22–24.

5.2.3.3.5 Hellmut Marschall v Land Nordrhein-Westfalen In 1994, a teacher named Mr Marschall applied for a promotion to an open position at a German comprehensive school. In response, Mr. Marschall was informed that, in accordance with the civil service law of the Land, a female candidate of equal suitability, competence and professional performance was to be appointed to the position because there were fewer women than men in that particular grade post in the career bracket. Mr. Marschall brought legal action. The Administrative Court of Gelsenkirchen found that the outcome of the case was dependent on the compatibility of the Land's provision with Art. 2(1) and (4) of Directive 76/207 and so a preliminary ruling was sought from the Court.⁶⁶

The Court began by distinguishing the case from Kalanke. Unlike in Kalanke, the provision in question contained a 'savings clause' that stated that where an individual male candidate had qualifications that might tilt the balance in his favor, a female candidate would not be given priority. After citing the third recital in the preamble to Recommendation 84/635/EEC on the promotion of positive action for women, which highlights the need for positive action to counteract prejudices that arise in the employment context due to social attitudes, behaviors, and structures, the Court agreed with the Land and other governments that, even when candidates of the opposite sex are equally qualified, male candidates tend to be promoted in preference to female candidates because of a multitude of stereotypes. Thus, ". . . the mere fact that a male candidate and a female candidate are equally qualified does not mean that they have the same chances."⁶⁷

The Court reasoned that a national rule may be lawful under Article 2 (4) if, in each individual case:

"[I]t provides for male candidates who are equally as qualified as the female candidates a guarantee that the candidatures will be the subject of an objective assessment which will take account of all criteria specific to the individual candidates and will override the priority accorded to female candidates where one or more of those criteria tilts the balance in favour of the male candidate. In this respect, however, it should be remembered that those criteria must not be such as to discriminate against female candidates." [emphasis added]

Thus, the Court ruled that a national rule which, conditional on a guarantee that the candidatures will be subject to an objective assessment on an individual basis and where that objective assessment tilts in the favor of a male candidate the priority will be overridden, provides a priority to female candidates who are equally qualified, with the purpose of counteracting prejudiced tie-breaking, is compatible with Art. 2(1) and (4) of Directive 76/207.⁶⁸

5.2.3.3.6 Katarina Abrahamsson and Leif Anderson v Elisabet Fogelqvist In 1996, eight candidates applied for a professorship at the University of Göteborg, including Ms. Abrahamsson,

⁶⁶Hellmut Marschall v Land Nordrhein-Westfalen, paras 6–10.

⁶⁷ibid 28–30.

⁶⁸ibid 33–35

Ms. Destouni, Ms. Fogelqvist, and Mr. Anderson. The selection board voted twice: (1) in relation to the scientific qualifications of all candidates, Mr. Anderson received five votes and Ms. Destouni received three votes; (2) considering both scientific merits and a special measure provision, Ms. Destouni received six votes and Mr. Anderson two votes. The selection board proposed that Ms. Destouni be appointed, placing Mr. Anderson in second and Ms. Fogelqvist in third. Later, Ms. Destouni withdrew her application, and the Rector of the University appointed Ms. Fogelqvist to the position. The Rector stated that the difference between Mr. Anderson and Ms. Fogelqvist was not so great as to violate the requirement of objectivity in the selection process. Mr. Anderson and Ms. Abrahamsson brought legal action that eventually came before the Överklagandenämnden för Högskolan, and a preliminary ruling was requested from the Court.⁶⁹

The Court held that national rules which give a priority to candidates of an underrepresented sex who possess sufficient qualifications for a given post over a candidate of the opposite sex who would have been appointed otherwise on the basis of merit, are precluded under Article 2(1) and (4) of Directive 72/207 and Article 141(4) EC even if the difference between the candidates' qualifications are not so great as to breach the requirement of objectivity. The Court also ruled that national legislation which limits differential treatment to a predetermined number of posts, or to posts specifically designed for that purpose, is still precluded because of the absolute and disproportionate nature of the practice.⁷⁰

5.2.3.4 Non-Discrimination and Fair Machine Learning

Simply measuring the group similarity of outcomes in a decision-making process alone has no effect on the final result. For instance, the measurement could be used to analyze whether a given feature might create a disparate impact to determine proportionality in accordance with indirect discrimination doctrine, or to determine whether diversity goals have been reached. However, measuring the group similarity of outcomes is different than constraining those outcomes to be group similar. Other suggestions from the algorithmic fairness literature that might be in accordance with substantive equality of opportunity could include outreach programs designed to attract talent from underrepresented groups, stakeholder involvement throughout the decision-making pipeline (including feature selection),⁷¹ and a diverse group composition amongst the designers of the system.⁷² So long as those suggestions do not "imply an attempt to achieve a final result."⁷³

As described previously, the process of ensuring a final result is known as 'debiasing.' Before explaining how 'debiasing' is performed technically, it is important to understand how bias is defined and the implications of that definition. In data-driven processes like machine learning,

⁶⁹Katarina Abrahamsson and Leif Anderson v Elisabet Fogelqvist, paras 16–27.

⁷⁰ibid 50-59

⁷¹[Lee+19].

⁷²[KJC20].

⁷³"As the Advocate General observes in point 41 of his Opinion, the provision at issue in the main proceedings does not imply an attempt to achieve a final result — appointment or promotion — but affords women who are qualified additional opportunities to facilitate their entry into working life and their career." Georg Badeck and Others, interveners, para 60.

bias is traditionally defined as a deviation from the true value of a parameter or variable.⁷⁴ In fair machine learning, bias is defined as a deviation from group equality or similarity in decision outcomes.⁷⁵ Why is this an important distinction? The distinction between these two definitions of bias illuminates the goals of the processes. Where machine learning is a historical, descriptive, and predictive process; 'debiasing' is an ahistorical, prescriptive process.

When the true value of a parameter leads to group dissimilarity in outcomes, the true value is dubbed biased. This is due to the fact that group dissimilarities in outcomes can either be the result of: (1) group disparities existing in the target population that are reflected in a representative sample and carried into the outcomes by generalizable hypothesis assumptions (accuracies), or (2) an unrepresentative sample and/or non-generalizable assumptions that have the potential to underestimate or exaggerate group disparities (inaccuracies). 'Debiasing' in accordance with a group fairness metric is the purposeful underestimation of group disparities. In other words, decisions made on a representative sample have the potential to reflect the target population in the model outcomes, and those outcomes would have the same disparities between groups that exist in the target population. Thus, to reach group similar outcomes the sample must be made unrepresentative or the hypothesis assumptions non-generalizable.

Why is it important to understand the difference between is and ought? Conclusions on *what ought to be* based solely on observations of *what is* are fallacious. This is commonly referred to as the is/ought fallacy.⁷⁶ It is an error, premised on the implicit assumption that the state of affairs necessarily dictates how the state of affairs should be. Conversely, a less discussed but equally fallacious reasoning is what might be called the ought/is fallacy. This involves a reverse projection, where ideals about how things should be are assumed to reflect the actual state of the world. This form of reasoning often leads to mistaking one's moral vision for reality. For instance, if a person holds that all individuals should be treated equally (a normative statement) and, based on this belief alone, assumes that all individuals are equal (a descriptive statement), they are engaging in the reverse of the Humean fallacy. This assumption, precisely the **axiomatic** assumption that "we are all equal," has already been noted as a common underlying axiom of algorithmic fairness.^{77 78}

⁷⁴[Eve06].

⁷⁵[PS22];[Meh+];[Cas+22].

⁷⁶"I cannot forbear adding to these reasonings an observation, which may, perhaps, be found of some importance. In every system of morality, which I have hitherto met with, I have always remark'd, that the author proceeds for some time in the ordinary way of reasoning, and establishes the being of a God, or makes observations concerning human affairs; when of a sudden I am surpriz'd to find, that instead of the usual copulations of propositions, is, and is not, I meet with no proposition that is not connected with an ought, or an ought not. This change is imperceptible; but is, however, of the last consequence. For as this ought, or ought not, expresses some new relation or affirmation, 'tis necessary that it shou'd be observ'd and explain'd; and at the same time that a reason should be given, for what seems altogether inconceivable, how this new relation can be a deduction from others, which are entirely different from it. But as authors do not commonly use this precaution, I shall presume to recommend it to the readers; and am persuaded, that this small attention wou'd subvert all the vulgar systems of morality, and let us see, that the distinction of vice and virtue is not founded merely on the relations of objects, nor is perceiv'd by reason." [Hum96, Book III Of Morals]

⁷⁷[FSV16];[FSV21]

⁷⁸Such an assumption is absurd when one considers that the realization that "we are not all equal" is the exact motivation behind the egalitarian strands of algorithmic fairness. Dismissing the trade-off between generalizable outcomes and group similar outcomes based on the insistence that "we are all equal" is an example of the ought/is

While philosophers, natural or otherwise, might best understand the thrust of the point through these remarks on the distinction between *is* and *ought*, jurists have long made an additional clarification to the distinction between *is* and *ought*, which is the distinction between *ought* and *must*.⁷⁹ The separation thesis insists on the separation between (1) what the law is and (2) what the law ought to be. This distinction will be further explored in the Legal-Design or Design-made-Legal section. This entire work is a process of moving from *is* to *ought* to *ought* and *must*—such a journey is non-linear.

To understand the trade-off between *is* and *ought* through modern-technical citation, reference can be made to the trade-off between “accuracy” and “fairness.” For instance, researchers have argued that the conflict between “accuracy” and “fairness” is the result of framing the trade-off as an optimization problem.⁸⁰ That argument rests on a causal fallacy. Recognizing the “inherent conflict” between generalizable outcomes and group similar outcomes in a fact-pattern or **data setting** which contains group disparities and then optimizing between those competing interests cannot be the cause of differences between subgroups of a target population that exist independently in that data setting. However, the resulting **differential treatment via optimization must be lawful**.

The lower bound of that trade-off has been estimated via proof.⁸¹ And research has shown that in the case of a binary classifier it will be asymptotically possible to maximize both “accuracy” and “fairness” simultaneously only if the protected feature and the target variable are perfectly independent.⁸² On the other extreme, if the protected feature is highly correlated with the target variable, then it is only possible to maximize either the “accuracy” or the “fairness” at the same time. In between those two extremes, the trade-off is determined by the strength of the correlation between the protected feature and the target variable. As the proof states, if the protected feature and the target variable are perfectly independent of one another, the more generalizable the model is, the more group parity will be present. The framework developed in the Distributive Decisions chapter will explain this in depth.

The above **fact** is sometimes used to argue that “accuracy” and “fairness” are generally in accord. That is true where no group disparities are present. While it is true that under certain conditions generalizable outcomes and group similar outcomes are compatible,⁸³ the reliance on that truth to minimize the importance of the trade-off is highly misleading. Generalizable outcomes and group similar outcomes can only be compatible in a data setting where no group disparities exist (necessarily defined as group parity in the context of perfect independence). If there is no group disparity in the data setting, there is no need for ‘debiasing.’ If group disparity

fallacy.

⁷⁹ “The existence of law is one thing; its merit or demerit is another. Whether it be or be not is one enquiry; whether it be or be not conformable to an assumed standard, is a different enquiry. A law, which actually exists, is a law, though we happen to dislike it, or though it vary from the text, by which we regulate our approbation and disapprobation. This truth, when formally announced as an abstract proposition, is so simple and glaring that it seems idle to insist upon it. But simple and glaring as it is, when enunciated in abstract expressions the enumeration of the instances in which it has been forgotten would fill a volume.” [Har57, p.596].

⁸⁰[CA21].

⁸¹[GLR20]; [ZG22].

⁸²[MW18].

⁸³“Compatible” is used to describe those situations where there is no trade-off between “accuracy” and “fairness.”

exists in the data setting, generalizable outcomes and group similar outcomes will be incompatible (i.e., the protected feature and target variable will be correlated.) Others observe that, in practice, constraining outcomes to be group similar can sometimes increase accuracy.⁸⁴ Again, the observation is correct but can lead to a misunderstanding. When the use of a “fairness” constraint increases the “accuracy,” either the protected feature and target variable are independent (and so see the above argument) or the data sample was so unrepresentative that enforcing group similarity increased the “accuracy,” either by happenstance⁸⁵ or, more likely, by using the informative value of the protected feature, but only that information which leads to group similarities by removing that information which leads to group dissimilarities through data processing.

The trade-off between generalizable outcomes and equal or similar group outcomes is obvious. The logical conclusion of the trade-off is also obvious: where there exists the greatest need for ‘debiasing’ (i.e., data settings that contain large group disparities), data-driven processes like machine learning are most useless. In other words, as the connection between the model outcomes and the target population becomes more tenuous to become less dissimilar amongst sub-groups, the use of machine learning becomes harder to justify. The more the outcome is already known (manually coded), the less need there is for a data driven approach—a script or quota could fulfill the same purpose. Thus, the trade-off presents a threat to the field. Beyond practical implications about energy sustainability and the waste of compute, why is this an important point? The use of quotas and differential treatment for the purpose of balancing group disparities in society is not a new phenomenon, and the legal questions surrounding their use have likely already been developed in a given jurisdiction.

One of the three following ‘debiasing’ strategies can be adopted: (1) pre-processing the input data to remove, alter, or curate the underlying data that lead to group dissimilarities in outcomes,⁸⁶ (2) in-processing where the model is constrained to produce group similar outcomes by modifying the learning algorithm’s objective functions,⁸⁷ and/or (3) post-processing the output of the model, rather than changing anything about the sample or hypothesis assumptions, by using an algorithm based on a function that detects potential group dissimilarities and adjusts the labels accordingly.⁸⁸ If the chosen ‘debiasing’ process requires the elimination of differences between groups based on a protected feature, while disregarding the base-rate differences between those groups, the effect would be to give systematic, differential treatment to one group at the expense of the other. The severity of that systematic deviation from the **principle** of equal treatment would depend on the strength of the correlation between the protected attribute and the target variable in the original, unprocessed data sample. The trade-off between an automated system that seeks to achieve equality of treatment versus equality of outcome is inextricably linked to the trade-off between generalizable outcomes and group similar outcomes, where the generalizability in employment decisions is an instantiation of qualification assessment objectivity, *Marschall Test*, and group similarity in outcomes (“fairness”) is an instantiation

⁸⁴[WpT19].

⁸⁵[Sch24].

⁸⁶[RPT10]; [Fel+15]; [ZWW17]; [HDF13].

⁸⁷[Ber+17].

⁸⁸[KGZ19].

of differential treatment. Placed in this context, the “cost of fairness”⁸⁹ is the sacrifice of the individual, fundamental right to equal treatment. What does **objectivity** mean? An explanation will be given in the Distributive Decisions chapter.

5.2.3.5 Sources of Discrimination within Fair Machine Learning

To begin with the question posed at the heart of fairness in machine learning: should we address group base-rate differences through a process of ‘debiasing,’ thereby creating differential conditions for some based on their protected feature in order to reach group equality or similarity in a final result, or should equal treatment be maintained in the competition itself, relying instead on institutions committed to substantive equality and internal positive action policies to redress factual inequalities between groups in society? In the context of hiring in the European Union, that normative question has already been answered. In *Kalanke*, the Court put forward the primary concern and determining factor of proportionality in the employment context: whether the practice substitutes substantive equality of opportunity for the outcome that is only to be reached by the realization of factual equality in society.

In *Marschall*, the differential treatment of the underrepresented sex was limited to tie-breaking scenarios of equally qualified candidates to counteract prejudiced tie-breaking that existed in social reality in accordance with the goal of substantive equality of opportunity. The Marschall “savings clause” ensured that outcome equality would not be pursued—requiring the employer to subject the candidatures to an objective assessment, where the preference would be overridden if the candidate of the over-represented sex had qualifications that would tilt the balance in their favor. Unlike the practice in Marschall, candidates subjected to fair automated hiring processes that ‘debias’ in accordance with group fairness metric, are not objectively assessed in the first place, let alone given the assurance of an override. Previous to the selection process and comparison of applicants, the data sample would have been modified and/or the hypothesis assumptions trained to undervalue the qualifications of some and overvalue the qualifications of others based on their protected feature. In other words, the weights of the applicants’ features, without differential treatment based on a protected feature, are not brought to bear on the hiring decision. Thus, the integrity of a tie-breaking scenario is compromised at the outset.

In *Abrahamsson*, the Court considered legislation which required that a candidate for a public position belonging to the under-represented sex and possessing sufficient qualifications for that post must be given a preference over a candidate of the opposite sex that would have been appointed otherwise in order to achieve equal gender representation in the given field of employment. The Court found that the objectivity of the selection process could, therefore, not be precisely determined. Such a practice, the Court reasoned, would result in the selection of candidates with qualifications not equal to but inferior to those of candidates of the opposite sex, ultimately substituting the individual assessment of candidate merit for group membership. The Court also ruled that even if the scope of such a practice was limited to a predetermined number of posts, or to posts specifically designed for that purpose, it would still be precluded because of the absolute and unconditional nature of the practice.

⁸⁹[MW18].

Unlike in the *Abrahamsson* case, the objectivity, or the lack thereof, of the selection process of an automated hiring system *can be* determined. A system which rids the outcome of group skew (defined as the quotient of between group distance and within group distance) or group dissimilarity (in accordance with a group fairness metric) and, in the process of doing so, necessarily disregards the representativeness of the sample and generalizability of the model, shows its lack of an objective assessment. Further, *Abrahamsson* tells us that creating a threshold at which candidates are qualified and then ensuring equal outcomes between groups post threshold satisfaction, would likely be precluded under an interpretation of the derogation of the relevant equality directive. For the above reasons, fair automated hiring systems that ‘debias’ in accordance with group fairness metrics would likely be deemed unlawful due to their automatic differential treatment.

5.2.3.5.1 Explanation with Experimental Results To ground the theoretical discussion surrounding non-discrimination, epistemology, and technical design, three Random Forest Classifiers (RFC) were trained. The goal was not to learn anything about a particular data setting, nor is it the goal to actually decide anything with any of the RFC trained. This is solely for explanation. The dataset used is publicly available.⁹⁰ **No use of any legal consideration attached to Ricci v. DeStefano U.S. Supreme Court case, or the U.S. legal system more generally, is made or implied.** The experiment was conducted for the purpose of assessing techniques which use a protected feature (in this case, race) in an automated system, the effects of ‘debiasing’ techniques (specifically, reweighing), and the consequences of ‘debiasing,’ where bias means a deviation from group equality or similarity in outcomes (what is often referred to simply as ‘bias,’ sometimes with the qualifier of ‘systemic bias,’ or as simply ‘discriminatory information’ in technical design). If such techniques were implemented in a system their use would be unlawful unless proportionate. The dataset is about firefighter promotion exams. The dataset comprises three numeric features: Oral, Written, and Combine. Table 1 summarizes the descriptive statistics and Table 2 summarizes the distribution between the protected feature (race) and target variable (position):

	Oral	Written	Combined
count	118	118	118
mean	65.523390	71.652542	69.200881
std	12.421927	10.622808	9.387575
min	40.830000	46.000000	45.932000
25%	55.387500	65.000000	60.942000
50%	66.040000	71.500000	69.502000
75%	73.810000	78.500000	75.832000
max	92.080000	95.000000	92.808000

Table 5.2: Descriptive Statistics for Oral, Written, and Combined Scores

⁹⁰<https://jse.amstat.org/v18n3/miao.pdf>; <https://www.key2stats.com/data-set/view/690>.

Position	B	H	W
Captain	8	8	25
Lieutenant	19	15	43

Table 5.3: Position vs. Race Distribution

Three models were evaluated to understand the impact of including race as a feature and applying a ‘de-biasing’ technique:

- RFC with the use of a protected feature
- RFC without the use of a protected feature
- RFC with the use of a protected feature and a ‘reweighing’ process

The Random Forest classifier incorporating race features achieved an F1 score of approximately 63.89. The classification report is as follows:

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.50	0.31	0.38	13
1	0.68	0.83	0.75	23
Accuracy			0.64	36
Macro Avg	0.59	0.57	0.56	36
Weighted Avg	0.61	0.64	0.62	36

Table 5.4: Classification Report: RFC with Protected Feature

Excluding race from the feature set resulted in a decrease in F1 score to approximately 55.56. Of course, this is because the protected features (B, H, W) are correlated with the target variable (Captain and Lieutenant). This is a benefit in terms of prediction. That is (only) one of the reasons fair machine learning techniques are used. The classification report is as follows:

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.33	0.23	0.27	13
1	0.63	0.74	0.68	23
Accuracy			0.56	36
Macro Avg	0.48	0.49	0.48	36
Weighted Avg	0.52	0.56	0.53	36

Table 5.5: Classification Report: RFC without Protected Feature

Applying the Reweighting technique to the original model improved the F1 score to approximately 61.11. The classification report is as follows:

The inclusion of race as a feature increased model F1 score to 63.89, which suggests that race contributes to the model’s predictive capabilities—as explained previously. This raises concerns

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.44	0.31	0.36	13
1	0.67	0.78	0.72	23
Accuracy			0.61	36
Macro Avg	0.56	0.55	0.54	36
Weighted Avg	0.59	0.61	0.54	36

Table 5.6: Classification Report: RFC Reweighed with Protected Feature

about potential biases, as the model may leverage racial information in decision-making. That is why access to the feature space is essential, not only for making non-discriminatory systems, but for the external verification—based on a distinction which must be made between a predictive system and a discriminatory one. The usual story goes something like this:

‘Excluding race from the feature set resulted in a noticeable decrease in accuracy to 55.56. This decline indicates that race holds predictive value within the dataset, which, if unmitigated, can perpetuate existing disparities. Applying the Reweighting ‘debiasing’ technique improved the model’s F1 score to 61.11 compared to the model without ‘debiasing,’ while still incorporating race as a feature. This suggests that Reweighting effectively balances the trade-off between ‘fairness’ and ‘accuracy’ by adjusting sample weights to mitigate bias without entirely removing the informative value of race.’

The protected features (B, H, W) are correlated with the target variable (Captain and Lieutenant) which conveys information that ‘de-biasing’ techniques partition into two types of information: discriminatory or non-discriminatory. The determination of what is discriminatory and what is not (bias as a deviation from group equality of similarity in outcomes) is based on whether the information had a negative affect based on a definition using the protected features as privileged and unprivileged classes. This might be the ethical-technical design, but it surely is not the legal design. This is a summary of my understanding of legal design:

Stage	Description of Discrimination
Using Protected Features or their Indissociable Proxies for Decision-making	If the Designers of an artificial intelligence train on a data sample that includes protected features or their indissociable proxies as features, and these features are used in the decision-making process, the effect would be to treat persons differently based on a protected feature when the artificial intelligence is deployed—resulting in direct discrimination—unless such differential treatment is justified by purposes such as public security, the maintenance of public order, crime prevention, health, or the protection of the rights and freedoms of others, and the means of achieving that purpose are appropriate and necessary.
Using Dissociable Features that Result in a Disparate Impact on a subgroup of a protected feature	If the Designers of an artificial intelligence use features which, while dissociable from a protected feature, nonetheless lead to a disparate impact on a sub-group of a protected feature, this may put persons possessing a sub-group of a protected feature at a particular disadvantage compared to others—resulting in indirect discrimination—unless the provision, criterion, or practice is objectively justified by a legitimate aim, and the means of achieving that aim are appropriate and necessary.
Processing a Data Sample	If the Designers of an artificial intelligence, using a function to detect correlations between the protected feature and the target variable in a data sample and alter the correlation by removing information which leads to group dissimilarities systematically treats groups differently based on a protected feature—resulting in direct discrimination— unless that ostensible violation of equal treatment can be justified as a proportional special measure, derogating from the principle of equal treatment, or that differential treatment is justified by purposes such as public security, health, or the protection of the rights and freedoms of others, and the means of achieving that purpose are appropriate and necessary.
Altering the Objective Function of the Algorithm	If the Designers of an artificial intelligence alter the objective function of an algorithm to ensure that the correlation between a protected feature and a target variable is not preserved in the outcomes of an artificial intelligence the result would be to systematically treat persons differently based on the protected feature when deployed—resulting in direct discrimination—unless that ostensible violation of equal treatment can be justified as a proportional special measure, derogating from the principle of equal treatment, or that differential treatment is justified by purposes such as public security, health, or the protection of the rights and freedoms of others, and the means of achieving that purpose are appropriate and necessary.
Changing Labels During Post-Processing	If the Designers of an artificial intelligence, using a function to detect correlations between the protected feature and the target variable in the outcomes of the AI system during post-processing, adjusts the labels to ensure that only information which leads to group similarities is derived from that correlation the effect would be to systematically prefer persons belonging to one group over another based on a protected feature when the artificial intelligence is deployed—resulting in direct discrimination—unless that ostensible violation of equal treatment can be justified as a proportional special measure, derogating from the principle of equal treatment, or that differential treatment is justified by purposes such as public security, health, or the protection of the rights and freedoms of others, and the means of achieving that purpose are appropriate and necessary..

Table 5.7: Sources of Discrimination in the Machine Learning Pipeline

5.2.3.6 Legal-Design or Design-made-Legal?

"In the beginning there was chaos and brute force. A world without law. In the mythology of Ancient Athens, Agamemnon sacrificed his daughter so that the Gods would allow his fleet to sail to Troy. His wife murdered him to avenge the deed and she, in turn, was murdered by her son. Athena, the Goddess of Wisdom, put an end to the cycle of violence by creating a Court to impose a solution in what today we would call the public interest, a solution based on reason, on the experience of human frailty and on fear of the alternative.

In the final part of Aeschylus's great trilogy, the *aristeia*, the Goddess justifies her intervention in the world of mortals with these words, "Let no man live uncurbed by law or curbed by tyranny." Now, that was written in the 5th century BC but the message is timeless and it's universal. Law is not just an instrument of corrective or distributive justice, it is an expression of collective values and an alternative to violence and capricious despotism.

It is a vice of some lawyers that they talk about law as if it was a self-contained subject, something to be examined like a laboratory specimen in a test tube, but law does not occupy a world of its own. It is part of a larger system of public decision making. The rest is politics. The politics of ministers and legislators of political parties, of media and pressure groups, and of the wider electorate." [emphasis added]
Lord Sumption, THE REITH LECTURES 2019: LAW AND THE DECLINE OF POLITICS

The above quote brings attention both to the beginning and now the end of this chapter. The analytic treatment of legal judgments and the rule of law may lead one to believe that the author is arguing that law is a self-contained system. What at first appears like contradiction is often uncharted complexity—nuance unstated.

In the practice of translating fundamental rights jurisprudence into technical specifications for automated distributive decisions, the law of a given moment and jurisdiction should have priority over political or moral passion when providing legal expertise that will later guide design and the live use of such systems in a jurisdiction.

A cornerstone of AI Governance generally, and Trustworthy AI specifically, is the premise that unlawfulness in artificial intelligences inherently undermine their ethical standing—a point made repeatedly in the Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (also cited in the preamble of the AI act)—while also accommodating and encouraging the lawful, moral aims of individuals, businesses, and institutions operating within those boundaries. While many engage in and applaud going "beyond the law" to achieve a desired moral aim, the law itself must not be contradicted. And, before asking "in what direction," it should be understood that the cases which further apply, and thus define, fundamental rights are among the most controversial.

While moral conflict may sometimes be resolved through an appeal to reason, morals themselves are not *solely* the design of reason—whether naturally or artificially processed. Morals are inherited from generation to generation, constructing our intuition through the observation of conduct and cultural learning—whether familial, local, societal, or global—appealing to our

sense of proportionality⁹¹ for agreement with others, whose moral axioms are similar enough to allow for the identification of conflicts between axioms in application to a *shared* and *relevant fact pattern*. “Thought experiments” are useful for showing others that hard moral questions exist regardless of our awareness of them. But hard moral questions exist because the experimentees experience a contradiction of held axioms and force a synthesis, a moral reconstruction—prioritization via re-balancing, removal, or replacement of morals. It is the process of moral learning simplified.

However, there is no substitute for nuance. The moral wealth of humanity (with beautiful and tragic complexity and contradiction) cannot be expressed in a standard, nor should we delude ourselves that it might. While one’s own moral compass might *appear* linear, non-discrimination law is emphatically not. Instead, it is *proportional*.⁹² The interpretation and application of the Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union begins and ends at the Court of Justice of the European Union. If normative standardization is the goal, at the very least rely on legal standards to form the axiomatic basis of ethical compliance. What does that mean? It at least means that it is not one’s own morals in question, which opens the possibility that in hard legal cases (like those involving equal treatment and justice) one’s own moral beliefs may be contradicted.

If a moral conclusion mirrors a legal one, then at most it is a supplementary justification for lawful behavior. If a moral conclusion deviates from a legal conclusion, then it was brought about by a moral, not legal, interpretation. The difference between a hard question of morality and a hard question of law is, *itself*, the **rule of law**—through which **equal treatment** grew.⁹³ To whatever extent the results of an ethical impact assessment have an obligatory nature, this point should be taken seriously. And, if AI ethics experts legitimize their value selection by deriving them from the fundamental rights of a given jurisdiction, then it follows that the definition should be left to fundamental rights jurisprudence. Thus, the question is not should the Court set the standard but, instead, has the standard already been set?

The risk posed is one of moral pursuit. But that is not the only risk: it can easily be that these are difficult questions that involve knowledge of a number of fields for the approximation of truth. To a lawyer or an ethicist, what is written might be insulting but for an engineer it may well be useful—that incongruity is true in all directions of expertise.

The question of value alignment is not the question of whether and how artificial intelligences can be made Good. The question of value alignment is, in practice and in policy, whether and how the design of artificial intelligences (which are advancing faster than our responsible

⁹¹Not to be confused with proportionality as a legal term of art.

⁹²See Art. 52 (1) ‘1. Any limitation on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by this Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others.’ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union art 52.

⁹³‘The principle of equal treatment is a general principle of EU law, enshrined in Article 20 of the Charter, of which the principle of non-discrimination laid down in Article 21 (1) of the Charter is a particular expression. According to settled case-law, that principle requires the EU legislature to ensure, in accordance with Article 52(1) of the Charter, that comparable situations must not be treated differently and that different situations must not be treated in the same way unless such treatment is objectively justified.’ *Wolfgang Glatzel v Freistaat Bayern*, para 43.

decision-making about them) can be aligned with legal obligations—both present and emerging—and their designers held accountable for violations. The objective outlined by the European Commission has been twofold: create a legal framework encouraging the adoption and innovation of artificial intelligences in both the private and public sector, while ensuring that “high risk” purposes are brought into alignment with standards for health, safety, and the protection of fundamental rights. The enthusiastic yet cautious approach of the European Union is a response to immediately cognizable intranational and international concerns, ranging from socio-political stability to economic and defense competitiveness.

The most complex of value alignment questions require a deep understanding, not solely of the related legal or technical subject matter but, most importantly, the foundations which interconnect them. The problem is not that solutions are unavailable because of the novelty of artificial intelligence and the application of it—at least that is not true in all cases. This research suggests that the solutions are in the past, but the researchers are in the future—more precisely in a Utopia. The crucial difference between the theoretical construction of a Utopia and the actual attempted construction of a Utopia is the systematic violation of fundamental rights, always. Before determining whether and how scholars are able to align a super-intelligent being with the Good—a dangerous and confused task to begin with—it should first be understood how to align an automated decision-making system (of any kind) with legal obligations and not the other way around. Otherwise, we are quite literally talking about a **data revolution** in the legal-political sense of the term.

None of that is to say that what is lawful is necessarily moral, but one takes that responsibility on their own shoulders—that is what makes such unlawful moral action rare but essential.

This research is about events, distributive decisions that happen in jurisdictions whose actions may have legal consequences, and if violations of equal treatment occur there may be redress for victims. The argument is that the definition of fundamental rights modeled technically *must* be based on a faithful and current interpretation of the law—that means jurisdiction (cannot be global if about fundamental rights). A *cautionary* explanation may be required: in reality it is a mix of enforcement mechanisms, the definitions of which are tailored by legislation, fact-patterns that arise leading to the application of law in the courts, and the non-binding but influential opinions of legal communities more generally. These are among the most morally charged questions at the intersection of economics, statistics, law, philosophy, and design. Being boring, elusive, and/or ideological is not good enough though, because the requirements of **attention** and **trust** of readers *should not* be ignored where the goal is interdisciplinary communication. Reading an author in the best light could also prove essential—that is exceedingly difficult both for writer and reader when analytic clarity is pursued in a moral or ethical domain. *Analytic clarity* though is precisely what is required for **legal certainty** where it can be had. It is difficult to think clearly about concepts like justice and discrimination. If it has not been difficult for a decision-maker, there may be a problem.

5.2.4 A Transition: from Fair Machine Learning to Distributive Decisions

The previous chapter explored the complex interplay between law and ethics in the governance of artificial intelligence within the European Union. It highlighted the challenges that arise when

ethical principles extend beyond legal obligations, particularly when the two conflict. The demarcation between legal obligations and ethical principles was examined, emphasizing the importance of aligning artificial intelligence design with legal standards to uphold the rule of law and protect fundamental rights.

A significant example of this tension is found in the domain of fair machine learning and automated hiring systems. Those systems engage in differential treatment through ‘debiasing’ techniques, which can inadvertently lead to the systematic violation of non-discrimination law. The use of group fairness metrics, which adjust information contained in a data sample, change the objective function of an algorithm, or simply achieve group equality or similarity via post-processing of decision outcomes, necessarily result in differential treatment based on a protected feature. Again, differential treatment based on group membership is different than predictive accuracy regardless of group membership. The prior ‘fairness,’ is defined as group equality or similarity in decision outcomes, and in the latter ‘fairness’ is defined as generalizability, which, by definition, means predictive performance regardless of group membership. One cannot know what is just until one knows what is true. Truth cannot be found solely in an analysis of outcomes because humans make decisions. Decision-makers are **responsible** for their decision making. Responsible decision making is necessary to reach **factual equality**, necessary both for designers of distributive decisions and those they measure. The question of factual equality is how to get there? The next chapter will attempt to formalize these concepts.

The case law of the Court, in particular *Kalanke*, *Marschall*, and *Abrahamsson*, provides clear guidance on the distinction between factual equality via substantive equality and equality of outcome. These rulings emphasize that while measures to promote substantive equality are encouraged, practices that guarantee equal outcomes between groups through automatic or unconditional priority based on protected features are precluded. Such practices undermine the principle of equal treatment and violate established non-discrimination law.

These **complexities** underscore the necessity of a deeper understanding of how artificial intelligences make distributive decisions. There is a need to develop a framework that accounts for the moral and ethical purposes and legal constraints inherent in the allocation of benefits and burdens among individuals or groups.

Decision Theory allows for a systematic examination of the trade-offs between **treating distributees equally and treating distributees unequally so that that decision outcomes may be equal among them**, thereby determining the boundaries of differential treatment, and all of the real-world legal variances found in between in differing fact-scenarios in different jurisdictions. It highlights the consequences of different patterning choices and how they impact individuals and groups within society. Concepts like the distributive decision format, categorical ordering, and patterning (both anterior and posterior) are central to understanding how decisions can be made in a manner that is ethically sound to the extent that it may be determined legally compliant.

By applying this theory to AI system design, particularly in areas like automated hiring, it becomes clearer how certain practices may lead to unlawful discrimination. In moving from Fair Machine Learning to Distributive Decisions, the focus shifts to creating artificial intelligences that aim for factual equality by adhering to the distinctions made between substantive equality

and the ideal of *Equality of Outcome*. This approach is an aid to the development of artificial intelligences that respect fundamental rights and uphold the rule of law. By grounding the design of artificial intelligences in a robust theoretical understanding of distribution and justice, it might be possible to navigate the complex normative landscape where law, ethics, and technology intersect.

5.2.5 Distributive Decisions

5.2.5.1 Decision Theory and Group Disparities

Decision theory merges insights from economics, statistics, philosophy, law, and psychology to better understand decision-making processes in the face of uncertainty.⁹⁴ It is recognized within this interdisciplinary field that decisions occur amidst various options, with goal-oriented actions highlighting deliberate, *non-random* choices.⁹⁵ Two principal branches underpin decision theory: normative and descriptive. Normative decision theory is concerned with developing models for optimal decision-making, emphasizing rationality and the maximization of utility. *Rationality* is defined as selecting the option that optimizes the decision-maker's utility, factoring in their preferences and the information at their disposal.⁹⁶ And, *utility* refers to the level of satisfaction or benefit gained from specific outcomes.⁹⁷ Normative decision theory differentiates between decisions made under risk (with known probabilities) and uncertainty (with unknown probabilities).⁹⁸

Descriptive decision theory, on the other hand, focuses on how decisions are actually made in real-world settings, acknowledging that human behavior often deviates from purely rational models. Research in the field of behavioral economics reveals that people often make choices based on the perceived potential for gains and losses, rather than focusing on the ultimate outcome.⁹⁹ Investigations into cognitive shortcuts and biases have deepened understanding in the field, illustrating the systematic errors that can manifest in human judgment and the decision-making process.¹⁰⁰

In the European Union, principles of normative decision theory, like the precautionary principle, are inherently linked to the practices of risk and impact assessments, particularly within regulatory and policy-making frameworks.¹⁰¹ The descriptive decision theory approach has been

⁹⁴[Pet17].

⁹⁵[Han11]; [Hano5].

⁹⁶[Sav72].

⁹⁷Introducing game theory to analyze and predict the outcomes of competitive situations where participants' choices are interdependent, see [DVNM45].

⁹⁸Distinguishing between measurable risks and un-measurable uncertainties, arguing that the latter forms the basis of profit in a competitive market economy, see [Kni21].

⁹⁹Presenting an experiment where individuals displayed a marked propensity to overvalue minor probabilities and undervalue significant ones, deviating from expected utility theory by demonstrating risk aversion in gain scenarios and risk-seeking in loss contexts, see [KT79].

¹⁰⁰Investigating the impact of cognitive shortcuts like representativeness, availability, and anchoring on the frequent miscalculations in estimating probabilities and making decisions when faced with uncertainty, see [TK74].

¹⁰¹Performing a comparative legal analysis of the precautionary principle's implementation in the US and EU, introducing a taxonomy of the principle which showcases a gradient from minimal intervention, encouraging research

applied in legal research as well, where user-centric legal design moves beyond plain-language interpretation to consider how users process information.¹⁰²

Over the years, at the intersection where artificial intelligence research and the humanities and social sciences met, jurists, ethicists, and computer scientists worked to better frame and define the myriad potential impacts of introducing artificial intelligences into society and to determine how best to guide that process. Working under the premise that "code is law,"¹⁰³ a variety of tools have been developed to prescript normative constraints on automated decision-making systems e.g., privacy-preserving technologies, explainable artificial intelligence techniques, fair machine learning, and hate speech, disinformation, and misinformation detection systems.¹⁰⁴ The Artificial Intelligence Act relies on such prescriptive technologies to perform value alignment between automated decision-making systems and European fundamental rights.

It is in this way that technologists—whether scientist, jurist, ethicist, or any variation of the three—are becoming the watchmen of European fundamental rights. However, these are highly specialized fields that take focused study to understand even a portion of what is recommended as fundamental rights ensuring. The information asymmetry between experts in the field and those traditionally engaged in legal interpretation, raises the age-old question of who is to watch the watchmen themselves?¹⁰⁵

The *economics of discrimination* investigates how differential treatment based on a protected feature affects economic outcomes for individuals and groups within societies.¹⁰⁶ It is reasonable in historical contexts to consider that disparities between groups can and have manifested in various contexts—in some cases because of past differential treatment—such as wage disparities, employment opportunities, and access to education or credit; and this fact may lead to stereotyping based on a protected feature.¹⁰⁷ It is also reasonable to conclude that a statistical modeling can potentially include proxy features for protected features.¹⁰⁸ Furthermore, the role of social capital and the inter-generational transmission factors are relevant to understanding group disparities.¹⁰⁹ That means that group disparities are not solely caused by discrimination. Recent work underscores how economic disparities arise from a complex interplay of cultural, social, and policy-related factors.¹¹⁰

and better understanding of risks, to more definitive actions like mandating the best available technology or outright prohibition when risks are substantial and cannot be adequately managed within the other categories, see [Com06].

¹⁰²Arguing for a turn from lengthy and unstructured disclosures ('dark strategies') to transparency-enhancing design patterns, see [RL20b].

¹⁰³Making the case that programs implemented in the digital environment can control decision-makers operating in that environment, see [Les99a].

¹⁰⁴In-depth surveys have been conducted on each of these technologies: [BDC20]; [Gui+18]; [Nto+20]; [AK24].

¹⁰⁵"[Q]uis custodiet ipsos custodes?" [Noak].

¹⁰⁶Introducing a neoclassical economic approach to discrimination, modeling it as a preference that can influence market dynamics and individual earnings, see [Bec71].

¹⁰⁷Discussing how discrimination can persist in competitive markets due to factors like imperfect information and the reliance on stereotypes in decision-making, see [Arr71].

¹⁰⁸Introducing statistical discrimination, explaining how economic agents might use observable characteristics as proxies for unobservable features, see [Phe72].

¹⁰⁹Highlighting how historical discrimination and social context can lead to ongoing group disparities through mechanisms like unequal access to networks, resources, and opportunities, see [Lou76].

¹¹⁰Examining the reasons behind economic differences among groups, emphasizing the importance of systemic

Building upon the foundation that decisions occur amidst various options, with purposeful actions highlighting **deliberate, non-random choices**, laid by normative and descriptive decision theories; as well as the exploration of how economic disparities can arise from discrimination and other complex factors including decision-making, attention turns to the distribution of resources and opportunities within societies.

Not all decision-making processes are, nor should they be, subject to the same level of scrutiny; personal choices, such as which grandchild receives a treat or neighbor receives support, fall outside the realm of structured evaluation. The focus here is on distributive decisions that are **structured, documented, and programmed**—those made by institutions and private organizations (ever becoming digitized and data dependent), or algorithms more generally that significantly impact societal outcomes. The aim is to develop a better understanding of how these structured decisions shape the allocation of benefits and burdens in society. In the following section, the principles and mechanisms that underlie justice in distribution are discussed, exploring how moral purposes and legal frameworks intersect in the design of distributive decisions.

To be clear, the proposition that people *should* be compared is not being put forward. Nor is the proposition that where people are compared it *must* be lawful, identifying risks along the way. Those propositions have already been put forward. Instead, the proposition being put forward here is: if people are to be compared, exceptions to the principle of equal treatment *must* be proportional at both ends of the two ideals of Justice: *Formal Equality* and *Equality of Outcome*. Substantive equality, by definition, reflects both ideals—the more complete story of justice in distributive decisions. Whether it is substantive equality in the European Union, or some other fine-grained legal doctrine developed in another legal system, access to the feature space of decision-processes may already be provided for by law. In the European Union that seems the case for decision-making processes of artificial intelligences as well.

5.2.5.2 Justice and Distribution

Distributive justice seeks *Goodness* in the allocation of resources among members of a society, asking and answering questions about what should be distributed to whom and how. The reader may have encountered maxims of distribution before, like, "[f]rom each according to his ability, to each according to his need."¹¹¹ Or, "[a]ll social values are to be distributed equally unless an unequal distribution of any, or all, of these values is to everyone's advantage."¹¹² Set aside whether these maxims are good or bad, here the focus is on: what are distributive decisions, how *can* those decisions be driven by moral purpose, and how that moral purpose *can* be lawful or unlawful in relation to the first chapter.

A distributive decision is the process by which a benefit or burden (distribuendum, A) is allocated among individuals or groups (distributees, Y , where each $y_i \in Y$ is an individual distributee) based on applied criteria (pattern of distribution, P) established by a decision-maker (distributor, X) for a specific purpose (designer's purpose, D). Such decisions have always been made and continue to be made—because it is a necessary process—by a central authority, such

factors and individual choices over solely attributing disparities to discrimination, see [Sow19].

¹¹¹[Mar21, p.16].

¹¹²The difference principle is the most widely cited principle in algorithmic fairness, see[Raw71].

as a government, organization, or algorithm in the calculation of risk for decision-making (i.e., hiring, admissions, creditworthiness, etc.) in the comparison of distributees. The decision involves determining who will receive what, based on relevant features (categorical ordering) such as need, merit, or group membership, and reflects specific goals held by the designer in the pursuit of the equality or similarity in individual or group outcomes. So, what is a distributive decision?

Distributive Decision Format: X distributes A among Y according to P for the purpose of D .^a

^a[Hano1] (Sven Ove Hansson, Chair of Philosophy and History of Technology at the Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm, is well-regarded for his contributions to decision theory and the philosophy of science. His work, *Equity, Equality, and Egalitarianism*, was a major influence on this approach. Hansson delineates the conceptual landscape of human-driven distribution processes. Rather than advocating for specific distributive principles, Hansson aimed to clarify the often-confused and conflated terms and ideas within discussions of justice in distribution. The goal in the forthcoming section will be to expand on Hansson's treatment of what has been referred to as *distributive decisions* throughout this work, with the ultimate objective of using the schema developed to identify the limits and trade-offs of 'de-biasing' techniques.)

As the reader will notice, whenever examples of the variables of a Distributive Decision Format (DDF) are given, the associated normative aspects become identifiable. It is important to recognize and understand that the final holdings of goods in any given time-slice of a population is not solely the process of past distributive decision-making. Take, for example, the figuratively innumerable privately made decisions that structure a market economy and the state of holdings that is produced.¹¹³ Distributive decisions are not solely "human-driven" but *purpose-driven*. "Distribution processes are undertaken with a purpose, and they can be more or less efficacious with respect to that purpose."¹¹⁴ Centralized human distribution processes are designed, and they are designed to fulfill the purpose of a designer or group of designers.¹¹⁵

5.2.5.2.1 Designer The designer (D) is the agent with the purpose and decision-making authority to establish the criteria, goals, and mechanisms by which the distribution is executed. This includes formulating the objectives of the distribution, determining the distribuendum (A), the distributees (Y), the pattern of distribution (P), and selecting the distributor (X) who will carry out the distribution. The purpose of the designer (D) should, of course, orient the function of the distributor (X); otherwise, the distributor (X) would be defective.

Hypothetical: A city's Department of Education (D) aims to improve student performance by hiring 100 new teachers (A) for public schools (Y). They task their Human Resources division

¹¹³Distinguishing between centralized and decentralized decision-making, emphasizing the efficiency and adaptability of decentralized decision-making as opposed to central planning, see [Hay45].

¹¹⁴[Hano1, p. 535].

¹¹⁵Placing the conversation in context, for stark historical and ideological contrast, compare [Len51] (outlining the need for economic and administrative reform, including the nationalization of industry and the implementation of central planning essential for the transition towards an economy that can meet the population's needs, eliminate capitalist exploitation, and lay the foundations for communism) with [BT99] (advocating for a system that aims for decisions to be made with near-unanimity, minimizing the coercive power of the state, and ensuring that collective action is genuinely beneficial to the community, reflecting the decentralized decision-making of the market, where individual choice leads to efficient outcomes without centralized control.)

(*X*) to recruit candidates based on specific criteria (*P*) such as teaching certifications, subject expertise, and a demonstrated ability to engage students, all to fulfill the purpose (*D*) of enhancing educational outcomes.

5.2.5.2.2 Distributor A distributor (*X*) need not have human agency. **Hypothetical:** The Department of Education (*D*) employs an AI-driven recruitment platform (*X*) to hire 100 new teachers (*A*) for public schools (*Y*). The automated system screens and selects applicants based on predefined criteria (*P*) like certifications, subject expertise, and engagement metrics from digital teaching portfolios, aligning with the department's goal (*D*) of improving student performance through high-quality education.

A designed distribution process defines the variables of the DDF to fulfill a purpose, and that purpose corresponds to a set of normative values held by the designer *D*. Those interested in justice compare the final distribution of a designed distributive process with a principle of justice in distribution. Or they design distributive decision processes according to a principle of justice. There are many such principles recorded which seek to be the basis of future distributive processes, either by *justifying* existing distributions¹¹⁶ or by *condemning* them to redistribution.¹¹⁷

5.2.5.2.3 Distributum A distributum (*A*) must be assignable and transferable to distributees. For a distributum to be assignable and transferable, it cannot be an object ('good') that relates to a mental state (like security or welfare) or capability (like the ability to play the flute)—though proxies for such objects can be selected (like universal basic income as a proxy for economic security or distributing flute lessons as a proxy for distributing the ability to play).¹¹⁸ As the old adage goes: you may lead a horse to water, but you can't make it drink.¹¹⁹ **That is not, of course, to say that individual, communal, or governmental action cannot be helpful to others, but it is instead to say that helpful action is not and cannot be solely accomplished via beneficent purpose.**

5.2.5.2.4 Ordering and Patterning How is a distributive decision made? It is made in two distinct phases: categorical ordering and patterning.

¹¹⁶Nozick emphasizes individual rights and entitlements, arguing that justice is not about the end-state distribution of goods but about the processes that lead to that distribution. He introduces the entitlement theory, which justifies distributions based on principles of just acquisition, transfer, and rectification.[Noz74].

¹¹⁷John Rawls embeds his argument for distributive justice in a thought experiment known as the "Original Position," which asks decision-makers to operate under a veil that obscures their own (original) position in society. He argues reasonable persons would agree to two principles of justice—the liberty principle and the difference principle—which prioritize basic liberties for all and allow social and economic inequalities only if they benefit the least advantaged members of society—technically speaking the rule of law is embedded in his argument and provides safety from equality of outcome) but that does not remove the requirement that in reality, such decision processes based on that maxim must be lawful.[Raw71].

¹¹⁸Here, Hansson's point ([Hano1, p. 532]) rests on a distinction already emphasized in the algorithmic fairness literature; see [FSV21] (distinguishing between construct features, like creditworthiness, and their observable proxies, like loan default).

¹¹⁹Translating from Old English "Hwa is thet mei thet hors wetrien the him-self nule drinken?" to "Ah! who is he that may water the horse that will not drink himself?," see [Mor68, pp. 8-9].

Categorical Ordering defines the feature space (\mathcal{F}) for distributive decisions. The feature space refers to the relevant characteristics or **features** selected to describe distributees y_i . By establishing the feature space, the decision-maker determines the dimensions along which distributees will be measured. These characteristics could be anything relevant to the specific context of the distribution. This process is not concerned with how distributions will occur but simply with selecting which features matter in describing the distributees.

Categorical ordering is essential for the creation of a DDF, and patterning is essential for the application of a DDF. A DDF necessarily relies on a categorical ordering—distinct from patterning because it is a prerequisite of patterning—which parses the relevant from the non-relevant information for the measurement of distributees. Categorical ordering is required because, out of all **observable** categories of information about distributees through which they may be compared, it must be determined which information is useful and proper for a given measurement (e.g., what qualities does the successful candidate have for a given job posting). Once a DDF is designed via categorical ordering, it must be designed via patterning: each distributee y_i may be described in relation to that format, ranked, and the distribuendum may be distributed accordingly.

There are two types of patterns: anterior and posterior.¹²⁰

5.2.5.2.5 Anterior Patterning For anterior patterning, the distribuendum received will usually be an increasing or decreasing function of their holdings, characteristics, or **features** (which exist prior to the process of distribution) of the pattern. “It is, for instance, the health care needs before, not after, health care has been distributed that should determine its distribution.”¹²¹ Anterior patterns interrogate the actual features of the distributees in the pattern (like healthcare based on need or reward based on performance), and so the **final distribution** is **unknown** before the evaluation of distributees. The distinction between anterior and posterior patterning and between conservative and non-conservative metrics is also identical to Nozick’s distinction between historical and end-result principles of distribution.

Basing the distribution pattern on an anterior pattern is to allow for differences in the distribuendum received by distributees. When comparing distributees is permissible, inequality in the distribuendum is permissible.

Plato observed, “[w]hen equality is given to unequal things, the resultant will be unequal...”¹²² and Hayek clarified, “[f]rom the fact that people are very different it follows that, if we treat them equally, the result must be inequality in their actual position...”¹²³ An additional clarification may be needed. The “equal” in “treat them equal” does not refer to the quantitative equality between the outcome of two persons. Instead, “treat them equally” as it relates to designed distribution processes means **continuity** between the anterior pattern (the initial state

¹²⁰The distinction between posterior and anterior pattern is identical to the distinction between conservative and non-conservative fairness metrics and their respective implications of use; see [R21] (arguing that “non-conservative” independence metrics like statistical parity can be useful to account or compensate for historical injustice in line with the goal of social justice).

¹²¹[Hano1, p. 534].

¹²²[Pla+14].

¹²³[Hay76].

or condition of the distributees) and the **final distribution**. The practice of treating distributees equally can be formalized as:

Let Y be the set of distributees, where each distributee $y_i \in Y$ is an individual recipient. Let Z_i be the vector representing the pre-distribution features (priors) of distributee y_i . Let $f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D)$ represent the pattern of distribution (P) using an anterior pattern, where:

$$f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D) = Q_i, \tag{5.1}$$

Z_i is the feature vector of distributee y_i . D is the designer's purpose or purpose guiding the distribution. Q_i is the outcome for distributee y_i after the distribution process, reflecting the variability based on Z_i .

The function f_{anterior} maps the initial features Z_i of each distributee y_i to an outcome Q_i , in alignment with the designer's purpose D .

5.2.5.2.6 Posterior Patterning Posterior patterns, on the other hand, set out to achieve a *desired* distribution, where the holdings or characteristics of individuals are not determinate—because considering them might lead to an *undesirable* distribution. Posterior patterns look to achieve a predetermined distribution state, such as "distribute total economic resources so as to ensure that resources are equally distributed among the distributees."¹²⁴ Other examples might include, "Distribute pay equally among employees, regardless of differences in production or hours worked," or "Distribute grades equally among students, regardless of their performance on an exam." These examples use posterior patterning to achieve numerically equal outcomes. The practice of treating distributees differently so that that decision outcomes may be equal can be formalized as:

Let Y be the set of distributees, where each distributee $y_i \in Y$ is an individual recipient. Let $f_{\text{posterior}}(y_i; D)$ represent the pattern of distribution (P) using a posterior pattern, where:

$$f_{\text{posterior}}(y_i; D) = C_D, \tag{5.2}$$

y_i is the distributee. D is the designer's purpose or purpose specifying the desired distribution outcome. C_D is a constant value determined by the designer's purpose D , signifying that every distributee receives the same outcome.

The function $f_{\text{posterior}}$ assigns the same value C_D to each distributee y_i , reflecting the designer's objective to achieve a specific distribution outcome.

¹²⁴[Han01, p. 535].

5.2.5.2.7 Combined Patterning A designed distribution process using both anterior and posterior patterning necessarily results in a trade-off between the two.

The Combined pattern function is defined as:

$$f_{\text{Combined}}(Z_i, \lambda; D) = \lambda f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D) + (1 - \lambda)C_D, \quad (5.3)$$

where:

Z_i is the feature vector for distributee y_i . $f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D)$ is the anterior pattern function based on individual features and the designer's purpose. C_D is the desired constant outcome determined by the designer's purpose D . $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ balances the influence of individual features versus the designer's intended uniform outcome.

This formalization illustrates the inherent trade-off between anterior patterning and posterior patterning. Adjusting the parameter λ allows the designer to navigate this trade-off according to the specific objectives of the distribution process.

Given a variance threshold θ , the distribution can be adjusted as:

$$f_{\text{adjusted}}(Z_i, \lambda; D) = \begin{cases} f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D) & \text{if } \text{Var}(Q) \leq \theta, \\ \lambda f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D) + (1 - \lambda)C_D & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (5.4)$$

$\text{Var}(Q)$ represents the variance in the outcomes based on the anterior patterning, reflecting inequality among distributees. θ sets the allowable variance limit based on policy goals or the designer's purpose.

This adjusted function allows the designer to apply anterior patterning when inequality is within acceptable limits and to introduce posterior adjustments when inequality exceeds those limits.

5.2.5.3 Social Justice and Distribution

In the previous section, distributive decisions were examined without explicit reference to group membership. The framework should extend to include group membership as a category in the categorical ordering, because there are limited but legitimate uses of group membership in decision-making. This allows us to identify specific groups and apply posterior patterning to achieve desired distribution outcomes for those groups.

5.2.5.3.1 Categorical Ordering with Groups Categorical ordering defines the feature space \mathcal{F} , which consists of the relevant features used to describe and compare distributees. Group membership can be included as one of these features.

Let:

Y denote the set of distributees, where each distributee $y_i \in Y$ is an individual recipient. Z_i denotes the vector of features for each distributee y_i , so that:

$$Z_i = (z_{i1}, z_{i2}, \dots, z_{in}, g_i),$$

where g_i represents the group membership of y_i .

By including g_i in Z_i , group membership becomes part of the features considered in the distributive decision.

5.2.5.3.2 Anterior Patterning with Groups Using anterior patterning, the designer bases the distribution on individual features within each group. This approach involves applying a distribution function that considers the full feature vector Z_i of each distributee y_i .

Let $f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D_{g_i})$ represent the pattern of distribution (P) using an anterior pattern, where:

$$f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D_{g_i}) = Q_i, \quad (5.5)$$

Z_i is the feature vector (including group membership g_i) for distributee y_i . D_{g_i} is the designer's purpose guiding the distribution for group g_i . Q_i is the outcome for y_i .

The function f_{anterior} maps individual features to outcomes, potentially allowing group membership g_i to influence how features are weighted or interpreted within the context of the group, in alignment with the designer's purpose D_{g_i} .

5.2.5.3.3 Posterior Patterning with Groups Using posterior patterning, the designer aims to achieve specific desired outcomes for different groups. This involves setting target distributions for groups regardless of individual features.

Let $f_{\text{posterior}}(y_i; D_{g_i})$ represent the pattern of distribution (P) using a posterior pattern that targets group outcomes, where:

$$f_{\text{posterior}}(y_i; D_{g_i}) = C_{D_{g_i}}, \quad (5.6)$$

y_i is the distributee. D_{g_i} represents the designer's purpose or purpose for group g_i . $C_{D_{g_i}}$ is the constant outcome specified by the designer's purpose D_{g_i} for group g_i .

This formulation allows the designer to set different distribution targets for different groups, directly reflecting the designer's objectives for each group.

5.2.5.3.4 Combined Patterning with Groups The combined anterior and posterior patterning, incorporating group membership can be formalized as follows:

The Combined pattern function is defined as:

$$f_{\text{Combined}}(Z_i, \lambda; D_{g_i}) = \lambda f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D_{g_i}) + (1 - \lambda) C_{D_{g_i}}, \quad (5.7)$$

where:

Z_i is the feature vector for distributee y_i , including group membership g_i . $f_{\text{anterior}}(Z_i; D_{g_i})$ is the anterior pattern function based on individual features and the designer's purpose for group g_i . $C_{D_{g_i}}$ is the desired outcome for the group to which y_i belongs, determined by the designer's purpose D_{g_i} . $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ balances the influence of individual features versus group-level objectives set by the designer. This formalization illustrates the inherent trade-off between rewarding individual merit or need (anterior patterning) and achieving desired group outcomes (posterior patterning). Adjusting the parameter λ allows the designer to navigate this trade-off according to the specific objectives of the distribution process for each group.

5.2.5.4 Examples of the Trade-Off

There are two limiting cases where formal equality and equality of outcome are compatible. First, it is possible that a well-defined categorical ordering of correct information treats distributees or groups of distributees the same and, at the same time, results in the same outcomes. Such an instance is only possible where distributees or groups of distributees are, in fact, the same in measurement with the standard. Second, it is possible to create a standard of such minimal content so as to not recognize differences between distributees or groups of distributees, such that all distributees or groups of distributees are both treated the same in relation to the standard while ensuring the same outcomes. The crucial qualitative difference between the two limiting cases that must be understood is that in the first a designer reaches equality of outcomes via factual equality (a process bounded by the categorized descriptions of distributees competing under a specific standard but cooperating in societies allowed for by such standards, i.e. the preservation of emergence in centralized, distributive decisions) and, in the second, the designer reaches equal outcomes via mere presentation (a process bounded by designer choice in preference).

In between these two limiting cases, formal equality and equality of outcome are incompatible. A designer may set a threshold at any point between these two extremes, demarcating how much difference in outcomes between distributees or groups of distributees is acceptable in their distributive decision, and by doing so, necessarily demarcates how much difference in treatment between distributees or groups of distributees is acceptable.

- **Example A** imagine an automated loan approval system, where the algorithm is designed to approve loans based on credit score (categorical ordering: e.g. on-time payment history, credit-debt ratio, open and closed lines of credit, and so on, to predict the likelihood of loan default), it may result in different approval rates among various sub-groups of protected characteristics, not because it is based (if protected characteristic or indisso-ciable proxy was not a category) on those protected characteristics but because there

may be a correlation between the protected characteristic and creditworthiness in the target population. By setting a threshold (necessary use of protected characteristic or an indissociable proxy) for acceptable variance in approval rates between sub-groups of a protected characteristic (equality of outcomes, difference in treatment), the bank increases the likelihood that applicants who would have been deemed uncreditworthy for the loan specifics are given loans—putting the borrower at risk of loan default by-default (based on the protected characteristic) and the lender at risk of a loss. Remember, while a bank is likely to shift that burden to others via fraud and/or taxpayer bailouts or socialization, the borrower will be left with little recourse. When a distributive decision process is automated, evidence of that choice exists. In short, it exists in the space between a representative sample and generalizable hypothesis assumptions, and so by measuring the relationships between distributees or groups of distributees in the data sample and comparing them with the relationships in the outcomes of an automated distributive decision, violations of equality of treatment are quantitatively detectable.

- **Example B:** imagine an automated hiring system, where the algorithm is designed to evaluate candidates based on qualifications such as education, work experience, and skill assessments (categorical ordering: e.g., degree level, years of relevant experience, results of standardized tests, and so on, to predict job performance). It may result in different hiring rates among various sub-groups of protected characteristics, not because it is based (if protected characteristic or indissociable proxy was not a category) on those protected characteristics but because there may be a correlation between the protected characteristic and certain qualifications in the target population. By setting a threshold (necessary use of protected characteristic or an indissociable proxy) for acceptable variance in hiring rates between sub-groups of a protected characteristic (equality of outcomes, difference in treatment), the company increases the likelihood that candidates who would have been deemed less qualified for the job specifics are hired—putting the company at risk of decreased performance and the candidate at risk of struggling in the role. Remember, while a company may try to address performance gaps through training or reassigning roles, the hired candidate might face challenges in job satisfaction and career growth.

5.2.6 Appendix: Code for Data Analysis for 5.2.3.5.1

```
1 import pandas as pd
2 import seaborn as sns
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
5 from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
6 from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
7 from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, accuracy_score
8 from aif360.algorithms.preprocessing import Reweighing
9 from aif360.datasets import BinaryLabelDataset
10
11 # Load the original dataset
12 original_dataset_path = '/content/FF.csv'
```



```
13 original_data = pd.read_csv(original_dataset_path)
14
15
16 # descriptive statistics for numeric features:
17 numeric_columns = ['Oral', 'Written', 'Combine']
18 print("\nDescriptive Statistics for Numeric Features:")
19 print(original_data[numeric_columns].describe())
20
21 # Distribution plots for numeric features:
22 for column in numeric_columns:
23     sns.histplot(data=original_data, x=column, hue='Position', kde=True
24                 )
25     plt.title(f'Distribution of {column} Scores by Position')
26     plt.show()
27
28 # Analyze the distribution of positions across different races
29 position_race_distribution = pd.crosstab(original_data['Position'],
30                                         original_data['Race'])
31 print("\nPosition vs. Race Distribution:")
32 print(position_race_distribution)
33
34 # Plot the distribution of positions across races
35 sns.countplot(data=original_data, x='Race', hue='Position')
36 plt.title('Distribution of Positions Across Races')
37 plt.show()
38
39 # Pairplot to visualize relationships between all features
40 sns.pairplot(original_data, hue='Position')
41 plt.title('Pairwise Relationships between Features')
42 plt.show()
43
44 # Calculate correlations between numeric features
45 correlation_matrix = original_data[numeric_columns].corr()
46 print("Correlation Matrix:")
47 print(correlation_matrix)
48
49 # Show correlation heatmap
50 sns.heatmap(correlation_matrix, annot=True, cmap='coolwarm')
51 plt.title('Feature Correlations')
52 plt.show()
53
54 # Preprocess the data (one-hot encoding the 'Race' column)
55 X_with_race = pd.get_dummies(original_data[['Oral', 'Written', 'Race'
56                                             ]], columns=['Race'])
57
58 # Ensure all race categories are present in the DataFrame
59 for race in ['Race_B', 'Race_H', 'Race_W']:
60     if race not in X_with_race.columns:
61         X_with_race[race] = 0
```



```

59 |
60 | # Create another dataset without the race features
61 | X_without_race = original_data[['Oral', 'Written']] # Only include '
        |     Oral' and 'Written' scores
62 |
63 | # Encode the 'Position' column to numerical values
64 | le = LabelEncoder()
65 | y = le.fit_transform(original_data['Position']) # Encode 'Position'
66 |
67 | # Split the data into training and testing sets for both with and
        |     without race features
68 | X_train_with_race, X_test_with_race, y_train, y_test =
        |     train_test_split(X_with_race, y, test_size=0.3, random_state=42,
        |     stratify=y)
69 | X_train_without_race, X_test_without_race, _, _ = train_test_split(
        |     X_without_race, y, test_size=0.3, random_state=42, stratify=y)
70 |
71 | # Verify no NA values in training and testing sets
72 | print("X_train_with_race missing values:\n", X_train_with_race.isna()
        |     .sum())
73 | print("y_train missing values:\n", pd.Series(y_train).isna().sum())
74 | print("X_test_with_race missing values:\n", X_test_with_race.isna().
        |     sum())
75 | print("y_test missing values:\n", pd.Series(y_test).isna().sum())
76 |
77 | # Train the original Random Forest Classifier using race features
78 | original_rf_classifier_with_race = RandomForestClassifier(
        |     n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
79 | original_rf_classifier_with_race.fit(X_train_with_race, y_train)
80 |
81 | # Predict outcomes using the original model with race features
82 | original_y_pred_with_race = original_rf_classifier_with_race.predict(
        |     X_test_with_race)
83 |
84 | # Train the second Random Forest Classifier without race features
85 | rf_classifier_without_race = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100,
        |     random_state=42)
86 | rf_classifier_without_race.fit(X_train_without_race, y_train)
87 |
88 | # Predict outcomes using the model without race features
89 | y_pred_without_race = rf_classifier_without_race.predict(
        |     X_test_without_race)
90 |
91 | # Create a BinaryLabelDataset for reweighing
92 | train_df_with_race = pd.concat([X_train_with_race.reset_index(drop=
        |     True), pd.DataFrame(y_train, columns=['Position']).reset_index(
        |     drop=True)], axis=1)
93 | test_df_with_race = pd.concat([X_test_with_race.reset_index(drop=True
        |     ), pd.DataFrame(y_test, columns=['Position']).reset_index(drop=

```



```

True)], axis=1)
94
95 # Update the protected attribute names to include all race categories
96 protected_attributes = ['Race_B', 'Race_H', 'Race_W']
97
98 train_bld = BinaryLabelDataset(favorable_label=1, unfavorable_label
    =0,
99                                df=train_df_with_race,
100                               label_names=['Position'],
101                               protected_attribute_names=
102                                   protected_attributes)
103
104 test_bld = BinaryLabelDataset(favorable_label=1, unfavorable_label=0,
105                               df=test_df_with_race,
106                               label_names=['Position'],
107                               protected_attribute_names=
108                                   protected_attributes)
109
110 # Apply the Reweighting preprocessing technique
111 RW = Reweighting(unprivileged_groups=[{'Race_W': 1}], # Privileged is
    'W'
112                 privileged_groups=[{'Race_H': 1}, {'Race_B': 1}]) #
    Protected groups are 'H' and 'B'
113
114 train_bld_transf = RW.fit_transform(train_bld)
115
116 # Train the Random Forest Classifier using the transformed dataset
117 reweighed_rf_classifier_with_race = RandomForestClassifier(
118     n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
119 reweighed_rf_classifier_with_race.fit(X_train_with_race, y_train,
120     sample_weight=train_bld_transf.instance_weights)
121
122 # Predict outcomes using the reweighed model with race features
123 reweighed_y_pred_with_race = reweighed_rf_classifier_with_race.
124     predict(X_test_with_race)
125
126 # Save the model outcomes to CSV files
127 original_model_outcomes_with_race_df = pd.DataFrame(
128     original_y_pred_with_race, columns=['Original_Outcome_With_Race'])
129 original_model_outcomes_without_race_df = pd.DataFrame(
130     y_pred_without_race, columns=['Outcome_Without_Race'])
131 reweighed_model_outcomes_with_race_df = pd.DataFrame(
132     reweighed_y_pred_with_race, columns=['Reweighed_Outcome_With_Race']
133 )
134
135 original_model_outcomes_with_race_df.to_csv('/content/
136     original_model_outcomes_with_race.csv', index=False)
137 original_model_outcomes_without_race_df.to_csv('/content/
138     model_outcomes_without_race.csv', index=False)

```



```
127 reweighed_model_outcomes_with_race_df.to_csv('/content/  
    reweighed_model_outcomes_with_race.csv', index=False)  
128  
129 # Evaluate performance metrics for all three models  
130 print("\nOriginal Model Performance Metrics (With Race):")  
131 print(classification_report(y_test, original_y_pred_with_race))  
132 print("Accuracy (With Race):", accuracy_score(y_test,  
    original_y_pred_with_race))  
133  
134 print("\nModel Performance Metrics (Without Race):")  
135 print(classification_report(y_test, y_pred_without_race))  
136 print("Accuracy (Without Race):", accuracy_score(y_test,  
    y_pred_without_race))  
137  
138 print("\nReweighed Model Performance Metrics (With Race):")  
139 print(classification_report(y_test, reweighed_y_pred_with_race))  
140 print("Accuracy (Reweighed Model With Race):", accuracy_score(y_test,  
    reweighed_y_pred_with_race))  
141  
142 # Analyze feature importance for all three models  
143 feature_importances_with_race = pd.Series(  
    original_rf_classifier_with_race.feature_importances_, index=  
    X_train_with_race.columns)  
144 feature_importances_with_race = feature_importances_with_race.  
    sort_values(ascending=False)  
145  
146 # Plot feature importance (with race)  
147 plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))  
148 sns.barplot(x=feature_importances_with_race, y=  
    feature_importances_with_race.index)  
149 plt.title('Feature Importance (Original Model with Race)')  
150 plt.show()  
151  
152 feature_importances_without_race = pd.Series(  
    rf_classifier_without_race.feature_importances_, index=  
    X_train_without_race.columns)  
153 feature_importances_without_race = feature_importances_without_race.  
    sort_values(ascending=False)  
154  
155 # Plot feature importance (without race)  
156 plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))  
157 sns.barplot(x=feature_importances_without_race, y=  
    feature_importances_without_race.index)  
158 plt.title('Feature Importance (Model Without Race)')  
159 plt.show()  
160  
161 reweighed_feature_importances_with_race = pd.Series(  
    reweighed_rf_classifier_with_race.feature_importances_, index=  
    X_train_with_race.columns)
```



```
162 reweighed_feature_importances_with_race =  
    reweighed_feature_importances_with_race.sort_values(ascending=  
        False)  
163  
164 # Plot feature importance (reweighed model)  
165 plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))  
166 sns.barplot(x=reweighed_feature_importances_with_race, y=  
    reweighed_feature_importances_with_race.index)  
167 plt.title('Feature Importance (Reweighed Model with Race)')  
168 plt.show()
```


6 Conclusion

The results showcased in these report represent a significant example of how the interdisciplinary training and research of the ESRs within the ambitious program of the LeADS project can lead to insights. Our data driven society requires, and us as well to understand the phenomena that govern it and to be able to regulate them, skills and knowledge that transcends those from each single discipline taken singularly —be them law, computer science, data science, ethics.

The collection of studies and analyses that this deliverable, D.7.5 - Final Scientific ESRs Reports, are a digest of the scientific contribution that the ESRs have developed during their years of PhD research. Overall, they have been carried out span across a wide range of topics that are paramount for a thriving contemporary, and future, society, such as:

(a) the increasing interaction and influence between data protection law, consumer protection law and competition (which can result in spillovers in terms of remit). Data is fluid, changes and flow. who tries to regulate it requires to understand how data processing works, what data portability is, what is the life cycle of data and how it can change by morphing slowly in something else, and harmonize such know-how with a solid knowledge of legal research.

(b) how requirements for data security and privacy in different domains, like that of digital identity management, general data governance and information management, and their relying on innovative architecture that prefer, as common today, a distributed processing and thus a distributed reliability, call for innovative solutions. They, theoretically or pragmatically, need to overcome a series of subtle hurdles before being successful in providing security and privacy that in addition to be satisfiable from an information security stand point are also in compliance with current regulations.

(c) how to share data, often required for advance research and to provide better services (e.g., in health care) while at the same time matching other requirements like ensuring consent, preserving ownership, removing bias and defend each one's privacy. The unsolved issues to personal, sensitive and non-personal data sharing in public, private or mixed contexts, requires once more a set of skills and some deep understanding of the problems and its implications, as this report exemplifies.

(d) how to understand the issue of ensuring fairness in the design and use of artificial intelligence, the revolutionary technology of our time that is intensively data greedy. In this report, ESRs have highlight that when it come to machine learning and artificial intelligence there is not easy solutions, not one we can use off-the-shelf. The architecture being the technology is complex and naïve solutions are just ineffective. Even the same very notion of fairness can be

misunderstood unless one dive into technicalities and put thoughts and energy to understand the problem and the subtle legal and philosophical implication of wishing to align our technology to our values.

The LeADS project is almost over, but has successfully managed to instill promising seeds of legality-attentive data science within the ESRs, the wider scientific community, and policy-making. The intent is that these seeds will sprout and pollinate even further stakeholders, sectors and domains.

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